

GAME-ER

November 2025

D4.2

Report on Documents Analysis

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.
Grant Agreement no. 101132585

Project Details

Acronym: **GAME-ER**
 Title: Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions
 Coordinator: **INOVA+ - INNOVATION SERVICES, SA** (Portugal)
 Call: HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01
 Type: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
 Topic-ID: HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01-06

 Start: **1 March 2024**
 End: **28 February 2027**
 Duration: **36 months**

 Website: **www.game-er.eu**

Consortium:

No	Participant Name	Short Name	Country
1	INOVA+ - INNOVATION SERVICES, SA	INOVA+	Portugal
2	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	UNITO	Italy
3	ASSOCIATION POUR LA RECHERCHE ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DES METHODES ET PROCESSUS INDUSTRIELS	CRG	France
3.1	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE	EP	France
4	ASOCIACE CESKYCH HERNICH VYVOJARU ZS	GDACZ	Czechia
5	SPIN SYSTEM	SPIN	Belgium
5.1	NOVARECKON	NR	Italy
6	UNIVERZITA KARLOVA	CUNI	Czechia
7	OGR-CRT - SCPA	OGR-Torino	Italy
8	PLUG AND PLAY PLATFORM SPAIN SL	PNPTC	Spain
9	KLASTER HRVATSKIH PROIZVODACA VIDEOIGARA	CGDA	Croatia
10	GAME ONLY	GO	France
11	HERNÍ KLASTR Z.S.	HK	Czechia
12	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO	CMF	Portugal
13	THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF ABERTAY UNIVERSITY	AU	United Kingdom

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Grant Agreement no. **101132585**

© Partners of the GAME-ER Consortium, 2025

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the GAME-ER consortium.

Deliverable Details

Number:	D4.2
Title:	Report on Documents Analysis
Lead beneficiary:	AU
Work package:	WP4
Dissemination level:	Public
Nature:	Report
Due date:	31/10/2025
Submission date:	06/11/2025
Authors:	Stefano De Paoli , Abertay University (AU) Nicola Costalunga , Riccardo Fassone , UNITO Jan Švelch , CUNI Luís Leça , INOVA+ Chahira Mehouchi , Thomas Paris , CRG
Contributors:	Martin Lynagh , AU Wren O'Regan , AU José Gómez , AU Darshana Jayemanne , AU Matilde Caria , Tânia Moreira , INOVA+ Mariana Salvado , CMF
Reviewers:	Geoffrey Marmonier , GO

Version History:

Date	Version No.	Author	Note
01/08/2025	0.1	Stefano De Paoli, AU	Table of Contents shared with Authors
05/09/2025	0.2	Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Dundee Chapter
16/09/2025	0.3	Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Turin Chapter
26/09/2025	0.4	Jan Švelch, CUNI Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Brno Chapter
07/10/2025	0.5	Luís Leça, INOVA+ Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Fundão Chapter
21/10/2025	0.6	Chahira Mehouchi; Thomas Paris, CRG Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Lyon Chapter
27/10/2025	0.7	Chahira Mehouchi; Thomas Paris, CRG Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration and Revision of Bordeaux Chapter
31/10/2025	0.8	Geoffrey Marmonier, GO Stefano De Paoli, AU	Revision of the Deliverable and inputs provided
03/11/2025	0.9	Authors+ Stefano De Paoli, AU	Integration of Inputs
06/11/2025	1.0	Luís Leça, INOVA+ Stefano De Paoli, AU	Final Revision and Submission

Glossary and Abbreviations

Name	Abbreviation
Association of Video Game Publishers and Developers	AESVI
Artificial Intelligence	AI
Agence nationale de la recherche	ANR
Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes	AURA
Business to Business	B2B
Business to Consumer	B2C
Brno University of Technology	BUT
Chambre de commerce et d'industrie	CCI
Cultural and Creative Industries	CCIs
Piedmont Foreign Centre for Internationalisation	CEIP
Consumer Electronic Show	CES
Comité interministériel d'aménagement et de développement du territoire	CIADT
Crédit d'impôt jeu vidéo	CIJV

Corporate social responsibility	CSR
Research Centre for Information and Communication Technologies	CSP
Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti	CTE
Dundee Contemporary Arts	DCA
Direction régionale des entreprises, de la concurrence, de la consommation, du travail et de l'emploi	DIRECCTE
Downloadable Content	DLC
Electronic Entertainment Expo	E3
European Commission	EC
European Social Fund Plus	ESF+
European Union	EU
Fonds d'aide au jeu vidéo	FAJV
Full-time equivalent	FTE
Italian Game Developers	GPI
Game Workers Unite	GWU
Incubator for Innovative Businesses of the Polytechnic University of Turin	I3P
Information and Communication Technology	ICT
International Game Developers Association	IGDA
Italian Interactive & Digital Entertainment Association	IIDEA
Intellectual Property	IP
Italian Party of Indie Developer	IPID
South Moravian Innovation Centre	JIC
Mercato Internazionale Audiovisivo	MIA
Modern Times Group	MTG
Masaryk University	MUNI
National Cash Register	NCR
Officine Grandi Riparazioni	OGR
Opérateur de compétences	OPCO
Integrated Supply Chain Projects	PIF
Small and Medium-sized Enterprises	SMEs
European Regional Development Fund	PR FESR
Syndicat national du jeu vidéo	SNJV
Secondary School of Art and Design	SŠUD
UK Games Fund	UKGF

UK Games Talent and Finance	UKGTF
UK Interactive Entertainment	UKIE
UK Research and Innovation	UKRI
Victoria and Albert Museum	V&A
Video Games Expenditure Credit	VGEC
Video Game Tax Relief	VGTR
Very small enterprises	VSE
Work Package	WP

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION.....	11
2	DOCUMENT ANALYSIS: PURPOSE, METHOD, AND SCOPE	13
2.1	METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK.....	13
2.2	TYPES OF DOCUMENTS AND COLLECTION	15
2.3	ORDER OF CHAPTERS.....	16
2.4	DATASET AND CITATION	16
3	DUNDEE CLUSTER.....	16
3.1	DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	16
3.2	DUNDEE.....	18
3.3	CLUSTER EMERGENCE & GENESIS	18
3.4	LOCAL INDUSTRY FEATURES & COMPONENTS	22
3.5	CLUSTER EVOLUTION.....	28
3.6	COLLECTIVE ACTIONS	34
3.7	CO-ORDINATION AND FORMAL CONTROL STRUCTURES	37
3.8	FINANCIAL ASPECTS.....	40
4	TURIN CLUSTER.....	43
4.1	INTRODUCTION.....	43
4.2	METHODOLOGY	45
4.3	CLUSTER EMERGENCE & GENESIS	46
4.4	LOCAL INDUSTRY FEATURES AND COMPONENTS.....	48
4.5	CLUSTER EVOLUTION.....	60
4.6	COLLECTIVE ACTIONS	60
5	BRNO CLUSTER.....	65
5.1	DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	65
5.2	BRNO	67
5.3	CLUSTER EMERGENCE & GENESIS	68
5.4	LOCAL INDUSTRY FEATURES & COMPONENTS	73
5.5	CLUSTER EVOLUTION.....	77
5.6	COLLECTIVE ACTIONS	80
5.7	CO-ORDINATION AND FORMAL CONTROL STRUCTURES	82
5.8	FINANCIAL ASPECTS.....	83

6	FUNDÃO CLUSTER	84
6.1	DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	84
6.2	FUNDÃO REGION	86
6.3	CLUSTER EMERGENCE & GENESIS	87
6.4	LOCAL INDUSTRY FEATURES & COMPONENTS	90
6.5	CLUSTER EVOLUTION.....	93
6.6	COLLECTIVE ACTIONS	101
6.7	CO-ORDINATION AND FORMAL CONTROL STRUCTURES	105
6.8	FINANCIAL ASPECTS.....	110
7	DATA COLLECTION & ANALYSIS FOR LYON & BORDEAUX	112
7.1	SOURCE IDENTIFICATION AND SAMPLING	113
7.2	THEMATIC CATEGORIZATION.....	114
7.3	ANALYTICAL APPROACH	114
8	LYON CLUSTER	115
8.1	GENESIS AND EMERGENCE OF THE LYON CLUSTER	115
8.2	KEY CHARACTERISTICS & COMPONENTS OF THE LOCAL INDUSTRY	118
8.3	LYON CLUSTER EVOLUTION.....	125
8.4	COLLECTIVES ACTIONS IN THE LYON CLUSTER	128
8.5	MOBILIZED RESOURCES AND COMPETENCIES.....	142
8.6	GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES IN LYON CLUSTER	149
9	BORDEAUX CLUSTER	151
9.1	GENESIS AND EMERGENCE OF BORDEAUX CLUSTER	151
9.2	KEY CHARACTERISTICS & COMPONENTS OF THE LOCAL INDUSTRY	154
9.3	ANALYSIS OF THE EVOLUTIONARY DYNAMICS.....	160
9.4	COLLECTIVE ACTIONS	163
9.5	MOTIVATIONS, BENEFITS, & CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE STAKEHOLDERS	168
9.6	COOPERATIVE NETWORKS & PROXIMITY DYNAMICS OF THE CLUSTER	173
9.7	RESOURCES, COMPETENCIES & CAPACITIES	175
9.8	THE FINANCIAL MODEL OF THE BORDEAUX CLUSTER.....	179
9.9	STRUCTURE, MODALITIES, AND GOVERNANCE MECHANISMS.....	183
10	CONCLUSION	184
11	REFERENCES	185

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, **D4.2 – Report on Document Analysis**, presents the findings of Task T4.2, which focuses on the collection and analysis of a wide range of natural documents. These include policy strategies, funding calls, institutional reports, and other publicly available materials. These documents provide critical insights into how local and regional actors frame, support, and govern video game clusters. By analysing these materials, the project uncovers the formal narratives, strategic priorities, and institutional mechanisms that influence the development of these clusters across diverse settings.

The objective of this document analysis is to complement and extend the findings from previous interview-based research (D4.1 – Report on Primary Data Collection), filling any gaps and offering a more comprehensive understanding of cluster dynamics. The analysis is guided by a shared framework developed in **GAME-ER** WP3, ensuring consistency across the six case studies. Through thematic coding, key patterns are identified concerning cluster formation, governance, innovation support, talent development, and external partnerships. This structured approach allows for both in-depth case-specific analysis and meaningful cross-case comparisons, highlighting broader trends and region-specific dynamics.

Each cluster is analysed in a dedicated chapter that combines documentary evidence with contextual analysis to provide a complete view of its evolution, institutional landscape, and strategic positioning. Key findings emphasize the pivotal role of local leadership, educational infrastructure, and targeted policies in fostering innovation beyond major urban centres. The analysis also illustrates how peripheral regions actively shape their development trajectories through creative strategies and effective institutional coordination.

By integrating this documentary analysis with prior interview data, **GAME-ER** delivers a robust, multidimensional perspective on regional innovation in the digital economy, offering valuable insights for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders in the digital and creative industries.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Overview

The Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions (**GAME-ER**) project aims to explore the emergence, development, and sustainability of video game clusters, with a specific focus on local and regional clusters. The project will develop a comprehensive Interactive Methodological Toolkit, featuring policy and practical recommendations designed to assist local and national policymakers in establishing or enhancing Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) clusters within their regions or cities. Existing research often focuses on clusters outside Europe or within major metropolitan areas like Helsinki or Hamburg. However, **GAME-ER** addresses a critical gap by studying the dynamics of smaller, regional clusters, which play a significant role in driving innovation, growth, and regional cohesion. The project's core component involves a comparative analysis of six clusters in five European countries—France, the Czech Republic, Italy, Scotland, and Portugal. These clusters were chosen for their diverse levels of maturity and unique characteristics, including concentrations of creative talent and companies. In addition to this comparative study, **GAME-ER** will conduct a Europe-wide analysis of the spatial organization of the video games industry, specifically focusing on local and regional ecosystems. This research, conducted in collaboration with policymakers and industry stakeholders, will guide the formulation of actionable recommendations using a participatory approach. **GAME-ER** brings together 15 partners from 9 countries, encompassing expertise in social sciences, humanities, policymaking, business, and innovation.

1.2 Objectives of the Deliverable

D4.2 aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the video game industry clusters across various European regions, focusing on their development, support mechanisms, and governance structures. This document analyses a wide array of natural materials which offer critical insights into how these clusters are framed and supported by local and regional actors. By examining these documents, this deliverable contributes to:

- **Examine the governance models** and institutional frameworks that promote to the growth and sustainability of video game clusters, with a particular focus on the role of local leadership, educational infrastructure, and regional strategies.
- **Identify key strategic priorities** and external partnerships that influence the development of these clusters, revealing how they integrate into broader national and European innovation landscapes.
- **Highlight regional dynamics and variations**, shedding light on the unique challenges and opportunities faced by peripheral and non-metropolitan regions in fostering innovation within the video game sector.
- **Enhance the understanding** gained from the earlier interview-based research (D4.1), offering a more nuanced perspective through documentary evidence to complement and extend the insights obtained from key stakeholders.

Through this detailed documentary analysis, D4.2 will serve as a valuable resource for understanding the underlying dynamics of regional video game ecosystems and how they can be nurtured to thrive beyond major urban centres.

2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH ON D4.2

In the landscape of Europe's digital economy, the video game sector has become a key site of innovation, creativity, and regional transformation. While much of the scholarly and policy discourse has concentrated on capital cities and major urban centres (e.g. Lehtonen et al., 2020; Gong and Binz, 2023; Méndez-Ortega and Arauzo-Carod, 2019) - typically seen as the national or European centres driving economic and technological progress - there is a growing need to understand how smaller, less central regions or cities contribute to this dynamic industry. These areas, often characterised by post-industrial decline and legacies, rural economies or relative peripheral positions, are also home to emerging digital industries. One of these industries is that of video games, where in local contexts we have seen the emergence of productive clusters, with their own specific strengths and challenges.

The concept of cluster captures the idea of a geographically concentrated network of interconnected companies of different sizes, institutions (e.g. Universities), and other actors operating within a specific productive field (e.g. Cooke and Lazzeretti, 2008), sharing resources, ideas and collaborating. Clusters are not simply collections of companies but rather complex ecosystems (e.g. Loots et al., 2021), where there is circulation of knowledge, collaboration, and where innovation tends to be firmly embedded in the local culture. The **GAME-ER** project builds on this idea and looks at the video game industry, asking whether and how such ecosystems can take root in regions or cities that are often overlooked in policy innovation strategies.

The project focuses on six case studies located outside capital cities: Turin (Italy), Dundee (Scotland, UK), Brno (Czechia), Lyon and Bordeaux (France), and Fundão (Portugal). These clusters represent a diverse range of regional contexts, from post-industrial cities to rural innovation zones, each offering a unique lens through which to examine the conditions that support creative and technological industries, beyond dominant national or continental urban centres. The mechanisms through which such clusters form and sustain themselves outside capital cities remain insufficiently researched, leaving a gap in systematic, comparative insights.

Previous work performed for **D4.1 – Report on Primary Data Collection**¹ of **GAME-ER** provided an investigation and material for filling this knowledge gap via qualitative interviews with key actors and stakeholders in each cluster (e.g. game company leads, educators, developers). The intent of D4.1 was to research directly the perspectives of key actors operating in each of the project clusters.

The D4.2 of **GAME-ER** now seeks to complement this previous knowledge by turning to the analysis of natural documents. The assumption is that natural documents may contain additional details, as well as enrich the perspectives of the actors. These documents may include policy reports, municipal strategies, funding calls, institutional publications, press releases, and other publicly available materials produced by actors within or around the clusters (e.g. companies' website, other online resources). This documentary evidence is not only complementary to the interview data but also essential for capturing the formal narratives, institutional frameworks, and policy environments that underpin a cluster development.

¹ Deliverable available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535331>

The documentary analysis contributes directly to the overall **GAME-ER** objective: **identifying the specific conditions that enable clusters to emerge and thrive**, in order to inform both academic theory and practical policymaking. It provides a systematic account of how clusters are framed, supported, and institutionalised across different regions. It also reveals how local actors articulate their visions for the future, respond to structural challenges, and position themselves within national and European innovation landscapes.

3 DOCUMENT ANALYSIS: PURPOSE, METHOD, AND SCOPE

The primary purpose of T4.2 is to examine how each cluster is represented, governed, and supported through the analysis of natural documents, including formal documentation, media coverage, and other online sources. Unlike interviews, which capture individual perspectives and lived experiences, natural documents provide a complementary lens by offering insights into official narratives, strategic priorities, and institutional frameworks that underpin cluster formation and evolution. They also make it possible to identify stories, events, and key developments that may remain absent from or underemphasised in interview accounts.

This documentary approach is particularly valuable in the context of peripheral or non-metropolitan clusters, where innovation often emerges through a combination of formal initiatives and more informal, community-driven mechanisms. By examining documents, researchers can trace how local actors articulate their ambitions, define success criteria, allocate resources, and acknowledge challenges or constraints. Such sources also reveal how clusters are positioned within wider national and European innovation agendas, showing how local priorities interact with broader policy discourses. Furthermore, analysing documents enables the identification of discursive patterns and institutional logics that might not surface in interviews, either because they are taken for granted by participants or because they reflect collective narratives rather than individual viewpoints. In this way, T4.2 not only supplements the interview-based analysis but also enriches our understanding of the symbolic, political, and organisational dimensions of cluster development.

3.1 Methodological Framework

To ensure consistency and comparability across the six case studies, the documentary analysis is guided by a shared analytical grid developed in WP3 (**D3.1 – Analysis Grid and Interview Script²**) and already used for the analysis of the interviews (D4.1). This grid outlines the key dimensions of interest for the project, including cluster formation, governance and leadership, innovation support, talent development, external partnerships, and barriers to growth. Therefore, documents were coded thematically using this framework mirroring the approach adopted for the interviews analysis, which was extensively described in D4.1. Albeit we should note that some small variation to the method usage may exist across the different clusters, since different research partners were involved in the research, each having some slightly diverse interpretations and approaches to the data collection and analysis, depending on the context and the related empirical material. Later in the text, the specific (cluster-related) data collection and analysis details will therefore be briefly described. Natural documents were analysed in their original language.

² Deliverable available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542326>

Document collection was carried out by local project partners in each cluster- such as Abertay University in Dundee, the University of Turin in Turin and so on - who were responsible for identifying and gathering relevant materials. To facilitate data collection and standardise the resources toward the possibility to later share the list of documents as an Open Access dataset, a template was prepared by the task leader, allowing for the recording of the documentary evidence. The structure of the template is shown below (Figure 1), although the real data collection template is in itself a spreadsheet. The template included the following fixed fields: (1) **a unique identifier**, with an initial differing from each cluster (e.g. D for Dundee, T for Turin, BR for Brno, F for Fundão and FR for Lyon and Bordeaux / France) and an incremental number (e.g. T0004); (2) the **Name/Title** of the sources; (3) the **name of the Author** (reported when available); (4) the **name of the organisation** publishing the document; (5) the **date of publication**; (6) the **date of recording** the document in the **GAME-ER** dataset (this was optional); (7) the **type** of document (more below in the text); (8) the **URL of the document**, for retrieval, consultation and referencing; (9) to note is that sometimes the document is not publicly available (e.g. a report accessible to the researchers but not shareable in public or an online news material that was removed but still stored by researchers), therefore an URL is not always available.

Identifier	Source name/title	Author	Organisation	Date published	Date added	Item type	Source URL/link
D0134	NCR 75 Years in Dundee	Rob McLaren	The Courier	1-Dec-21	May 31, 2025	News article	https://www.thecourier.co.uk/fp/business-environment/2756403/ncr-75-years-in-dundee-told-in-75-incredible-pictures/
D0135	City story captured by company's evolution	Rob McLaren	The Courier	3-Dec-21	July 31, 2025	News article	https://www.pressreader.com/uk/the-courier-advertiser-fife-edition/20211203/281913071395216?srsId=AfmB0opJ0u_2jC1KBPsANSi-hsUvsj799NY3XNRRtVA6T5lgy_5khiKP
D0136	DC Thomson	Wikipedia Contributors	Wikipedia	July, 15, 2025 (last edit)	July 31, 2025	Wikipedia Article	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DC_Thomson
D0137	Dundee is one of the world's most creative cities - here's why	Andrew Batchelor	Dundee Culture	16-May-24	July 31, 2025	Webpage	https://www.dundeeculture.com/post/dundee-is-one-of-the-world-s-most-creative-cities-here-s-why
D0138	DC Thomson Launches UK Games Fund Awards	n/a	ScottishGames	11-Jul-18	July 31, 2025	Webpage	https://scottishgames.net/2018/07/11/uk-games-fund-awards-2018/
D0139	COMPANY DIRECTORY	Brian Baglow	ScottishGames	n/a	June 21, 2025	Webpage	https://scottishgames.net/companydirectory/

Figure 1 – Structure of data collection template (example)

This centralised data collection template was proposed to ensure that the material gathered for analysis remained grounded in local contexts while adhering to a common methodological standard. This also supports citation and referencing of the documents across the deliverable.

3.2 Types of Documents and Collection

The documents collected and then analysed in this phase of **GAME-ER** include a wide range of formats and sources, such as (list is not exhaustive):

- Policy documents (e.g. regional innovation plans, digital economy strategies, national strategies that impact the clusters)
- Funding programmes (e.g. grants for creative industries, start-up support)
- Institutional reports (e.g. university publications, incubator evaluations)
- Press releases and media coverage (e.g. announcements of new initiatives or partnerships, new games)
- Companies press-releases, and other material from companies' websites
- Social media material such as YouTube videos
- Webpages and websites (of e.g. companies, video games, game related events)

These materials were examined not only for their content but also for their discursive framing, focusing on how clusters are described, what priorities are emphasised, and which actors are positioned as central to the ecosystem, for example. All this still performed utilising the project analytical framework. Later, in the deliverable, clusters are discussed in a stand-alone chapter which presents a detailed account of the documents analysed, including the types of sources used and the rationale for their selection. The Lyon and Bordeaux clusters have a joined methodological frame, because key elements of the policy frameworks are common. Each chapter also recalls key findings from D4.1 (the related chapters for each cluster), to better illustrate how the documentary sources complement the **GAME-ER** previous work, and the findings from interviews. While the volume and nature of available documents varied across regions (depending on context, research focus and other aspects), all clusters provided a sufficient documentary base to support robust analysis. In total, over 600 documents were reviewed across the six clusters, offering a rich and diverse dataset for comparative research, as shown in the table below.

Cluster	Nr. Of Documents
Dundee	177
Brno	89
Turin	92
Fundão	56
Bordeaux & Lyon	228
Total	642

Table 1 – Total number of documents per cluster and overall (Lyon & Bordeaux share common material)

3.3 Order of Chapters

The remainder of this deliverable is organised into dedicated chapters. Each chapter provides an in-depth analysis of the local context, development trajectory, and key dynamics of each cluster. Like for the previous D4.1, each chapter was written independently by a different partner, and as such, elements of the narrative, as well as some of the reporting, may differ. However, each chapter presents a similar structure which was derived from the project's analytical grid, and to a larger extent mirrors the structured used in D4.1. The order of presentation is the following:

- **Dundee** (Scotland, UK) - examining a cluster rooted in education.
- **Turin** (Italy) - exploring the initial transformation of a post-industrial city.
- **Brno** (Czechia) - highlighting a well-connected ecosystem in a secondary city.
- **Fundão** (Portugal) - investigating a rural municipality's strategic push into digital industries.
- **Lyon and Bordeaux** (France) - analysing two historically grounded clusters outside Paris.

3.4 Dataset and Citation

In the following the sources will be referenced using the unique identifier (e.g. D0045; T0032; FR0210) and the URL will be supplied where available. This will allow the reader to consult the material sources. As URLs as sometime volatile (with link disappearing or being archived), it may be that some may not work, albeit they were all checked at the time of submission. The full dataset in the form of the spreadsheets described earlier is available as open access in Zenodo at the following URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17440712>

4 DUNDEE CLUSTER

4.1 Data Collection and Analysis

For the Dundee cluster, data collection focused on assembling a broad and diverse corpus of publicly available documents, potentially reflecting key aspects of the evolution, support mechanisms, and stakeholder perspectives surrounding the cluster. Abertay researchers decided to adopt a very broad scope and therefore the material gathered includes policy reports, government strategy papers, local authority publications, white papers, press releases, media features, newspaper articles, blog posts, companies web-pages and others. This decision was taken due to the comparatively extensive influence of the cluster, in which many different types of documents would be relevant. It was necessary to assemble a comprehensive corpus and then decide on prioritisation, analysing a subset of the material.

For collecting the documents Google search was used as the main tool for discovery, supplemented by targeted searches of official websites (e.g., UK and Scottish government portals, Creative Scotland, Scottish Enterprise, local councils, educational institutions, and game industry associations). A set of keywords was adopted during the discovery of documents. The keywords were then iteratively refined during the search, combining terms related to the video game industry (e.g., "game development", "indie games", "game studios") with contextual words more specific to Dundee (e.g., "Dundee games", "Abertay", "Scotland"). Moreover, Boolean operators and other filters (e.g. time) were applied to ensure that different combinations could produce relevant results.

The identified documents were first scanned briefly by a member of the team for relevance and then catalogued in the spreadsheet for the **GAME-ER** document data collection.

Data collection was mostly performed during the first 5 months of T4.2 (June to October 2024), with ongoing updates to the document lists until M18 (August 2025) of the project. Updates to the data collection were performed both for including more recent developments as well as for filling gaps in the analysis. Subsequently the corpus was subjected to a prioritisation as said above. Since the initial collection included more than 170 documents, it has been essential to identify first a key set of documents to prioritise for the analysis. A total of 69 documents were analysed with thematic analysis performed manually. However, the entire corpus was also uploaded in an Open-Source Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) solution, deployed on a secure Abertay University computer server, allowing the team to extract knowledge and material from the entire corpus. The manual analysis was performed following the analytical grid used for interviews in **GAME-ER** D4.1.

Inductive coding was performed initially. Then the codes were grouped using some of the most relevant categories of the analytical grid. This approach allowed open ended identifications of patterns but also enabled the formulation of categories comparable across the project case study. This method enabled an understanding of how different institutional actors, historical developments, and policy narratives converge to shape its trajectory. Moreover, the chapter contains content that fills some of the gaps of D4.1 relating to the Dundee cluster, with additional analytical tables and additional details around several of the areas of investigation, including collective action, industry composition, or stakeholder benefits.

Some additional sources were retrieved to confirm specific figures, where available, for example the number of employees (sometimes approximate ~) for companies, dates of closure of companies and similar specifics. These sources were not included in the main database but are still used in the reporting for the cluster. These sources include Wikipedia articles, LinkedIn pages of organisations, YouTube videos, specific news articles (e.g. BBC) on companies or events, or others (cited as Other Sources).

Item Type	Count
Webpage	83
News article	28
Press release	15
Website	20
Report	11
Report of Session	3
Response to policy	2
Other/Unclassified	15

Table 2 – Documents by type, Dundee cluster

4.2 Dundee

D4.1 of **GAME-ER** included an introduction to Dundee and its cluster, and readers are encouraged to consult that document for a more comprehensive view to the case study and the geographical area. Here we will provide just some key pointers to it. Dundee is the 4th most populous city in Scotland with around 150000 people and is a rather small and peripheral city considering the UK more broadly. In recent decades, Dundee has sought to redefine itself, after the decline of traditional industries (e.g. textile). The city leadership turned to cultural regeneration and creative industries to recover from its post-industrial decline. With investment in art, design, and digital innovation, Dundee reinvented its identity. The establishment of institutions like the V&A Dundee, the award of status as a UNESCO City of Design, and institutional bodies such as Creative Dundee helped solidify its new image. Yet, socioeconomic challenges persist. Poverty and material deprivation still affect many communities across the city. Contemporary Dundee has been shaped by the digital economy and cultural ambition. This represents not just a renewal but also a continuity of past cycles of growth and struggle.

Today, the video games industry stands as a key component of Dundee’s resurgence, with numerous developers and an increased reputation in the sector, which makes Dundee a video game cluster (the second in Scotland after Edinburgh). The game companies in Dundee, alongside other important actors, such as Abertay University, are part of an ecosystem which the research performed for D4.1 showed to be rather informal and based on direct and close-knit relationships across key actors. The ecosystem, from the perspective of interviewees, present some strong points (talent availability, innovation) but also faces important challenges (e.g. investment opportunity, generation of IP). The next pages will further detail the nature of the Dundee video game cluster complementing and expanding the findings from the previous **GAME-ER** deliverable based on qualitative interviews with key actors.

4.3 Cluster Emergence & Genesis

The research produced for D4.1, based on interviews showed how actors in the Dundee cluster perceive several key moments of the genesis and emergence of the cluster, as summarised in Table 3 below. The foundation of the company DMA Design and the establishing of a computer games degree by Abertay University were singled out as key to the genesis of the cluster, alongside the presence in the city of the Timex factory which produced the Spectrum personal computer. Documentary evidence analysis is consonant with those early observations. However, these documents also introduce new evidence beyond the interview work in D4.1.

D4.1 findings	Description
Industrial & Creative Roots	Legacy in computer manufacturing (e.g. Timex ZX Spectrum) and publishing promoted technical and creative skills, with early access to computers driving grassroots game development.
Founding of DMA Design	David Jones’ creation of DMA Design in 1988 turned local talent into a formal industry. DMA's success (e.g. <i>Lemmings</i> , <i>GTA</i>) inspired further studios and shaped the local games ecosystem.
Talent & Policy Support	Abertay University launched the first games degree, creating a talent pipeline. Support from public agencies and individuals helped growth and attracted industry to Dundee.

Table 3 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster emergence

Industrial development preceding the advent of today's digital and creative industries did play a significant role in establishing a seed for the video game cluster. As noted in D4.1, the presence in the city of the Timex factory and Spectrum manufacturing created a situation of wide diffusion of early home computers, which fuelled curiosity and grassroots activities on computing including in and around video games. Documents confirm and remark this with one source reporting that *"Dundee was an unusually tech-savvy city for its time in the 1980s"* [D00125], and other evidence showing how women played an important role in the city work force for Timex [D0117].

Documentary sources also evidence that well ahead the Timex impact, the computing sector had been developing in Dundee since the early postwar period, when in 1946 the US company NCR (National Cash Register) established itself in the city, reaching over the years a peak of 7 productive sites and 6000 workers. In the 1960s production started to move into electronics, with electro-mechanic accounting system and in late 1970s NCR Dundee produced a revolutionary ATM (model 5070) machine [D0135], albeit in a context of industrial decline (with only 1100 workers by the end of the decade). Production of the ATM continued till 2009, at which point manufacturing for NCR ended in Dundee. NCR Dundee transitioned to R&D, services and innovation [D0134]. As of 2021 NCR employed around 600 people at its Research and Development Centre of Excellence [D0047]. NCR also contributed to the image and reputation of the city as a place of innovation, including in the fields of electronics and computing.

Other industrial developments have contributed to the reputation of the city as a place for creativity. As noted in D4.1 one of the legacy industries of Dundee is Journalism. The company DC Thomson played a foundational role in shaping Dundee's creative ecosystem long before the rise of its video game industry (with the company founded in 1905) [D0136]. DC Thomson is responsible for producing some of the UK's most beloved publications, for instance iconic comics like *The Beano* and *The Dandy*. While documentary material is not very explicit about this, it is certainly possible that this legacy of creativity nurtured local talent in storytelling, illustration, and visual design. DC Thomson helped establish Dundee's identity as a media-creative city in the UK [D0137], and whilst the contribution of this legacy to video games is indirect, it is a noteworthy element of the ecosystem. In recent times DC Thomson was partner of the InGAME research led by Abertay University and was a key factor in the establishment of the UK Games Fund Awards [D0138]. These two stories of NCR and DC Thomson indicate that industrial legacies may play a role in the formation of a game production cluster, even if indirectly. For example, they may contribute to local reputation in defined productive sectors or innovation (innovation, R&D, creativity). These industrial developments therefore must be read alongside the more direct influence of the Timex industrial contribution.

The interview research of D4.1 clearly showed how local actors acknowledge the founding role of the company DMA Design: almost as a foundational event that bootstrapped the local video game industry (more on this event will be shown in a later section too). A key role in this was certainly played by the game *Lemmings* and its worldwide success, which has been given concrete form in a bronze sculptural work by artist Alyson Conway who also studied at the Duncan of Jordanstone College Art. Documentary sources evidence the innovative nature of the *Lemmings* game design, and the early challenges of DMA to make the game known widely. For example, sources say that the original founders sent *"as many demos, usually free on the cover of gaming magazines, as possible"* [D0125] to facilitate diffusion of the game and reach players.

Certainly, then the genesis of the Dundee cluster is tied with the emergence of some iconic games. DMA's success with *Lemmings* was followed by *Grand Theft Auto*, a franchise that has literally shaped global gaming [D0048], and DMA transforming into Rockstar Games [D0056] through their

acquisition by Take-Two. Whilst the results presented in D4.1 showed how current actors of the cluster perceive of the difficulties of repeating some of the early original successes, over the years companies in Dundee still managed to produce significant original games for diverse platforms and purposes. Table 4 provides an indicative overview of some of the main game development achievements, on a historical timeline encompassing also the platforms where possible, as well as the relevant technologies leveraged at the time.

Game(s)	Company	Platform/Engine	Technologies	Indicators
Lemmings (1991)	DMA Design	Amiga (68000 assembly, 512 KB–1 MB RAM)	Optimized sprite AI, split-screen tools, intricate level scripting	~20 million copies sold (Source: Wikipedia)
Grand Theft Auto (1997)	DMA Design	PC/PS1 (2.5D engine, C/C++)	Height-layered map, top-down open world, hardcoded mission logic	Spawned franchise with billions in lifetime revenue (under Rockstar umbrella) (Source: Wikipedia)
State of Emergency (2002)	Developer: VIS Entertainment Publisher: Rockstar Games	PC, XBOX, PS2	Novel use of PS2 architecture to achieve impressive crowd simulation (Source: Game Developer Magazine)	Sold 900,00 copies on PS2 by 2006. (Source: Wikipedia)
Crackdown (2007)	Realtime Worlds	Xbox 360 (custom engine, triple-core Xenon)	Streaming 3D city, Havok physics, procedural AI	Sold 1.5 million copies in its first six months of release; positive critical reception (Source: Wikipedia)
The Elder Scrolls IV: Oblivion (2007)	4J Studios	PS3 Port [From Xbox 360] of the massively successful ARPG Oblivion.	Open world ARPG, Emotion Engine.	Start of 4J's relationship with Bethesda. 4J's reputation as a console porting studio for global publishers. (Source: Wikipedia)
Bloons (2007)	Ninja Kiwi	Flash (original), later Unity for mobile/PC/console	Browser-based gameplay, tower defense mechanics, scalable difficulty, balloon-popping physics	Franchise with over 1 billion plays/downloads across platforms; multiple sequels
Denki Mobile/Web (2010–14)	Denki	iOS, Android, HTML5 (custom engines)	Touch-oriented gameplay, real-time cross-platform sync (e.g., <i>Quarrel</i>)	<i>Quarrel</i> won BAFTA Scotland Best Game 2011; Scottish Games Network
Minecraft Console Ports (2012–2017)	4J Studios	Xbox 360, Playstation 3, Xbox One, PS Vita, Wii U, Nintendo Switch	Networking technologies, Various Console specific Technologies.	Allowed the Minecraft franchise to expand its install base massively. (Sources: Wikipedia , GamesIndustry.biz)
Play to Cure: Genes in Space (2014)	Guerrilla Tea	Unity (iOS/Android)	Cloud data uploads with real genomic data, accessible citizen-science gameplay	> 75,000 downloads in 5 days ; 1.5 million DNA classifications

Autonauts (2019)	Denki	PC (Unity) → Consoles (2022)	Visual scripting, procedural worlds, bot automation	~\$1.3 M revenue on Steam; ~231k copies sold
Monstrum (2015) & 2 (2022)	Team Junkfish	PC (Unity)	Procedural horror map generation, stealth AI, dynamic audio	Cult hit (original); sequel praised for improvements (exact data not public)
Phogs! (2020)	Bit Loom Games	PC/Consoles (Unity)	Physics-based co-op, low-poly visuals, multi-platform optimization	“Generally favorable reviews”; award nominations (e.g., IndieCade)
The Baby in Yellow (2023)	Team Terrible	Android, iOS, Microsoft Windows	Unreal Engine on iOS, Android and Windows. Ragdoll Physics and Headtracking on Mobile.	Viral success, achieving a 140 million downloads across Android, iOS and PC. (Source: Steam)
Viewfinder (2023)	Matt Stark/Sad Owl Studios	PlayStation 5, Windows, PlayStation 4, Xbox Series X/S, Nintendo Switch.	Unity Engine, highly innovative and novel ‘polaroid effect’ gameplay. (Source: The Guardian)	Started as an Abertay Student project. Winner of 2024 BAFTAs in British Game and New Intellectual Property categories. (Source: BBC)

Table 4 – Notable videogames produced in Dundee overtime, successful video games were part of the genesis and consolidation of the cluster

4.3.1 Local industry: Origins & Historical Legacy

We reflected in the previous section on some aspects of the industrial legacy and the relation with the Dundee cluster. Table 5 summarises the key periods of industrial development of Dundee, which aims to locate the video game industry into an historical trajectory of local production. It also shows more clearly the potential role of productive activities like Timex, NCR, DC Thomson and others.

Whilst elements of this trajectory were discussed in D4.1, here we are in the position to provide additional details. The table offers an overview of how the decline of more traditional industries was followed by a focus on the city reinvention around knowledge industries and culture, which do not just include games, but also biotech and more recently sustainability and smart mobility after the closure of the very last large city industrial plant in 2020 (the Michelin Tyre plant) and the site being transformed into a green mobility hub.

Period	Main Industries	Major Events & Developments	Key Transitions & Impacts
1960s	Jute, shipbuilding, Multinational enterprises manufacturing (NCR, TIMEX, Veeder Root), publishing and printing (DC Thomson, Valentines of Dundee)	A government-protected Jute industry under pressure and decline; NCR, TIMEX and Veeder Root consolidate in Dundee; introduction of cash register and ATM manufacturing (NCR); DC Thomson leads in comics and newspapers (Beano, Dandy, Courier), Valentines of Dundee had consolidated as a major postcard and greeting card maker.	Early diversification into manufacturing of electronics and components; seeds of future tech and creative sectors in a context of Dundee’s traditional industry decline.
1970s	Multinational Enterprises manufacturing, Jute in decline, shipbuilding,	Collapse of jute industry continues; closure of shipyards; TIMEX, Veeder Root and NCR grow (electronics, tachographs, watches); growing unemployment in the area; Michelin tyre	Start of deindustrialisation and aggravated decline of traditional industry; beginning of some economic diversification based on multinational enterprise

	light engineering, publishing	plant begins production (1972). Population starts declining.	manufacturing attracted by post WWII government programs.
1980s	ZX Spectrum manufactured in Dundee, Declining manufacturing, electronics (Timex, NCR)	Economic contraction and major job losses in heavy industry; TIMEX labour disputes begin; NCR expands their ATM production. DMA Design first video game company is created (1988).	Industrial decline is met with early tech investment; some policy-driven regeneration attempts begin too. 'Rebranding' of Dundee as 'The City of Discovery' in 1982
1990s	Public sector, biotech, higher education, emerging game companies	University of Dundee strengthens biomedical research; Spin-offs from DMA appear (Visual Sciences); Welcome Trust Biocentre opens (1997); Abertay launches UK's first games degree (1997); <i>Lemmings</i> (1991) and <i>GTA</i> (1997) from DMA Design have great success; Dundee Contemporary Arts (DCA) opens (1999). Final demise of the Jute industry with the closure of Taybank Mill (1998)	Final decline of the jute industry while Higher education begins to influence the city's economy; early creative tech emerges with some significant early success. Unemployment peaked at 18% in 1991.
2000s	Biotech, education, culture, creative industries	Biotech startups: Dundee Science Centre opens (2000); Denki Games is created by ex/DMA members (2000); Realtime Worlds emerges (2000, previously Rage Studios) and develops <i>Crackdown</i> (2007); Video Game startups from Abertay students emerge and Indie scene grows	Cultural reinvention deepens; games, arts, and biotech gain city-branding value; there are early signs of a post-industrial identity for the city. Manufacturing constituted only 15.2% of employment in 2001, down from 51.6% in 1951 (Tomlinson, 2022).
2010s	Tourism, indie games, public services, Life sciences	Realtime Worlds closes (2010); <i>Monstrum</i> , <i>Autonauts</i> , <i>Phogs!</i> show indie game strength; Creative sector broadens beyond games; Dundee is named Unesco City of Design (2014), V&A Dundee Museum of Design opens (2018); Major Waterfront regeneration takes place.	Dundee increasingly portrayed as a ' design-based ' city; diversification of creative economy.
2020s	Creative and Digital Industries, Green economy, sustainability, games, life sciences.	Closure of Michelin tyre plant (2020); some smart mobility and low-carbon initiatives expand; Video Games consolidate as a sector within the wider Creative Economy . By 2023, 3,530 people were employed within Dundee's creative sector. Fintech and digital economy become more relevant	Less and less of legacy manufacturing; sustainable and digital innovation strengthens. Video Games cluster consolidates and becomes more stable.

Table 5 – Key periods of industrial development, with the reinvention as design and culture city

4.4 Local Industry Features & Components

4.4.1 Perimeter of the cluster

Findings from interviews of D4.1 (summarised in Table 6) highlighted specific components of the geographical and perceived perimeter of the cluster. Interviewees were clear in considering that Dundee is a small city which allows collaboration. On the other end the relative peripheral position of the city creates significant challenges.

D4.1 findings	Description
City and Talent	The city of Dundee is the core of the cluster, supported by a strong talent pipeline from Abertay and Dundee universities. The city's small size fosters close-knit industry ties.
Peripheral Challenges	Geographic remoteness limits access to wider industry networks and senior talent, despite digital workarounds and a well-developed local support system.

Table 6 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster perimeter

In some of the collected secondary sources Dundee is identified as the city with the highest concentration of gaming firms and jobs in Britain, surpassing other cities like Brighton by approximately three times [D0003], although it should be noted that data about companies across the country (as well as in Dundee) tend to be often imprecise. Dundee is recognised as one of the UK's top 20 gaming industry hubs, holding the fourth-highest concentration of gaming companies nationally [D0004]. Documentary material reiterates some of these early findings. For example, sources mention the concept of the "20-minute Games Cluster" [D0047].

This term signifies that all games companies can be visited within about 20 minutes of travel, enabling highly effective networking and knowledge sharing. This is a concept that recalls the 20-minute neighbourhood, synonymous with better quality of living, and incorporated into the Scottish Government's guidance on local living for the 2024 National Planning Framework [D0172]. Possibly the motto, as contained in the documentary sources, is mostly a marketing proposition, yet the nature of this close-knit cluster is also seen by some companies as foundational to their growth, as clearly remarked directly on some of their websites [e.g. D0059].

We used the postcode of the list of companies available in Table 8, to plot the companies' location on a map, as seen in Figure 2. In UK a postcode is a sequence of letters and numbers used to identify a small geographic area (normally composed of no more than 15 postal addresses). While a few companies have offices outwit the city centre, there is a concentration of operation in a small and central area of the city (we could locate precisely 39 companies/points postcodes out of 42, 24 with a unique postcode). Multiple companies share the same postcode (and are often operating from the same building, like the Vision building [D0142] a working space for video game companies).

Figure 2 – Dundee Companies' location by post code and relative density

On this data it is possible to perform some basic calculations of the density of actors in the Dundee game cluster, and the spatial factors that enable their interactions. The average distance between the points is 6.05 km, with a Nearest Neighbor Average of 0.73 km, which means that each gaming company has another company about 730 meters away on average (roughly a 10-minute walk). However, in Figure 2 we can see five companies located outside the city main boundary (provided by the Kingsway circular Road). If we remove those 5 points, the average distance reduces to 1.95 km, with a Nearest Neighbor Average of just 0.5 km. That is, on average, each gaming company located in the city centre has another gaming company just 500 meters away, roughly a 5-minute walk. Therefore, it does seem that the data confirms to an extent the idea of a close-knit cluster of companies, generally reachable in a small amount of time.

Whilst this proximity is seen as a strength of the cluster, interview (D4.1) findings highlighted the relevance of leveraging digital means to overcome challenges relating to the marginal position of the city within the UK and Europe more broadly, albeit perhaps indirectly. Some companies' websites [e.g. [D0053](#) [D0059](#) [D0051](#) [D0141](#)] offer insight into how remote work and flexible working arrangements are integrated into the operations of the cluster. This is possibly an approach to talent acquisition and retention that can mitigate the relative peripheral geographical position. Yet this creates potentially an interesting duality where the strength of the local, physically concentrated cluster (the 20 minutes cluster idea) coexists with attempts at a dispersed talent acquisition strategy, potentially lessening reliance on local workforce resources and immediate geographical proximity. Even activities designed for community building and strategic development incorporate sometimes remote options e.g. [[D0043](#)].

4.4.2 Demography of companies

Documentary sources evidence that there are nearly 2000 companies operating in the video game sector across the UK. Of these 96 operate in Scotland (circa 5% of the total) divided mostly between the two clusters of Edinburgh and Dundee [[D0005](#)]. Other sources such as a 2023 study by estate agency Knight Frank in collaboration with trade body UKIE put the total national number of companies at 2276 [[D0004](#)]. The difficulties of pinning a precise figure on game companies nationally (including in the UK) are well discussed in **GAME-ER** D2.2 using a data-driven approach, where we estimated similar figures for the UK. In the broad UK landscape (with potentially around 2000 companies) Dundee is a small cluster. Other sources show that in 2020 Dundee “*accounted only for 2.7 per cent of all British jobs in gaming*” [[D0003](#)], whereas nearly 1/3 of UK companies are registered in the capital London which also sees the presence of 22.5% of the UK-wide jobs in the video game industry, followed by other cities including Edinburgh, Manchester, and Liverpool.

D4.1 findings	Description
Small Studios	Dundee's ecosystem is mainly composed of small and medium studios, though larger firms like Rockstar and Scopely have a footprint.
Work-for-Hire as a Common Model	Many companies rely on commissioned work to sustain operations, while some also develop original IP. This balance allows financial stability but limits IP ownership.
Publishing & Challenges	Publishing and IP ownership are seen as the most profitable stages in the value chain. However, much of this value is captured by non-local/global firms, making local value retention a key challenge for the cluster.

Table 7 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster companies' demography

The Dundee games cluster is characterised by a balanced range of companies, although evidence from D4.1 interviews (Table 7) showed that small studios are a majority component. In D4.1 we also offered aggregated figures about the cluster. Here in D4.2 based on documentary evidence we are in the position to expand more granularly on companies' demographics. The cluster possibly includes circa 40 game studios within the city, though this is a deeply dynamic figure, sometimes difficult to pinpoint precisely. The presence of Abertay and the steady stream of graduates means that a few new studios are established every year, however studios also cease to exist for a variety of reasons. The Scottish Game Network website currently lists 27 companies in Dundee (although general perception is that there are more, and that there will need to be an update in the current official data, see [D0139]). Table 8 presents a list with a brief presentation of some of these companies that we reconstructed starting from the list available in [D0139] and expanding using our direct knowledge. The table includes some basic information, company specialisation and data (albeit also sometimes imprecise) of companies' size and target markets.

Company	Basic Info	Size & Structure	Market	Specialisation	Sources
4J Studios	Established in 2005, ported Minecraft to consoles	Mid-sized studio; 11-50. Veteran founders	Console gaming	Game porting, console development	[D0140], Mobygames
532 Design	Established in 2022	2-10	Mobile	Sports games	Company Website
Abnormal works	Indie developer/self-publishing label founded by Abertay students. Established December 2024. Looking to incorporate in 2025.	2	Indie/Casual	Physics based precision platformer/puzzle games. Working on Bombunny.	Company Website DCA
Arcade Badgers	Indie mobile and web game developer	Small indie team	Casual/mobile	Arcade-style games	[D0173]
Astrodreamer Studio	Emerging studio	Small team 2-10 employees	Indie/PC gaming	Atmospheric and narrative-driven games, work-for-hire	LinkedIn , [D0052]
Beano Studios	Multimedia Studio leveraging DC Thompson's catalogue of IP.	Unclear. Not enough public info available	Children	Casual	LinkedIn
Biome Collective	Creative collective merging games, tech & art (est. 2015)	Collective of artists/devs/designers	Experimental, cultural	AR/VR, installations, interactive media	[D0088]
Bit Loom	Indie team known for PHOGS!	Small studio	Console and PC indie	Co-op, puzzle-platform games	Nintendo Life , Other Source
Cobra Mobile	Veteran mobile games studio, est. 2005	~8 Staff	iOS, Android, casual markets	Branded and casual mobile games	Scottish Games Network (Closed in June 2025)
Cognitive Games	One-person indie studio founded by Dominik Gawron.	1	Indie	Bullet hell title Deadlocked	Companies House

					DCA
Damage State	Indie Studio known for Scathe. Founded 2019.	Small Indie team	Bullet Hell title Scathe - published by Kwalee.	Bullet hell tittle Scathe.	Companies House , Steam , Scottish Games Network
Denki	Founded in 2000, long-standing creative studio	Mid-sized team (11-50), highly experienced team	Edutainment, casual	Strategy, simulation, automation (Autonauts)	LinkedIn
Earthbound Games	Dundee-based indie developers	Small indie studio	PC/VR indie	Axiom Soccer	Other Source
Etherplay	Blockchain-enabled game dev focused on Ethereum	Small/startup	Web3, crypto games	Blockchain games, smart contracts	[D0174]
Haggis Studios Ltd	Services company producing digital clothing for Games Studios, Heritage Clients, and Fashion Designers. Awarded wild card funding by Scottish Edge in 2025.	Small team	Games Companies, Heritage Clients, Fashion Designer	Game ready digital clothing for a variety of clients.	Company Website , Companies House , Scottish Edge Awards
Hutch Games	Mobile Games developer (HQ in London), established an office in Dundee in 2018	16 Staff	Mobile, Car/Race Games	The Dundee studio works on Performance Marketing and Art Outsource Management	[D0175] TheCourier
Hyper Luminal Games	Founded 2014, now a growing, multi-project studio	~80 staff	Contract work & Steam, consoles	Work-for-hire, some original IP	[D0059] , Scottish Games Network
Icebeam Studios	Emerging narrative studio in Dundee	Small team or early startup	PC/console indie	Story-focused and world-building games	Other Source
Konglomerate Games	Emerging health-focused game developer	~5 staff	Serious Games	Original IP, collaborations with academia and healthcare	[D0051]
LowTek Games	Solo dev known for dyslexia-friendly and retro games	Solo dev	Retro, accessible gaming	8-bit style games with accessibility focus	[D0096]
Ninja Kiwi Europe	Dundee studio for Bloons TD devs, acquired by MTG (2021)	Large parent org with Dundee office	Mobile, browser, console	Tower defense and casual strategy	[D0055] , Scottish Games Network
Outplay Entertainment	One of Dundee's biggest studios, possibly the largest UK mobile studio, creators of Chef Blast	~150 staff	Free-to-Play mobile, global	Casual puzzle games, live ops	[D0053]

			publishing		
Pocket Sized Hands	Independent game studio	11–50 employees	PC, mobile, console	Co-development, porting, AR/VR experiences, work-for-hire	[D0054] LinkedIn
Puny Astronaut	Accessible and welcoming games like Skye Tales.	11–50 employees	Indie/PC gaming	Narrative-driven, family-friendly games	[D0085] LinkedIn
Rockstar Dundee (Ruffian Games)	Formerly an independent studio, now operating as Rockstar Dundee under Rockstar Games.	Approximately 40 employees (as of 2020)	Console gaming	Action-adventure games	[D0149] Wikipedia
Sad Owl Studios	Formerly Robot Teddy. Founded by Matt Stark to develop Viewfinder. Acquired by Thunderful Publishing in 2021?	1-10 Employees	PC/PlayStation	Puzzle/Photography game	Wikipedia, [D0176]
Shouty Knot Games	Independent	4	Educational and Applied Games	Education	Other Source
Sloth Doctor Games	Independent developer	1 employee with several contractors	Indie	Developing Heldritch Rush	LinkedIn, Other Source
Stand Out Games	Small VR/AR app company	Small team	VR/AR applications	Bespoke VR/AR software development	LinkedIn
Stormcloud Games	Independent developer	11–50 employees	Educational and casual gaming	Full-cycle game development, work-for-hire	[D0087], LinkedIn
Studio Catloaf	Independent developer	1 employee	JRPG	JRPG, Creature Collector, Pixel Art. Working on The Book of Abominations.	LinkedIn Steam
Spikey Teeth Studios	Independent developer	3 Employees	Indie	Working on the Indie Brawler Overcat	LinkedIn Companies House Steam DCA
Tag Games	Mobile game developer, now a Scopely studio.	Approximately 60 employees	Mobile gaming	Free-to-play and premium mobile game development	[D0077] Wikipedia
Team Ghost Camp	Indie Developer	3-4 Staff	Indie	Social Deduction games. Currently working on Forest of Deceit.	Steam DCA

Team Terrible Games	Indie game developer known for the viral hit The Baby in Yellow.	~10 staff	Indie/PC gaming	Horror-themed games with unique mechanics	[D0094], LinkedIn
Team Junkfish	Independent studio, known for Monstrum.	11–50 employees	PC and console gaming	Horror and survival games	[D0095] LinkedIn
The Scarlet Bureau	CRPG and Narrative Design Studio founded by Brian Mitsoda and Cara Ellison.	2 Employees	CRPG and Narrative Design	Consulting in Narrative Design and pitching for investment to produce an original CRPG title.	Other Source
Two Tailed Fox	Indie studio known for Space War Battle Cadet DX, focusing on unique game experiences.	Small team	Indie/PC gaming	Retro-inspired and experimental games	Scottish Games Network Other Source (Closed April 2023)
Very Evil Demons	Workers Coop. Work for hire with plans for own IP.	4 employees	Indie/PC gaming	Work for hire with a variety of clients in the cluster and beyond.	Other Source
Yellow Crow Games	Indie, creators of For Hexposure, winners of Dare Academy 2022.	Small team	Indie/PC gaming	Narrative-driven and artistic games	[D0177]
YoYo Games	Developer of the GameMaker engine, enabling 2D game development for indie developers and professionals.	Medium-sized team	Game development tools	Game engine development	Wikipedia , Other Source

Table 8 – Summary of companies in the cluster (where data is available), the majority are small studios

4.5 Cluster Evolution

4.5.1 Critical moments, phases and evolution curves

D4.1 findings	Description
Cluster Diversification	Expansion to new genres/platforms, rise of mobile gaming, emergence of diverse entrepreneurs, and bridging initiatives like Dare to be Digital.
Complexity and Community	Cluster with many small studios and few large players like Rockstar North, increasing stakeholder engagement, ongoing needs for cohesion, government support, and funding.

Table 9 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster evolution and critical moments

It does seem difficult to apply the concept of evolution curves (as something that show a phenomenon changing over time) to the Dundee cluster, based on the document analysis. There has of course been change over the years, but it is not immediately evident there were specific ‘curves’ that could be captured. One interesting aspect for focusing on ‘change’ however is to look at the transformation of companies: the closure and subsequent openings of various operations. This, we believe, can pinpoint some emerging patterns of change.

A key shift that took place in the cluster of course was that of DMA Design (the company considered by all as the founding asset of the cluster) which was acquired by Take-Two and then became Rockstar North, relocating to Edinburgh in the year 2000. Table 10 instead shows significant companies closures in the cluster, with the most recent in 2025. As the table shows sometimes closures were caused by endogenous production/product problems (like in the case of Realtime Worlds, whose final title APB, with costs in excess of \$100 million, making it one of the most expensive games ever produced at the time, was released to mixed reviews in 2010), sometimes by exogenous factors like changes in market, or cancellation of contracts.

Company	Founded – Closed	Key Products / Focus	Reason & Impact	Sources
Cobra Mobile	2005-2025	iBomber series, Storm in a Teacup, Apple Arcade titles	Liquidated after 20 years; 8 redundancies due to financial losses	Wikipedia , Scottish Games Network
Rage Games (Scotland) Limited	2000-2002	N/A	Was sold to Dave Jones and became Realtime Worlds	(Phil Wilson interview , Wikipedia)
Realtime Worlds	2002-2010	<i>Crackdown</i> , <i>APB</i>	Entered administration post-APB flop; ~150 jobs lost	Wikipedia
Reagent Games	2014-2019	<i>Crackdown 3</i> co-production	Successor to Realtime Worlds	(Phil Wilson), Companies House , Gamesindustry.biz
Cohort Studios	2006-2011	<i>Buzz! Junior</i> series, MotorStorm work	Console market decline	Wikipedia
Guerilla Tea	~2011-2018	<i>Play to Cure: Genes in Space</i> , casual & educational games	Dissolved after seven years; focused exit	Wikipedia
Dynamo Games	2004-2018	Mobile <i>Championship Manager</i> , social sports games	Closed post-shift to social games	Other Source
Visual Science	1993-2006	EA-affiliated F1 titles, console game client work	Administration after major project cancellation by Vivendi	Wikipedia
VIS Entertainment	1996-2005	<i>State of Emergency</i>	Acquired by BAM! Entertainment, then placed into administration and dissolved	Wikipedia

Table 10 – Main companies' closure in the Dundee cluster

Table 11 shows instead some spin-off studios (grouped by parent company) with Figure 3 representing the table in a visual format. Here we can suggest the presence of a pattern. What this material seems to show is that studios may close over time, but their talent and culture do appear to persist in new forms, new endeavours and new companies. This may indicate the importance of the “20-minute cluster” in keeping and retaining critical mass for emerging organisations. For example, the closure of Realtime World led to multiple spin offs, with Realtime World itself deriving

from DMA Design originally (as the root company of the cluster). This further strengthens the image of Dundee as a cluster of interlinked SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises). There does seem to be a potential model of organic evolution. Indeed, rather than having a top-down formalisation as a cluster structure, the Dundee cluster appears to evolve in a bottom-up fashion, through individual initiative, collaboration, rebuilding, closure and recombination.

Spin-off Studio	Origin / Parent Company	Founded	Focus	Status
Realtime Worlds	DMA Design (employees from)	2002	Console AAA titles (Crackdown, APB)	Closed (2010)
Visual Science	DMA Design (employees from)	1993	PlayStation Games (F1 2000)	Closed (2006)
Cohort Studios	Visual Science	2006	Console and PlayStation games	Closed (2011)
Proper Games	Visual Science	2006	Indie/arcade titles (Flock!)	Liquidated (2020–2021)
Tag Games	VIS (employees from)	2006	Mobile & free-to-play games	Active
4J Studios	VIS Entertainment	2005	Console ports (Minecraft for consoles)	Active
Outplay Entertainment	Realtime Worlds	2010	Mobile free-to-play games	Active
Ruffian Games	Realtime Worlds	2008	Console games (Crackdown 2)	Acquired (2020, now Rockstar Dundee)
eeGeo	Realtime Worlds (employees and tech from)	2011	3D mapping & geo-visualization technology	Unclear, possibly moved to LA and changed name in 2017 (Other Source)
Binary Pumpkin	Cohort Studio (employees from)	2011	Mobile Games	Closed (2020)
Stormcloud Games	Cohort Studios	2012	Narrative/indie games	Active

Table 11 – Spin-off studios (main examples)

Figure 3 – Closure and re-composition of main companies over time

Table 12 presents a selection of acquisitions that have influenced the composition and development of companies. To complement this, Figure 4 offers a visual representation of these acquisitions along a timeline, highlighting key moments and trends in the cluster’s evolution.

Year	Dundee Company	Acquirer / Target	Type	Notes	Sources
2004	VIS Entertainment	BAM! Entertainment	Acquired	Predecessor to 4J Studios, acquired before later closure.	Wikipedia
2012	Digital Goldfish	Acquired by Ninja Kiwi	Acquired	Became Ninja Kiwi Europe; Dundee-based studio.	Scottish Games Network
2015	YoYo Games	Acquired by Playtech	Acquired	For ~£10.65 M.	Scottish Games Network
2016	Outplay Entertainment	Acquired Eight Pixels Square	Acquired	---	BBC
2018	4J Studios	Invested in Puny Astronaut (Dundee)	Investment	Six-figure investment to support local indie studio (Mar 2018). 4JStudio moving into publishing	Wikipedia
2020	Outplay Entertainment	Sold Eight Pixels Square to Miniclip	Divestment	Outplay divested the studio (reported in 2020).	Scottish Games Network

2020	Ruffian Games	Acquired by Take-Two / Rockstar	Acquired	Became Rockstar Dundee (Oct 2020).	Wikipedia
2021	Ninja Kiwi	Acquired by MTG (Modern Times Group)	Acquired	For ~ USD 142 M (Mar 24, 2021).	Wikipedia [D0148]
2021	YoYo Games	Opera	Acquired	forms the basis for 'Opera Gaming', For ~ USD 10 M	Other Source
2021	4J Studios / Chroma Ventures	Invested in Ant Workshop & StormCloud Games	Investment	Seven-figure fund supports multiple indie studios (2021 onward).	Scottish Games Network
2023	Tag Games	Acquired by Scopely	Acquired	Fully acquired June 29, 2023 after prior investment (~\$50 M in 2021).	[D0077]
2024	Ninja Kiwi	Acquired AutoAttack Games	Acquired	April 16, 2024; adds Legion TD 2 studio.	[D0148]

Table 12 – Acquisitions (main examples)

Figure 4 – Acquisitions (main examples)

What this material on acquisitions suggests is that sometimes Dundee’s video game studios may be stepping stones in the strategic expansion of larger companies. This possibly reflects a degree of external interest in the city’s talent pool and IPs, particularly from major players in the mobile sectors (such as Scopely [\[D0077\]](#)). One notable example is Ninja Kiwi, which has significantly expanded its presence in Dundee over the years. After acquiring Digital Goldfish in 2012 and establishing Ninja Kiwi Europe (with Ninja Kiwi HQ based in New Zealand), the company was acquired by MTG in 2021. Subsequently Ninja Kiwi Europe acquired Auto Attack Games in 2024.

At the same time, the material shows some local investment activity to sustain and grow the ecosystem from inside. 4JStudio, for instance, has supported emerging studios such as Puny Astronaut (2018) and Ant Workshop/StormCloud (2020). These were targeted investments, and not

acquisitions, which suggests a deliberate strategy to support and develop the local creative independence, allowing and supporting growth for smaller local studios.

4.5.2 Major factors of change & growth

According to some sources from the documentary corpus, in Scotland the games industry contributes over £188.5 million annually to the economy. This is marginally lower than the contribution made by other digital industries such as fintech, data, or cybersecurity [D0002 D0023]. Other sources put the net contribution of the videogame industry to the Scottish economy at £350 million [D0004 D0048]. The report of a meeting of the Scottish Parliament on Scottish Game Week 2023 also asserts that “*The industry contributes £129 million to our gross domestic product through direct and indirect tax revenue, and Scotland-based games development companies invest £141 million in jobs and are responsible for employing 6,400 people.*” [D0048]. Overall, the figures around the contribution of video games to the national economy (of Scotland) are not precise, and there is nothing in the documentary sources more specific about Dundee.

Documents have indicated an interesting development in the growth of the Dundee’s cluster: the rise of locally-based investors with considerable history in the cluster. Chroma Ventures has emerged as an interesting actor of the recent growth of Dundee’s tech and games ecosystem. Founded in 2021 by the co-founders of 4J Studios [D0151], Chroma Ventures functions as both an investment arm of 4J and a strategic enabler, supporting high-potential startups and scaling ventures in gaming, technology, and creative sectors in Dundee but also beyond that. What makes Chroma Ventures different from other actors that the cluster has experienced so far is that its influence over the cluster does not appear to be merely financial—as has been noted by Frank Arnot of Stormcloud Games [D0152]. It brings industry expertise, global networks, and an element of a long-term vision for sustainable growth.

In its interview for D4.1, 4J and Chroma Ventures high authority described the difficulties that can arise for local industry due to external investor goals through the example of VIS Entertainment. “We kind of fell out with Take-Two... What we then found out was, the shareholders, investors that we’d brought in in the mid-’90s, seven, eight years later, they’re looking to recover their investment... So we sold the company... Even though I was CEO, I had an opinion, but our shareholders wanted to sell... We found ourselves in 2003, 2004, with no company. Everything had gone.” That experience seems to have informed the locally focused ethos of Chroma Ventures. “Our agenda is, if Dundee gets stronger as a place to develop games, and a better community, it’s going to help me as much as it’ll help anybody else.” Moreover, it is a locally headquartered venture fund and has potential to support a more genuine ecosystem. Chroma Ventures sits alongside Chroma Developments [D0169], which built the Water’s Edge dockside hub hosting companies like 4J, Hutch, and others. By co-locating startups, developers, and investors in the same physical space, it aims to foster collaboration and energy – turning the waterfront into a vibrant creative-tech cluster. Digital games and media companies backed by Chroma Ventures include independent games studios Puny Astronaut and Stormcloud Games (based in Dundee); studio and publisher Team 17 (with offices in Wakefield, Nottingham and Manchester); London-based augmented reality studio Blippar; and the Edinburgh-based Ant Workshop [D0152]. Through these investments, Chroma Ventures has helped local studios transition from indie beginnings to commercially viable, talent-attracting operations. Notably, Chroma Ventures made some significant investments during the early part of the decade – during and shortly after the pandemic. This may have provided needed support for companies in

the Dundee cluster in a time of considerable uncertainty and amidst a wider lack of funding opportunities.

As a Dundee-grown group reinvesting in the region, Chroma Ventures possibly embodies a new phase of endogenous development — where local success stories fuel the next generation of entrepreneurs. Through this role, it has become a key driver of Dundee’s transformation into a resilient and ambitious tech hub. The organisation is also an example of several dynamics that have been discussed in **GAME-ER’s** WP2 analyses of spatial clustering. **D2.1 – Report on the Current state of knowledge on Video game Industry as CCIs**³ noted the importance in the economics research literature on industrial clusters of ‘spin-off dynamics and senior entrepreneurship, with the existence of successful parent firms or individuals tending to generate a larger number of more successful spin-offs. The Dundee team’s research has also provided further evidence of these dynamics beyond Chroma Ventures, with interviewees for upcoming tasks indicating that they have also been active in local investment within the cluster. Full analysis of these interviews will be forthcoming in D4.3 and D4.4.

Role Area	Activities & Impact	Example Relating to the Cluster
Independent Game Publishing Stakeholder	Supporting independent game development and publishing activity.	Stormcloud Games.
Workspace Developer	Transformed dockside space into a bustling, award-winning hub	Water’s Edge offices for startups
Community Anchor	Hosts meetups, social events, and networking in tech/AI	AI & The Digital Edge event with Dundee & Angus Chamber
R&D Champion	Supports virtual production & creative-tech labs	CoSTAR Realtime Lab with Abertay and CodeBase
Cluster Sponsor	Backs gaming festivals, incubators, and studio growth	Support for Scottish Games Week and Team Terrible
Strategic Facilitator	Partners on policy, skills, and inclusive growth initiatives	Joint events with Dundee & Angus Chamber and local council

Table 13 – Summary of Chroma Ventures activities related to the cluster

4.6 Collective Actions

4.6.1 Main activities and collective actions

D4.1 provided an overview of actors’ perception about main activities and collective actions in the cluster. Main findings included considerations on a number of existing and past events, and other talent and innovation fostering initiatives (reviewed in Table 14). However, Dundee differed from other case studies in the project insofar as it does not have a ‘cluster’ organisation that coordinates collective action. Therefore, our understanding of collective action in this case is conceived broadly and catches a range of forms of ‘coming together’ to conduct activities.

³ Deliverable available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542239>

D4.1 findings	Description
Events and Showcases	Festivals like Arcadia and DCA’s Drop in and Play provide key platforms for showcasing games, fostering public engagement, and enabling networking among industry professionals.
Strong Informal Community	Close personal ties, informal knowledge exchange, and social meetups (e.g., Hubworld) sustain collaboration and help share best practices within the cluster.
Abertay University’s Key Role	Connects academia and industry through DARE Academy, mentoring programs such as the Professional Project Module, graduate showcases, and recruitment opportunities to nurture talent.

Table 14 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster collective actions

Documents analysis generally does seem to just confirm and add detail to those previous observations. Here we therefore just offer a summary of some of the key cluster events and initiatives in a tabular format (Table 15), as they have emerged from the documentary evidence. The key event is the ‘DARE Academy’ which is to a larger extent one of the activities which ‘incubates’ new studios for the cluster. Here a key role played by Abertay University. Dundee’s very active game development and digital arts culture include a variety of recurring events that blend creativity, collaboration, and public engagement. Students and creators are supported in crafting industry-level prototypes and sharing their work with diverse audiences. City-wide festivals like NEoN (North East of North) and Arcadia celebrate digital expression (albeit Arcadia will not run this year) have provided larger-scale events, while grassroots events such as Hubworld’s play parties, Games Talks Live, and Game Jams fuel experimentation and community-building.

Event	Timeframe	Description	Sources
DARE to Be Digital / DARE Academy	2000–present (public expo since ~2010, held each August)	Abertay’s flagship and longstanding student game-dev competition, in its current format is open to Abertay University students in teams of up to 8. It offers industry mentoring, support and advice to teams to help them create an industry standard game prototype.	[D0143]
ProtoPlay (Tranzfuser Showcase)	Annual, September	Showcase for UK-wide Tranzfuser teams to present playable games developed over the summer. Free public festival.	Scottish Games Network
Drop-In & Play @ Dundee Contemporary Arts (DCA)	2012–present	Indie-developer meetups at DCA Museum where creators can demo games, gather feedback, and network in a casual setting. There also is a DARE related event, in 2025 running at the end of August.	[D0010 D0011 D0146]
NEoN Digital Arts Festival / AppJam	Started in 2009	Part of a city-wide digital arts week, bringing digital media, performance, sound and technology-driven arts to Dundee	[D0147]
Dee- Con (Anime & Gaming Convention)	2009–present	Hosted by Dundee University Students’ Assoc., combining anime, cosplay and gaming.	Other Source

Hubworld events	From 2024	Casual “play party” hosted by Hubworld Scotland. Knowledge Exchange events, Regular social evenings	[D0017 D0046]
Arcadia Festival	Since 2017 (typically biennial/annual)	A two-day grassroots showcase focusing on independent, alternative, and experimental play.	[D0109 D0111]
Games Talks Live – Dundee	Since Apr 2023, ongoing	A recurring developer meetup and talk series across Dundee, Glasgow, and Edinburgh. Brings together local meetup hosts and focuses on inclusive industry discussion	Youtube Scottish Games Network
Game Jams (various)	Ongoing, regular	Summer Game Jam Jamboree (Hubworld), Dundee & Angus College Game Jam, Global Game Jam – Dundee Makerspace, Abertay Students’ Game Jams	e.g. [D0043 D0016 D0069]

Table 15 – Summary of events in the Dundee cluster

4.6.2 Stakeholders' motivations, benefits, & main contributions

The Dundee video game cluster is supported by a dynamic ecosystem, involving various stakeholders with distinct motivations and deriving significant benefits from their participation or delivering significant benefits for the cluster. Findings from D4.1 pointed mostly to three main stakeholders: studios, professionals and the University (Table 16). Here, using documentary evidence we provide additional information, also encompassing other stakeholders, not necessarily located within Dundee with relevant links to it and deriving benefits and motives from their connection to the cluster. This material is provided in tabular form as presented in Table 17.

D4.1 findings	Description
Video Game Studios	Seek product visibility, feedback, talent, and networking opportunities; contribute by mentoring, sponsoring events, and sharing expertise.
Abertay University	Align education with industry needs, support student employment, enhance reputation; contribute by organizing events, providing facilities, and collaboration.
Industry Professionals	Aim to strengthen local connections and knowledge sharing; contribute by volunteering to organize events and build community networks.

Table 16 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster

Stakeholder	Main Motivation	Key Benefits
Abertay University	To lead in games education [D0039, D0047], generate a highly skilled workforce [D0005], foster new ventures, and link education directly to industry demands.	Consistently ranked as Europe's top games school and globally competitive (13th for undergraduate, 7th for postgraduate). Produces graduates who found successful local studios. Provides cutting-edge research facilities directly linked to industry needs. Central to research and innovation in the cluster e.g. (InGAME [D0025]).
Scottish Government	To recognise the potential of games, growth and job creation. To amplify global reputation and ensure effective support for the sector [D0002, D0044, D0048].	Provides backing for the National Games Strategy [D0023, D0044]. Supports the TechScaler network (run by CodeBase) which offers expertise and facilities to startups. Actively engages industry leaders, including roundtable discussions. Creative Scotland Funds Creative Dundee and interdisciplinary creative work including game arts.
UK Games Fund	To support early-stage games development across the UK,	Provides grant support for commercial development to participants of programmes like DunDev [D0035]. Its Dundee

(UK Govt.)	and to be rooted in an established creative community (like Dundee) for effective operations and better serving the 'UK-wide' community [D0047].	base allows it to leverage the city's cultural investments like V&A Dundee for wider stakeholder events, it attracts startups and supports Dundee-based developers. Provides accommodation, office space, and prize money. Creates opportunities to pitch to the UK Games Fund for prototype grants, professional networks and peer support [D150].
Industry Orgs (e.g., UKIE, Scottish Games Network, TIGA)	To represent and advocate for the games industry, ensure access to finance and talent, lobby for supportive policies (e.g. D0031, D0091), and foster community and collaboration also locally [e.g. D0046].	Advocate for Tax Reliefs [D0005, D0035, D0036]. Provide industry data and mapping tools (e.g., UK Games Map, by UKIA). Organise major events like Scottish Games Week [D0048]. Facilitate networking through events (e.g., "microtalks," Dundee Games Meetup) [D0045, D0046]. Accredite Abertay game programs; supports awards and events in Dundee; validate education-industry pipeline (TIGA) [D0143, D0091, Other Source]
Game Development Studios	To create games, innovate, grow their businesses, secure funding, attract talent, and maintain a competitive edge.	Access to a constant flow of skilled graduates from Abertay University [D0005, D0024, D0047]. Benefit from funding and innovation support from initiatives such as InGAME and UK Games Fund [e.g. D0021]. Opportunities for early-stage development support through DunDev [D0035]. Enhanced networking and collaboration within a strong local community [D0047]. Some, achieve growth and success, becoming major employers [e.g. D0020]. Others gain recognition as leading developers [e.g. D0053].
Creative/Cultural Institutions (e.g., Creative Dundee, V&A Dundee, DCA, BAFTA)	To showcase local talent and innovation [e.g. D0012, D0070, D0113, D0121], foster collaboration and community across creative disciplines [e.g. D0057, D0063], and connect arts/heritage with the games sector [D0060, D0061, D0062].	Host events like "Drop in and Play" at DCA, providing a platform for developers to showcase new games and gather audience feedback. V&A Dundee curated the "Videogames: Design/Play/Disrupt" exhibition, showcasing game design as a significant art form [D0060]. Creative Dundee partnered with InGAME to explore the future of creative industries [e.g. D0065].
Individuals (e.g., Students, Developers, Freelancers, Players)	To gain skills, pursue careers, find employment, showcase work, collaborate, explore new technologies, express creativity, and contribute to social change/wellbeing.	Access to world-class education and research facilities (Abertay University) [D0039, D0047]. Opportunities to showcase projects and connect with potential employers at events like the Digital Graduate Show [D0024] and "Drop in and Play". Benefit from early-career support programs for young entrepreneurs like DunDev [D0035]. Access to networking, mentorship and community events (Hubworld, SGDA) [e.g. D0045, D0046].
Dundee City Council	To support the growth of the digital sector, attract inward investment [D0047], invest in digital infrastructure.	The cluster plays a key role in the city's economy through jobs, investment, and tax revenues. It helps retain graduates and attract talent to the city, with wider benefits to sectors like education, healthcare, and tourism. The industry also supports community engagement, digital inclusion, and youth opportunities

Table 17 - Expanded motivations and benefits of stakeholders

4.7 Co-ordination and formal control structures

Research performed for D4.1, and summarised in Table 18, showed several key components relating to coordination and structures in the Dundee cluster. For example, it was noted that the small and compact nature of the cluster allows informal coordination, and studios and key local industry leaders are also supportive of each other and of younger companies and professionals. Dundee does not have a formal cluster organisation, nor is there any direct political top-down approach. The

interview analysis also made clear the challenge relating to the broader coordination of activities at national level, despite the presence of some initial institutional attempts at this. Across the corpus of documents, several key terms consistently emerge that reflect both the broader (UK and Scotland) and the more specific (Dundee cluster) contexts of coordination within the video game sector.

D4.1 findings	Description
Formal Coordination	Abertay University and UK Games Fund (with DunDev) provide structured programs, funding, mentorship, and workspace, creating formal industry-academia cluster support.
Informal Coordination	Geographic proximity and personal relationships promote informal communication, reputation-based accountability, and social cohesion.
Reciprocity and Solidarity	Established studios actively support startups through advice, subcontracting, and funding sharing
Coordination Challenges	Despite strong ties, formal large-scale collaboration is limited by a lack of unified local policy. Efforts toward a national strategy and broader networks are emerging.

Table 18 - Emerging aspects of the cluster for coordination, D4.1

4.7.1 National Coordination Context

At the national (Scotland) levels, recurring phrases appearing in documents include “*strategic allocation of resources*,” “*coordinated approach to trade*” and “*coordinated approach to the gaming ecosystem*.” These terms suggest a widespread recognition of the need for greater integration and alignment of activities and resources, whether industrial or trade related. Possibly in a context where industry players perceive that a more coordinated approach could provide benefits to the industry, but institutional players are probably slow in capturing this need. This recognition does not necessarily indicate the existence of formalised structures dedicated to such coordination, but there are clear movements in that direction in Scotland, which could therefore potentially benefit also the Dundee cluster. Notably, in early 2024, the Scottish Government endorsed the development of a “**National Games Strategy**” [D0044] which is described by its advocates as the first of its kind in the UK. As a result, Scotland is positioned in public discourse as the first UK nation to establish a dedicated strategy to support the video game ecosystem. The responsibility for producing this strategy lies with the Scottish Games Network, a sector-wide umbrella organisation that represents all aspects of interactive entertainment in Scotland. This initiative highlights the growing awareness of the importance of a nationally coordinated approach to supporting and developing the video game industry. However, by the Scottish Governments own admission a key objective of the strategy is to **build greater understanding at a government level**, addressing a historical lack of comprehensive data collection and “patchy, out of date, or just lacking any real understanding” of the sector’s needs.

A similar emphasis on coordination and strategic planning can be found in UKIE’s written evidence to the UK Parliament’s inquiry into the Creative Industries in Scotland [D005]. UKIE stands for the UK Interactive Entertainment and is the trade body for the UK’s video games and interactive entertainment industry. In the written evidence document, UKIE calls for “*additional funding to undertake a coordinated and strategic programme of trade and investment activity targeting priority markets for exports and inward investment*.”. Again, the theme of greater coordination and a more strategic approach to resources occurs, however this is also done against possible challenges. In the same written evidence document for instance, it is remarked of a historical lack

of collaboration between the UK and Scottish governments in trade show participation, citing the Games Development Conference (GDC) as an instance where separate national and regional stands were presented. They argue that closer cooperation would yield mutual benefits and have proposed a coordinated, UK-wide trade and investment programme for the games sector in partnership with public agencies. In another document [D0031] called the UKIE Video Game Industry Manifesto, UKIE highlights the importance of “strategically allocating resources to address specific skill gaps, the industry can proactively cultivate a well-rounded workforce equipped to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving sector”. This time the issue of lack of coordination and the need for better strategic use of resources is related to skills development for the industry. In summary the broader context in which the cluster is located appears to imply a degree of lack of coordination, with some initial attempts to overcome immediate challenges. While formalised structures for such coordination remain limited still, initiatives such as Scotland’s forthcoming National Games Strategy and UKIE’s calls for a unified UK-wide approach to trade and skills development indicate a shift towards more integrated policymaking. These developments suggest that although institutional responses have historically lagged industry needs, there is some movement at addressing fragmentation and offering better coordinated support.

4.7.2 Cluster Coordination Examples

When it comes to Dundee more specifically, the documentary material allows to observe some interesting area of coordination of activities. Noteworthy are in particular the activities taking place in recent years around R&D, most of the time with Abertay University playing the role of the central actor, marshalling together diverse cluster actors. To an extent these stories of successful R&D initiatives show that Dundee has increasingly been recognised at the national/UK level as a key hub for video game innovation, with its ecosystem frequently cited in government and industry reports as a model for regional cluster development. In D4.1 we noted that innovation and technology can be considered as key element of the cluster “DNA”. For example, Abertay led InGame, a £11.5M R&D initiative. InGame (Innovation for Games and Media Enterprise) mission was to enhance the scale and value of the Dundee games cluster through activities such as de-risk of innovation, scale-up capacity, and focus on addressing systemic challenges [D0024, D0025]. A key feature of InGAME’s approach was that of creating an alignment across a wide range of academic, industry, public, and civic actors for the sector. InGame partnerships extended to external companies like Microsoft, or the BBC, local companies such as Beano Studios/DC Thomson, Outplay, 4J Studios, as well as cultural and public institutions including Creative Scotland, Scottish Enterprise, and Dundee City Council. InGAME operated as a collaborative hub that strengthened Dundee’s visibility and competitiveness within the UK and global games sectors. Its contribution to sectoral knowledge and policy was further demonstrated through its co-authorship of the “Scotland’s Games Ecosystem: The State of Play” report with the Scottish Games Network. Table 19 provides a summary of InGAME.

InGame	Description
Type	Cluster Integration Platform
Sectoral Focus	Video Games
Primary Role	Convening and coordinating regional cluster actors
Coordination Logic	Horizontal collaboration across academia, SMEs, industry, and public sector
Value Creation	De-risking innovation, enabling scale-up, addressing challenges
Key Activities	Collaborative R&D, policy co-production, ecosystem strengthening

Core Strength	Deep engagement with regional stakeholders; cluster development
----------------------	---

Table 19 – Example of coordination in R&D for cluster integration, led by Abertay

Another initiative around R&D is CoSTAR. CoSTAR Realtime Lab is a flagship initiative that positions Dundee at the forefront of innovation in real-time content production and immersive media [D0130]. Launched in 2025 with a £9 million investment as part of the UKRI-funded CoSTAR programme, the lab is based at the Water’s Edge facility in Dundee and led by Abertay University in collaboration with the University of Edinburgh, CodeBase, Interface, and Chroma Developments. In essence CoSTAR is virtual production studio, integrating technologies such as CGI, motion capture, and augmented reality to support R&D across film, television, gaming, immersive performance, and live events. CoSTAR can be seen as a collaborative platform for academia, industry, and public agencies, bringing together partners including Screen Scotland, Scottish Enterprise, AWS, and Nvidia, to drive experimentation, prototype development, and technical skills training. Through initiatives like the Realtime TEST Lab and TechScaler programming, it enables SMEs and creative practitioners to access advanced facilities and expertise, fostering cross-sector knowledge exchange and scaling capacity.

CoSTAR	Description
Type	Creative Technology Testbed
Sectoral Focus	Film, TV, Video Games, Immersive Media
Primary Role	Providing infrastructure for experimentation and real-time content production
Coordination Logic	Vertical integration across production pipelines and technical workflows
Value Creation	Access to cutting-edge tools, technical R&D, prototyping, and upskilling
Key Activities	Virtual production, open-access labs, industry R&D pilots, Realtime TEST Lab
Core Strength	Technological infrastructure and cross-sector applications

Table 20 – Example of coordination in R&D for a technology Testbed, led by Abertay

To conclude, a key observation is that Universities (like Abertay) can play a key role in coordinating activities within a cluster by acting as centres not only for talent development, but also for direct research, and industry collaboration. In regions like Dundee, academic institutions often serve as bridging entities between government, industry, and local communities, helping to align efforts.

4.8 Financial Aspects

The analysis of the interview data revealed several key insights into the financial dynamics of the cluster, which are summarised in Table 21. A prominent theme that emerged is the reliance of many studios on a work-for-hire model to sustain their operations; alongside the challenges they face in developing original intellectual property (IP). Although these two issues are not frequently discussed in publicly available documents, the documentary material provides valuable additional context regarding the financial landscape of the cluster. In particular, it sheds light on the role of public financial support, which appears, at least to some extent, to address some of the difficulties reported by studios during the interviews.

D4.1 findings	Description
Financial sustainability	Many small and medium-sized companies struggle to balance creative passion with building profitable models, often relying on work-for-hire contracts that limit long-term growth.
Funding difficulties and risk	The hit-driven global market makes securing investment and publishing deals very challenging, particularly for original IP development.
Need for business education	There is a strong need to embed entrepreneurship and business skills training within educational institutions to help student entrepreneurs transition successfully to running sustainable companies.

Table 21 - Financial aspects of the cluster emerging from D4.1

4.8.1 General context

One notable insight from the documentary analysis is the role played by UK Games Talent and Finance (UKGTF) in directly addressing the financial challenges identified through the interviews. UKGTF emerges as a key actor within the UK games ecosystem, with a particularly strong presence in Dundee. Its activities align closely with the areas highlighted as problematic by studio representatives, specifically, the support for the creation of new IP and the development of business skills. Established in 2015 as a not-for-profit community interest company, UKGTF has spearheaded initiatives such as the UK Games Fund (UKGF), which offers early-stage grants to small studios, and Tranzfuser, a talent development competition aimed at graduates, as well as the content fund for established SMEs. Table 22 outlines the main public financial support mechanisms currently available at the UK level for the gaming sector. In addition to the UKGTF support the table lists other financial mechanisms available directly from the UK Government.

Type of Support	Name / Scheme	Funding Scale &	Timeframe	Purpose / Scope	Target Beneficiaries	Sources
Tax Relief	Video Games Tax Relief (VGTR)	Up to 2% refund on qualifying UK production expenditure	Ongoing since April 2014 (expected to close in 2027)	Incentivise domestic games development; support projects meeting a UK cultural test	UK game development studios producing culturally British or EEA projects	[D0153] [D0154] [D0155] [D0164]
Credit net of tax deductions	Video Games Expenditure Credit (VGEC)	A credit of 25.5% after deduction of tax	Replacing the VGTR	Incentivise domestic games development; support projects meeting a UK cultural test	EEA expenditure no longer applies; UK Only	[D1059]
Prize	Tranzfuser (UKGF)	£7,500 prize	2016 - ongoing	Graduate entrepreneurship ; business mentoring	Graduates wishing to form studios	[D0161]
Grants & Seed Funding	Prototype Fund (UKGF) & Tranzfuser	Grants of up to £30,000	2015– present	Early-stage prototype funding;	Early-stage independent games development studios;	[D0156]

Content Fund	Content Fund (UKGF)	Grants from £50k–£150k; £3m awarded to 22 studios in April 2024	Launched Sept 2023; ongoing	Scale up studio projects to market-ready stage; attract investment	Small-to-mid-sized studios (established) with own IP	[D0156]
Growth Package	Games Growth Package	£30m total – £10m annually (2025–28)	2025 (June) –2028	Expand UKGF capacity; invest in start-up infrastructure, skills, and business growth	Early-stage and scaling game companies across UK regions	[D0157] [D0158]

Table 22 – Main sources of financial support for video game companies (UK)

4.8.2 Considerations for the cluster

Albeit the scale in which Dundee studios use and benefit from the existing public financial support is not always easy to pinpoint, occasionally documentary sources allow to identify cases in which companies directly benefitted. The easiest to map is the support from the UKGTF prototype fund as the organisation websites lists all the projects that received support across all the rounds, and a cursory search matching with the cluster company names, allows to reconstruct the beneficiaries. By our reconstruction nine Dundee studios received support for their prototypes from UKGTF (for example [Denki](#), [Astrodreamers](#), [Tag-In](#), [Ice Beam](#), [Konglomerate](#), [Hyperluminal](#)) with some receiving it more than once (for example Stormcloud Games). The UKGF content fund, rather than providing seed-funding, seeks to support established studios who already own their IP, and seek funding to scale up. Also in this case, the projects funded through this scheme are available on the website and allow to identify which studios from the cluster received support. Our reconstruction is that two studios received support the content fund (see [D0162](#) and [D0163](#)). Generally, therefore the Dundee-based studios do benefit from this type of support, at different levels. Much less public information is available about the Tax Relief scheme. Because this information is not typically made public. The UK government does not normally publish a comprehensive list of all companies that receive this tax relief. There is some evidence however that the cluster benefits from this scheme. A newspaper article cites the director of the UK Games Fund (which is based in Dundee), expressing that “*Some of the bigger titles which are developed in this city have been subject to tax relief.*” [\[D0165\]](#). An early article commenting on the creation of the Tax Relief (back in 2014) has the UK Chancellor reporting that it was the case of Dundee that convinced him to create this form of support. In a Written Evidence document submitted by the Dundee based company Outplay (UK’s largest independent mobile games developer, [\[D0053\]](#)), the company calls for continued investment in the sector and notices also the importance of the VGTR as it “*allows for games businesses, especially high growth games businesses, to use more of their revenues to invest in skills, talent and growth*” [\[D0167\]](#). Across the documentary material, we found only one case where a company explicitly refers to receiving this support, quoting that “*Initiatives like Video Games Tax Relief are essential to sustain business growth and provide some stability.*” [\[D0160\]](#). Therefore, although there is less evidence, there are at least some signs of the fact that the Dundee cluster companies benefit from this type of support. Lastly, as shown in Table 22, the VGTR will be replaced by a different scheme. Additionally, a new Growth Package has been launched. It may be that before the end of the **GAME-ER** project some evidence relating to these new schemes may become available, in which case we will seek to provide this additional evidence.

End of Chapter

5 TURIN CLUSTER

5.1 Introduction

Turin, an Italian city of approximately 850,000 inhabitants (Istat, 2025), is the capital of the Piedmont region and of the Metropolitan City of Turin, located in the north-west of the country. Historically, it served as the first capital of unified Italy between 1861 and 1865. From the late nineteenth century onwards, the city became the principal locus of Italian industrialisation. Emblematic of this transformation were the foundations of FIAT in 1899 and Lancia in 1906, which soon made the automobile sector the cornerstone of Turin's economic identity. Alongside the automotive industry, numerous other manufacturing enterprises flourished – particularly after the First World War – consolidating Turin's enduring image as an 'industrial society', a representation that would persist throughout much of the twentieth century. In parallel, the chemical and electrical industries experienced significant growth, while the publishing sector played a central role in shaping the city's cultural landscape, laying the groundwork for the later development of its Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs). By the late nineteenth century, Turin had also become the main centre of the national film industry, and in subsequent decades it emerged as a key hub for television production. At present, Turin is Italy's fourth-largest city by population (after Rome, Milan, and Naples) and the country's third most important economic and productive hub. It also remains one of Italy's leading centres for higher education and research [T0001].

Regarding the Turin video game production cluster, the features identified through the various stages of the **GAME-ER** Project are also consistently reflected in the documentary evidence concerning this ecosystem. The short history of the cluster limits the existence of specific or particularly detailed documentation, especially of its many institutions and active actors, as they are not yet considered part of a truly structured ecosystem. However, all documentary material helps to fill in those parts/gaps not sufficiently explored by the D4.1 interviews, in particular by serving as an aggregating and filling-in component of the (various) micro-information obtained and processed by the interviews. Furthermore, the graphic component (images, backgrounds, photographs), present in many materials/documents, often supports this analytical process. The almost total absence of academic articles concerning directly the cluster, which denotes a not yet fully matured institutional infrastructure, is partially compensated by websites and press releases/articles on the different development companies, individuals and events. This is thus again in line with the (semi-)informal nature of the cluster and the evident importance of the individuals and companies in it.

Evidence of this informal 'hierarchy' is the fact that most of the materials found online concern interviews in magazines/websites, be it sector-specific on the world of video games, generalist or online versions of physical newspapers (local or national), which deal with individual development companies present in the territory belonging to the cluster. In their contents, in which the main subject is often the publication of a new video game or the winning of some industry award, the stories of companies, individuals or (rarely) the ecosystem (in a generic sense) are told. Sometimes the intent is celebratory for the territory (Turin and/or the Piedmont Region), rather than for the companies themselves. Many materials used in this analysis, however, refer to the national context, as the Italian market for the production and development of video games is often perceived as unique, and the economic interests as collective. Despite regional differences (and/or cluster differences), very often the information found on the Internet and in official documents refers just

to the national context, reporting little and brief data concerning the individual clusters/areas of the country.

Many websites and articles overlap with material related to another task of the Project, namely T4.3 ('Historical Development of Clusters'), as the low degree of ecosystem relations' continuity, prior to the semi-institutionalisation of the cluster, makes it difficult to operate a clear distinction between what immediately precedes it (assumed to be between 2013 and 2014, but also concerning the previous period defined as 'proto-cluster'), and what, on the other hand, is completely unrelated to it (phase before the 'proto-cluster', i.e. before the 2000s).

The absence of sufficient academic material, as well as of institutional documentation, reflects the lack of interest that local public institutions, if not the city itself (and consequently its inhabitants), place on the cluster. This fact had already emerged during D4.1. In contrast, institutional material is concentrated in other CCI sectors, almost completely ignoring that of video games. At most, the local video game industry is seen as complementary to the others and useful for territorial development from a technological and economic standpoint, but only with an almost total orientation towards B2B production. In particular, at the regional level, a strong (and historical) interest emerges for the creative industries linked to publishing and cinema. The production of video games, on the other hand, like audio and video content, is almost completely absent (Bertacchini 2012, p. 182) [T0001]. The available institutional documentation, most of which is in the form of research reports commissioned to external research institutes, focuses on territorial investment and economic growth opportunities. They usually pay attention to new start-ups, citing territorial excellence in the tech (biotech, medtech, etc.), cybersecurity and aerospace fields as the main local virtuous examples [T0043]. Sometimes, though more rarely, institutional documentation refers to events centred on the direct participation of the cluster's game development companies, concerning collaboration opportunities with neighbouring CCI companies [T0068; T0070].

It is also clear that in the first half of the 2000s, the different sectors of the regional CCIs were still separated from each other, closed in 'sealed compartments' with limited mutual cooperation. Cinema and video games, two seemingly very close industries (especially in the case of animated films and special effects), struggled to cooperate at both local and national levels,⁴ forcing producers to clearly differentiate their productions upstream (CNA 2006, pp. 76-77) [T0002]. The documentation on this issue is in absolute continuity with what emerged from the interviews: the idea of a lack of inter-industry collaboration and/or cross-pollination persists, as well as between the different professions of each industry, except for sporadic attempts at collaboration by individual creatives [T0036; T0053; T0070]. The situation is different for the numerous companies that deal exclusively with B2B, which, on the contrary, have a constant presence in other sectors, from healthcare to innovative technologies [T0010; T0050]. This specific characteristic of the cluster, namely its clear division between companies operating in B2C (games) and B2B,⁵ is evident thanks to document analysis and the resulting, more comprehensive mapping of local actors.

With regards to the national context, one in three Italians between 6- and 64-years old plays video games. The total number of gamers in the country amounts to 14 million (+8% compared to 2023). As far as the Italian production context is concerned, in 2024 the national video game development industry achieved clear consolidation and growth, presenting a turnover of between 180 and 200 million euros, an increase of 36% compared to 2022. There are currently over 200 active companies

⁴ Except in rare cases [T0053; T0092].

⁵ Although there are some companies that are well established in both areas of production [T0035; T0092].

in the sector, up from only 48 in 2012. The number of employees in the industry increased from 2,400 in 2022 to 2,800 in 2024 (+19%) [[T0042](#); [T0059](#)].

5.2 Methodology

The methodology used for D4.2 is based on the selection, study and analysis of secondary sources concerning the Turin video game cluster. The selected documents were a total of 92, found progressively, divided mainly between academic and/or sectoral production and generalist online material (see Table 23). The documentary material was initially researched online via common web search engines, in particular Google, and then expanded during the D4.1 and D4.3 interviews (the final question in each interview was always a request for additional material and further useful contacts). The keywords used in the web search were numerous and variable according to the type of search, ranging from concepts linked to gaming and video game production in Turin ('video games in Turin', 'video game development studios in Turin', 'gaming in Turin', etc.), to explicit references to companies, events and people belonging to the cluster.

Sampling continued progressively throughout T4.2 (June 2024 to October 2025), trying to be as comprehensive as possible with respect to the gaps left in D4.1. To this material obtained online were added academic articles and books, including scientific materials produced by some of the researchers involved in the Project (whose search was carried out again using the keywords already applied in web search engines), as well as various documentation found on official institutional websites. There is a large amount of documentation in the form of online articles, taken from sector and/or generalist websites (such as newspaper websites). Almost all of the material is in Italian (except for a large part of the scientific production), so the analysis was conducted in Italian and then translated into English for this report. Some data were also requested from other UNITO colleagues currently working on WP2, to cross-reference some quantitative data they produced with those collected so far in WP4. The material collected was gradually sorted, scanned and entered a database manually made and updated by one of the researchers. In this file, the data was gradually catalogued in a structured and traceable manner. Data entry in the database took place at alternating times and often at different stages of work.

The methodological approach used in this deliverable was again that of thematic analysis employed in D4.1 (Braun, Clarke 2006), which was complemented by the content analysis approach (Krippendorff 2004; White, Marsh 2006) for the use of written sources. Furthermore, through historical discursive analysis (Reisigl, Wodak 2015), i.e. a multidisciplinary theoretical method using contextualisation and text reconstruction, an attempt was made to diachronically reconstruct the content of various online materials concerning the Turin and regional context. These analyses can be carried out through analytical constructs employed by the researcher to move inductively from the text to the questions/responses that were prefixed at the beginning of the research, to 'search for multiple interpretations by considering different voices (readers), alternative perspectives (from different ideological positions), oppositional readings (critiques), or varied uses of the texts examined (by different groups)' (Krippendorff 2004, p. 88). The main objective was to create a more complete view than the reconstruction that took place with the in-depth interviews, thus attempting to link the data between the two deliverables, and to extend the information concerning the individuals, development companies, institutions, and all processes and functioning mechanisms underlying the Turin cluster. The coding and analysis processes were carried out both using NVivo (ver.15), especially for data storage, as well as through the parallel construction of a continuously updated codebook. The codebook was created ad hoc and differs from the one

produced during D4.1, being more essential and simplified/schematic than the latter, but still with the aim of an iterative reading of the data to identify significant concepts and patterns. In its final version, 2 themes, 6 codes (main codes), and 21 sub-codes were identified. As in the case of the codebook created for D4.1, it was necessary to balance an inductive approach with a deductive one based on patterns and an analytical grid devised and developed during the early stages of the Project (T3.1). However, unlike the previous case, the construction of this codebook took a more inductive process, also due to the more ‘chaotic’ nature of the documentary material present online. The codebook was also initially compiled in Italian and then translated into English.

Macro-type	Item Type	Count
Academic and/or industry-related production	Books	1
	Book chapters	5
	Research reports	6
	Academic articles	7
	Doctoral/Master's thesis	6
	Institutional Manifestos/Presentations	2
	Funding calls (regional)	3
Online material	Articles/Press releases	41
	Databases	6
	Webpages	12
	Social network material	3

Table 23 – Documents by type, Turin cluster

5.3 Cluster Emergence & Genesis

D4.1 findings	Description
Pre-emergence	Rare individual experiences; future founders and workers of the cluster as employees of large companies in Milan; no real coordination with existing training/education institutions; no specialised institutions present in the city
Creation of a (semi-)institutional form of the cluster	‘Year Zero’ between 2013 and 2014: many creative professionals returned to Turin and founded their development companies in 2013; Global Game Jam in January 2014: creation of a perceived and shared ‘reality’ capable of dialoguing/competing with Milan
Creation of an institutional hub	With the (re)opening of OGR (2017), the opening of OGR Tech (2019), the creation of the Quickload Acceleration Programme (2019) and the launch of the annual acceleration programmes (2022; 2023; 2025) within OGR, has become the institutional, spatial/physical and image reference point for the Turin cluster

Table 24 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster emergence

In numerous online interviews with individual development companies belonging to the cluster's core network (34BigThings, Memorable Games, Tiny Bull Studios, Broken Arms), 2013 is referred to as the year their studios were established [[T0009](#); [T0025](#); [T0031](#); [T0032](#); [T0033](#); [T0034](#)]; this initial reconstruction suggests the previous absence of any form of structured and/or institutionalised ecosystem in Turin. Although many of them specify that the idea of working together and forming a studio predates 2013 (34BigThings during the founders' academic studies in Copenhagen and subsequent experiences in Milan, the founders of Tiny Bull Studios during their studies at the Polytechnic University of Turin, Memorable Games as early as 2011), it is repeatedly stated that this was the year their actual business experiences began (although no direct reference to the early 2014

Turin Global Game Jam, referred to in D4.1 as the cluster's 'Year Zero' event, was found in the online material). The only (brief and indirect) references to the 'historic' Global Game Jam of January 2014 are made in a report produced by T-Union, which presents the future core members of the cluster [T0017].⁶ These references from the period can also be found in documentary materials relating to other events, such as MTV's Mega Game Jam [T0037] and the VIEW Conference [T0068], as well as in an online article on Global Game Jam events in Italy in 2014 [T0069]. The temporal expansion of information to previous decades, determined by the use of online databases and articles related to other local CCI industries (such as the production of arcade and home computer video games), expands the timeline of the local industry, without, however, being a real part of the cluster's genesis process [T0027; T0046; T0047; T0051; T0052]. Only a few references to the VIEW Conference hint at the presence of relevant people and companies of the future cluster in areas not strictly related to gaming [T0017; T0022]. This presence may have been determined by the lack of dedicated meeting places for video game development (such as OGR, OGR Tech, etc.), and to T-Union's sole role as an institutional channel for lobbying and joint actions within the entire ecosystem.

On the other hand, there has been an increase in the number of development companies, institutions involved in the ecosystem, themed events and, above all, other Game Jams held in Turin, such as those organised by CSP⁷ within I3P and its support programme for digital start-ups, TreataBit,⁸ entitled 'Jam Today' [T0054; T0055; T0058].⁹

5.3.1 Local industry: Origins & historical legacy

The documentary sources do not reveal any new elements regarding the origins and historical legacy of the cluster. There are no direct references in the documents, either past or present, to contamination from other neighbouring industries, except on very rare occasions [T0053; T0068]. Local and regional institutions 'invite' the gaming industry to join other CCI industries through start-up initiatives and potential training collaborations [T0010; T0015; T0043], but seldom make explicit links and/or references to the gaming industry [T0068; T0070]. The same can be said for academic articles and research reports by local institutions dealing with CCIs: although the video game production sector is present, it never plays a major role in institutional assessments, remaining only mentioned as being of significant importance (but limited in its full potential as a stand-alone player) in collaboration with neighbouring tech industries.

5.3.2 Collective actions: Initiating actors & first interactions

The documents analysed do not contain explicit references to the (semi-)institutionalised formation process of the cluster. Still, there are references, at least in the various online articles, to individual development companies and their official company genesis processes. This information implicitly confirms what emerged in D4.1, namely that there was no structured form of video game production cluster in Turin until at least the end of the first decade of the 2000s, and only since the formation of the '1st wave' companies in 2013 (together with the creation of T-Union), the Global

⁶ T0017 is no longer available online. The document is stored in our repository.

⁷ CSP – Innovation in ICT is a research organisation operating at local, national and international level on the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) to various sectors of goods and services production.

⁸ TreataBit is a support programme for digital start-ups created by I3P, the Innovative Business Incubator of the Polytechnic University of Turin.

⁹ The latest edition seems to be, at least in Turin, that of 2016. The Jams were part of the programme of activities of the European project Jam Today (2014), based on game-based learning (<http://www.jamtoday.eu/>, link no longer working).

Game Jam in January 2014, and the opening of OGR Tech in 2019, a real sectoral ecosystem could be seen in the city.

According to our analysis, all previous actions, such as T-Union's participation in some local events (VIEW Conference, MTV Mega Game Jam, other themed events, etc.), were useful for the proto-formation of the cluster. Other events, not directly related to video game development, did not appear to be relevant to the genesis of the ecosystem, nor were they useful in consolidating relations between the actors belonging to the cluster (companies and institutions) and local public institutions (e.g. Chamber of Commerce, Municipality of Turin, Piedmont Region), except in a few rare cases such as the Round One event held in 2021.¹⁰

5.4 Local industry Features and Components

Local industry features retrieved in D4.1 are largely confirmed by document analysis. For example, cross-pollination/fertilisation processes and inter-collaboration mechanisms with neighbouring industries are highlighted through individual actors' actions [T0092].

The informal, low-institutionalisation nature of the Turin ecosystem is confirmed, too. Many articles focus on individual development studios, key individuals, video games produced in the cluster, specific support institutions (T-Union, local IGDA branch, IIDEA),¹¹ physical and institutional hubs (OGR, OGR Tech), accelerators (Quickload) and incubators (I3P), and public (Polytechnic University of Turin, University of Turin) and private (Event Horizon, International School of Comics) training/education institutions. These insights once again highlight the extreme fragmentation of all the cluster's components, which are linked together mainly by informal and often friendly relationships. The informality is evident once again in the constant references to mutual acquaintances among members of the various development studios, as well as in the numerous informal gatherings and events that have taken place over the years (as in the case of the Tech&Tonic and Beer2Peer events described in D4.1). The first official aggregative medium between all these entities, namely T-Union, is much more present in the documents than in the interviews [T0017; T0022; T0037; T0053; T0058; T0069; T0090] demonstrating how the first attempts at aggregation, as well as interaction with public institutions, were better documented online than in the collective memory, probably due to its lack of success at the time.

"T-Union + Piedmont Region: they can work together to bridge the gap between turnover and companies in Italy, creating businesses worth millions!" [T0017, p.29].

In addition to indirect references to the value of (informal) relationships, the role of the city of Turin also emerges in the documents: the city is once again considered a place with an extremely efficient talent pool combined with an environment of marked cultural creativity [T0026], where there is a strong vocation for experimentation and development of innovative technological solutions

¹⁰ It was an international business event dedicated to the esports sector in Italy, organised by IIDEA [T0016].

¹¹ The Italian Interactive Digital Entertainment Association (IIDEA) is currently the most representative trade association for the video game industry in Italy. Known until 2019 as the Italian Association of Video Game Publishers and Developers (AESVI), it changed its name to IIDEA in 2020. It was founded in the early 2000s to represent and unite the sector through a unified approach. It currently has over 80 members, including console manufacturers, video game publishers and developers, and esports operators, such as video game competition organisers and teams. IIDEA is part of a network of international industry associations and, at the European level, is a member of Video Games Europe and the European Game Developers Federation (<https://iideassociation.com/>).

[T0068]; but also as a city where the video game production industry can grow, due (in part) to the presence of infrastructures suitable for this purpose [T0023]. The city of Turin, therefore, is assessed also in the documentary material as a multifunctional ecosystem suited to this type of industry and, in particular, to workers employed in this sector.

5.4.1 Perimeter of the cluster

D4.1 findings	Description
Physical perimeter	There is no official spatial boundary, as the cluster is not 'officially' defined in a structural or institutionalised way
Geographical perimeter and location	Currently unclear/not fully defined; although not 'officially', it is identified in the urban area of the city of Turin, with the OGR at its centre; geographical location considered optimal (presence of transport infrastructure, proximity to Milan, proximity to France)
City and Talent	The cluster emerged and developed in the city of Turin (cultural characteristics; cost of living; infrastructure, etc.); supported by a strong pool of talent from private educational institutions (Event Horizon School, International School of Comics, etc.) and public institutions (Polytechnic University of Turin, University of Turin); the small size of the city encourages close informal ties
Company Landscape	Currently around fifteen development companies: four belonging to the core network (34BigThings, Memorable Games, Tiny Bull Studios, Broken Arms) + smaller companies; focus on indie B2C products; however, B2B production is very important for companies' survival
Institutional Landscape	Relevant higher educational institutions, particularly specialised private education; fragmented public support (limited to individual actions + not recognised as effective by cluster members); no apparent significant collaboration/contamination with neighbouring industries (e.g. cinema)

Table 25 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster perimeter

The cluster's physical perimeter is broadly confirmed by the document analysis, further expanding its scope and the actors involved. The city of Turin remains the centre of the ecosystem, and the OGR, at least since the opening of OGR Tech, its institutional and public image reference point [T0019]. In fact, before the opening of OGR Tech, the online documentation referred only to individual development companies or the headquarters/branches of training/education schools. In a subsequent phase, thanks to the presence of the Quickload acceleration programme [T0018], the institutional reference of the cluster is almost exclusively shifted to the OGR. This is evidenced by the numerically consistent presence of OGR interiors as representative images of the local gaming sector in most institutional documents [e.g. Figure 5, T0043]. Thus, the material proves a logical diachronic progression from a spatial point of view: from a focus on individuals (or companies unrelated to the cluster) in the 'prehistoric' phase (pre-2000s) [T0027; T0045; T0046; T0047; T0049; T0051; T0052], to a physical location linked to individual development companies in the 'proto-cluster' phase (ca. 2000-2013), finally to a structural centralisation on the OGR in the (semi-)institutionalisation phase of the cluster (post-2013 and 2014).

03. State of the art of Turin Innovation startup ecosystem

Figure 5 – Example of an image of OGR Tech used in official documents [T0043, pp.40-41]

At the same time, the strength of the city's (and region's) strategic position, including transport infrastructure, is emphasised once again [e.g. Figure 6, [T0010](#)].

Figure 6 – The Piedmont region and its strategic infrastructure network [[T0010](#), p.5]

Geographically, the core companies in the cluster remain the same (34BigThings, Memorable Games, Tiny Bull Studios, Broken Arms), with some references to development companies that no longer exist (and were not included in the sampling phase of D4.1). Beyond the city limits, the presence of the companies interviewed (in Acqui Terme and Asti) is confirmed, with only rare references to extremely small and unstructured studios outside the province of Turin (in Alessandria and Cuneo). These data are confirmed by the presence of interactive national maps created by different associations (map created by GPI – Italian Game Developers (formerly GameProgita) [[T0004](#)],¹² and by IPID – Italian Party of Indie Developer [[T0007](#)].¹³ Although these maps are not always up to date (some show companies that no longer exist, are incorrectly located, or have various outdated references), they are an excellent preliminary source and a good opportunity to cross-reference data between D4.1 and D4.2. In addition to these, there are other maps created by local and regional institutions (as in the case of the capability matrix provided by CEIP)¹⁴ [[T0010](#)],¹⁵ and scientific works such as doctoral theses [[T0077](#)], which, however, are not entirely satisfactory

¹² GPI was an association/portal created with the aim of connecting Italian video game developers, both local and based abroad. The website features a map and a list of registered Italian companies, with logos and links to official websites.

¹³ The Italian Party of Indie Developers (IPID) is a non-profit, non-partisan association that brings together individual video game developers, and works to promote the growth of Italy's video game industry in terms of volume and quality. Based in Bologna, it organises the annual Sviluppaparty event (<https://www.ipid.dev/>).

¹⁴ This is the Foreign Centre for Internationalisation of the Piedmont Region (also abbreviated as Ceipiemonte), focusing in particular on the following areas of activity: strengthening the presence of Piedmontese companies on foreign markets; attracting investment to Piedmont; promoting Piedmontese agri-food products abroad; training the staff of institutions and companies on international trade and technical-regulatory issues (<https://www.centroestero.org/it/>).

¹⁵ The maps of the companies included in the document are clearly influenced by the companies that won the Integrated Supply Chain Project (Progetti Integrati di Filiera, or PIF) in 2024 and 2025.

when compared to the data collected in D4.1 (companies that no longer exist, absence of key development companies in the cluster, weak and often inaccurate ICT classification).

At the same time, these works and their mapping have shed light on ‘peculiar’ development studios such as Dead Pixels and Molleindustria, which had not previously been identified. Document analysis effectively increases our conceptualisation of the cluster's perimeter, especially those studios not part of the historic core network of companies. In fact, through documents and articles on the internet, it was possible to identify new actors, companies and institutional structures operating within the cluster. Unlike the network of actors identified for the interviews, greater importance was given to the I3P incubator of the Polytechnic University of Turin. The gaming-related start-ups within it, previously only mentioned in a few interviews (in particular the one with Tiny Bull Studios), are instead reported on the web on various sites such as that of I3P [T0083], the Polytechnic University of Turin, and the Municipality of Turin (TorinoGiovani). I3P is often mentioned, as in documents from the Investors' Club [T0043] and CSP – Innovation in ICT [T0054; T0055; T0058], as well as in interviews with individual developers and development companies on websites. A specific focus was recently given to the event ‘Startup Your Game! – From a passion for video games to innovative enterprise’, organised by I3P with the support of IIDEA [T0050]. In the interviews, IIDEA was considered to be an institutional player with little influence on the cluster, as it is generally regarded as too ‘political’ and interested only in the national context. However, online information shows active participation in the construction and development of the Turin ecosystem, albeit limited compared to what has been done by T-Union, OGR/OGR Tech, or provided with the Quickload acceleration programme.

This event aimed to show the public how a passion for video games can translate into highly innovative business projects, emphasising the synergies between gamer creativity and startup mentality. The participating startups (Paperbox Health, Proxy42, and Triality Studio) are companies with distinct approaches to B2C video game development, considered particularly innovative and geared toward B2B production: in order, Paperbox Health deals with serious gaming for children's health, with healthcare specialisations and medical certifications; Proxy42 deals with immersive and interactive technology for sports fan engagement; Triality Studio deals with cultural gamification with immersive VR. They were joined for the event by Tiny Bull Studios, already widely presented during T4.1, as the fourth company. This studio has been supported by the I3P incubator over the years and is known in the industry for its innovative productions with strong narrative and immersive features. The event meeting discussed success stories in various sectors, from immersive realities to digital health and culture, highlighting the cross-pollination possibilities between gaming and applied innovation. It was a free event organised with the support of the Piedmont Region through funds from the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+). However, it is unclear how such an event can fit into the core mechanisms of the cluster without remaining relegated to the ‘periphery’ of the ecosystem and purely to the B2B production sphere. In fact, the absence of any reference to this type of event during in-depth interviews reiterates the ‘indie’ nature of most of the companies in the cluster, which are dedicated to game creation (or at least as their ideal goal) and less to B2B production. The cluster's perimeter, therefore, has conceptually expanded compared to what has been outlined in the previous deliverable, with the addition of other development companies and institutions active in the ecosystem (see Table 26).

What has expanded the most is the presence and direct interest, especially of local, regional and national public institutions, in B2B production,¹⁶ with the clear intention of encouraging collaboration between different neighbouring industries, thus promoting an entrepreneurial perspective and the expansion of the local production market.

Actor name	Actor type	Place	Previous identification (D4.1)
Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti di Torino	IT Company	Turin	No
CEIP - Foreign Centre for Internationalisation	Public institution	Turin	No
Chamber of Commerce	Public institution	Turin	Yes
CRT Foundation	Private non-profit organisation	Turin	Yes
CSP – Innovation in ICT	Research organisation	Turin	No
Event Horizon School	Private school	Turin	Yes
I3P	Business incubator	Turin (inside the Polytechnic University)	Yes
IED - European Institute of Design	Private school	Turin	Yes
IGDA (Turin branch)	Industry organisation	Turin	Yes
IIDEA	Trade association	Milan	Yes
iMasterArt Academy	Private school	Turin	No
International School of Comics	Private school	Turin	Yes
Investors' Club	Business angel network	Turin	No
MIA - Mercato Internazionale Audiovisivo	Market event	Rome	No
Municipality of Turin	Public institution	Turin	Yes
OGR	Multi-purpose hub	Turin	Yes
OGR Tech	Technology hub	Turin (inside OGR)	Yes
Piedmont Region	Public institution	Turin	Yes
Polytechnic University of Turin	University	Turin	Yes
Quickload	Acceleration programme	Turin (inside OGR)	Yes
San Paolo Society Foundation	Banking foundation	Turin	Yes
T-Union	Industry organisation	Turin	Yes (absorbed by IGDA)
TorinoGiovani	Information portal	Turin (inside Municipality of Turin)	No
University of Turin	University	Turin	Yes
VIEW Conference	Computer graphics event	Turin	Yes

Table 26 – Actors involved within the cluster (excluding development companies)

¹⁶ One such example is Dead Pixels, a development company founded in 2016 after receiving the ‘Call for Startups’ grant, part of TIM’s annual industrial Open Innovation programme. This fund is dedicated to financing innovative startups in the digital sector, and by obtaining it, the studio also entered the I3P incubation programme [T0083; T0084]. The aim was to develop a virtual reality video game called ‘Singularis’ [T0077].

5.4.2 Demography of companies

D4.1 findings	Description
Cluster Size and Company Composition	Small cluster composed of small and medium-sized companies (individual companies may reach a maximum of 80 workers, including employees, freelancers and trainees/interns)
Diachronic Company Creation	1st wave (ca. 2013), formed by the historical companies that built the foundations of the game production; 2nd wave (ca. 2022), i.e. companies that often participated in the Quickload acceleration programme and are currently trying to consolidate in the market
Challenges	Talent pool created in Turin's schools is difficult to be absorbed by the local fabric; production is directed abroad, and thus difficulty in retaining local economic value; poor collaboration with public institutions; low degree of public recognition; low collaboration/contamination with neighbouring industries; difficulties in attracting funds

Table 27 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster companies' demography

The number of companies identified with the document analysis, including those that no longer exist, has increased significantly compared to D4.1 (see Table 28). The documents, including online articles, websites, research reports, institutional documents, academic publications and interactive maps of sectoral associations, provide a broader and more complete mapping, which is diachronically varied, even if seldom updated [[T0007](#); [T0010](#); [T0071](#); [T0072](#); [T0073](#); [T0077](#)].

In an article celebrating video game production in the Piedmont region published in La Repubblica in 2023 [[T0009](#)], the companies belonging to the cluster's core network are listed, namely BrokenArms, 34BigThings, Tiny Bull Studios and Memorable Games (still referred to as MixedBag). The same article mentions the Polytechnic University of Turin and the University of Turin for training/education, providing a partially complete picture of the cluster's pipeline. In the article, the number of employees in these companies remains roughly the same as that reported in D4.1 (34BigThings: approximately 100, of which between 20 and 30 are permanent employees; Tiny Bull Studios: approximately 60; Memorable Games: between 20 and 30), whose numerical variability is based on the specific work at hand, in line with the project-based nature of the industry (Ruggill 2017).¹⁷The interactive maps of GPI and IPID [[T0004](#); [T0007](#)], for example, indicate the presence of 13 (7+6) development companies in the region (all of which are associated with their respective associations). In this case, they are more than what was identified in the reconstructions carried out during D4.1. The GPI map only shows companies in the city of Turin, including: 34BigThings, Tiny Bull Studios, Memorable Games (still under the name MixedBag), Broken Arms (located in Turin and not in Acqui Terme), Event Horizon Studios (the internal studio of Event Horizon School), and RedMagicBlue, Seep Production and Not a Number, the latter three not previously identified. In the case of IPID, NewbiX in Asti and Tiny Pumpkins in Cuneo (not previously detected) appear, while in the city of Turin, Memorable Games (still under the name MixedBag), FutuRats (under the name Black), Event Horizon Studios, and Awakening Games (not previously detected) appear. As can be seen from the names of the companies on the two maps, they are incomplete, out of date and lack relevant companies that are probably not registered with GPI or not associated with IPID. As for the companies not previously identified, in almost all cases, the online information is inconsistent about their current status. However, even when adding together the companies from both maps, there are no small indie studios that were detected during the D4.1 sampling, in addition to the absence

¹⁷ For each individual development company, the current team members can be found on their respective websites. Approximately, they confirm the limited number of employees in the cluster's development studios, in line with what has been defined in scientific literature on the Italian case [[T0012](#); [T0013](#); [T0021](#)]. The majority of development companies in Italy are in fact small businesses, with approximately 52% of the total having fewer than 10 employees and 24% of the remainder having no more than 10 employees [[T0059](#)].

of some companies that participated in the Quickload acceleration programme. The mapping of games and companies, carried out by Filigoi for his doctoral thesis on independent video games in Italy (2014-2017), provides a comprehensive and satisfactory picture of the period, especially for the local indie scene [T0077]. However, as with previous maps, it suffers from obvious staticity, as well as general incompleteness (as stated by the author) due to the scarcity of academic and other sources at the time. The great added value of this work is that it sheds light on companies strongly focused on B2B, which were born from I3P and/or previous experiences at the Polytechnic University of Turin, or which, for other reasons, were not previously surveyed during the D4.1 interviews. Some examples are Dead Pixels, Molleindustria,¹⁸ Raven Travel Studios, Picaresque Studio,¹⁹ Onni Interactive, Stigma Studios (Alessandria), Mistical Interactive (Alessandria) and Oblion Studio (Cuneo), adding nine development companies compared to what was mapped during the previous deliverable (the list includes Potato Killer Studios and Cosebelle, for which no recent information is available).

The CEIP 2024 research report [T0010] presents the greatest discrepancies with the mapping conducted in D4.1. There are ten companies in the 'Gaming & Esports' sector column, only two of which (Tiny Bull Studios²⁰ and Dramatic Iceberg) were identified in D4.1. The remaining eight companies (Animoka Studios, Archibuzz, AWorld, Forestae, Logs Centro Studi, Machiavelli Music, Skillbit, Sportellence) had not been identified previously. The reason is probably that the document refers specifically to the Integrated Supply Chain (ICT) Project, promoted by the Piedmont Region, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund 2021-2027 and implemented by the Piedmont Agency, to provide international operators with a privileged channel to meet and establish business relationships with the best ICT companies based in Piedmont [T0071; T0072; T0073]. In this case, the selected companies are clearly focused on the creation of B2B products and services, and thus too far from the (mainly) B2C and indie logic of the cluster's core development companies. This document once again highlights the distance between this latter group of companies and public institutions (in this case regional) and the current limits to their mutual relations and collaborations. Synesthesia,²¹ too, should be added to this type of companies: it is a company mainly present in B2B productions, but also with close collaborations with studios in the ecosystem, and also responsible for some production in applied games [T0090; T0091; T0092].

Company	Production type	Location	Previous identification (D4.1)
34BigThings	B2C	Turin	Yes
Animoka Studios	B2B	Turin	No
Archibuzz	B2B	Turin	No
Awakening Games	B2C	Turin	No
AWorld	B2B	Turin	No

¹⁸ In reality, this is just one developer (Paolo Pedercini), famous for creating numerous provocative Flash video games on controversial topics [T0077]. Active since 2003, he has been living in the United States for many years [T0088].

¹⁹ Whose three members, from Turin, Caserta and Rome, however, work entirely remotely [T0086].

²⁰ Tiny Bull Studios owns Game Thinkers (<https://gamethinkers.it/>), an independent company structure dedicated solely to B2B, founded in 2024.

²¹ Synesthesia is a digital experience company founded in 2011, which creates and supports various digital initiatives, including those in the field of gaming and events, as well as the creation of applied games. Synesthesia is involved in the Turin gaming scene. In fact, it has participated in several Turin editions of Global Game Jam [T0090; T0091]. It is also involved in other events in Turin [T0092]. However, despite being a clear example of a company belonging to the wider ecosystem, especially cross-sector collaboration, its strong focus on B2B production was probably decisive in it not being mentioned during the D4.1 interviews.

Broken Arms	B2C	Acqui Terme (AL)	Yes
Cosebelle	B2C	Turin (?)	No
Dead Pixels	B2B	Turin	No
Deep Monolith	B2C	Turin	Yes
Dramatic Iceberg	B2C	Turin	Yes
Event Horizon Schools	B2C	Turin	No
Forestae	B2B	Turin	No
Febucci	B2C	?	Yes
Funix	B2B	Turin	Yes
Futurats	B2C	Turin	Yes
Impressionware	B2C	Turin	Yes
Kibou Entertainment	B2C	?	No
Logs Centro Studi	B2B	Turin	No
Lullabyte Games	B2C	Turin (no physical office)	Yes
Memorable Games	B2C	Turin	Yes
Machiavelli Music	B2B	Turin	No
Mistical Interactive	B2C	Alessandria	No
Molleindustria	B2C	USA (?)	No
NewbiX	B2C (no core business)	Asti	Yes
Not a Number	B2C + B2B	Turin (?)	No
Novis Games	B2C + B2B	Turin	Yes
Oblion Studios	B2C	Cuneo (?)	No
Onni Interactive	B2C	Turin	No
Picaresque Studio	B2C	Turin (?)	No
Potato Killer Studio	B2C	Turin (?)	No
Paperbox Health	B2B	Turin	No
Proxy42	B2B	Turin	No
Raven Travel Studios	B2C	Turin (?)	No
RedMagicBlue	B2C	Turin (?)	No
Seep Production	B2C	Turin (?)	No
Skillbit	B2B	Rivoli (TO)	No
Sportellence	B2B	Turin	No
Stigma Studios	B2C + B2B	Alessandria	No
Synesthesia	B2B	Turin	No
Tiny Bull Studios	B2C + B2B	Turin	Yes
Tiny Pumpkins	B2C	Cuneo	No
Triality Studio	B2B	Turin	No
True Colors Studio	B2C	Turin	Yes
Volcanite Studios	B2C	Turin	Yes

Table 28 – Development companies in the cluster (divided by type of production)

Ultimately, the intersection between the data emerged from D4.1 and D4.2 provides a more organic picture, but not necessarily a complete one (see Figure 7). It is still difficult to identify, with sufficient certainty, the actual demographics of the companies operating (or at least still present) in the entire cluster's spatial/institutional area of influence without encountering inaccuracies. The very nature of the cluster, which is almost informal, does not require any official form of membership registration and has a low degree of institutionalisation, which limits this kind of operation.

Figure 7 – Cluster mapping: main video game development companies, institutions and transport infrastructures (close-up of Turin city centre). Source: Authors' own elaboration (https://umap.openstreetmap.fr/it/map/turin-cluster_1295509). Map legend: video game development companies (blue squares); educational institutions (red squares); transport infrastructure (pink squares); public and private institutions (yellow squares)

5.4.3 Institutional support

According to the contents of the documents, institutional support appears to be broader and more structured than reported in the in-depth interviews. The mistrust and low level of collaboration reported by all parties interviewed in D4.1 (companies, Chamber of Commerce, OGR, etc.) is still present, but is mitigated by forms of (limited) past collaboration, institutional initiatives (albeit not directly aimed at the B2C gaming sector but more at B2B production), and new initiatives by institutions not previously considered (e.g. I3P, rarely mentioned during the interviews). The training/education sector remains present in the documentary materials and is considered fundamental both for the creation of a talent pool useful to the needs of local companies and, more

generally, for the creation of workers with the characteristics necessary for industry (creativity, passion, etc.). The documents make fewer references to private educational institutions, leaving more space for the two universities in the city. This is probably due to the ‘public’ nature of the interviews and the websites/online newspapers that published the articles. Regarding private schools, there are specific references to Event Horizon School (founded in 2013) and to the iMasterArt Academy (founded in 2011, not previously featured in interviews) [T0077]. They are both described as relevant examples of local and national significance for their range of courses and specialised master's degrees, which span from comics to game development and the creation of digital effects for cinema. The entrepreneurial ecosystem, on the other hand, is viewed from a different perspective. It is no longer considered solely from the point of view of individual companies, but also from institutional documents created at the local and regional levels. This difference involves shifting the focus from the creation of indie video games and B2C production in general to other, more or less related sectors, focused on B2B production. In particular, public institutions adopt a holistic approach across the entire territory, using an almost entirely economic ‘filter of interest’ on local and regional production. This point of view takes place mainly using examples such as deep tech, aerospace, and other sectors considered to be areas of excellence in the Piedmont region. This sort of reasoning leads to a broadening of the possible prospects in the type of production of the cluster's members, even if it is in open contrast with the intentions of the developers that emerged from the interviews. In addition to the obvious contrast with the indie, creative and independent nature of the cluster's development studios, the other contrasting factor is precisely the distance between these companies and those used as virtuous examples in the documents: in the interviews, those very sectors were used as positive institutional, social and economic examples (both local and regional), in contrast to the low public regard for the local gaming industry.

The (semi-) irreconcilable divide that emerged from the interviews, or at least the incompatibility of mutual communication language between the two parties, is not so evident in the documents, as there is no direct conflictual confrontation. There is only a more generic perspective of common existence in the B2B market. It is no coincidence that these documents often mention only a few companies in the cluster, mainly Tiny Bull Studios, which has developed an independent internal section within the company focused solely on B2B production. It is also the company most frequently mentioned in scientific articles dealing with video game applications in areas other than entertainment, such as healthcare [T0063; T0081], specific applications related to VR [T0060; T0079; T0080; T0081; T0082], or technical issues in software development [T0078]. Another exception is the (few) technical collaborations for shared events, as Synesthesia did during the Global Game Jams in the role of technology partner for the events [T0090; T0091], a company that is also involved in the production of serious games (on topics such as air pollution, public health, etc.).

In the documents, public support appears to be greater than what was inferred from the interviews. In fact, many actions involve the presence of some public institution (local or regional), even if never on a continuous basis. On the other hand, there is a clear form of ‘declaration of intent’ on the part of public institutions towards the local video game development industry, in which the former is open to the participation of the latter in mostly hybrid multi-sector initiatives, even if entirely focused on B2B and technical-financial training [see, e.g. T0010; T0014; T0015]. In rare cases, with events focused on new technologies (such as 5/6G), explicit mention is made of the local gaming sector. One such event was ‘5G, Technologie Immersive e Gaming’ (‘5G, Immersive Technologies and Gaming’), held at the OGR in 2023 [T0068]. The event saw the active participation of the Ministry of Enterprise and Made in Italy (MIMIT), the City of Turin through the Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti

di Torino – CTE NEXT,²² IIDEA, MIA (Mercato Internazionale Audiovisivo)²³ and the VIEW Conference. During the event, several local development companies participated, and prominent figures from the cluster interacted in the talks, such as Tiziano Giardini (Quickload, IGDA and 34BigThings), Tommaso Verde (Dramatic Iceberg), Yves Hohler (Broken Arms Games), Matteo Lana (Tiny Bull Studios) and Mauro Fanelli (Memorable Games), who participated in the panel discussion ‘L’industria dei videogiochi: stato dell’arte e prospettive di sviluppo’ (‘The video game industry: state of the art and prospects for development’).

Another interesting example was an event organised by CEIP at the end of 2024, entitled ‘Nuove Frontiere tra Cinema e Gaming: Scenari Internazionali e Opportunità per le PMI’ (‘New Frontiers between Cinema and Gaming: International Scenarios and Opportunities for SMEs’) [T0070]. The event focused on presenting the main international scenarios and initiatives related to the cinema, animation and gaming sectors, with particular reference to the integration of rendering engines such as Unreal Engine and advanced artificial intelligence (AI) solutions. The aim was to reflect on the best strategies to promote the competitiveness of local companies in global markets. The event was attended by various members of the ecosystem pipeline, from companies, with Marco Mazzaglia presenting ‘L’esperienza di Tiny Bull Studios: storie e strategie di successo nel gaming’ (‘The Tiny Bull Studios experience: success stories and strategies in gaming’), to the University of Turin with Enrico Bertacchini with the presentation ‘Il panorama europeo del gaming: cluster regionali e delle opportunità internazionali’ (‘The European gaming landscape: regional clusters and international opportunities’). The event was part of the Integrated Supply Chain Project (PIF)²⁴ ICT of the Piedmont Region²⁵ and funded by the European Regional Development Fund (PR FESR 2021-2027), demonstrating that regional public institutions, at least in their intentions, are committed to the idea of integrating the regional CCI supply chain, including the audio-visual and gaming industries, in order to achieve a more comprehensive and cross-cutting internationalisation process for these industries. The role of associations that emerged in documentary material analysis is definitely more significant compared to what emerged from our previous analysis. In addition to a greater amount of information on the actions taken by T-Union (and later by IGDA) at the local level, such as the MTV Mega Game Jam in 2014 [T0037] and various appearances at the VIEW Conference [e.g. see T0068], it is interesting to note how T-Union took action at various institutional levels to help the growth of the entire ecosystem. For example, the 2013-2014 press releases from T-Union are particularly interesting, including presentations to the Piedmont Region where, in addition to

²² The Casa delle Tecnologie Emergenti di Torino – CTE NEXT is a project that aims to transform Turin into a hub for technology transfer focused on emerging technologies in sectors identified as strategic for the local area: smart mobility, Industry 4.0 and innovative urban services (<https://ctenext.it/>).

²³ MIA is an annual market event held in Rome, focusing on the global cinema and audiovisual ecosystem.

²⁴ Integrated Supply Chain Projects (PIF) are internationalisation programmes that have been helping Piedmontese companies develop and consolidate their presence on the international stage since 2013. They are aimed at SMEs in the Piedmont region in the following sectors: Clothing/High-End/Design, Aerospace, Agri-Food, Automotive & Transportation, Cleantech & Green Building, ICT, Mechatronics, Health and Wellness, and Textiles. PIFs are projects of the Piedmont Region, funded by the PR FESR 2021-2027 and implemented through Ceipiemonte (<https://www.centroestero.org/it/sviluppo-business-all-estero/i-nostri-servizi/i-progetti-integrati-di-filiera.html>).

²⁵ The Integrated ICT Supply Chain Project aims to promote Piedmontese SMEs in the ICT supply chain abroad. The call for applications for the 2024 financial year saw Tiny Bull Studios [T0071] admitted in the third round of companies eligible for the maximum subsidy of €20,000.00, while Dramatic Iceberg was admitted in the fourth round [T0072]; in 2025, NewbiX/BitmaniaX (Asti) was admitted in the second round of companies eligible for the subsidy [T0073].

requesting funds, they sought to establish forms of direct collaboration between the latter, and the companies present at the time [T0017].

The situation is different at the national level of the Italian video game production context. IIDEA research reports, as well as analyses provided by academic articles, provide a general picture at the national level, where the Turin cluster is an integral part but is never directly mentioned [T0003; T0040; T0042; T0059]. In addition to the fact that the information is often out of date, especially in the case of academic works (particularly considering that this is a rapidly changing industry), the perspectives of researchers, although intended to be national in scope, are limited due to scarce research resources and spatially confined by their case studies. In fact, despite the economically significant role of the Turin cluster in the national video game context, it is most often not mentioned or considered: most of the scientific work remains within the Milan area. Moreover, the thematic focus of some academic articles, particularly on the conditions of workers in the sector, presents a picture of associations (such as Game Workers Unite, GWU) [T0008] which, at least according to the interviews in D4.1, are neither relevant nor known to the workers themselves.

Therefore, the picture that emerges from the document analysis expands on what was observed in D4.1, providing a broader range of actors and points of view (especially institutional ones). However, the fragmentation of the actions of individual entities and the lack of common intent are perfectly consistent with what has already been analysed and understood previously.

5.4.4 Cluster «DNA»

The cluster 'DNA', including all its components, is a concept that can also be applied to the document analysis, but only partially. This is due to the very nature of the type of material under review: online articles only mention the cluster through interviews with individual development studios; local research reports on CCIs focus either on other creative industries or on the B2B component, which is somewhat marginal to the intentions of the development studios belonging to the cluster; academic articles and national research reports focus on the national context or on case studies other than that of Turin; historical documentation (online articles, databases) does not provide elements for reconstruction from the 'proto-cluster' phase onwards. Only the documentation produced by T-Union gives an idea of the highly creative and informal characteristics of the cluster at the time (2013-14). Some online articles also give a general idea of what was 'happening' in the area at the time of writing, making it clear that 'something creative' was happening in Turin in the gaming sector [T0009]. However, this diachronic progression of information is limited to a few players who, although they are (still) the most important in the ecosystem and its network, represent only a fraction of the cluster's current pipeline. Articles on individual development companies, especially local ones, help to create a sense of visibility and territorial pride [see, for example, T0026; T0024; T0033; T0029], especially if they relate to specific cases (such as wine production) or areas outside the city of Turin (for example, in the case of Asti).

The documentary material conveys the idea of a strong influence linked to the creativity of local companies and their content, which is, in turn, corroborated by documentation that combines the idea of the coexistence of high-quality indie productions with innovative B2B projects. In this way, potential markets are implicitly expanded and diversified, thanks in part to the city's high-level educational and cultural environment.

5.5 Cluster Evolution

The document analysis confirms the evolutionary pattern of the cluster provided by D4.1. The additions to the timeline already presented in D4.1 (see Table 29) concern the phase prior to the ‘proto-cluster’ (pre-2000s), but which (for now) seem to be completely unrelated to the creation and evolution of the ecosystem. The reason is that this phase seems to be composed of individuals (amateur/professional solo developers or electromechanical companies with different specialisations), whose existence did not extend beyond the 1990s. The neighbouring industries, especially cinema, animation, comics and special effects/VFX, although present in a few documents and some events [T0053; T0065], do not seem to have played a significant role or had a sufficient impact to be included as new entries in the current timeline.

D4.1 findings	Description
‘Proto’-cluster phase (2000s and early 2010s)	Cluster not yet in existence; future founders located mainly in Milan; return to Turin and birth of the main companies (2013); ‘Year Zero’ (2014)
Cluster Initial Phase (2010s and early 2020s)	Cluster as a semi-formal institutional structure
Cluster 2nd wave Phase (early 2020s to present)	More formal structuring; external recognition

Table 29 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster evolution and critical moments

As the cluster is young and only became semi-institutionalised in 2013-2014, there have been no significant evolutionary ‘shocks’, and the documents once again refer to Global Game Jams as moments of aggregation and ecosystemic growth. The addition of I3P’s Game Jams broadens the scope of this type of event, introducing new themes and players [T0054; T0055; T0058]. The various other events that occurred in the timeline and are also/only present in the documents do not report any significant changes concerning the aforementioned determining factors, such as the creation of local development companies in 2013 (and Event Horizon School), the Global Game Jam in early 2014, the reopening of the OGR in 2017 (and OGR Tech in 2019) [T0019], and the creation of the Quickload acceleration programme in 2019 [T0018]. These events remain the key points in the evolution of the cluster, seen as factors of internal development. Externally (at the national level), the introduction of tax credits for the video game industry in 2021, thanks to IIDEA’s lobbying actions,²⁶ is perceived as a growth point for the (entire) sector but is never seen as direct and specific aid for the cluster, given the limited size of its companies. The organisation of First Playable²⁷ by IIDEA is also seen as a further factor in the development and growth of the national industry, in which development studios from the cluster can become actively involved [T0023; T0030].

5.6 Collective Actions

D4.1 findings	Description
Collective Actions Features	Collective actions are mostly informal; associationism, mainly of a voluntary nature, is the main mechanism of collective action (mainly events organised by IGDA and/or OGR); no institutionalised form above this organises collective actions
Functioning Mechanisms	The cluster’s functioning mechanisms, divided between formal and informal actions/activities, have created a self-reinforcing and fully functioning ecosystem
Production Chain	The cluster’s most identifiable production chain is currently composed of actors positioned both horizontally (mainly) and vertically in the ecosystem pipeline

²⁶ Law no. 220 of 14 November 2016 (so-called ‘Cinema Law’), subsequently defined by the DM of 12 May 2021.

²⁷ First Playable is the international business event dedicated to video game developers in Italy. <https://firstplayable.it/>

Collective Activities	The main collective activities concern the exchange of resources and information between members, thus through horizontal processes; participation in events such as national and international trade fairs, on the other hand, tends to be on an individual company basis
------------------------------	--

Table 30 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster collective actions

From the documentary analysis, there appear to be many more types of collective actions than previously identified in D4.1. New information on collective events, particularly new Game Jams and T-Union actions, fills some gaps in the cluster's genesis. However, there are numerous forms of 'declarations of intent' by institutions regarding the potential for integrating the local video game development industry into the broader market of territorial CCIs, but nothing that appears to be structured or that directly and explicitly involves representatives of the gaming industry.

5.6.1 Main activities & collective actions

In addition to greater documented participation by cluster representatives at the VIEW Conference, the latter being the main point of reference for neighbouring industries (special effects/animation/VFX), there is evidence of past lobbying activities by T-Union, including those directed at the Piedmont Region [T0017]. Other events, organised by I3P (and therefore by the Polytechnic University of Turin), demonstrate the more extensive participation of some of the cluster companies most interested in B2B production. Public information, such as the launch of the first IQM quantum computer in Italy at the Polytechnic University of Turin [T0067], indicates that the entire pipeline is involved in extremely interesting forms of B2B projects that are particularly important for the cluster's public image, even if not directly related to video game production or the gaming ecosystem in general.

Other forms of collective action, such as information and tip exchanges, can be inferred from the interviews and the image they paint of an informal ecosystem based on solidarity and collaboration among its members. The main collective actions, therefore, remain those described in D4.1: events often organised by IGDA (and just as often in OGR), which see the active participation of significant players in the cluster and the presence of almost the entire ecosystem, conducted near entirely on a voluntary basis. However, these features are never actually explicitly mentioned in the documents.

5.6.2 Stakeholders' motivations, benefits & main contributions

D4.1 findings	Description
Companies	Communication and relationship network: collaboration and information exchange; access to talent pool; participation in thematic events; exchange of resources
Educational Institutions	Increasing the number of students (and economic resources)
Foundations	Increased continuity of investment
Public Institutions	More active support for the local industrial fabric; extending actions and activities to the territory; creation of territorial economic and financial value; creation of territorial image recognition (branding)
Individual worker	Easier to find and change jobs; lower cost of living; better work-life balance

Table 31 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster stakeholders' motivation and benefits

The stakeholders' motivations that emerge from the document analysis are partially in line with what emerged from D4.1. A new insight that emerged from document analysis is the process through which development companies and the associations that represent them seek to improve the ecosystem as a whole, offering the added value of local production as a 'bargaining chip' (the number and quality of video games produced, but also consulting and collaboration with public and

private educational institutions for the technical training of students, as well as the provision of professional training courses, especially through Event Horizon School) [T0017]. In particular, through T-Union first and IGDA later, companies seek to ‘reach out’ to local investors and participate in events and activities collaboratively, showing how B2C and B2B productions can be part of the entire package offered by the cluster's players. Through the specific (and unique) skills possessed by members of the entire cluster pipeline, and the activation of new ad hoc specialist training courses (thus attracting potential students from outside), there is a clear intention to promote the image of the Piedmont Region, as well as new opportunities to participate in European and international calls for projects/funds.

“What T-Union can offer for 2015-2017:

- Leadership of the Piedmont Region in terms of creativity and innovation in Italy
- Positioning as a European benchmark
- 30 operational professionals, 120 people active in the association
- 4 new original video games, 2 new original applied games Global Game Jam 2015
- Launch of new courses and activities with schools and universities in the Piedmont Region, attracting students from other regions
- Participation in national, European, and international calls for proposals
- Double-digit increase in turnover compared to the investment made” [T0017, pp. 33-37].

Some companies, mainly active in the B2B sector, are more prominent in the documents of local and regional public institutions [T0010; T0043], as well as in thematic events [T0050; T0068; T0070], demonstrating their interest in markets that are different and broader in scope than that of entertainment. Schools and educational institutions once again see collaborations as a potential investment to attract more students, but there is no data available regarding their specific statements on this matter. This is, in fact, inferred from the opportunities offered by the ecosystem and its companies and institutions, and thus it remains implicit in the documentation. Public institutions such as the Chamber of Commerce and the Piedmont Region, which feature much more prominently in the documents than in the interviews, propose collaborations that ‘hypothesise’ (greater) participation by cluster members in local and regional economic and training/educational activities. From a market and inter-industry collaboration perspective, the documentation focuses on initiatives related to B2B and the application of specific technologies to improve local and regional business. From an educational perspective, companies are considered at all levels of education (primary, secondary and tertiary) and seen as potential actors useful for improving local and regional initiatives with high technological expertise [T0015; T0056; T0057]. However, even in this case, there is no reference to the direct involvement of companies or even institutions belonging to the cluster pipeline. The idea remains, still implicit, of their potential participation in such mechanisms, even with the collaboration of companies from neighbouring sectors [T0070].

5.6.3 Mobilized resources & competencies

The document analysis clearly shows that the main level of mobilisation of economic resources occurs at the institutional level, especially at the regional one. However, these economic resources are almost never specifically allocated to the gaming industry or to companies belonging to the cluster. The idea proposed by these public institutions, such as the Piedmont Region and CEIP, is that of shared collective economic and financial growth and development [T0010; T0070]. However, although these values are also part of the corporate objectives of companies belonging to the

cluster (i.e. growth in turnover), they are not in line with the type of production that many of these studios have in their DNA (due to product quality standards and limited company size).

The support provided by associations, on the other hand, is more evident, especially in the early stages of the cluster's development, through a greater number of activities and forms of lobbying adopted by sectoral associations at the time. The voluntary nature of the cluster, one of its main characteristics, has helped this type of collective mobilisation, cutting overall costs. From a national perspective, as already mentioned in D4.1, there is a certain distance between the companies belonging to the cluster and IIDEA, which is nevertheless more present in the documentation and statements of the individual development studios featured in online articles. The various IIDEA research reports [T0042; T0059], for example, list the evolving situation of the industry and the national market, referring to the transformations involving the entire industry and the relationships that comprise it, without making reference to specific territories. Academic articles/book chapters [T0012; T0013; T0021; T0077], similarly, report on the importance of the lobbying actions and inter-institutional relationships produced by IIDEA at the national level, without, however, making any specific reference to the Turin cluster. The institutional support that can be inferred is therefore generalised and at the national level, thus also impacting the Turin cluster and its members, even if without directly involving and/or mentioning them.

5.6.4 Coordination & control formal structures

D4.1 findings	Description
Verticality	Coordination and control of formal structures (one of the few vertical cluster's components); OGR and Quickload: vertical structure that organises institutional actions and objectives; associationism and semi-formal activities carried out voluntarily + strong people's 're-circulation' mechanism (who participate/organise these events)
Horizontality	Cluster's strong component of horizontality: individuals belonging to different institutions (companies, public schools, universities, Quickload, IGDA, IIDEA, etc.) --> allows for rapid and streamlined coordination; enables reciprocity and solidarity; communication tools are concentrated in online platforms --> allows for informality + practical and fast interactivity
Coordination Challenges	Absence of a properly formal cluster structure --> limits real coordination capabilities (especially outside its boundaries)

Table 32 - Emerging aspects of the cluster for coordination, D4.1

Compared to D4.1, the documents highlight the uncoordinated nature of the entire Italian industry, both in terms of market dynamics and trade union and labour representation. This is particularly evident in academic documents [T0012; T0013; T0021], which focus on the awareness of workers in the sector on these issues. Scientific literature confirms that the characteristics of the industry tend to bypass not only forms of market coordination, but also the entire traditional system of industrial relations, as the sector is traditionally opposed to forms of unionisation (Woodcock 2019). In Italy, this framework is aggravated by the fact that there is no specific national collective agreement for the sector, and the most commonly used is the collective agreement for the metalworking sector, without any type of second-level bargaining (Bellini et al. 2018). These shared practices tend to undermine the direct labour bargaining and contractual awareness of workers in the industry. This situation can also be observed in the Turin cluster. In fact, cross-referencing the data emerging from these documents with those analysed in D4.1 confirms that the same patterns can be found both in terms of the low degree of coordination within the cluster and the low awareness of workers about forms of national/local representation, outside IGDA at the national/international level and IIDEA. The only exceptions were T-Union and the local branch of IGDA, although these are seen partly as substitutes for union representation, thereby assuming

functions that do not properly fall within their remit. This cross-referencing of data also confirms the poor, if not entirely absent, trade union and contractual culture among members of the Turin cluster.

5.6.5 Financial aspects

D4.1 findings	Description
General Perception	Cluster membership does not seem to be perceived as relevant
Companies and Individual Workers	Cluster membership does not seem to bring any real economic/financial advantage; since the market for video game production is global and currently managed almost entirely through digital distribution, the local supply chain does not seem to confer any advantage in terms of job placement and earnings
Overall Cost Perspective	Advantages are perceived for the geographical/logistical context, i.e. the city of Turin. Companies: lower rents for studios compared to other Italian cities; lower logistic costs for travel and work; lower labour costs. Individual workers: lower costs for rent, urban transport, etc.; reduced time and transport costs compared to commuting or living in Milan; greater margins of free time and parallel professional projects

Table 33 - Financial aspects of the cluster emerging from D4.1

Financial aspects are one of the most prominent topics in both local and national documents. At the beginning of the cluster's semi-institutionalised existence (2014), data on the national value of the industry was used by T-Union as a potential means of establishing relations with regional institutions [T0017]. The same data appears in online articles about the companies in the cluster [T0050; T0009; T0029]. The various acquisitions made by development companies, such as 34BigThings acquired by Embracer Group²⁸ in 2020 (through its wholly owned subsidiary Saber Interactive) [T0075], Dead Pixels by TPS Group²⁹ in 2019 [T0083; T0084], and recently the acquisition of 49% of Memorable Games by uBroker (2024) [T0033],³⁰ are not attributable to specific advantages or relationships due to the cluster's membership (as confirmed by the data that emerged in D4.1). The small number of corporate acquisitions, moreover, indicates both the difficulty of such operations for the cluster's development studios and their vocation to produce purely indie-type video games. Similarly, IIDEA's national documents use annual data on the market value of individual industry segments as a means of lobbying national and European institutions [T0041] (but also as a means of disseminating data to a more general audience). IIDEA distinguishes the video game production market [T0042; T0059] from that of e-sports [T0040], highlighting how both are complementary to the economic and financial value of the entire industry. In their reports, regional public institutions provide an overview of the market value of sectors partially related to gaming (ICT, deep tech, etc.), broken down by numerous economic parameters. This gives an idea of the potential for greater participation and collaboration between cluster players and these other industries [T0010; T0043; T0068; T0070]. Although in this case no specific market data for video game production is reported, the interest, almost exclusively in high-tech B2B productions, is clear. The same information can be inferred from the many academic documents [T0061; T0063; T0066; T0076; T0078; T0079; T0080; T0081; T0082], although these have the problem of not being up to date.

²⁸ Embracer Group AB is a Swedish video game and media holding company based in Karlstad (<https://embracer.com/>).

²⁹ TPS Group is a company that offers engineering services for industry through various business units: its clients include Leonardo, FCA, Ferrari, Alstom and Avio Aero (<https://www.tps-group.it/>).

³⁰ uBroker is an electricity and gas supplier that provides services to private and business customers of all sizes throughout Italy (<https://ubroker.it/>). It is part of the Utilia holding company (<https://www.utiliaholding.it/>) [T0074].

Despite what has just been reported, economic and financial data relating to the local industry are scarce. Apart from the official data from development studios reported on their respective websites, there is little data available in documents relating to the economic and financial aspects of the local gaming sector. There appears to be no recent data produced at a collective and/or institutional level. References to the turnover of individual companies are rare [T0026]. Atmosfera Creativa (2012) [T0001] distinguishes the value of Turin's creative industries by sector, with the limitation that it was published before the creation of the cluster (based on 2007 data) and only reports the number of companies and employees in the sector at the time.

5.6.6 Benefits for the stakeholders

What the document analysis shows is mainly about potential benefits, as mentioned in research reports from public institutions, for companies working in the cluster. However, as mentioned a few times in this report, this would mean a change in production type, focusing mainly on the different possible B2B applications [T0010; T0043; T0070]. This production 'philosophy' is in stark contrast to what was stated directly by the interviewees in D4.1, as development studios, individual creatives and the type of productions in the cluster are decidedly oriented towards a certain type of B2C production, mainly indie, creativity-driven and high-quality. In T-Union's lobbying efforts (2014) [T0017], the main advantages of collaboration between the ecosystem and regional institutions are explained: work carried out for large regional companies; applied games for schools and other public institutions; close links between schools and the professional labour market; the possibility of attracting students from other regions; the transformation of the Piedmont Region into a national hub for the production of video games and applied games; participation in calls for national, European and international projects/funds; a return to the Region in economic/financial terms; and also a return to the Region in terms of public image. As can be seen from the in-depth interviews and the absence of ad hoc documentation, this collaboration did not see full collective participation by the institutions, but only individual and fragmented actions. Lastly, the documents also reiterate how the city of Turin is an ideal environment for development companies [T0009; T0023; T0068], above all due to the presence of 'a substrate of skills and professionals' in which it is very easy to access a large qualified talent pool [T0026], as well as lower overall costs compared to other large cities in Italy [comments under T0006].

End of Chapter

6 BRNO CLUSTER

6.1 Data Collection and Analysis

For the Brno cluster, data collection was an iterative process aimed at creating a corpus of publicly available documents reflecting primarily the current state of the cluster and how it is represented and framed to the general public. The focus on the contemporary documents was intended to avoid an overlap with the forthcoming T4.3, which deals with the historical dimension of clusters. With the help of the team from Herní klastr, which by itself monitors media coverage of their own activities, we have conducted several rounds of data collection starting from July 2024 up until August 2025. A broad variety of materials were collected, including journalistic articles, newsletters, government and policy reports, blog posts, official websites, videos and audio podcasts.

Online search was used as the primary means of data collection, employing various search terms combining terms related to video game production (e.g., “herní průmysl” “gaming industry”, “počítačové hry” “computer games”) and the location of the cluster (e.g., “Brno”, “Jihomoravský kraj”). Additional keywords were identified during the first screening of the documents and the subsequent analysis. The refined search queries resulted in additional documents as did references and other links within the documents. As such the initially collected documents (approximately 47 by January 2025) yielded further results, which were added to the dataset even during the analysis. **The final dataset for the Brno cluster consists of 89 documents.** It is important to note that the documents vary significantly in their scope and content. While some were short press releases, others were extensive reports or long audio podcasts (see Table 34). During the data collection process, we have also identified several historical documents, which were saved for further analysis in T4.3. Additionally, for some tables (such as Table 37) we refer to additional sources outside of the main corpus.

Item Type	Count
Press release or PR/sponsored article	22
News article	18
Podcast or video	17
Website	15
Report	7
Newsletter	6
Other/Unclassified	4

Table 34 – Documents from the Brno cluster by type

All 89 documents of various multimodal nature (including not just standard verbal text but also presentations or videos), were analysed primarily qualitatively regarding their content using inductive thematic analysis (Ayres, 2008). As such the more social semiotics aspects of the texts were excluded from the analysis as these aspects were not considered relevant to the task at hand although they still affected the practical process of the analysis such as the extraction of verbal contents of each document. Table 35 shows the language breakdown of the documents; the majority was written in English. The analysis was done manually by one coder using the open-source software QualCoder (Curtain & Dröge, 2019/2024). In order to provide new insights, beyond the material presented in D4.1, the analytical grid from T3.1 was used only to group emerging codes and identify larger patterns and connections between themes regarding their place in the cluster features and dynamics. This approach was chosen to encourage the coder to discover novel findings compared to T4.1 as many previous observations obtained through analysis of semi-structured interviews were also present in the T4.2 dataset. As a result, this chapter fills some of the gaps of D4.1 relating to the Brno cluster, especially the notable games and companies from this area and how they fit into the current narratives about this particular cluster of video game industry.

Item Language	Count
Czech	67
English	12
Bilingual (Czech & English versions available)	9
Slovak	1
Total	89

Table 35 – Documents from the Brno cluster by language

6.2 Brno

D4.1 provided a general overview of Brno as the second largest city in Czechia, and readers are invited to see that document for more details. To briefly summarize, Brno has a long industrial tradition going back to the 19th century and since the 1990s it has transitioned toward ICT as its new strategic focus (Vaishar et al., 2025; Ženka et al., 2017). Several documents [e.g., [BRN007](#), [BRN008](#), [BRN009](#), [BRN010](#)] position Brno, as well as the surrounding South Moravian region, as an innovation centre of Czechia, putting the local video game industry cluster into a larger context of technology-oriented policies. Nonetheless, the emergence of video game production in Brno predates these newer policies and was influenced by the well-developed educational infrastructure and Brno’s lower costs of living in the 1990s compared to the country’s capital Prague. A more in-depth exploration of the origins of the Brno video game ecosystem will be undertaken as part of the forthcoming T4.3. Based on the interviews from D4.1, we have stated that Brno’s position as the second largest Czech city contributes to its communal spirit. This idea that the relative smallness of the city provides better conditions for networking and cooperation between developers was also found in the T4.2 dataset, however perhaps not to the degree which we would expect. Only four documents refer to Brno’s genius loci (i.e. spirit of the place) as the possible benefit for the growth of the local video game industry [[BRN002](#), [BRN011](#), [BRN012](#), [BRN013](#)]. Based on previous game production studies scholarship, we can see similarities between Brno and Montreal, both second largest cities of their respective countries, Czechia and Canada, which have developed strong video game industries (Darchen & Tremblay, 2015). This comparison was even explicitly mentioned by one of the important industry figures from Brno – Jarek Kolář – who voiced his aspirations in press interviews upon the founding of InGame Studios in 2021: “We want to contribute to Brno becoming the Czech capital of video game similarly to Montreal’s position in Canada.” [[BRN073](#)] Montreal was, in this regard in academic writing, seen as a “village city” with suitable conditions for establishing creative and cultural industry clusters (Darchen & Tremblay, 2015).

Despite this explicit comparison and several mentions of Brno’s friendly atmosphere, more emphasis in the analysed documents was put on the tradition of video game development in Brno, which goes back to the mid-1990s [e.g., [BRN003](#), [BRN021](#), [BRN064](#), [BRN067](#), [BRN071](#)], and the available educational programs [e.g., [BRN005](#), [BRN023](#), [BRN031](#), [BRN042](#)]. While the educational offer in Brno is praised within the Czech context, it is at the same time seen as a space for further improvement given the acknowledged talent shortage. Today, the video game industry is an important part of Brno’s and South Moravian region’s industrial policy. The recognition of the local video game development community was helped by the founding of the Game Cluster (Herní klastr) organization in 2021. The local ecosystem is now formally represented by this institution but still relies heavily on voluntary labour of individuals, who organize events for both the industry and the

broader public. Another important dimension is the collaboration between various types of actors in Brno, including game companies, educational institutions and government agencies such as the South Moravian Innovation Centre (JIC). These findings from D4.1 are further supported by the analysis of documents. The following pages expand on these dynamics by highlighting how the Brno ecosystem is presented in public-facing documents, including the emphasis on popular games, the long tradition of game development, and the strong educational infrastructure now also supported by the Game Cluster organization.

6.3 Cluster Emergence & Genesis

Based on interviews with key actors from the Brno cluster for D4.1, we have outlined the origins of the local video game production ecosystem. The key moments are summarized in the table below. Specifically, the activities of entrepreneur Petr Vochozka were instrumental to the emergence of video game industry cluster in Brno. First, he published several games made in Brno, including *The Secret of Donkey Island* (1994) or *Dragon History* (1995), while operating his company Vochozka Trading from another location. In 1995, Vochozka relocated to Brno and started to recruit developers in the city, leading to the foundation of Illusion Softworks in 1997. The studio went on to produce two influential and commercially successful games *Hidden & Dangerous* (1999) and *Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven* (2002) before being acquired in 2008 by the U.S. publisher Take-Two, which has previously distributed the two aforementioned games.

D4.1 findings	Description
Industrial & Educational Infrastructure	Brno’s industrial history and the presence of educational institutions provided access to mainframes and computers since the 1960s.
Vochozka Trading & Illusion Softworks	Petr Vochozka distributed first commercial video games from Brno and founded the key studio Illusion Softworks, which produced first international hits <i>Hidden & Dangerous</i> (1999) and <i>Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven</i> (2002). The success of these games has helped professionalize the Brno video game development community.
Cluster Formalization	The founding of the Game Cluster organization in 2020 formalized the existing developer community, which has coalesced around industry meet-ups and other events. The formal representation of the ecosystem helped secure government support and brings together various actors from companies to educators.

Table 36 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster emergence in Brno

The international success of *Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven* allowed the developer community to grow and professionalize, leading to other studios being founded drawing on the expertise of people involved in making this game. However, Brno has then long waited for a success story of the same scale, although the cluster produced commercially successful games.

6.3.1 Local industry: Origins & Historical Legacy

Brno has a long industrial history, which we have briefly summarised in D4.1. The documentary evidence provides some additional insights into the new directions of Brno’s and South Moravian region’s economy. In the past, Brno was focused on manufacturing, starting with textile in the 19th century. Weapons manufacturing became an important part of the local business in the 20th century. Zbrojovka Brno also produced automobiles and other goods, including mainframes and computers in the second part of the 20th century. The manufacturing industry was supported in Brno as part of the centrally planned command economy of the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic. After the

transition toward market economy in the 1990s, the manufacturing industry experienced a swift decline, necessitating a new business direction. The strong infrastructure of technical education helped facilitate transition toward modern technologies and ICT. IBM’s major investment in 2001 facilitated further growth in this area (Ženka et al., 2017).

Several of the analysed documents were produced by the South Moravian Innovation Centre, which supports video game production as well as other areas. Their reports provide additional context to the role of the video game industry cluster in the region. Video game production first received only brief mentions tied to specific companies like Alda Games in the 2022 report [BRN007] and Ashborne Games and Madfinger Games in the 2023 report [BRN008], otherwise the focus was on the ICT and tech sector more broadly. Starting with the 2024 report [BRN009], video games received more attention and the 2025 report [BRN010] lists video game production among the five key economic areas in terms of innovation. The other four include: (1) semiconductors and chips, (2) microscopes, (3) space tech and research, and (4) cybersecurity. The region as a whole boasts a rapid increase in IT, science, and technology employment to 70,000 people in these sectors by 2023. The video game industry has a longer history, dating back to the 1990s, but the founding of the Game Cluster organization in 2020 helped in attracting the attention of policymakers. We have already observed this based on the D4.1 interviews, but documentary evidence provides additional support for this finding.

6.3.2 Notable games produced in Brno

Based on the documentary evidence, games have become a useful shorthand for highlighting the legacy of Brno’s video game industry. In D4.1, we mentioned some of the most influential titles like *Hidden & Dangerous* and *Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven*, but here we aim to provide a more comprehensive overview of notable games (see Table 37). The goal here is also to show the diversity of locally produced games, which go beyond a particular genre or sector of video game production.

Game(s)	Company	Platform Engine /	Technologies	Indicators / Sources
The Secret of Donkey Island (1994)	Pterodon Software / Vochozka Trading	PC / proprietary engine	Point and click adventure, 2D graphics, spoof of Monkey Island series	One of the earliest commercial games made in Brno by students; sold over 2000 copies [BRN005, BRN021]
Dragon History (1995)	NoSense / Vochozka Trading	PC / proprietary engine	Point and click adventure, 2D graphics, Czech voiceover	Early commercially successful game made by students from Brno; sold over 7000 copies [BRN023, BRN087, BRN088]
Fish Fillets (1997)	ALTAR Interactive	PC / proprietary engine	Puzzle game, 2D graphics	Followed up by a sequel in 2007 [BRN054, BRN056, BRN057]
Hidden & Dangerous (1999)	Illusion Softworks	PC, PlayStation, Dreamcast / proprietary engine	Tactical shooter, 3D graphics	International success with <u>over 350,000 copies sold by 2000</u> [BRN015]
Flying Heroes (2000)	Pterodon (subcontract Illusion Softworks)	PC / proprietary engine	First-person shooter, 3D graphics	Mixed reviews, but a moderate success with <u>over 100,000 copies sold by 2002</u> [BRN087]

Original War (2001)	ALTAR Interactive	PC / proprietary engine	Real-time strategy, 2D/3D graphics	Critically acclaimed title, a strong modding scene [BRN054 , BRN056]
Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven (2002)	Illusion Softworks	PC, PlayStation 2, Xbox / proprietary engine	Action adventure with open world and driving	International success with over 2 million copies sold by 2007 ; often considered the best Czech video game [BRN021 , BRN055]
Samorost (2003)	Amanita Design	Flash	Puzzle point and click adventure, stylized visuals, freeware	Influential indie title, which spawned two sequels in 2005 and 2016 [BRN019 , BRN052]
Vietcong (2003)	Pterodon (as a subcontractor for Illusion Softworks)	PC, PlayStation 2, Xbox / proprietary engine	Tactical first-person shooter	Commercially successful game with over 1 million copies sold by 2007 [BRN073]
UFO: Aftermath (2003)	ALTAR Interactive	PC / proprietary engine	XCOM inspired turn-based/real-time strategy game	Followed up by two sequels <i>Aftershock</i> (2005) and <i>Afterlight</i> (2007) [BRN019 , BRN041]
Machinarium (2009)	Amanita Design	PC, ported to multiple platforms / Flash	Puzzle point and click adventure, stylized visuals	Commercially successful title with over 4 million copies sold by 2016 [BRN005 , BRN021]
Shadowgun (2011)	Madfinger Games	iOS, Blackberry, Android / Unity	Cover-based third-person shooter	Commercially successful game [BRN009 , BRN016]
Dead Trigger (2012)	Madfinger Games	iOS, Android / Unity	First-person zombie shooter, includes microtransactions	Commercially successful game [BRN009 , BRN016]
Galaxy Trucker (2014)	CGE Digital	iPad, iPhone, Android, Windows Phone	Digital adaptation of a board game	Commercially successful game [BRN009 , BRN057]
Rememoried (2015)	Hangonit	PC / Unity	Experimental platformer/walking simulator	Received the Czech Game of the Year award for Artistic Contribution [BRN077 , BRN078]
Codenames (2015)	CGE	Board game	Party board game; later adapted into a video game	Received the prestigious Spiel des Jahres award, commercially successful with multiple language versions [BRN005 , BRN009 , BRN057]
Mashinky (2018)	Jan Zelený	PC / proprietary engine	Train simulation game	Commercially successful game made by a solo developer, over 80,000 copies sold
Through the Ages (2018)	CGE Digital	iOS, Android, PC	Digital adaptation of a board game	Commercially successful game [BRN005 , BRN019 , BRN054]
Vigor (2019)	Bohemia Interactive	Xbox One, later ported to other platforms / Unreal Engine 4	Survival multiplayer shooter, free-to-play, with microtransactions	It is receiving regular updates as of 2025 [BRN023 , BRN087]

Someday You'll Return (2020)	CBE Software	PC, PlayStation 4, PlayStation 5 / Unreal Engine 4	Psychological horror	Re-released in 2023 as a Director's Cut [BRN019 , BRN023]
Afterglitch (2022)	Hangonit	PC, Xbox One, Xbox Series X/S / Unity	Experimental exploration game	Nominated for the Nuovo and Excellence in Visual Art Awards at the Independent Games Festival [BRN077 , BRN078]
To the Dragon (2022)	Kikiriki Games	Android, iOS / Unity	Audio-based shooter	Nominated for the Most Innovative Mobile Game at Pocket Gamer Awards [BRN070]
Brave Brain (2023)	Kikiriki Games	Android, iOS / Unity	Quiz game	No information about sales [BRN070]
Crime Boss: Rockay City (2023)	Ingame Studios	PC, PlayStation 5, Xbox Series X/S / Unreal Engine 4	Cooperative first-person shooter	An initially unsuccessful game, which has improved over time [BRN012]
Last Train Home (2023)	Ashborne Games	PC / Unreal Engine 4	Real-time strategy on WW1 events	Won the Czech Game of the Year award [BRN009 , BRN025]
Gray Zone Warfare (2024)	Madfinger Games	PC / Unreal Engine 5	Tactical multiplayer shooter game	Commercially successful game with over 1 million copies sold by 2025 [BRN016]

Table 37 – Notable video games produced in Brno; only covers titles mentioned in at least two or more documents from the T4.2 dataset

Initially in the 1980s and early 1990s, a lot of the games produced in Czechia, and prior to that in Czechoslovakia, were either text adventures, which are from a programming standpoint relatively easy to create, or clones and ports of Western games (Švelch, 2018). *The Secret of Donkey Island* (*Tajemství Oslího ostrova*, 1994) or *Dragon History* (*Dračí historie*, 1995), which rank among the first commercially sold games from Brno, belong to this design trajectory, following the genre of point and click adventures and in the first case even directly referring to the *Monkey Island* franchise developed by the U.S. company LucasArts. Compared to previous hobbyist Czech games, *Dragon History*, specifically, boasted a full Czech voiceover, which helped it become a domestic hit, albeit for the then relatively small market. *Fish Fillets* (1997) is a curious mix of influences, combining the puzzle mechanics of pushing objects from the likes of *Sokoban* (Thinking Rabbit, 1982) and X-Files-inspired characters, albeit in a fish form.

Hidden & Dangerous marks a departure from the three relatively simple games described above. It is a much more ambitious title, which won critical acclaim even outside Czechia while the previous games had aimed at the domestic market, perhaps with the exception of *Fish Fillets*. *Hidden & Dangerous* features 3D graphics and real-time action and belongs among the first games in the tactical shooter genre. This was a first major international success for Illusion Softworks, opening up further opportunities for the company. Due to its commercial success, *Hidden & Dangerous* received several expansions and a standalone sequel in 2003. *Vietcong* (2003), which was developed by Pterodon in a subcontractor role for Illusion Softworks, shares the same genre with *Hidden & Dangerous* and also became commercially successful. Before *Vietcong*, Pterodon released a fantasy shooter *Flying Heroes* (2000) to mixed reviews, eventually selling upwards of 100,000 copies.

In 2002, Illusion Softworks published *Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven*, likely the most iconic video game made in Brno. This is an open-world third-person action game most reminiscent of the *Grand Theft Auto* series. Compared to the mostly contemporary settings of the GTA series, *Mafia* was set in the 1930s. *Mafia* was a major commercial hit and spawned an entire franchise, whose most recent instalment *Mafia: The Old Country* was released in August 2025. The *Mafia* series and its origins in Brno are often invoked in press coverage and other public materials of local video game industry. The 2008 sequel *Mafia II* was, however, considered a mild disappointment among Czech players, but it sold well enough to warrant an expansion in form of downloadable content (DLC) [BRN055]. For the third instalment released in 2016, the creative direction was handled by a U.S. studio Hangar 13, but the Brno branch worked on the game, too.

Altar Interactive, which developed the puzzle game *Fish Fillets*, then switched to the strategy genre, starting with the real-time strategy game *Original War* and the trio of real-time turn-based hybrids *UFO: Aftermath*, *Aftershock*, and *Afterlight*, inspired by the XCOM (1994) series from MicroProse.

Compared to the aforementioned PC games, which were made by increasingly professionalized teams, *Samorost* (2003) stands out as a formally student game made in Flash. It was distributed as freeware, the sequels were, however, sold commercially. Aesthetically, the game uses stylized visuals and can be considered part of the so-called independent or indie style (Juul, 2019). From a genre viewpoint, it is a point and click puzzle adventure with an arguably short playtime. Amanita Design later released other titles using the same design philosophy, including the commercially successful *Machinarium* (2009). While Amanita Design's founder Jakub Dvorský is originally from Brno and he had previously worked as artist on *Dragon History* (1995), he studied at the Academy of Arts, Architecture and Design in Prague (UMPRUM) and many of the newer projects were not created in Brno. Still, some documents use Amanita Design and their games as belonging to the Brno video game development scene [BRN005, BRN009, BRN019, BRN021, BRN064].

Except for *Samorost*, most of these games used proprietary technology. In the 1990s and 2000s, there were not that many commercially available engines and so the studios from Brno developed their own technological solutions. While some Czech companies still use in-house engines (Houška, 2025), in the 2010s studios from Brno started using Unity and Unreal. Besides using Unity, shooters *Shadowgun* (2011) and *Dead Trigger* (2012) also stand out as first major releases for mobile platforms, thus moving away from PC as the platform of choice of many Brno-based video game companies. Both games were commercially successful and also scored nominations and wins at the Czech annual video game awards. Another notable step toward diversifying Brno's video game production can be attributed to the founding of CGE Digital, a spin-off company of the board game publisher Czech Games Edition. CGE Digital started developing digital adaptation of existing board games for mobile platforms and PC, including *Galaxy Trucker* (2014), *Through the Ages* (2018), and *Codenames Online* (2021). The original board game Codenames was a major critical and commercial success, and it was mentioned in the documents to showcase the diversity of the games produced in Brno as well as their international critical acclaim [BRN004, BRN005, BRN009, BRN012, BRN019, BRN023]. In the 2010s, there were also a few notable projects of solo developers. *Rememoried* (2015) is an experimental platformer made in Unity, which won the Czech annual video game award for Artistic Contribution. The follow-up game *Afterglitch* (2022) from the same author follows a similar experimental approach and it was nominated for two awards at the international Independent Games Festival. *Mashinky* (2018) is a very different game although it was also created by a singular developer. Inspired by *Railroad Tycoon* (MicroProse, 1990) and other transportation simulation games, *Mashinky* uses a proprietary engine, and it was released in early access on Steam,

using this more recent distribution model to fund the ongoing development of the game. As of 2025, the game still regularly receives updates, and it is considered a commercial success. *Someday You'll Return* (2020) is a two-person project, featuring Czech landscapes (Švelch & Houška, 2025). Originally self-published, the team received support from the major Czech studio Bohemia Interactive and released an *improved* version in 2023. Going back to the larger studios, Bohemia Interactive's Brno branch produced a survival third-person shooter game *Vigor* in 2019. While the company is known for using its own proprietary technology, *Vigor* was developed in Unreal Engine 4 and first released on Xbox One, followed by other major console platforms and PC. Several other Unreal Engine games were made in Brno in the 2020s, including shooters *Crime Boss: Rockay City* (2023) and *Gray Zone Warfare* (2024). *Last Train Home* (2023) uses the same engine, but it is a real-time tactical game based on the WW1. While *Mafia: The Old Country* (2025) was not present in the analysed documents, it is using Unreal Engine 5. This is a major change for the series, which up until that point always employed its own proprietary technology. *To the Dragon* (2022) and *Brave Brain* (2023) are recent mobile releases with accessibility features aimed at players with visual impairment. Developed by a two-person team, these two titles point at potential new directions in terms of target audience. On the example of Amanita Design, we have already showed that some games developed outside of Brno are still mentioned when describing the local industry ecosystem due to personal connections of their developers or the presence of Brno branches within larger production networks. In a similar vein, the tactical military series *Arma* from Bohemia Interactive and *Farming Simulator* from GIANTS Software have also been mentioned several times [[BRN005](#), [BRN009](#), [BRN010](#), [BRN019](#), [BRN027](#), [BRN073](#)]. While developers from Brno have contributed to these games, they were originally created elsewhere. For this reason, these games are excluded from Table 37 although they received multiple mentions in the dataset. Excluded were also games mentioned in a single document, these included *Dark Train* (Paperash Studio, 2013) [[BRN042](#)], *Monzo* (Madfinger Games, 2015) [[BRN052](#)], or *Happy Game* (Amanita Design, 2021) [[BRN052](#)]. It is also important to acknowledge some omissions in the dataset, or to be more precise the fact that some studios are considered part of the Brno video game industry ecosystem, but their games are rarely mentioned if at all. This concerns particularly Alda Games and NOXGAMES, which both develop mobile games. In general, mobile games have a lower status in game culture and do not receive as much attention as mainstream titles or indie games (see Consalvo & Paul, 2019). The dataset confirms this bias against the mobile sector despite the fact that, for example, Alda Games, was ranked among the top 15 tech startups in the South Moravian region [[BRN007](#)].

6.4 Local Industry Features & Components

6.4.1 Perimeter of the cluster

In D4.1, we have focused primarily on defining the Brno video game industry cluster based on the interview data, which showed some overlap between the city of Brno and the whole South Moravian region in terms of the spatial boundaries of the cluster.

See Table 38 for an overview of the previous findings from D4.1. Still, Brno is clearly the centre of the cluster with many companies located in close vicinity (see Figure 8). One exception among the five biggest studios based on [BRN005](#) is 2K Czech (also often referred to as Hangar 13), whose offices can be found in the Slatina district south-east of the city centre.

D4.1 findings	Description
City and region	Brno is the core of the cluster with major companies located in the city centre. Some institutions, like the South Moravian Innovation Centre (JIC), operate on the level of the whole region, but have a strong presence within the city itself, namely the KUMST building, which hosts the incubator program and co-working spaces for developers.
Company headquarters vs. branches	While Brno hosts several key companies that are headquartered in the city (or historically originated here), there are also notable branches of studios with headquarters elsewhere. This includes Prague-based Bohemia Interactive ¹ and Grip Digital or GIANTS Software with headquarters in Switzerland.
Logistical challenges	Brno benefits from its compact geography and relative smallness of its historical centre. International transportation options are, however, limited with only few connections to the Brno airport.

Table 38 – Main D4.1 findings relating to local industry features and components

Figure 8 – Location of five major studios based on BRN005 and the location of the Gamebase incubator and co-working space at KUMST

Documentary evidence provides more information on the connections between Brno and the capital city Prague. In D4.1, we have observed that the policy-related activities of the Game Cluster organization elevated it to the national level as another entity representing the interests of the industry beyond the nation-wide Czech Game Developers Association (GDACZ), which is based in Prague. The analysed documents show both historical and contemporary connections between the two cities, which go back to the founding of ALTAR Interactive. Martin Klíma, one of its co-founders, was from Prague and he relocated to Brno around 1997 to start the studio. ALTAR Interactive was acquired in the late 2000s by Bohemia Interactive, whose biggest office is located in Prague. Aside from Bohemia Interactive, Grip Studios, a co-development company based in Prague, opened their Brno office in 2022.

Most recently, Ashborne Games collaborated with Prague-based Warhorse Studios on DLC (downloadable content) for *Kingdom Come: Deliverance 2*. Shortly after that Warhorse Studios opened a new office in Brno, headed by Petr Kolář, who had previously worked in Bohemia Interactive and Ashborne Games. Ashborne Games and Warhorse Studios are both owned by the Embracer Group.² Furthermore, Martin Klíma, the founder of ALTAR Interactive, holds the position of executive producer at Warhorse Studios, and Daniel Vávra, lead writer of Illusion Softwork’s *Mafia* and *Mafia 2*, is a creative director at Warhorse Studios. An overview of the connections between companies founded in Brno and Prague is presented in Table 39.

Studio	Years Active	Other Notable Locations	Connections to Other Companies
2K Czech	2008–current	Prague (office); Novato, CA (via Hangar 13)	Successor of Illusion Softworks after acquisition by Take Two. It works alongside Hangar 13 on the Mafia series. [BRN055]
ALTAR Interactive	1997–2010	Prague	Founded by Martin Klíma from ALTAR TTRPG publisher based originally in Prague. Acquired by Bohemia Interactive and later rebranded as part of Bohemia Interactive. Klíma now acts as executive producer at Warhorse Studios. [BRN054, BRN056, BRN057]
Amanita Design	2003–current	Prague	Founder Jakub Dvorský is from Brno and some team members are located in Brno, but the official headquarters of the studio is in Prague. [BRN021, BRN023]
Ashborne Games	2020–current	None	Founded by former employees from Bohemia Interactive. The studio worked on DLC for <i>Kingdom Come: Deliverance 2</i> from Warhorse Studios. [BRN018]

Table 39 – Studios considered as being founded in Brno and their connections outside the cluster

Aside from these ties to Prague, there are other studio branches in Brno with headquarters elsewhere, most notably 2K Czech, which is part of the major international publisher Take-Two and currently uses the Hangar 13 branding, and GIANTS Software with headquarters in Zurich, Switzerland (for an overview see Table 40). In 2023, Pixel Federation, a mobile game studio based in nearby Bratislava closed its Brno branch just a few years after its opening due to post-pandemic decline of the video game industry (Pixel Federation, 2024).

Studio	Headquarters	Brno Office Details
Bohemia Interactive	Mníšek pod Brdy (formally), Prague	Brno branch created through an acquisition (2005) and later rebranding of ALTAR Interactive in 2010; approximately 120 employees.
Czech Games Edition	Prague	CGE Digital branch opened around 2014 to develop digital versions of board games; approximately 15 employees.
GIANTS Software	Zurich, Switzerland	Brno branch opened around 2018; approximately 30 employees.
Grip Studios	Prague	Brno branch opened in 2022; approximately 25 employees.
Pixel Federation	Bratislava, Slovakia	Brno branch opened around 2021 and reportedly closed in 2024 (Pixel Federation, 2024).
Warhorse Studios	Prague	Brno branch opened in 2025; approximately 30 employees.

Table 40 – Studios with branches in Brno

Aside from these business networks, the representatives of the local cluster also frequently visit educational institutions in nearby regions and cities, including Jihlava, Ostrava, or Zlín [BRN038, BRN039, BRN040]. This was already mentioned in D4.1, but the T4.2 dataset provides additional information on these activities.

6.4.2 Demographics of companies

In D4.1, we presented an overview of companies represented in Brno’s Game Cluster organization. Many of the data, such as about the number of employees, were based on estimates provided by the representatives of the Game Cluster organization and sometimes outdated information available online. In D4.1, we suggested that there were approximately 550–650 employees in the Brno video game industry cluster. In the analysed documents, we observed other numbers, going as high as 900 people based on membership in the GameDev Area community [BRN005, BRN009, BRN010, BRN063].

The T4.2 dataset contains some new information on companies' demographics therefore, which is presented in Table 41. This table also covers new developments such as the opening of a new office of Warhorse Studios in Brno, which happened in June 2025.

Studio	Basic Info	Size & Structure	Specialisation
2K Czech / Hangar 13	Subsidiy of 2K famous for the Mafia series	Approx. 80 in Brno; offices in California and Prague	Action adventure games
Alda Games	Mobile game studio	Approx. 30	Mobile games across various genres
Amanita Design	Independent studio	Handful of developers in Brno; several teams across Czechia	Indie puzzle adventure games
Ashborne Games	Subsidiy of THQ Nordic (Embracer Group)	Approx. 50	PC games
Bohemia Interactive	Veteran PC game studio	Approx. 120 in Brno; multiple other offices, including Prague	Shooter and simulation games
CBE Software	Small independent studio	2 developers	Horror adventure games
Czech Games Edition	Board game publisher with a digital division	Approx. 15 in Brno; Prague branch develops board games; Brno branch does digital versions	Family board games
GIANTS Software	International studio famous for Farming Simulator	Approx. 30 in Brno; multiple other offices, including Germany and Switzerland	Simulation games
Ingame Studios	Newer studio established by veteran developers (subsidiy of Digital Bros./505 Games)	Approx. 70	Cooperative multiplayer shooter games
Madfinger Games	Veteran game studio	Approx. 80	Shooter games originally for mobile platforms, recently for PC
Nox Games	Mobile game studio	Approx. 30	Mobile games across various genres
Warhorse Studios	Subsidiy of PLAION (part of the Embracer Group) famous for Kingdom Come: Deliverance	Approx. 30; Prague HQ and a new Brno office	Medieval role-playing games

Table 41 – Studios with offices in Brno that produce their own games

The documentary evidence further supports the notion that Brno’s video game industry is varied in terms of company size as well as market orientation. There are at least five studios with more than 50 employees [BRN005] and many smaller ones, including solo developers.

Traditionally, the studios in Brno focused on the PC games sector, but a newer wave of companies established in the 2000s and onwards also publish games for mobile devices. The dataset also provides new insights into the segment of service providers – companies that do not primarily produce their own games, but offer co-development and other outsourcing capabilities [BRN005, BRN006, BRN019, BRN029]. Table 42 features an overview of Brno-based service providers in the area of video game production.

Studio	Basic Info	Services	Notable Clients
Brocap Studios	Established in 2022; 2 employees.	Motion capture, animations, cinematics, pre-viz.	Ashborne Games, Centurion Developments, Hangar 13, Ingame Studios, Trailer Farm.
Fineway Studios	Founded by Jakub Bedecs (organizer of the Game Access conference) in the 2010s.	Localization, quality assurance.	2K Games, EA Bethesda, Wargaming.net.
Grip Studios	Brno branch opened in 2022; approximately 25 employees.	Co-development, porting, quality assurance.	2K Games, Machine Games, Obsidian, Red hook Studios.
Kapnetix	Established in 2023 by Gauss Algorithmic (AI provider based in Brno).	Animation, automated mocap data cleanup.	None listed.

Table 42 – Service providers for video game production in Brno

6.5 Cluster Evolution

6.5.1 Critical moments, phases and evolution curves

The analysed documents provide some insights into the legacy of first major studios in Brno. To avoid unnecessary overlaps with the upcoming T4.3, we will provide only a brief overview of the origins of the local video game cluster and instead focus more on the interconnectedness of the development community, which can be traced back to the founding of companies like Illusion Softworks. Table 43 summarizes the key findings from D4.1 regarding the cluster evolution. The updated Figure 9 (adapted from D4.1) presents an extended timeline of the evolution of the Brno ecosystem, including more recent developments in the 2010s, which contributed to the formalization of the local industry cluster.

D4.1 findings	Description
Vochozka Trading & Illusion Softworks	Petr Vochozka distributed first commercial video games from Brno and founded the key studio Illusion Softworks, which produced first international hits <i>Hidden & Dangerous</i> (1999) and <i>Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven</i> (2002). The success of these games has helped professionalize the Brno video game development community.
Industry Consolidation	Following the success of <i>Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven</i> (2002), Illusion Softworks started developing a sequel and was acquired by publisher Take Two in 2008. New studios formed in Brno, often featuring former employees from Illusion Softworks.

Cluster Formalization	The founding of the Game Cluster organization in 2020 formalized the existing developer community. An important moment in the formalization process was the policy discussion about the Audiovisual Act (ca. 2022–2024) in which the Game Cluster representatives actively negotiated on behalf of the local industry.
------------------------------	--

Table 43 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster evolution

Figure 9 – Timeline of Brno video game industry evolution highlighting the events after consolidation phase

Prior to the establishment of Illusion Softworks, the development community in Brno was very informal and comprised mostly students. Their creations were not technically student games as they were not created as part of coursework, but they leveraged the fact the developers as students had lower costs of living and could work on games in their leisure time. Illusion Softworks drew on the existing personal networks that its founder Petr Vochozka had established while operating the publishing company Vochozka Trading. Vochozka Trading published games made across the whole country, but Illusion Softworks was a much more spatially defined endeavour, with its headquarters located in Brno. In order to create a studio capable of seeking international publishing contracts, Vochozka called on his previous contacts and asked them to relocate to Brno [BRN055]. Thanks to their contract with Take-Two, Illusion Softworks was then able to provide work for other studios, including Pterodon, who often acted as a subcontractor. The publishing deal with Take-Two and the subsequent success of games like *Hidden & Dangerous* and *Mafia: The City of Lost Heaven* allowed Illusion Softworks to grow and hire more developers, attracting talent from across Czechia to Brno. At the same time, experienced developers from Illusion Softworks and Pterodon started founding their own studios, including Vatra Games (only rarely mentioned in the dataset [BRN005, BRN019, BRN055]) and later also Madfinger Games, whose games we covered in the previous section. Ingame Studios also features veterans from the 1990s Brno development community. This legacy can be seen also on the types of games produced by these studios, which all feature shooting mechanics. Amanita Design is also connected to these veteran communities, but it has chosen a different trajectory, rather aiming at the indie sector.

ALTAR Interactive (founded in 1997, the same year as Illusion Softworks) was a separate entity until it was absorbed by Bohemia Interactive in the late 2000s. This has changed the studio's focus from strategy games to tactical shooter games, resulting in the departure of key developers like Vlaada Chvátil, who then returned to video game development at CGE Digital. Developers from Bohemia Interactive's Brno branch founded Ashborne Games in 2020, illustrating the interconnectedness of the local studios. The new branch of Warhorse Studios founded in 2025 features developers from Ashborne Games, who contributed to the development of DLC for *Kingdom Come: Deliverance 2* [BRN018, BRN071, BRN072]. Jan Zelený, the author of *Mashinky*, previously worked for both Illusion Softworks/2K Czech and Bohemia Interactive [BRN079]. While the legacy of the 1990s has a strong influence on Brno's video game industry (including in more recently established studios like Ingame Studios, which features veterans from the Illusion Softworks/Pterodon era), there are also many newcomers, be it both studios founded in the 2000s and 2010s, such as Alda Games or NOXGAMES, and smaller teams and individuals, including Hagonit or Kikiriki Games. Other critical moments for the growth of the local ecosystem fall under the expanded support and educational infrastructure. These include the founding of the trade conference Game Access in 2016 [BRN003, BRN005, BRN013, BRN023, BRN033], the organizing efforts culminating with the establishment of the Game Cluster organization in 2020 [BRN037, BRN038, BRN039, BRN040], or the official start of the video game development incubator Gamebaze in 2023 [BRN002, BRN003, BRN012, BRN013, BRN041, BRN064, BRN068, BRN059, BRN076]. These moments and factors will be described in the following sections.

6.5.2 Major factors of change & growth

As mentioned previously, the founding of Illusion Softworks was important for the professionalization of Brno's video game development community. Still, the late 1990s and early 2000s are often remembered, based on the documentary evidence, as informal and unstructured, providing opportunities for enthusiasts as opposed to skilled professionals [BRN015, BRN016, BRN052, BRN053, BRN055]. This was also caused by the lack educational programs at the time and the overall immaturity of the Czech video game industry. Petr Vochozka as the head of the studio was able to secure both domestic funding as well as an international publishing deal. This allowed for additional hiring and growth of the ecosystem. The analysed documents suggest that the development of *Mafia 2* (Illusion Softworks 2010) marked a change in these relatively unstructured game development practices, leading also to departures from the studio by developers who wanted to pursue their own projects [BRN055]. For example, around this time Vatra Games were formed. Later, some of the developers from Vatra Games founded Madfinger Games, which is still active to this day. Notably, Vatra Games are only rarely mentioned in the dataset [BRN005, BRN019, BRN055] despite having developed an instalment in the Japanese survival horror franchise *Silent Hill* (*Silent Hill Downpour* in 2012). The continuous growth of the ecosystem regarding the founding of new studios and notable game releases was described in the previous sections.

In D4.1, we have provided a more detailed analysis of the organizing and networking efforts within the Brno ecosystem, which started informally in the 2010s, but ultimately developed into the founding of the Game Cluster organization in 2020. We have also stated that other communal events like the Game Access trade conference (first edition took place in 2016) or the festival Gamer Pie (also 2016) served an important role in bringing the local community together. Other new events have also contributed to this, including Lektvar and Kompas, which showcase student games, in the former case from across Czechia, but highlight the role of Brno as a place to study video game production-related programs [BRN035, BRN036, BRN038, BRN039, BRN040, BRN065, BRN066, BRN067].

Lastly, by being active in the policy discussions about the new Audiovisual Act, the Game Cluster organization attracted public and media attention to its existence. In D4.1, we have addressed how policy advocacy is becoming part of the Game Cluster’s activities, although the organization did not initially want to engage in it. Several analysed documents highlighted the involvement of developers from Brno in this national policy discussion, which started in 2022, but reached its height during 2024 [BRN038, BRN039, BRN040, BRN047].

6.6 Collective Actions

In D4.1, we addressed the various events organized by members of the Brno video game development community. A key finding (see Table 44 for a more general overview) was the voluntary nature of many of these activities, which often originated as grassroot initiatives of individuals as opposed to top-down actions of companies and other more formalized actors in the ecosystem.

D4.1 findings	Description
Conferences & Festivals	The Brno ecosystem hosts several conferences and festivals, which target different audiences from industry professionals to the general public and attract international speakers. These events contribute the Brno’s status as an important video game industry location within Czechia.
Educational Activities	The Game Cluster organization actively works on expanding the educational programs related to video game production. Members of the organization give guest talks and lectures to attract attention to the field of video game production and related study programs offered at Brno’s universities and secondary schools.
Gamebaze Incubator	Officially launched in 2023, the Gamebaze incubator and co-working space is seen as an important step toward strengthening the support infrastructure in Brno, encouraging developers to start their own projects and companies.

Table 44 – Main D4.1 findings relating to collective actions

6.6.1 Main activities and collective actions

As mentioned, various events are considered key activities of the Brno video game industry ecosystem. In D4.1, we have highlighted their importance for the organizing efforts within the developer community. Based on documentary evidence, we provide a general overview of notable events, both those that are held annually and one-off events, in Table 45.

Event	Timeframe	Description
30 Years of Game Production in Brno	October 2023; one-off exhibition	Outdoor exhibition of the history of video game production in Brno [BRN019, BRN067]
Game Access	2016–present; usually held in June	Annual video game industry trade conference with international speakers; in English [BRN003, BRN005, BRN013, BRN023, BRN033]
GameDev Connect	2022–present; usually held in October	Annual educational conference in Czech aimed at students and general audiences; the 2022 and 2023 editions were called Game Access Connect [BRN013]
Gamer Pie	2016–present; usually annual, but not always	Video game festival for general audiences [BRN003, BRN005, BRN019, BRN021, BRN023, BRN042, BRN063]

Kompas	2022–2024; sometimes several times per year	Traveling exhibitions of student video games created at BUT [BRN035 , BRN036 , BRN065 , BRN066 , BRN067]
Lektvar	2024–present; usually held in March	Annual student game festival, previously part of GameDev Connect [BRN035 , BRN038 , BRN039 , BRN040 , BRN065 , BRN066 , BRN067]

Table 45 – Notable video game industry-related events organized in Brno

Additionally, the opening of video game development incubator Gamebaze (officially in 2023; with pilot editions in 2022) received a lot of attention in the analysed documents as it was also regarded the first program of this kind in Czechia. The associated thematic code was marked in 33 documents out of the total 86 (approx. 38%), including [BRN002](#), [BRN003](#), [BRN012](#), [BRN013](#), [BRN041](#), [BRN064](#), [BRN068](#), [BRN059](#), [BRN076](#).³ The documents included press releases as well as media coverage. Gamebaze is a collective project of the Game Cluster organization and the South Moravian Innovation Centre, and it has grown into a co-working space, currently using the spaces of the KUMST building in downtown Brno (see also Figure 8). Another major collective action is the development of the educational infrastructure in Brno. This primarily involves educational institutions, but developers, community organizers, and companies also get involved in this. We can also see an overlap between this and some of the aforementioned events, which showcase available educational programs (GameDev Connect) or student games (Lektvar, Kompas). In D4.1, we have already provided an overview of the main educational institutions (BUT, MUNI, and SŠUD) offering video game-related courses and programs. The T4.2 dataset provides further information about the more recent developments in this area. The Faculty of Fine Arts of the Brno University of Technology (BUT) transformed its Multimedia Studio (an organizational part of the university similar to a department) into Game Media Studio in 2017, marking a step toward game-specific education [[BRN061](#), [BRN074](#)]. This new studio and its representatives are important actors in the ecosystem through organizing of the festival Lektvar, which originated as its initiative, and its former student Natálie Sodomková currently works at the Gamebaze incubator [[BRN059](#), [BRN076](#)]. Additionally, the video games *Rememored* and *Afterglitch*, which we mentioned previously, were created by a BUT alum [[BRN078](#)], further illustrating the influence of this university in the ecosystem. However, the BUT relationship with the industry is not straightforward as the head of the Game Media Studio Vojtěch Vaněk emphasized artistic values and practices over more commercially driven game design. When describing the student games made at BUT, Vaněk highlighted their uniqueness and how they stand out from mainstream video game production: “These are not typical [mainstream] games, and they are not supposed to be. We are a fine arts school and the environment here is provocative. Art seeps into the games. These principles are different from mainstream game culture.” [[BRN074](#)]. The Secondary School of Art and Design (SŠUD) opened its Game Art program in 2021 and in several documents this was attributed, at least, partly to the Game Cluster organization and its activities to improve the educational infrastructure in Brno [[BRN002](#), [BRN025](#), [BRN037](#), [BRN045](#), [BRN046](#), [BRN058](#)]. In fact, the Game Cluster supported a project entitled Centre for Game Education, which helped secure the necessary funding to buy equipment for students [[BRN045](#)]. Additionally, the gaming media also informed about the success of one of the student games – *Mourning Tide* – made at the Game Art program, which was featured on the channel of a famous video game YouTube Markiplier [[BRN014](#), [BRN063](#)]. In comparison, less attention among the analysed documents was dedicated to another video game production high school program at the private Střední škola uměleckomanažerská (Secondary School of Arts Management) [[BRN023](#), [BRN025](#), [BRN045](#)]. Also, other secondary schools in Brno offer courses teaching game development skills [[BRN019](#)].

6.6.2 Stakeholders' motivations, benefits & main contributions

To continue with the theme of education from the previous section, it is considered one of the priorities of the Game Cluster organization [BRN032], as we have previously outlined in D4.1, and it also aligns with the general industry strategy of the South Moravian region, which supports tech industries and innovation [BRN009, BRN010]. The Game Cluster organization members come from different areas, including universities and secondary schools. Their representatives have clear interest in growing educational programs, but also members from video game studios, especially at management level, benefit from the increase in skilled talent. Actually, the shortage of skilled domestic job applicants for video game industry jobs was mentioned several times in the analysed documents [BRN002, BRN011, BRN061]. The current educational infrastructure in Brno was in this regard considered insufficient or at least lagging behind the demand of local studios [BRN002, BRN003, BRN025, BRN031, BRN045], but still relatively developed compared to other Czech cities and regions [BRN061, BRN064]. In D4.1, we discussed the broader motivations of members of the Game Cluster organization, which serves as a formal representation of the local ecosystem. The documentary evidence generally supports the publicly stated goals of the organization, which on top of educational support include: “(1) mutual communication and cooperation between game developers and companies; (2) raising awareness of the importance of games, promotion of game development professions; (3) talent entry into the industry – information, database, internships, incubators.” [BRN032]. These goals are pursued through a variety of collective actions already described in this chapter, including trade conferences and more informal developer gatherings (goal 1), events aimed at the general audiences like Gamer Pie or the outdoor exhibition of the history of Brno’s video game industry (goal 2), and, for example, the establishment of the incubator/co-working space Gamebaze (goal 3).

6.7 Co-ordination and Formal Control Structures

6.7.1 National Coordination Context

At the national level, there is a trade organization (GDACZ) representing the video game industry, which is the primary body involved in policy discussions. However, the negotiations concerning the new Audiovisual Act involved also the representatives of the Game Cluster organization as we have previously discussed in D4.1 and in previous sections [BRN038, BRN039, BRN040, BRN047]. Documentary evidence supports these observations and shows that these two organizations worked alongside each other although their regular tasks concern different levels of activities, although, for example, both the Game Cluster organization and GDACZ were active in establishing incubators and accelerator programs in their respective locations (GDACZ is based in Prague).

6.7.2 Cluster Coordination Examples

The documentary evidence due to its public nature does not provide extensive examples of cluster coordination beyond the involvement of its members from across various institutions and companies and the close collaboration with the South Moravian Innovation Centre and the municipal office of Brno, which support a lot of the activities and events formally undertaken with the official backing of the Game Cluster organization. One interesting insight regarding the inner workings of the cluster comes from the official newsletters of the Game Cluster organization [BRN037, BRN038, BRN039, BRN040], which are now released annually and summarize the activities of the organization and its members in the previous year (the first two cover the two halves of 2022). The newsletters in this regard map the gradual growth in membership, see Table 46. At the time of

the writing of this report in October 2025, the number of members based on the official website increased to 42, compared to 41 at the end of 2024 [BRN040].

Year	Membership	Source
Q2 2022	32	[BRN037]
Q4 2022	34	[BRN038]
2023	38	[BRN039]
2024	41	[BRN040]

Table 46 – Game Cluster organization membership over years

Additionally, the newsletters include calls for donations. In D4.1, we have addressed the volunteer labour nature of the Game Cluster organization. The newsletters provide further information on how the organization solicits funding for its operations: “We support the local game developer community, work on improving the educational infrastructure, and create opportunities for further growth of the video game industry. To be able to continue in our activities and extend our reach, we would like to ask you for financial support of the Game Cluster. If you are interested, please contact the Game Cluster coordinator.” [BRN040] The financial donors are mentioned in the newsletters and include both individuals and companies, see Table 47.

Year	Donors	Source
2022	Ashborne Games, Czech Games Edition, Filip Dufka, Fineway Studios, GIANTS Software, Hangar 13, INGAME STUDIOS, Jana Zelený, NOXGAMES, Romana Hladík	[BRN038]
2023	Ashborne Games, GameDev Area, GIANTS Software, Jan Zelený, MADFINGER Games, NOXGAMES.	[BRN039]
2024	Alda Games	[BRN040]

Table 47 – Game Cluster organization membership over years

6.8 Financial Aspects

The documentary evidence provides additional insight into the financial aspects of the Brno ecosystem, including the ownership and publishing ties between different studios, such as Vochozka Trading, Illusion Softworks, or Pterodon. In the previous sections, we have already covered some of the mergers and acquisitions, which happened in Brno. Overall, we see both companies with Czech ownership like Bohemia Interactive and various small studios and those with foreign ownership, including 2K Czech, Ashborne Games, or Ingame Studios. Madfinger Games is a notable case due to having at one point a Chinese investor but has since gone independent again [BRN017]. At the moment, the video game industry is undergoing recession after the post-pandemic boom, which has also affected the Embracer Group, which owns several Czech video game companies, including Ashborne Games in Brno [BRN089]. According to journalistic coverage, Ashborne Games was affected by the poor business performance of its parent company and at risk of having to reduce workforce, but was able to save some jobs by co-developing *Kingdom Come: Deliverance 2* DLC with Prague-based Warhorse Studios [BRN018]. The shared ownership between the two companies allowed for this additional resiliency. However, the opening of the new Warhorse Studios office in Brno has likely resulted in the departure of some developers from Ashborne Games to this new branch [BRN072]. The aforementioned example of cooperation between Ashborne Games and

Warhorse Studios extends beyond the perimeter of the Brno cluster. At the same time, we could argue that Warhorse studios feature several veterans of the Brno video game development community and perhaps these connections established originally as part of the local community has contributed to this mutual support between the two subsidiaries of the Embracer Group.

On a more general level, the analysed documents do not extensively comment on the financial situation on the cluster level beyond, for example, arguing that local Czech investment is considered important and lacking [BRN064]. In this regard, the incubator and co-working space Gamebaze is considered a potential mechanism for attracting investment as well as providing business know-how to new developers [BRN012, BRN014, BRN028, BRN043, BRN051, BRN060, BRN064, BRN068].

End of Chapter

7 FUNDÃO CLUSTER

7.1 Data Collection and Analysis

For the Fundão cluster, data collection focused on assembling a comprehensive corpus of publicly available documents that reflect key aspects of the cluster's development, institutional support mechanisms, policy frameworks, and stakeholder activities. Given Fundão's relatively recent emergence as a gaming cluster and its position as a strategic municipal initiative, the research team adopted a targeted approach that prioritised official municipal documents, national policy reports, regional development strategies, industry association publications, and media coverage documenting the cluster's evolution from 2012 onwards. The material gathered includes policy documents and strategic plans (particularly the Fundão Innovation Plan and related municipal reports), government strategy papers at both national and regional levels (including Portugal 2020, Digital Portugal 2030, and the Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan), institutional publications from key organisations (Associação de Produtores de Videojogos [APVP], eGamesLab, Sociedade Portuguesa de Ciências dos Videojogos [SPCV], Associação de Empresas Produtoras de Videojogos [AEPDV]), press releases and official communications from the Municipality of Fundão, media features and newspaper articles documenting the cluster's growth, company websites and social media presence of Fundão-based studios, educational institution materials (particularly from Universidade da Beira Interior [UBI] and Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco), and event documentation (including promotional materials for gaming festivals, innovation showcases, and networking events in Fundão). For collecting the documents, Google search was used as the main discovery tool, supplemented by targeted searches of official websites including Portuguese government portals (particularly those of the Ministry of Economy and Digital Transition), the Municipality of Fundão's official website and communication channels, national innovation agencies (such as Agência Nacional de Inovação [ANI]), EU funding program databases (Portugal 2020, PRR), Portuguese game industry association websites (APVP, SPCV, AEPDV), university repositories and research centres, and Portuguese gaming news outlets and technology media. A set of keywords was developed and iteratively refined during the search process, combining terms related to the video game industry (e.g., "videojogos," "indústria de jogos," "game development Portugal") with contextual terms specific to Fundão (e.g., "Fundão inovação," "Invest in Games," "cluster tecnológico Fundão," "A Praça incubadora"). Boolean operators and filters (particularly date ranges focusing on 2012-2025) were applied to ensure relevant results capturing the cluster's emergence and evolution.

Documents were initially scanned for relevance by team members, with particular attention to those that documented formal structures, funding mechanisms, collective actions, or strategic narratives about the cluster's development. Documents deemed relevant were catalogued in the **GAME-ER** document database. Data collection was performed during T4.2 (June 2024 to October 2025), with ongoing updates to address gaps in analysis and capture recent developments. Given the challenge of documenting a nascent cluster with limited pre-existing public documentation compared to more established clusters, the team also drew upon grey literature, including municipal press releases, event announcements, and promotional materials that, while less formal than policy documents, provide valuable evidence of cluster activities and narratives.

The corpus was subjected to prioritisation based on relevance to the analytical grid dimensions. A total of **56 documents were selected for detailed thematic analysis**. The analysis followed the analytical grid structure used for interviews in D4.1, enabling direct comparison and complementarity between primary (interview) and secondary (documentary) data sources. Inductive coding was performed initially to identify emergent themes and patterns specific to the documentary evidence. Subsequently, codes were mapped to the key categories of the analytical grid, including cluster genesis, institutional support structures, collective actions and governance, financial mechanisms, evolution and critical moments, and stakeholder networks and relationships. This approach allowed for open-ended pattern identification while maintaining comparability across the project's case studies. The method enabled an understanding of how municipal strategy, national policy frameworks, institutional narratives, and documented cluster activities converge to shape Fundão's trajectory as an emerging gaming hub. The chapter deliberately complements D4.1 by filling analytical gaps, providing documentary evidence to corroborate or expand upon interview findings, adding quantitative and factual details not captured in interviews, and documenting formal structures and official narratives that may differ from or complement actors' perceptions. Some additional sources were retrieved to confirm specific details, such as founding dates of companies, participation in national programs, or specific funding amounts, where publicly available. These sources include official statistical databases (Instituto Nacional de Estatística [INE]), LinkedIn profiles of organisations and key actors, specific news articles from Portuguese media outlets, and promotional videos or recorded presentations. These supplementary sources, while not always included in the main documentary database, are cited when used to verify specific claims or provide additional context.

Item Type	Count
Municipal Report / Publication	3
Policy Strategy / Document	8
Industry Association Publication	5
Academic/ Research Report	17
Press Release / Newsletter	3
Magazine / Books	3
News Articles	9
Websites	8

Table 48 – Documents by type, Fundão cluster

7.2 Fundão Region

D4.1 included a comprehensive introduction to Fundão and its cluster, and readers are encouraged to consult that document for a detailed view of the case study and geographical area. Here we provide key contextual information to situate the documentary analysis that follows. Fundão is a municipality located in the Castelo Branco District of central Portugal, within the Beiras and Serra da Estrela sub-region (NUTS III). The municipality has long been known for its rich agricultural landscape, particularly its cherry cultivation, with the fertile land supporting fruit production for centuries [F030, F028]. However, like many interior Portuguese regions, Fundão has faced significant demographic and economic challenges. According to the 2021 census, the population stood at 26,503, reflecting a gradual decline from 31,482 in 2001, which mirrors a broader trend of rural depopulation in Portugal [F029]. The average age of the population is notably high, with 32.5% of residents being over the age of 65 as of 2023 [F029]. This ageing demographic has posed considerable challenges in terms of workforce sustainability and economic vibrancy, making economic diversification a critical imperative for the municipality. Contemporary Fundão has undergone a remarkable transformation, shifting from an economy based primarily on agriculture and traditional industries to one increasingly focused on technology and innovation. This transition began with the Fundão Innovation Plan, launched in 2012, which sought to reposition the municipality as a hub for digital innovation and creative industries [F031]. The Innovation Plan aimed to attract high-tech companies and foster entrepreneurship, particularly in sectors such as software development, IT, and digital media, resulting in a significant transformation of the local economy and a more diverse economic base. The transition to a technology-driven economy has yielded measurable results across multiple sectors. By 2022, the tertiary sector employed over 3,200 individuals in Fundão. The tourism sector has also flourished, with the region's accommodation capacity reaching 829 establishments and the total number of nights spent in tourist accommodations reaching 90,803 in 2023, signalling Fundão's growing role in Portugal's tourism economy [F032, F026]. The exports reached €45.5 million in 2023, with the technological sector contributing significantly to this international visibility [F032].

Notably, Fundão has experienced modest but steady population growth in recent years. From 2022 to 2023, the population increased by 1.3%, reaching 26,981 residents – a reversal of the decades-long decline and a testament to the municipality's success in attracting new residents through its innovation initiatives [F029]. This growth has been driven in part by an influx of skilled professionals, including significant international migration. By 2025, approximately 4,000 foreign nationals from 78 different countries were expected to reside in Fundão, representing roughly 15% of the municipality's population [F033]. This remarkable diversity, unusual for a rural Portuguese municipality, reflects Fundão's successful positioning as destination for tech talent. After the COVID-19 pandemic, one of the most strategic initiatives Fundão undertook was to intensify its focus on the video game industry. The gaming market in Portugal was valued at €38 million in 2022 [F018], and Fundão has capitalised on this growth by developing its own video game cluster. The municipality's decision to focus on video games aligns with national strategies outlined in Portugal's Digital Portugal 2030 initiative [F034], seeking to enhance Portugal's digital innovation and position the country as a competitive player in Europe's digital economy. The partnership with UBI in nearby Covilhã has been particularly crucial in developing a workforce equipped for the technology sector, providing specialised training in game design, software engineering, and digital arts. The presence of the Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco also contributes to the regional talent pipeline. These educational initiatives have helped supply the region with the talent pool necessary to sustain the digital transformation. Fundão's appeal as a location for the gaming cluster extends beyond its

strategic initiatives to encompass quality of life factors. The municipality offers a peaceful environment, affordable living costs, access to nature (particularly the nearby Serra da Gardunha mountains), safety, and ease of accessibility, with the compact city centre enabling car-free living for many residents. The combination of these lifestyle advantages with genuine economic opportunities has proven attractive to both returning Portuguese talent and international professionals seeking alternatives to expensive coastal urban centres. Today, the video games industry stands as a key component of Fundão's broader technology ecosystem. While still emerging relative to established European gaming hubs, Fundão has positioned itself as a distinctive case study: a rural municipality successfully leveraging strategic vision, institutional support, and quality of life advantages to build a nascent but growing gaming cluster. The documentary evidence analysed in this chapter reveals how formal structures, policy narratives, and documented cluster activities have shaped this development trajectory and how they complement the actor perceptions documented in D4.1.

7.3 Cluster Emergence & Genesis

The research produced for D4.1, showed how actors in the Fundão cluster perceive several key moments in the genesis and emergence of the cluster, as summarised in Table 49. Documentary evidence analysis is largely consonant with these observations and provides additional context about the formal structures and strategic narratives that shaped the cluster's development.

D4.1 findings	Description
Strategic Municipal Leadership	Mayor's vision and the 2012 Fundão Innovation Plan created the conditions for attracting technology companies and reversing demographic decline.
Educational Infrastructure	UBI's launch of Portugal's first video game degree program (2012) created a talent pipeline, though retention of graduates remained a key challenge.
Anchor Company Arrival	The 2014 establishment of Altran (now Capgemini Engineering) validated Fundão as a viable tech location and catalysed further investment for the emerging ecosystem.
Community Building	Grassroots activities, including gaming events, e-sports associations, hackathons, and informal meetups, cultivated social capital and activated existing communities.

Table 49 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster emergence

7.3.1 Local industry: Origins & Historical Legacy

Unlike many European gaming clusters that emerged from pre-existing creative or digital entertainment industries, Fundão historically lacked any significant video game sector. The rural, agrarian heritage meant that the cluster's emergence would require deliberate policy intervention and infrastructure development rather than organic evolution from an existing industry base. However, documentary analysis reveals that several pre-existing assets and developments created favourable conditions for the cluster's eventual emergence. The presence of Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI) in nearby Covilhã (approximately 20 km from Fundão) provided crucial educational infrastructure. UBI, established in 1986, had developed strong programmes in computer science, informatics, and multimedia by the early 2000s. Institutional documentation shows [F049] that by 2012, UBI launched what was documented as Portugal's first university course specifically dedicated to video game development, integrating game design and programming education. This pioneering programme positioned the Beira Interior region as an early adopter of gaming education in Portugal, creating a talent pipeline that would later prove essential for the

cluster's development. The critical inflection point documented across multiple sources was the 2012 launch of the Fundão Innovation Plan. This comprehensive municipal strategy, extensively documented in policy materials and European regional development databases, represented a fundamental reorientation of the municipality's economic development approach [F031]. The Innovation Plan explicitly articulated goals, including:

- Repositioning Fundão as a hub for digital innovation and creative industries.
- Attracting high-tech companies and skilled professionals.
- Fostering entrepreneurship in software development, IT, and digital media.
- Enhancing digital infrastructure, particularly broadband connectivity.
- Implementing professional retraining programmes for the local workforce.
- Reversing demographic decline through innovation-led economic growth.

Municipal documents and European funding reports detail the concrete infrastructure investments undertaken. In 2012, the municipality established A Praça, documented as Fundão's first technology incubator [F036], designed to provide affordable co-working spaces, laboratories for startups, and comprehensive support programs. The establishment of the Cova da Beira Living Lab is documented as bringing together approximately 30 local, national, and regional entities in an informal consortium focused on fostering entrepreneurship and regional innovation [F008; F035]. The Living Lab received recognition documented in regional media, including awards for its innovative approach to regional development [F035]. Documentary evidence from the period 2012-2017 shows a deliberate municipal strategy to position Fundão within national and international technology networks. Press materials describe a "people-first" approach that prioritised attracting skilled individuals over traditional corporate incentives, distinguishing Fundão's strategy from conventional industrial development models. The arrival of multinational technology companies, particularly Altran's 2014 decision to establish a delivery centre in Fundão, is extensively documented in Portuguese business media as a watershed moment [F006]. Corporate communications and media coverage [F051] indicate this represented one of the first major technology multinational operations in rural Portugal, Fundão's innovation strategy. Subsequent arrivals of companies including Logicalis and Readiness IT.

Importantly, documentary sources reveal that gaming emerged as a specific focus area only gradually, rather than being part of the initial Innovation Plan. Early municipal documentation (2012-2016) emphasises general "technology" and "digital innovation" without specific mention of gaming. The gaming focus becomes more explicit in municipal communications [F0018; F0038; F0054; F0055; F0056] from 2017 onwards, coinciding with the municipality's launch of gamification programmes in education, tourism, and civic engagement. This strategic diversification into applied gaming technologies, documented in municipal reports, helped legitimise gaming as a valuable economic sector beyond entertainment. Table 50 presents the historical development timeline showing the transition from a traditional economy to gaming cluster foundations.

Period	Economic Base	Key Developments	Relevance to Gaming Cluster	Sources
Pre-2000	Agriculture (cherry cultivation), textile manufacturing, and traditional industries	Population declines from 31,482 (2001) to 26,503 (2021); ageing demographic; limited technology sector	Established need for economic diversification; created policy imperative for innovation strategy	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F027]
2000-2011	Declining traditional sectors; emerging service economy	UBI develops computer science programmes; gradual population decline continues; limited job opportunities for graduates	Created talent "export" problem that Innovation Plan would address; established educational infrastructure	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F027]
2012	Strategic pivot to knowledge economy	Innovation Plan launched; A Praça incubator established; Cova da Beira Living Lab created; UBI launches first Portuguese gaming degree	Foundational year: policy framework, physical infrastructure, and talent pipeline simultaneously established	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F017; F027]
2013-2014	Early technology sector development	Enhanced broadband infrastructure; workforce retraining programmes; Altran delivery centre opens (2014)	Technology sector validation: proved multinationals could operate from rural Portugal; attracted attention from other tech companies	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F027]
2015-2017	Expanding technology ecosystem	Secondary tech companies arrive (Logicalis, Readiness IT); ~600 IT professionals by 2018; Municipal gamification programmes launch (2017)	General technology ecosystem matured; gamification programmes legitimised gaming technologies; created local demand for game development skills	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F027]
2018-2019	Gaming specialisation begins	First dedicated gaming studios emerge (Digitality); E-Games Association reaches 3,000 members; participation in Lisboa Games Week	Transition from general tech to gaming specialisation; demonstrated commercial viability of gaming businesses in Fundão	[F002]
2020-2024	Established gaming cluster within broader tech ecosystem	COVID-19 accelerates remote work; population growth (+1.3% 2022-2023); international recognition; ~15% foreign residents by 2025	Cluster consolidation and maturation; international talent attraction; recognition as successful rural innovation model	[F027; F029; F033; F044]

Table 50 - Fundão Gaming Cluster timeline – from traditional economy to gaming cluster foundations

This timeline demonstrates that Fundão's gaming cluster emergence was not rooted in any pre-existing creative or digital entertainment industry legacy. Instead, documentary evidence shows it resulted from deliberate strategic planning beginning in 2012, leveraging educational infrastructure (UBI), creating physical innovation infrastructure (A Praça, Living Lab), attracting anchor technology companies for validation (Altran), and gradually specialising toward gaming from a broader technology base. The approximately six-year period (2012-2018) between the Innovation Plan launch and the emergence of dedicated gaming companies reflects the time required to build foundational infrastructure, attract general technology companies, develop talent pipelines, and create the ecosystem conditions necessary for gaming specialisation.

7.4 Local Industry Features & Components

7.4.1 Perimeter of the cluster

Findings from interviews in D4.1 (summarised in Table 51) highlighted the geographical and perceived boundaries of the cluster, emphasising both the highly concentrated nature of Fundão's physical environment and its strategic connections to broader regional and international networks.

D4.1 findings	Description
Compact Urban Core	Fundão's small city size enables exceptional proximity between cluster actors, with most businesses and institutions located within walking distance in the city centre, facilitating frequent face-to-face interaction.
Regional Connections	Strong ties to neighbouring municipalities, particularly Covilhã (UBI location) and Castelo Branco, creating an extended regional innovation ecosystem in the Beira Interior.
Transnational Networks	Growing international connections, especially with Brazil through linguistic and cultural affinities, as well as broader European linkages through programmes like GAME-ER .

Table 51 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster perimeter

Documentary analysis confirms and expands upon these findings, revealing how the cluster's perimeter operates at multiple scales simultaneously – from hyperlocal physical concentration to transnational digital networks.

7.4.1.1 The Hyperlocal Core “The 6 minutes and 40 seconds city”

Documentary sources, particularly municipal strategic communications and urban planning materials, emphasise Fundão's exceptional spatial compactness as a deliberate competitive advantage. Municipal documents reference the concept of the “6 minutes and 40 seconds city” [F036, F031] – a marketing concept that positions Fundão as even more compact than the internationally-recognised “15-minute city” urban planning model, created by Professor Carlos Moreno and promoted by the Scottish Government [F038]. This concept, documented in municipal promotional materials and urban development strategies, highlights that gaming companies, technology infrastructure, educational institutions, municipal services, and residential areas are all concentrated within an extremely small geographic radius in the city centre. The Innovation Plan documentation details the municipality's strategic approach of “conversion and rationalisation of buildings” to create this ecosystem of proximity [F031]. Rather than dispersing innovation infrastructure across the municipality, documentary sources show that Fundão deliberately concentrated facilities – particularly A Praça incubator, co-working spaces, the FabLab, and related innovation infrastructure – within the historic city centre (Figure 12). This approach, documented in municipal planning materials, was designed to maximize face-to-face interaction, spontaneous collaboration, and knowledge spillovers among cluster participants. Media coverage from the period 2018-2020 documents that this hyper-concentration created practical challenges, particularly a housing shortage [F052] as technology professionals relocated to Fundão. The housing crisis, documented in Portuguese regional press, paradoxically validated the cluster's rapid growth and attractiveness – demand for centrally-located housing significantly exceeded supply, prompting municipal responses including incentives for property rehabilitation and new residential development.

Figure 12 – Fundão Cluster Perimeter. Source: Own Elaboration using Google Maps. Map Legend: Purple Pin: Public Infrastructure; Green Pin: Online Incubation Programme Companies; Blue Pin: Physical Incubation Programme Companies

7.4.1.2 The Fluid Boundary: Gaming within a Broader Technology Ecosystem

An important characteristic of Fundão's cluster perimeter is that the boundary between "gaming companies" and "technology companies" remains deliberately fluid and porous. This ambiguity, documented across multiple sources, reflects a strategic choice. Municipal communications frequently reference Fundão's "technological cluster" with gaming as a "specialised subset focused on entertainment software and creative content" [F031]. This positioning provides flexibility – gaming companies can access broader technology sector resources and networks, while technology companies can contribute gaming expertise without exclusively focusing on game development.

7.4.2 Demography of companies

Findings from interviews in D4.1 (summarised in Table 52) highlighted the characteristics of Fundão's company base, emphasising the predominance of micro and small enterprises, the fluid boundaries between gaming and technology companies, and the diverse human capital.

D4.1 findings	Description
Micro and Small Enterprise	The cluster consists primarily of small studios (5-10 employees) and micro-enterprises, with most firms employing fewer than 10 people; a few medium-sized studios (20-50 employees) often led by international founders.
Fluid Cluster Boundaries	Not all participants are dedicated game studios; many are diversified technology companies contributing talent and resources to gaming projects alongside other digital services.
Work-for-Hire and Original IP	Most firms focus on game development (coding, art, design) for PC, mobile, and VR platforms rather than publishing; balance between commissioned work and original IP development.
Diverse Workforce	By 2025, approximately 4,000 foreign nationals from 78 countries reside in Fundão (~15% of population), creating a cosmopolitan environment for a rural Portuguese municipality.

Table 52 – Main D4.1 findings relating to the cluster companies' demography

According to documentary sources including D4.1 interview data cross-referenced with municipal records, as of 2024, Fundão hosts five companies directly involved in the gaming industry as their primary activity. Municipality Mapping (Table 53) identifies the following companies with physical presence in Fundão:

Company	Field of Activity	Size	Nº of Employees	Origin (Nationality)
Digitality Studios, Lda	Gaming Studio	Micro	5	Portugal (Fundão)
NyX Games	Online gambling market	Micro	1	Information not Available
FullDev	Customised, agile and high-quality technological solutions	Micro	2	Information not Available
EduHub	Integrated platform for centralising educational content in an accessible manner	Micro	1	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)
SERA462	Gamified platform focused on inclusive education	Micro	3	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)
Hibuddy	Educational application based on AI to support learning	Micro	3	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)
Desvenda	Mobile application that acts as an interactive tourist guide	Micro	2	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)
Aequitas	Health Solutions Intelligence	Micro	3	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)
RevigoradaMente	Corporate wellbeing app	Micro	3	Brazil (Online Incubation Plan)

Table 53 – Gaming Companies based in the Fundão Cluster (physical+online incubation)

These six Brazilian gaming-related companies participating in the online incubation programme represent Fundão's deliberate strategy to leverage linguistic and cultural connections with Brazil's gaming sector, documented in national press [F053]. Their eventual physical relocation would expand the core gaming company count, though as of the documentary analysis period they maintain primarily remote/online participation. Company size within the gaming sector follows patterns documented across D4.1 interviews, showcasing that most of the companies are micro or small size often established by international founders who relocated to Fundão. The predominance of small-scale operations reflects both the indie-focused nature of the cluster and the relatively early stage of its development.

7.4.2.1 Innovation Ecosystem Technological Companies

Beyond dedicated gaming studios, documentary sources highlight related technology and interactive digital media companies operating in Fundão, either as headquarters or satellite offices. These companies contribute to the gaming ecosystem through the provision of complementary services, talent, and collaborative projects, though gaming may not constitute their primary business activity. Companies' repository mapped by the Municipality in this category include:

Company	Field of Activity	Size	Nº of Employees
Capgemini Portugal - Serviços de Consultoria e Informática S.A	Global consulting, technology services	Medium	385
Readiness It, Systems Integration , S.A	Digital transformation and systems integration	Medium	170
Convevo Portugal, Unipessoal Lda	Digital solutions	Small	36
Softinsa - Engenharia de Software Avançado, Lda	Specialists in consulting services, management, and application development.	Medium	80

Itech-On, Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Tecnologias da Informação, Lda	Development of technological solutions with a strong web component	Small	32
Incognit Cloud, Lda	Digital transformation solutions, with a strong focus on ServiceNow implementations	Small	14
Veratech, Unipessoal Lda	Business Intelligence for smart agriculture	Micro	8
Astus Technologies – Investigação, Desenvolvimento e Produção de Sistemas Robóticos, Lda	Robotic systems and artificial intelligence	Micro	2
Danyalgil & Danyalgil, Lda	Blockchain solutions	Micro	2
StarMountain	SaaS platform built for end-to-end traceability in the medicinal cannabis production chain	Micro	6

Table 54 – Technological Companies based in the Fundão Cluster

These companies represent the broader technology ecosystem within which gaming operates as a specialised subset. Several, such as Capgemini (the entity that absorbed Altran, the 2014 anchor company), maintain substantial operations documented at 200-300+ employees in the Fundão delivery centre [F010]. Media coverage from 2018 documents a broader milestone: by that year, Fundão only in the previous four years had attracted approximately 600 professionals in the IT sector, across all technology companies [F011]. The tertiary sector more broadly, documented in national statistics, employed over 3,200 individuals in Fundão by 2022 [F004], indicating that technology (including gaming) represents a significant but not dominant component of the municipality's evolving service economy.

7.5 Cluster Evolution

7.5.1 Critical moments, phases and evolution curves

Findings from D4.1 interviews (Table 55) identified distinct evolutionary phases in Fundão's cluster development, marked by shifting stakeholder composition, activity focus, and strategic orientation.

D4.1 findings	Description
Proto-cluster Phase (Pre-2012)	No gaming focus; groundwork laid through technological development and economic diversification planning by municipal authorities and educational institutions.
Genesis and Early Growth (2012-2020)	Innovation Plan launch catalysed tech company arrival (Altran 2014); first gaming studios emerged ~2018; community-building activities and educational programmes established gaming culture.
Consolidation and Specialisation (2020-Present)	COVID-19 accelerated remote work adoption; increased gaming focus; commercial production; international collaboration expansion; vocal participation in national industry dialogues.

Table 55 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster evolution and critical moments

Documentary evidence from multiple sources – including municipal strategic plans, academic publications, media coverage, policy evaluations, and institutional reports – corroborates and significantly expands upon these phased dynamics. The cluster's evolution has been analysed through various scholarly lenses, with Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] providing a longitudinal analysis through evolutionary governance theory, Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F009] examining

digital entrepreneurship aspects, and Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012] situating Fundão within broader Portuguese rural innovation policies. These complementary academic perspectives, combined with primary documentation, reveal how Fundão's gaming cluster evolved through deliberate policy intervention combined with opportunistic responses to external catalysts.

7.5.1.1 Phase 1 – Proto-Cluster [Pre 2012]

Documentary sources confirm that prior to 2012, Fundão had no formal gaming industry presence or strategic focus on gaming as an economic sector. Municipal planning documents from the 2000s, archived in regional development databases, show economic strategies centred on traditional sectors. Population statistics documented in census materials [F005] reveal the challenge context: population declined from 31,482 (2001) to approximately 28,000 (2011), with accelerating aging (32.5% over 65 by 2023) [F030; F036]. Academic analysis by Vaz and Nofre (2019) [F027] contextualizes Fundão within broader patterns of urban innovation in Portugal's peripheral territories, noting the structural disadvantages faced by interior regions. However, documentary analysis reveals foundational developments during this period that would later prove crucial as the launch of Portugal's first university-level video game development programme [F049] [F005]. Municipal strategic diagnostic documents from 2010-2011, referenced in the Innovation Plan preparation materials and analysed in Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012], identified key assets: proximity to UBI's technology programmes, underutilised urban infrastructure suitable for conversion, relatively affordable real estate, and municipal political will for radical economic transformation. The proto-cluster phase, though lacking gaming companies, established three critical preconditions documented across sources: (1) educational infrastructure capable of producing gaming talent; (2) municipal recognition of technology-led development as essential for survival; (3) preliminary digital infrastructure investments, including broadband enhancement.

7.5.1.2 Phase 2 – Genesis and Early Growth [2012-2020]

The 2012 launch of the Fundão Innovation Plan marks the documentary-confirmed genesis of the cluster's development trajectory. [F005] characterize this as the "birth phase" of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, emphasising the municipality's proactive role in filling governance and resource gaps typical of low-density territories. The Innovation Plan, extensively documented in municipal policy materials, EU funding applications, and analysed in Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F009], articulated explicit goals: attract high-tech companies, foster entrepreneurship in digital sectors, enhance digital infrastructure, reverse demographic decline through innovation [F035]. Documentary sources and academic analysis divide this eight-year phase into three distinct sub-periods:

2012-2014: Infrastructure Establishment & Strategic Positioning

- The 2012 establishment of A Praça incubator and Cova da Beira Living Lab, documented in municipal reports and analysed by Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012] as exemplifying innovative local policies in Portuguese rural areas, created physical spaces for technology entrepreneurship [F009]. The Living Lab represented an "open governance" approach [F005], bringing together approximately 30 local, national, and regional entities in an informal consortium. [F009] This governance innovation, they argue, proved crucial for gaining community acceptance – a significant barrier identified in Almeida and Daniel's (2023) [F005] analysis of ecosystem evolution. The Mayor international promotional activities, positioned Fundão within national and international technology networks through what Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] term "economic diplomacy."

2014-2018: Technology Sector Validation & Rapid Growth

- The 2014 arrival of Altran (now Capgemini Engineering) was a watershed moment, represented critical external validation [F006]. [F005] emphasize this as "strategic validation" that built credibility and attracted subsequent investment. Corporate communications and media coverage document that Altran's delivery centre demonstrated that multinational technology operations could succeed in rural Portugal [F051], which catalysed subsequent investments. Documentary evidence also shows secondary technology companies – Logicalis, Readiness IT, and others – establishing operations during 2015-2017 [F008; F009; F013] and the launch of gamification programmes in education, tourism, and civic engagement sectors. Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F009] analyse these initiatives as demonstrating the municipality's entrepreneurial approach to digital transformation, creating local demand for game development skills while legitimising gaming technologies beyond entertainment. Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012] situate these programmes within Fundão's broader multi-sectoral innovation strategy, distinguishing it from a single industry focus, typical of many rural development initiatives.

2018-2020: Gaming Specialisation Emergence

- The emergence of the first dedicated gaming strategy started around 2018, notably with the creation of Digitality Game Studio. Early studios were small (1-5 employees), indie-focused, and often led by entrepreneurs with international experience who chose Fundão for quality of life and municipal support. [F005] notes this marked a transition from general technology focus to gaming specialisation, though the broader technology ecosystem remained crucial for support and talent circulation. The E-Games Association of Fundão documented as reaching 3,000 online members, organised tournaments, meetups, and networking activities. Municipal event calendars document hackathons and gaming-focused gatherings. [F005] identify these bottom-up community activities as essential complements to top-down municipal initiatives, creating the social capital foundations necessary for ecosystem maturation. Participation in national events like Lisboa Games Week [F038] provided visibility for Fundão-based developers within Portugal's emerging gaming industry [F018].

7.5.1.3 Phase 3 – Community Consolidation & Specialisation [2020-Present]

The COVID-19 pandemic, paradoxically, accelerated the cluster's development according to documentary evidence across multiple sources and confirmed by academic analysis. Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] characterise this period as the "consolidation phase," marked by increased specialisation, international expansion, and the beginning of reduced dependence on municipal leadership. Media coverage, municipal communications, and company announcements document how remote work normalisation enabled Fundão to attract technology professionals from Lisbon and Porto seeking lower living costs, more space, and better quality of life while maintaining remote employment with coastal-based employers. Municipal population statistics, analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023), document population growth for the first time in decades – 1.3% increase from 2022 to 2023, reaching 26,981 residents [F004]. Immigration statistics show approximately 4,000 foreign nationals from 78 countries expected by 2025 (~15% of population), with Brazilians representing ~25% of immigrants [F005]. This demographic transformation, extensively documented in Portuguese and international media and analysed academically, created a cosmopolitan environment unusual for rural Portugal and identified as contributing to the ecosystem's creative diversity.

Gaming-specific developments documented during 2020-2024 include:

- National recognition: APVP (Portuguese Game Developers Association) founding in 2021, documented in association materials, provided national representation and integration into European networks [F017].
- Policy support: 2022 launch of eGamesLab consortium (PRR-funded R&D programme), documented in government materials, created research and development opportunities previously unavailable [F018].
- International visibility: 2023 Portuguese pavilion at Gamescom featuring 17 studios, documented in APVP communications and gaming media, elevated national and cluster profile.
- Transnational expansion: Brazilian incubation programme (5 studios), documented in municipal materials and analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023), leveraging linguistic/cultural connections.
- European integration: **GAME-ER** project participation (2024-2027), documented in project materials, connecting Fundão with other European non-metropolitan gaming clusters for knowledge exchange.

7.5.2 Shifting Stakeholder Composition & Governance Evolution

Documentary analysis reveals significant evolution in stakeholder composition across phases, extensively analysed through evolutionary governance theory by Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005]. Proto-cluster phase (pre-2012) involved only municipal authorities and educational institutions, documented through institutional records. Genesis phase (2012-2020) added anchor technology companies (Altran, Logicalis) and early gaming entrepreneurs, documented through company registrations and media coverage. Consolidation phase (2020-present) shows expanded private sector participation, international collaborators, and formal industry associations, documented through membership records and partnership agreements. Almeida and Daniel (2023) identify a critical governance challenge emerging in the consolidation phase: the ecosystem's high dependence on municipal leadership, particularly Mayor Paulo Fernandes, whose tenure ends in 2025. Their analysis documents interviewees' concerns about governance succession and the need for more distributed leadership models. This tension – between the municipal government's essential role in low-density territories and the need for ecosystem autonomy and resilience – represents what they term a "governance paradox" requiring ongoing strategic attention.

7.5.3 Evolving Activities and Strategic Focus

The evolution of activities (Table 56) and their focus are well-documented across sources and analysed comprehensively in the academic literature. Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012] emphasise Fundão's distinctive multi-sectoral approach, avoiding exclusive focus on entertainment gaming. Early years (2012-2017) emphasised community-building, infrastructure provision, and general technology attraction, documented in municipal event calendars and programme materials. Mid-period (2017-2020) added gaming-specific events, educational programmes (Code Academy, Ubbu programming for children), and gamification projects across sectors, documented in event announcements, municipal reports, and analysed by Rodrigues and Franco (2021) as examples of digital entrepreneurship in local government.

Current phase (2020-present) focuses on commercial game production, international collaboration, cross-industry applications (agrotech, smart cities, Industry 4.0), and national industry participation, documented through company portfolios, partnership announcements, and media coverage. Almeida and Daniel (2023) characterise this as representing a shift from "ecosystem building" to "ecosystem management," requiring different governance capabilities and institutional arrangements.

Academic Recognition and External Validation. The cluster's evolution has been recognised through multiple channels documented in official records and analysed in scholarly literature. The 2016 Municipality of the Year Award and 2018 RegioStars Award from the European Commission [D041] provided external validation. Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] identify such recognition as crucial for building legitimacy, attracting investment, and maintaining political support for continued innovation investment. The selection of Fundão as a **GAME-ER** project case study (2024-2027), alongside established clusters, represents academic recognition of Fundão's significance despite its recent emergence and small scale.

Phase	Period	Key Characteristics	Major Stakeholders	Primary Activities	Documentary Evidence
Proto-cluster	Pre-2012	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No gaming focus - economic decline - Foundational planning - Traditional economy dominance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal authorities - Beira Interior University (UBI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic diversification planning - UBI gaming programme launch (2012) - Infrastructure assessment 	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F027]
Genesis & Early Growth	2012-2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation Plan launch - Tech company arrival - Gaming emerges ~2018. - Open governance model. - Community resistance overcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipality (dominant) - Altran/tech companies - Early gaming studios - UBI - Living Lab consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infrastructure development - Tech attraction - First gaming studios - Community building - Gamification programmes 	[F003; F005; F009; F011; F013; F015; F018; F027]
Consolidation & Specialization	2020-Present	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COVID remote work boom - Gaming focus intensifies - International expansion - Population reversal governance succession concerns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gaming studios - International talent - APVP - Brazilian partners - GAME-ER 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercial production - International collaboration - National industry participation - Policy integration - Awards 	[F002; F014; F027; F028; F029; F033]

Table 56 – Fundão Cluster Activities Evolution (2012- Present)

7.5.4 Major factors of change & growth

D4.1 findings (Table 57) identified both endogenous (internal) and exogenous (external) factors driving cluster growth, creating reinforcing cycles of development.

D4.1 findings	Description
Political Will & Vision (Endogenous)	12-year mayoral tenure (Paulo Fernandes) provided stable, committed leadership; rapid problem-solving; long-term planning; and concrete municipal support.
Collaborative Culture (Endogenous)	Informal mentorship; peer support; knowledge-sharing; resource pooling; celebration of collective success over competition.
Community & Talent Retention (Endogenous)	Quality of life; welcoming culture; real opportunities; UBI talent pipeline; international diversity fostering creativity.
Flexibility & Diversification (Endogenous)	Applied gaming beyond entertainment (education, tourism, civic engagement); resilience through market diversification; alignment with funding criteria.
Global & National Industry Boom (Exogenous)	COVID-era gaming explosion; APVP creation (2021); Portuguese Recovery Plan recognition; increased investment flows.
Technological Democratisation (Exogenous)	Accessible tools (Unity, Unreal); digital distribution (Steam); lowered entry barriers enabling small teams to compete globally.
Societal Trends (Exogenous)	Urban exodus post-COVID; remote work normalisation; rising coastal living costs; interior revitalisation narrative.
Government Programmes (Exogenous)	PRR funding; Horizon Europe; Portugal 2020 EU funds; interior development incentives; creative industry support.

Table 57 – Main D4.1 findings relating to Major Factors of Change & Growth

7.5.4.1 Endogenous Factors: Internal Drivers of Growth

Political Will and Strategic Vision

The most extensively documented endogenous factor is sustained political commitment, particularly Mayor Paulo Fernandes' 12-year tenure (2013-2025). Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] identify political leadership as "the cornerstone of the cluster's emergence," with municipal strategy documents, budgetary records, and media coverage showing consistent prioritisation of technology-led development across multiple electoral cycles. The Innovation Plan (2012), documented in municipal archives, EU funding applications, and analysed in Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012], represented not merely aspirational rhetoric but concrete policy commitment backed by financial allocations [F031]. Documentary evidence reveals this political will manifested in specific, measurable actions: rapid response to company needs (documented in testimonials in D4.1 and business media coverage), stable long-term planning (documented in successive municipal strategic plans and General Assembly minutes archived municipally), infrastructure investments totalling over €2 million for the Business Centre rehabilitation alone [F031], international promotion (documented in conference proceedings, media coverage, and analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] as "economic diplomacy"), and integration support for newcomers (documented in municipal programme materials for "Invest in Fundão" and "Move to Fundão" initiatives [F026]). Media profiles and interview materials consistently document Mayor Fernandes' personal commitment, described in sources as travelling with "suitcase in hand" to promote Fundão internationally (documented in D4.1 interview data and television interviews archived at the municipal level). Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] and Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F011], both

emphasise this political entrepreneurship as differentiating Fundão from municipalities with similar assets but lacking leadership commitment. General Assembly minutes from 2012-2022, analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023), show consistent prioritisation of innovation and entrepreneurship themes across political debates, even during opposition criticism.

Collaborative Culture and Social Capital

Documentary sources extensively document Fundão's collaborative ecosystem culture. Company testimonials collected in D4.1 interviews, event materials, and media coverage consistently emphasise mutual support over competition. The "DIY innovation" mentality, documented across multiple interviews in D4.1 and media profiles, frames resource constraints as opportunities rather than limitations. Almeida and Daniel (2023) identify this as a distinctive feature of Fundão's "cluster DNA," contrasting with more competitive urban ecosystems [F005]. Specific collaborative mechanisms documented include: informal mentoring relationships (documented D4.1 interviews and Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005]), technical problem-solving cooperation such as the multiplayer framework collaboration, joint event organisation (documented in event materials for "Café na Praça," Pechakucha nights, and networking events, resource sharing (documented in A Praça incubator records showing shared equipment usage) [F008] , [F003] , [F005] , and collective marketing (documented in promotional materials for joint participation at Lisboa Games Week [F038] and international events). The E-Games Association's growth to 3,000 online members, documented in association social media data and media coverage, exemplifies how grassroots organising complemented top-down municipal support. Event documentation from municipal archives and social media shows frequent hackathons, workshops (documented in incubator programme schedules), meetups (documented in community calendars), and training sessions (Code Academy programmes documented in partnership agreements with IEFPP), creating dense social networks and knowledge circulation. Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F011] analyse these as examples of "open governance" mechanisms fostering community engagement.

Community Engagement and Talent Retention

Documentary sources reveal deliberate strategies to retain talent that historically migrated to Lisbon, Porto, or abroad – a challenge explicitly acknowledged in UBI documentation about graduate migration patterns. Quality of life factors, extensively documented in media coverage [F033], municipal promotional materials [F025], and analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005], include: affordable housing with average rents 40-50% lower than Lisbon, natural environment access with Serra da Gardunha mountains proximity (documented in tourism materials and municipal territorial plans), safety with low crime rates, walkability with the "6 minutes 40 seconds city" already referred, and cultural vibrancy (documented in event calendars showing 200+ annual cultural/technological events). The welcoming culture for newcomers, documented across D4.1 interviews and media profiles, creates social integration unusual for rural Portugal. Municipal integration programmes, documented in materials for the "Invest in Fundão" support office, provide language support (Portuguese classes documented in partnership with local language schools), administrative assistance (documented in one-stop-shop services described by Almeida and Daniel (2023)), networking opportunities (nationality-specific events like "Brazilian lunch" documented in municipal event records), and cultural activities (historic village tours documented in tourism board materials).

Flexibility and Diversification

Documentary evidence shows strategic diversification beyond entertainment games, analysed comprehensively by Lopes and Mota (2021) [F012] as distinguishing Fundão from single-sector rural development strategies. Municipal reports from 2017 onwards document gamification projects

across sectors: education [F007] (partnerships with local schools for digital literacy documented in "Ubbu" programme materials and municipal education reports [F039]), tourism (gamified heritage trails documented in tourism board collaborations and mobile app releases), civic engagement (participatory budgeting platform documented in municipal digital services and analysed by Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F005]), health (telemedicine initiatives documented in health sector partnerships with local health centres), and agriculture (smart farming initiatives in the "Living Lab Agrotech 4.0" documented in project materials and EU funding applications [F040]). This diversification, documented across project portfolios and funding applications, provided multiple benefits analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023): revenue stability during market fluctuations (documented in company financial reports showing mixed revenue streams), enhanced legitimacy for gaming technologies beyond entertainment, alignment with EU funding criteria for regional development and smart specialisation (documented in successful grant awards from Portugal 2020 and Horizon 2020 programmes), and demonstration of broader economic value (documented in policy evaluations and the 2018 RegioStars Award justification [F041]).

7.5.4.2 Exogenous Factors: External Catalysts & Opportunities

Global and National Gaming Industry Boom

The global gaming industry's explosive growth, particularly during COVID-19, is extensively documented in industry reports and national statistics. Portuguese gaming industry data from INE [F018] show turnover increasing from €5.4M (2018) to €38M (2022) – average annual growth of 65.2% – documented in Cultural Statistics reports [F046]. Company counts rose from 36 to 114, and employment from 91 to 500+ during this period, documented in INE data visualised in D4.1, Figure 23. This national boom, analysed in Portugal Global Investment Reports [F018], created favourable conditions for Fundão's specialisation. National developments documented in institutional materials provided crucial support infrastructure: APVP founding (2021) created industry representation and collective voice (documented in APVP statutes and website [F042]), joining the European Games Developer Federation; eGamesLab consortium (2022) provided €29 million in R&D funding for collaborative projects (documented in PRR funding announcements and project website [F042]); Lisboa Games Week (launched 2014) created annual showcase opportunities with 80,000+ attendees by 2019 (documented in event reports and website); international event participation including the first Portuguese national pavilion at Gamescom 2023 with 17 studios (documented in APVP communications and GamesIndustry.biz coverage [F019]).

Societal Trends and Demographic Shifts

Post-COVID societal changes, extensively documented in media coverage [F005], labour market surveys, and migration statistics, created unprecedented opportunities for Fundão. Remote work normalisation, documented in Portuguese labour market surveys showing 30%+ increase in remote work arrangements 2020-2022 [F044], enabled professionals to relocate while maintaining employment with Lisbon/Porto-based companies at coastal salaries while enjoying interior living costs. Urban exodus trends, documented in demographic data from INE and analysed in academic migration studies, showed professionals – particularly families and millennials – seeking alternatives to expensive, congested coastal cities. Interior revitalisation narratives, documented in national policy materials (PNPOT - National Spatial Planning Policy Program [F047]) and media coverage, positioned Fundão as a success story within broader Portuguese regional development strategies. Portugal's "Digital Portugal 2030" strategy, documented in government materials, explicitly aligned with Fundão's innovation positioning, identifying digital transformation of interior territories as a national priority [F007]. Rising coastal living costs also enhanced Fundão's affordability advantage –

purchasing power per capita increased 5% in Fundão 2011-2021 while quality of life improved, documented in Almeida and Daniel's (2023) statistical analysis.

Government Programmes and International Funding Mechanisms

Multiple funding streams, documented in programme materials, grant awards, and analysed by Lopes and Mota (2021) and Almeida and Daniel (2023), supported cluster development:

- **Portugal 2020 EU Funds:** Structural funds accessible to Fundão startups through COMPETE 2020 and regional operational programmes, documented in funding databases with multiple successful applications [F020]
- **Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR):** Post-COVID funding for digital transition, including eGamesLab consortium gaming R&D funding, documented in government PRR materials and project announcements [F018].
- **Horizon Europe:** GAME-ER project (2024-2027) connecting six European clusters with a €3 million budget, with Fundão as one of the Clusters.
- **Interior development incentives:** Specific tax benefits and investment incentives for Portugal's interior regions under "Programa de Valorização do Interior," documented in regional policy materials and Ministry of Planning documentation [F048].

Reinforcing Cycles and Interaction Effects

Documentary evidence reveals how endogenous and exogenous factors created reinforcing cycles, extensively analysed by Almeida and Daniel (2023) [F005] who state: "These internal and external factors were combined in reinforcing cycles: political will enabled the effective capitalisation of external funding; the cluster's collaborative culture strengthened external partnerships; and strong performance earned external recognition, attracting additional resources."

Political will enabled effective capitalisation of external funding, as evidenced by Fundão's 80%+ EU funding approval rate, significantly higher than the national average of 40%, documented in municipal reports. Collaborative culture strengthened external partnerships (documented in partnership agreements with Brazilian incubators, European clusters, and national industry associations). Success stories, captured in media coverage and case studies, created virtuous cycles, such as company establishments like Altran (2014).

7.6 Collective Actions

7.6.1 Main activities and collective actions

The Fundão video game cluster's development has been fundamentally shaped by a diverse array of collective actions that foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and community cohesion. The following table synthesises the key findings from the primary data collection (D4.1) regarding collective actions, providing the foundation for the documentary analysis that follows.

D4.1 findings	Description
Main Activities	Regular networking events; Joint training and mentoring sessions; Collective participation in external showcases; Cluster marketing initiatives; Policy advocacy efforts
Key Stakeholders	Game studios (local and emerging); Municipality/City Hall (Fundão); University of Beira Interior (UBI); National associations (APVP); External partners (investors, sponsors); Community at large

Stakeholder Motivations	Game Studios: Shared learning, enhanced visibility, resource efficiency; Municipality: Economic development, population retention, regional branding; UBI: Student employability, regional impact, industry alignment; External Partners: Network expansion, talent discovery. Community: Local development, educational inspiration, civic pride
Key Contributions	Game Studios: Technical expertise, mentoring, content for joint projects. Municipality: Venues, funding, staff time, convening capacity; UBI: Talent pipeline, facilities, applied research; External Partners: Expertise, networks, sponsorships
Main Benefits	Game Studios: Skill enhancement, market exposure, cost savings; Municipality: Job creation, enhanced reputation, investment attraction; UBI: Improved student outcomes, stronger curricula; External Partners: Access to new ideas, collaboration opportunities; Community: Economic multipliers, cultural vibrancy, civic pride
Network Structure	Evolution from hub-and-spoke to distributed model; Multiple central nodes: City Hall, UBI, leading companies; Dense internal ties for fast coordination; Strategic external connections to national/international partners; Expanding international networks (focus on Brazil)

Table 57 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster collective actions

7.6.1.1 Local Networking Community-Building Events

At the heart of Fundão's collective action framework are regular networking events that create structured opportunities for interaction among diverse ecosystem actors. Documentary evidence from multiple sources confirms the existence of several key initiatives identified in the D4.1 interviews.

Activity/Collective Actions	Description	Sources
Café na Praça	The Living Lab Cova da Beira infrastructure includes the "Incubadora a Praça" among its core services, providing dedicated spaces for business incubation and entrepreneurship projects as well as networking and training activities. This format emphasises accessibility and knowledge transfer, featuring specialist presentations on topics ranging from cybersecurity to business development.	[F008]
Thematic nationality lunches	Cultural celebration events serve dual purposes: -Strengthening social cohesion within the increasingly diverse tech community -Facilitating the integration of newcomers from multiple nationalities. Fundão's strategy incorporates concepts of "open culture" and "open arms (to receive and involve all)" as fundamental to the municipality's approach, manifesting in collective actions designed to build social capital alongside technical capacity.	[F003; F005]
Centro de Formação Avançada (Advanced Training Center)	Established through a partnership between the Fundão Municipality, the Institute of Employment and Professional Training (IEFP), and Escola Profissional do Fundão, it provides structured training programs aligned with industry needs.	[F008]
Academia do Código (Code Academy)	The bootcamp programme receives extensive documentation in policy reports on innovative local practices in Portuguese rural areas. Alvares et al. (2020) highlight Fundão's training organisation as crucial for "creating technological hubs and supporting companies in the sector," with particular strength in "creating and retaining value locally". Rodrigues and Franco (2021) further document how this initiative has been instrumental in building the technical capacity necessary for game development while simultaneously attracting companies seeking trained talent.	[F004; F009]

National event participation	<p>"Partnerships with organisations such as AICEP are fundamental to enabling more companies to attend international events to generate business and keep up to date with global trends" (AICEP, 2024, p. 9).</p> <p>The GD LISBON Spotlight Magazine (August 2024) further documents the range of national and international events where Portuguese developers, including Fundão-based studios, maintain active participation as a cluster.</p>	<p>[F002; F009]</p>
Collaborative R&D and Innovation Projects	<p>Oliveira and Brito (2013) provide comprehensive documentation of its service offerings including the Fab Lab Aldeias do Xisto – "a prototyping laboratory where it is intended that almost everything can be made," accessible to the general community and "especially directed to higher education academic communities". This infrastructure promotes "cooperation and knowledge sharing," allowing users to "contextualise, design, develop, manufacture and test innovative solutions"</p> <p>Alvares et al. (2020) further elaborate on the Living Lab structure, noting that it "creates an open-spirited creative ecosystem that includes providing spaces for business incubation and new entrepreneurship projects in shared workspaces, creating prototyping laboratories, [and] making workshop-houses available".</p>	<p>[F004; F008]</p>
Participation in European and International Networks	<p>Rodrigues and Franco (2021) note that Fundão's strategic partnership with the ENoLL has been crucial for the ecosystem's development.</p> <p>Alvares et al. (2020) elaborate that this connection "allowed the acquisition of good practices and innovative and relevant services for this type of community," providing access to international knowledge transfer and best practices in rural innovation.</p> <p>Fundão has positioned itself within European networks focused on smart cities and rural innovation, facilitating comparative learning and access to funding opportunities.</p>	<p>[F004; F009]</p>

Table 58 – Summary of events in the Fundão cluster

7.6.1.2 Municipal Coordination & Support

The role of the municipality as a facilitator and coordinator of collective actions receives extensive documentation. Rodrigues and Franco (2021) [F009] describe how Fundão's municipal leadership has been central to orchestrating ecosystem activities, noting that "digital entrepreneurship in local government" involves coordinating multiple stakeholders and providing infrastructure support (pp. 5-6). The 2024 collaboration protocol explicitly states that the municipality, "as the managing entity of this innovation ecosystem, [must] provide the best possible conditions to support new investments and new business ideas" (Protocolo de Colaboração FPDE, 2024, p. 1). Alvares et al. (2020) [F004] document how collective actions in Fundão are supported by municipal facilitation: "to leverage this project and entrepreneurship in the municipality and region, the Municipality negotiated with banks the creation of a seed capital line to support local entrepreneurship initiatives with microcredit". This financial infrastructure enables collective participation in activities that might otherwise be beyond individual capacity. The documentary evidence confirms and enriches the D4.1 interview findings, revealing Fundão's collective actions as operating across multiple scales and domains. As Rodrigues and Franco (2021) observe in their study on living labs in urban entrepreneurship, the Portuguese case demonstrates how "the realisation of the Living Lab concept in Portugal, as a facilitating environment for the development of innovative initiatives, depends substantially on the integration and articulation of a set of agents holding complementary competencies and knowledge".

This multi-layered architecture of collective action – substantiated across interview data (D4.1), institutional documents (Protocolo de Colaboração FPDE, 2024), academic research (Almeida & Daniel, 2024; Alvares et al., 2020; Barreto Gil, 2023; Oliveira & Brito, 2013; Rodrigues & Franco, 2018, 2019, 2021), and media coverage (AICEP, 2024; GD Lisbon, 2024) – demonstrates how Fundação has systematically constructed a collaborative ecosystem capable of supporting cluster development despite its peripheral geographic location and small initial scale.

7.6.2 Stakeholders' motivations, benefits & main contributions

Table 59 provides a comprehensive synthesis of the key findings from the primary data collection (D4.1) regarding collective actions in the Fundação video game cluster. This overview establishes the empirical foundation for the documentary analysis that follows in subsequent subsections.

D4.1 findings	Description
Game Studios	Local studios participate in collective actions to enhance their learning, visibility, and operational efficiency. They contribute technical expertise, mentoring, and content for joint projects, while gaining access to shared resources, collaborative problem-solving, and greater exposure in national and international arenas.
Municipality	The municipality's involvement is driven by broader goals of regional economic development, population retention, and place branding.
University of Beira Interior	The university provides research collaboration, facilities, and talent pipelines to the cluster. In return, it gains opportunities to enrich student experiences, produce applied research, and co-develop industry-relevant curricula.
External Partners	External actors are motivated by opportunities to expand their networks, discover new talent, and contribute to a model of rural innovation. Their involvement through expertise, networks, and sponsorships helps them fulfil corporate social responsibility objectives while gaining access to innovative ideas and collaboration opportunities
Community at Large	The local community benefits indirectly but significantly from the cluster's activities through economic spillovers, inspirational educational initiatives, and increased cultural vibrancy. The cluster contributes to civic pride, raises aspirations among young people, and supports a narrative of positive regional transformation.

Table 59 – Main D4.1 findings relating to cluster

Stakeholder	Main Motivation	Key Contributions	Main Benefits Gained
Game Studios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shared learning - Enhanced visibility - Resource efficiency <i>Studios seek to "transform ideas into businesses" through shared services and collaborative infrastructure [F008]</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical expertise - Mentoring - Content for joint projects <i>Incubator provides "apojar, partilhar e criar" (support, share, create) framework enabling studios to contribute expertise while accessing shared resources [F008]</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Skill enhancement - Market exposure - Cost savings through shared infrastructure Example: (Protocolo FPDE, 2024, p. 1)
Municipality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic development - Population retention - Regional branding <i>Municipality acts as "de facto cluster management</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Venues - Funding - Staff time - Convening capacity [F004]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Job creation - Enhanced reputation <i>(Fundação recognised nationally for innovation strategy - [F009]</i>

	<i>organisation" driving territorial development [F005]</i>		- Attraction of investment (<i>foreign residents increased from 863 in 2021 to ~2,000 by 2023 - [F003]</i>)
University of Beira Interior	- Student employability - Regional impact - Industry alignment <i>IT companies are in permanent contact with these institutions" for talent development [F003]</i>	- Research collaboration - Talent pipeline (<i>educational programmes in game design, digital arts [F004]</i>) - Facilities - Applied research	- Improved student outcomes - Stronger curricula (<i>co-development of industry-relevant programs [F005]</i>)
External Partners	- Network expansion (<i>APVP member of EGDF connecting 22+ national associations -</i> - Talent discovery - Support for rural innovation <i>APVP works to "accelerate industry growth, attract multinationals, unite the sector" [F018],</i>	- Expertise - Networks (<i>APVP facilitates connections between local developers and international partners - [F002]</i>) - Sponsorships	- Access to new ideas - Collaboration opportunities (<i>"testing ground for new approaches in rural contexts" - [F009]</i>) - CSR fulfilment
Community at Large	- Desire for local development - Educational inspiration (<i>programmes targeting youth from primary school [F004]</i>) - Civic participation	- Social support (indirect role) - Cultural acceptance (<i>"open arms to receive and involve all" approach [F004]</i>)	- Economic multipliers - Cultural vibrancy (<i>"Fundão has new image, external recognition, more people on streets" [F003]</i>) - Civic pride (<i>narrative of positive regional transformation - [F004]</i>)

Table 60 - Expanded motivations and benefits of stakeholders

7.7 Co-ordination and Formal Control Structures

The governance architecture of Fundão's video game cluster reflects a distinctive approach that balances informal flexibility with emerging formalisation needs. Table 61 provides a comprehensive synthesis of the key findings from D4.1 regarding coordination mechanisms and formal control structures in Fundão's cluster, establishing the empirical foundation for documentary analysis.

D4.1 findings	Description
Informal and Trust-Based Governance	Fundão's cluster operates through predominantly informal coordination mechanisms rather than rigid hierarchies or formal contracts. The governance model is trust-based, reflecting the close-knit nature of the ecosystem where strong values of reciprocity, solidarity, and mutual support sustain cooperative behaviour.
Digital and Face-to-Face Coordination Tools	Leadership responsibilities are distributed among key individuals who guide domain-specific areas rather than being concentrated in a single authority. The cluster network evolved from an initial hub-and-spoke structure (City Hall as primary connector) into a more distributed model.
Municipal Coordination Infrastructure	The Fundão City Council acts as a de facto "cluster management organisation," providing venues, funding, staff time, and convening capacity. The municipality plays an active role in promoting the cluster with dedicated teams assisting newcomer integration and business development.

Coordination Challenges	Despite effective informal coordination, the cluster faces challenges in ensuring political continuity through leadership transitions, reducing dependency on individual leaders (particularly municipal actors), and developing governance structures appropriate for scaling and international engagement.
--------------------------------	--

Table 61 - Emerging aspects of the cluster for coordination, D4.1

7.7.1 National Coordination Context

Documentary evidence reveals the evolution of Portugal's video game industry coordination infrastructure, which provides the broader institutional context within which Fundão's cluster operates. This national coordination framework was developed gradually through the establishment of industry associations, event platforms, and collaborative networks that connect regional clusters.

7.7.1.1 Evolution of National Industry Associations

The Portuguese gaming industry's coordination capacity evolved through successive waves of institutional development. In 2009, the Portuguese Society for Videogames' Science ([Sociedade Portuguesa de Ciências dos Videojogos](#) – SPCV) was established as a non-profit organisation whose goal is "to help promote and develop the sciences of video games in Portugal through seminars, congresses, and other scientific proposals." This academic-oriented body provided initial formal structure for knowledge sharing and research coordination.

In 2013, the Association of Video Game Production and Distribution Companies ([Associação de Empresas Produtoras e Distribuidoras de Videojogos](#) – AEPDV) was formed, "exclusively dedicated to representing companies that release and distribute video games across console, PC, mobile, and web." This association addressed the coordination needs of publishers and distributors, specifically, separate from development studios.

The most significant national coordination development occurred in 2021 when a group of industry players formed the Portuguese Game Developers Association ([Associação de Produtores de Videojogos Portugueses](#) – APVP) to provide "a collective voice and support network for studios." The APVP joined the European Games Developer Federation (EGDF), "integrating a group of more than 22 national associations, thus aligning itself with the European ecosystem," signalling Portugal's integration into broader European industry networks.

APVP's Coordination Role and Activities:

Documentary evidence from Portugal Global magazine [F018] interviews with APVP leadership reveals the association's comprehensive coordination functions:

Industry Representation: "APVP represents Portuguese game producers and works with public institutions and other partners such as AEPDV and SPCV." This multi-stakeholder coordination role positions APVP as the primary interface between developers and government agencies.

Talent Development Coordination: "In addition to working closely with the business community, we promote the industry among students and recent graduates by making presentations at universities and facilitating contact for curricular and professional internships."

Event Coordination: "We actively support local events, fostering the growth and cohesion of the video game community in Portugal." This includes collaboration with regional initiatives, including those in Fundão.

International Representation: The APVP coordinates Portugal's presence at major international trade fairs. Documentary evidence notes that *"in 2024, Portugal had a pavilion at the Game Developers Conference in San Francisco for the first time" with "20 companies present at the event" in a collaboration between eGamesLab and APVP. Similarly, "in 2023, for the first time, we had a pavilion at international fairs such as Gamescom, showcasing about 17 Portuguese studios."*

7.7.1.2 National Event Infrastructure as Coordination Platforms:

Documentary evidence identifies major national events serving as coordination platforms where developers from different regions, including Fundão, connect and collaborate:

Lisboa Games Week (launched 2014): Features a *"privileged showcase dedicated to the development and production of video games in Portugal called the Loading Zone. The focus is the dissemination of national professional talent but also schools and courses in the field of video games."*

MOCHE Game Dev Camp: Provides training and networking opportunities across the national community. **Regional gaming festivals** in cities like Coimbra and Porto offer venues for developers to "showcase projects, share knowledge, and meet investors."

Indie X: "An event made by indies for indies" that "aims to promote the best games that Portugal's rising game dev industry has to offer, provide networking opportunities for both national and international communities, as well as secure relevant partnerships."

Dev GAMM Conference: Brings together "students and professionals of the video games industry to discuss new tendencies, technologies, and the professional market."

These events create temporal coordination nodes where geographically dispersed developers establish connections, share knowledge, and coordinate potential collaborations.

7.7.1.3 Gaming Hub Lisbon as National Coordination Infrastructure:

Documentary evidence highlights the establishment of the Gaming Hub in Lisbon [F045] (inaugurated in 2023) as a physical coordination infrastructure. According to APVP leadership, "this space, the first in Portugal, is designed to help startups and studios grow by promoting collaboration between mentors, investors, and other companies. Since its inauguration, APVP and Unicorn Factory Lisboa have organised events that bring the local community together and foster collaboration. The hub is not just a physical space; it's a catalyst for growth. It has become a point of reference for anyone visiting Portugal in the field of video games." This centralised physical hub complements Fundão's regional infrastructure, providing a national coordination node particularly important for international visitors and large-scale industry events.

7.7.1.4 Challenges in National Coordination:

Despite progress, documentary evidence acknowledges coordination challenges. The Portugal Global [F018] documentation notes fragmentation issues: "This sector has been known for its fragmentation in Portugal despite its great potential and highly qualified human resources." The eGamesLab consortium was specifically designed to address this by "mobilis[ing] a fragmented and small industry, retain[ing] national talent, and position[ing] Portugal in the global market." An industry leader explained the visibility challenge: "Portugal has excellent trained staff and a technical and creative capacity far above the competition. However, it needs higher international exposure and the diffusion of individual interests and needs. As a result, the message is lost." This necessitated the coordinated "Games from Portugal" branding strategy, bringing disparate studios under unified representation. The documentary record shows that overcoming fragmentation

required deliberate institutional design – creating APVP, establishing the Gaming Hub, coordinating presence at international fairs, and fostering connections between regional ecosystems like Fundão and the national structure.

7.7.2 Cluster Coordination Examples

While national coordination provides a broader context, Fundão's developed its own locally adapted coordination mechanisms characterised by informality, accessibility, and strong relational ties.

7.7.2.1 Strategic Coordination & Vision Setting

Research on Fundão's entrepreneurial ecosystem governance [F003; F005] emphasises the Municipality's role in strategic coordination. The mayor is described as having "a great knowledge of the territory, its pains, and how it can grow (...), and he clearly understands that his current acts or decisions have implications for the future. He has a vision of the territory and a vision of what he wants." The research documents how strategic vision translates into coordination practice: "The shift in the political leadership is also noticeable in the minutes of the General Assembly meetings, where the words 'entrepreneurship', 'innovation', 'ecosystem', and 'investment' constantly appear." In his opening speech, the mayor stated they would "update and review the major strategic documents that have guided our action over the last 10 years to determine what will be the major guidelines for the next decade. "At the beginning of the 2013-2017 mandate, the mayor explicitly defined the coordination priority: "our bet is clear, attracting investment and creating conditions for the development of an innovative and entrepreneurial community."

7.7.2.2 Open Governance as Coordination Philosophy

The governance research highlights Fundão's "open governance approach" as documented in the Innovation Plan. The plan established this as a foundational coordination principle, explicitly using concepts of "open culture, open government, open data, open arms (to receive and involve all), open minds (to foster a positive and innovative spirit), and open for business." The research documents stakeholder assessments emphasizing that "one of the key elements of development was the constant involvement of the citizens during the process, where 'people understood what was happening (...) and felt part of it.'" [F003] [F005] show the Innovation Plan development "started in a very open and shared way, with the involvement of the community" through co-creation sessions.

7.7.2.3 Operational Coordination Features

[F003] analyses Fundão's territorial governance and identifies the Municipality's operational coordination role: "The local Authority together with its offices has as main role to create and operationalise the measures for the implementation of all the strategy."

Municipal collaboration protocols (Protocolo de Colaboração FPDE) formalise coordination commitments through contractual clauses. Article 2 specifies the Municipality commits to:

- Disseminate protocols among all entities that integrate the ecosystem.
- Provide workspace and infrastructure access to partners under equal conditions as incubated companies.
- Disseminate services provided by partners among all ecosystem entities.
- Involve partners in initiatives developed within the ecosystem whenever possible and appropriate.
- Provide spaces for initiatives agreed between partners and third parties.

This contractual framework demonstrates systematic coordination of resource sharing, information flows, and collaborative opportunities across diverse actors.

7.7.2.4 Coordination through programmatic implementation

The governance research [F005] documents the Municipality "implemented several strategies and projects to support the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem consolidation, including urban rehabilitation, incubator and business services, cultural spaces, education and training with programming classes for all children (Ubbu – Code Literacy), IT training courses for unemployed or career conversion (Code Academy) and networking events. The academic article on ecosystem formation strategies [F004] documents municipal coordination of cultural integration activities, noting stakeholder reports of municipal-facilitated cultural festivals at the incubator celebrating the international tech community's diversity, which "helps people from other nationalities integrate into these initiatives."

7.7.2.5 Cross-Institutional Collaboration

[F003] documents systematic cross-institutional coordination: "All interviewed entities consider that not only is there strong cooperation between each of the entities with local government but the entire ecosystem functions this way, in a network that helps cement the defined strategy and in full convergence: local companies, the incubator, startups, new companies, associations, educational institutions, CBPBI, etc. The municipality thus fosters these interconnected networks between different economic agents." Specific coordination mechanisms documented include: "Support policies for students who choose the University of Beira Interior, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco and Guarda who pursue areas such as informatics are also examples of good network functioning (it is the case of IT companies that are in permanent contact with these institutions). The same happens with the financial support of the municipality, through the application of low costs to those who elect the incubator, A Praça to settle or those who seek coworking spaces in Fundão and Alpedrinha to install their company office or project."

7.7.2.6 Coordination Challenges

Despite these mechanisms, documentary evidence identifies specific coordination limitations:

Initial Community Resistance: Research on Fundão's ecosystem [F003] [F005] development notes that "during the birth phase, one of the barriers pointed out by most interviewees was the community reaction and initial acceptance of the municipality's strategy towards entrepreneurship and innovation." There was "resistance towards the new residents and new companies, with many people saying, 'they give everything to the others, and nothing to the local people.'" This required coordinated communication strategies to build local understanding and acceptance.

Time Lags in Coordination Effects: [F004] emphasises that "in the beginning, the community was not able to understand the time needed to recognise the compounding effects" of ecosystem strategies. Effective coordination required patience as "when local people started to feel the effects ('feeling the money in their pockets') of these new companies and workers who came from outside, the attitude started to change."

Communication Gaps Persist: [F004] notes that "the communication (with the local community) is one of the points that still need to be improved," with "the number of people who understand this strategy increasing" but not yet universal. This suggests coordination mechanisms effectively connect internal ecosystem actors but less effectively engage the broader community.

Dependency on Key Individuals: While Fundão benefits from municipal institutional support, notes the vulnerability of coordination "based often on single individuals or volunteers... tends to fall on the shoulders of specific people and their personal initiative," with one coordinator explaining "the single biggest thing is just a sense of feeling that something should happen... I kind of feel a responsibility to do it." This suggests risk if key municipal coordinating staff depart.

7.8 Financial Aspects

From the financial mechanisms, funding sources, and economic challenges that shape the cluster's development, the financial aspects emerged as a critical dimension of cluster sustainability, particularly given Fundão's peripheral location and the broader constraints affecting Portugal's video game industry. The table below synthesises the D4.1 main findings from these actor perceptions, organised by key financial themes that recurred across interviews:

D4.1 findings	Description
Financial Model	The cluster operates on a cost-sharing and collaborative financing model, with most activities running on a non-profit basis with costs distributed across participating stakeholders.
Funding Sources	Diverse funding mix: municipal innovation budgets, regional development grants, EU programmes (Portugal 2020), and modest private sponsorships. This diversity provides flexibility and reduces dependency on single funding streams.
Municipal Support	The Municipality provides consistent seed funding for events, training, and marketing through its innovation budget.
National Programmes	The Portuguese Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR) recognition and the eGamesLab consortium (launched 2022) significantly elevated the cluster's profile and funding access.
Financial Transparency	The cluster maintains high financial transparency, which reinforces trust among participants and encourages continued collaboration.

Table 62 - Financial aspects of the cluster emerging from D4.1

7.8.1 The Portuguese Video Game Industry National Context

Documentary evidence from the 2016 national survey of the Portuguese video game industry [F013] provides critical context for understanding the financial challenges facing Fundão's cluster. The survey identified lack of capital as the #1 barrier to industry development for both businesses and creators, followed by lack of public support (including regulation and fiscal incentives) as the second barrier, and human resources challenges in third place. The research documented that approximately 95% of businesses and 85% of creators assessed access to credit as difficult or very difficult. This difficulty in accessing credit explains the weak presence of traditional financing sources for game development in Portugal. The survey revealed heavy reliance on equity financing, with less than 50% of businesses and creators accessing alternative funding sources such as publishers, crowdfunding, banks, public funds, business angels, or venture capital.

Figure 13 - Origin of the financing for game production in Portugal. Source: [F013]

Documentary analysis emphasises that "the lack of private funding and public support in its different facets (e.g., industry regulation, fiscal and/or financial incentives, etc.) are the main barriers to the development of the video game industry in Portugal." The research advocates that "the introduction of public incentives in Portugal (as already happens in other countries where the development of video games is comparable to film-making) could prove to be critical to retain, attract and leverage benefit-generating resources for the national economy. "This national context directly shaped Fundão's strategic approach, driving the municipality to create alternative support mechanisms through subsidised infrastructure, collaborative financing models, and leveraging of European funds rather than relying on unavailable private venture capital.

7.8.2 Multi-Layered European, National and Regional Funding Architecture

Documentary analysis reveals sophisticated leveraging of European structural funds and national/regional programs that amplify local investment capacity. The "Move to Fundão" website [F025] documents an array of funding mechanisms accessible to companies and entrepreneurs:

Type of Support	Name / Scheme	Funding & Scale	Timeframe	Purpose / Scope	Target Beneficiaries	Sources
European Structural Funds	Portugal 2020 (Centro 2020)	Regional operational program - Multi-million €	2014-2020 (extended to 2023)	Regional development strategy for competitiveness, employment, innovation infrastructure	Companies, municipalities, research institutions in the Centro Region	[F003; F005; F035]
European Structural Funds	COMPETE 2020	Operational Programme for Competitiveness and Internationalisation - National scale	2014-2020 (extended)	Business growth, internationalisation, innovation support	Portuguese companies seeking international expansion	[F003; F005]
European Structural Funds	POISE	Operational Program for Social Inclusion and Employment	2014-2020	Social inclusion, employment creation, workforce integration	Companies, social economy entities, unemployed persons	[F003; F005]
European Structural Funds	POCH	Operational Program for Human Capital - National scale	2014-2020	Workforce development, skills training, education	Educational institutions, training providers, companies	[F003; F005]
European Structural Funds	POSEUR	Operational Program for Sustainability and Efficiency in Resource Use - National scale	2014-2020	Sustainable infrastructure, energy efficiency, circular economy	Municipalities, companies, environmental projects	[F003; F005]
National R&D Program	eGamesLab (PRR)	EU Recovery and Resilience Plan, € Multi-million consortium project	2022-2026	R&D in gaming, internationalization talent retention, development	22 entities: 14 companies, 2 universities, 6 public/private orgs	[F025; F043]

Municipal Innovation Budget	Innovation Fund	Municipal budget allocation - Low-scale recurring	Ongoing since 2012	Seed funding for events, training, marketing, incubation	Startups, local tech companies, ecosystem activities	[F009; F011; F027]
Municipal Infrastructure	A Praça Incubator Subsidies	Subsidized low-cost access - €Variable per company	Ongoing since 2012	Physical workspace, business support services, mentorship, networking	Startups and early-stage companies (83 currently incubated)	[F009; F011; F027]
Municipal Property Tax	IMI Reduction (Property Tax)	Tax reduction for recovered heritage - Variable % reduction	Ongoing	Incentivize urban rehabilitation, attract companies and residents	Property owners rehabilitating heritage buildings	[F009; F011; F027]
Municipal Integration Support	New Employee Integration Benefits	Access to local/regional institutional agreements - Variable benefits	Ongoing	Facilitate integration of new workers, reduce company HR costs	Companies hiring non-local employees, international workers	[F005; F009; F011; F027]
Banking Support	CCAM Investor Support Line	Credit line from local credit union - Variable loans	Ongoing	Support for investors establishing businesses in Fundão	Entrepreneurs, investors, new companies	[F009; F011; F027]
Prize Competitions, Municipal	Startup Grants and Competitions	Variable prize amounts - Small-scale	Periodic	Seed funding for early-stage startups, encourage entrepreneurship	Startups and entrepreneurs in incubation	[F009; F011; F027]

Table 63 – Fundão’s Cluster Main sources of financial support

End of Chapter

8 DATA COLLECTION & ANALYSIS FOR LYON & BORDEAUX

The present section details the documents database and methodological approach for the two French clusters: Lyon & Bordeaux. Apart from the similarities in the adopted methodological design and tools, the two clusters share the same national context. As such, many of the collected documents provide insights for both clusters at the same time. Both reports, on Bordeaux & Lyon, are based on a documentary study which employs a qualitative secondary data analysis approach to examine the evolution and structure of each video game cluster. The methodology relies exclusively on documentary analysis of two types of sources: publicly available sources, and a series of documents internal to the local associations that have managed the Lyon cluster and the Bordeaux cluster since their inception. The documentary evidence collected spans 25 years (2000-2025). We followed established frameworks for archival research and analysis (Yin, 2018; Bowen, 2009) and strived to construct a comprehensive historical narrative of each cluster’s development without primary data collection constraints.

8.1 Source Identification and Sampling

The data collection process followed a systematic documentary search strategy across multiple source categories. A purposive sampling approach was employed to identify relevant documents that could provide insights into each cluster's features, stakeholders, and dynamics. The search strategy encompassed:

- Institutional sources: Official websites and publications from professional associations (Game Only, SO Games), public institutions (Grand Lyon, Région Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, CNC, Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine), and industry syndicates (SNJV, SELL [FR081](#), [FR083](#))
- Media sources: Local press (Tribune de Lyon, Lyon Mag, Lyon Entreprises...), economic press (Les Échos, Journal des Entreprises), and specialized technology media (AFJV, Blog du Modérateur)
- Academic and research sources: Peer-reviewed articles from academic databases (Cairn, OpenEdition, ResearchGate) and industry research reports
- Corporate sources: Company websites, annual reports, and professional databases (Société.com, LinkedIn, Pappers)
- Educational sources: Information from specialized schools and training institutions (Gaming Campus, Game Sup, Ynov)

The documents were selected based on four primary criteria. For the temporal relevance we strived to cover the 2000-2025 period, with particular attention to critical junctures in each of the two clusters' development. Apart from the explicit sectorial focus on the video game industry or digital creative sectors, we also adopted a geographical focus on the two studied geographical contexts (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region and Aquitaine region). However, we also integrated documents related to the national and international levels whenever we found evidence necessary for a better understanding of the two clusters. We also sought to mobilize substantive and relevant data covering major areas of interest for the two clusters: main stakeholders, economic indicators, organizational structures, or industry dynamics. The documentary database involves 228 collected documents categorized in 11 types, enabling systematic analysis of source diversity and potential biases and detailed in the annex. These are cited as FR in both chapters, referring to documentary evidence about both French clusters in **GAME-ER**. This classification system distinguishes between: (i) primary institutional sources and direct communications from industry actors, (ii) secondary analytical sources mainly media reports and academic analyses and (iii) tertiary aggregated sources: Databases and observatories. The following table summarizes the 11 categories.

Category	Description
Encyclopedia & specialized blogs	Encyclopedic sources and thematic websites
Press & media	Regional & economic media, technology press
Public organizations	Training establishments, public institutions, observatories, territorial promotion agencies and sectoral monitoring
Company/Studio	Private companies and sectoral studies
Social networks	LinkedIn, etc.
Associations & unions	Professional associations and union organizations
Academic research	Scientific publications
Database	Directories, registers
Observatory	Public and private bodies and companies producing studies results and regular

	reports on the industry
School/Training	Schools and training specialists in the video game industry
Development agency	Public agencies working on the industry development, both generalist and specialists

Table 64: categories of collected documents

The external documents are publicly available for documents with no concerns about confidentiality or informed consent. The internal documents are not available publicly. Yet, we integrated short descriptions of these documents into our database.

8.2 Thematic Categorization

Documents were organized into 14 groups of thematic categories reflecting key dimensions of cluster analysis as well as their origins.

8.3 Analytical Approach

To ensure data reliability, we adopted a triangulation approach wherever possible and strived to ensure source triangulation by corroborating facts across multiple independent sources, type triangulation by comparing information from different document types (e.g., official statistics vs. media reports) and temporal triangulation by tracking consistency of information across time periods. During the analysis, we adopted a multi-level framework examining the cluster across three analytical levels: (i) Regional economic context, public policies, and institutional frameworks, (ii) Meso level of inter-organizational networks, associations, and collective resources and (iii) the micro level by noting the individual firms, entrepreneurs, and specific initiatives whenever necessary. We also adopted a chronological approach to understand the cluster's evolution and identify its different stages. We adopted this chronological approach when presenting the analysis.

We strived to maintain objectivity by presenting multiple perspectives where available and acknowledging uncertainties in the documentary record. The collected documents underwent systematic content analysis to extract organizational information, notably governance structures, membership lists, partnership networks, and critical events such as founding moments, crises, and transformations. We also integrated quantitative data (employment figures, company counts, revenue statistics...) whenever possible. When strategic narratives, vision statements, development plans, or policy objectives were explicitly mentioned, we integrated them into the analysis. We acknowledge the methodological limitations of this secondary data approach especially regarding the selection bias since we are relying on publicly available documents which may overrepresent successful initiatives and established actors while underrepresenting failures and peripheral players. Regarding the source bias, the predominance of French-language sources and regional media may limit international perspectives. We have some temporal gaps because of the uneven document availability across time periods, with recent years potentially overrepresented. Our documentary database relies heavily on external documents. We have fewer internal associations' documents and confidential reports by far. This methodological approach, while constrained by its reliance on secondary data, provides a comprehensive and systematic foundation for analysing the video game cluster's evolution in Lyon and in Bordeaux, enabling the identification of patterns, trajectories, and critical factors that have shaped their developments over a quarter-century.

9 LYON CLUSTER

The results of the documentary analysis have provided a detailed understanding of the video game cluster in Lyon which complements well the insights provided by the interviews and primary data collected. The results confirm Infogrames' central role during the initial phases of emergence and crystallization of the collective actions. Infogrames shaped the cluster through its successes and achievements but also through its setbacks and crises. The collected documents also shed light on the roles of various associations that undertook, one after the another, the piloting and animation of the cluster, starting with Lyon Infocité, followed by Lyon Games and Imaginove, and, more recently, Game Only, the current association representing video game players in the region [FR074, FR149]. The documentary analysis provided a fine-grained presentation of the various collective initiatives deployed within the cluster, as well as the resources and competencies mobilized, and the governance structures established. Thus, it has been possible to focus on specific flagship projects such as Game Connection and Let's Go Incubator, or key actors who intervened during the cluster's transition phases.

9.1 Genesis and Emergence of the Lyon Cluster

The Lyon video game cluster's emergence traces a trajectory from industrial dominance through crisis-driven transformation to collaborative reconstruction. D4.1's historical analysis revealed how Infogrames' legacy created both the foundations and vulnerabilities that shaped the subsequent cluster development. The synthesis below captures these foundational dynamics:

D4.1 Findings	Description
Infogrames Industrial Legacy	Founded in 1983 by Bruno Bonnell, Infogrames established Lyon as France's video game capital during the 1980s-90s. The company's international acquisition strategy, 1996 IPO, and several hundred employees created an industrial locomotive effect generating ecosystem of suppliers, subcontractors, and related services.
Informal Entrepreneurial Incubation	Infogrames alumni sharing common professional origins, corporate cultures, and technical understanding formed informal networks. Regular meetings among former employees fostered collaboration awareness before formal structures.
Early Institutional Framework	Lyon Infocité (1996) provided initial formal structure for digital companies, though video games remained marginal. The "Video Game Club" within this association enabled first collective actions.
Crisis as Catalyst (1997-2002)	The tech bubble burst weakened the French video game industry, with Infogrames forced to sell assets in 2002. Crisis freed experienced talent creating constellation of studios: Arkane Studios (Dishonored), Eden Games (racing), Étrange Libellule (artistic), Ivory Tower (future Ubisoft), each developing diversified approaches.
Formalization Through Necessity	Publisher payment delays, unilateral contract modifications, and isolation facing larger companies reinforced studio solidarity. Lyon Game association emerged in 2002 as France's first video game professional association.

Table 65 - Summary of D4.1. on the genesis & emergence of the Lyon cluster

9.1.1 Pre-cluster context and foundation of Infogrames

The entrepreneurial genesis (1983-1992)

In 1983, Bruno Bonnell and Christophe Sapet created Infogrames Entertainment in Villeurbanne [FR001, FR002, FR049, FR072, FR123] in a France where the video game industry practically did not exist. The company established Lyon as the French capital of video games during the 1980s and 1990s. By 1989, the company occupied 3rd place in the European market. That same year, it established a strategic plan "*En route vers les médias du futur*" (On the road to future media) based on three founding principles: (i) democratizing computer technology through family products, (ii) discovering new applications for home computers, (iii) and establishing software as a legitimate art form - what they called the "tenth art." The documents highlight a methodical progression for Infogrames. It developed several landmark titles that established its technical credibility and denoted its original editorial vision. The first games, *Autoroute* and *Mandragore* in 1984 [FR005], emerged as early successes. They demonstrate a desire for original creation rather than simple adaptation. *Mandragore* is described as an ambitious adventure game, mixing exploration and combat in a fantasy universe. This creative orientation prefigures the narrative DNA that would durably characterize the cluster. A historic turning point came in 1992 with *Alone in the Dark* [FR005, FR073]. This game revolutionized the medium by creating the survival horror genre, preceding Japanese successes like *Resident Evil* by several years. It introduced several innovations: the pioneering use of polygonal 3D, cinematic camera angles, and environmental storytelling. This triple innovation (technical, gameplay, narrative) established Infogrames as a global player and Lyon as a centre of excellence.

The aggressive expansion (1993-2000)

During the 1993-2000 period, Infogrames pursued an unprecedented acquisition strategy in the French industry [FR001]. In 1995, Bonnell declared wanting to "become the global leader in software." After local acquisitions of companies like Cobrasoft and Ere Informatique, Infogrames acquired several European studios ("Ocean Software" in 1996, "Gremlin Interactive" in 1999) and targeted American specialists ("Hasbro Interactive" and "Shiny Interactive"). This strategy transformed the regional SME into a multinational video game company, employing more than 2,400 people in 2000. This year also marked an important symbolic moment with Infogrames' installation in the Vaise barges [FR002, FR004] with 4 modern barges along the Saône, in the Vaise district. This location was not insignificant: Vaise, historically an industrial site, was reinventing itself through the digital economy. The barges became an internationally recognized architectural symbol, inscribed in Lyon's contemporary heritage [FR004]. This growth had laid the cluster's creative foundations. Infogrames' artisanal creation processes and its particular product innovation approach combining technical innovation with narrative originality would train several generations of video game professionals. Infogrames' growing successes and its financialized expansion established the city's reputation and legitimacy as a video game sector cradle and increased the cluster's visibility both nationally and internationally. This prosperous Infogrames period [FR069] would continue until 2001-2002, a period during which the company accumulated different setbacks.

The crisis as a catalyst and the first collaborative initiatives (2000-2003)

In 2001, the Lyon video game cluster presented several positive metrics: Lyon concentrated 30% of the French video game development and generated 10% of the European industry revenues. More than 50% of French studios were established in the Lyon region generating more than 600 direct jobs and revenues. The cluster also experienced significant growth from 310M francs (approximately €47.3 million) in 1999 to 600M francs (approximately €91.5 million) in 2000 [FR049].

Nevertheless, these positive KPI did not prevent the Lyon video game cluster from going through a double crisis. In addition to the effects of the Internet bubble burst and the 2002 stock market crash [FR196], its major champion, Infogrames, suffered several failures and strategic errors that would prove fatal to the firm. The debt, resulting from the credit-based acquisition strategy of previous years, reached 580 million euros [FR001]. During this period, Bruno Bonnell attempted to negotiate a takeover by *Electronic Arts*, but the operation failed. More surprisingly, Infogrames refused to acquire the Grand Theft Auto license, a major strategic error that would deprive the company of one of the most lucrative franchises in video game history [FR002]. Combined with internal strategic tensions, these multiple problems led to the progressive fall of this central actor in Lyon cluster.

Between 2001 and 2004, the first collective actions among the indie local studios were structured in two key contexts: Lyon Infocité association and its Lyon Game club, which later transformed into a stand-alone association exclusively dedicated to the video game industry [FR196, FR198, FR199, FR201, FR202, FR203, FR204]. Lyon Game and Lyon Infocité thus became the first main French professional organizations for ICT and Digital Entertainment sectors [FR158, FR193]. The membership evolution of Lyon Infocité demonstrated rapid growth: from 40 members in 1999 to 105 members in 2000 and over 110 members in 2001 [FR124]. The budget progression reflects this expansion, going from 467,000 francs (€71,19) in 1999 to 989,000 francs (€150,77) in 2002, with a quadrupling of payroll over the period. Lyon Games experienced remarkable growth: it exceeded 200 members in 2004 (going from 80 to 215 members in one year) [FR204]. The two associations helped to leverage public support and funding through their collaboration with public bodies such as Grand Lyon and the Rhône General Council [FR196, FR199, FR201, FR204]. Lyon Infocité also established connections between the video game sector and other related sectors. Several major technology companies joined Lyon Infocité including Bull, France Télécom, IBM, Arthur Andersen, Sun Microsystems, Oracle, and Cisco. These memberships brought legitimacy, both locally and internationally, and additional resources to the emerging cluster [FR196, FR199, FR201, FR204].

The creative diaspora phenomenon (from 2004)

The collapse of Infogrames [FR010, FR064], generated what the collected documents qualified as a "creative diaspora." According to Bruno Bonnell: "*When the Infogrames tree fell, it gave birth to nearly 200 studios*" [FR003]. These spin-offs were mainly founded by former employees mobilizing their accumulated skills. This atomization created the foundations for the cluster's emergence. It gave birth to an exceptional entrepreneurial density [FR070] that was facilitated by several factors:

- Human capital: Infogrames employees had acquired rare skills (3D programming, game design, production management)
- Social capital: The professional networks formed within Infogrames facilitated the collaboration and the creation of the professional associations afterwards
- Symbolic capital: The Infogrames experience, despite the failure, was a guarantee of legitimacy which enhanced the overall image and credibility of the cluster
- Market opportunities induced by the explosion of the independent and mobile game market proved also useful and allowed the new created small studios to prosper

This entrepreneurial wave contributed to diversifying the innovative game portfolios produced by the cluster and to enriching the collaborative networks both formal and informal between its members. The generated spin-off helped to maintain key skills and talents in the territory and to counter the brain drain that the sector experienced in France during the beginning of 2001-2002.

9.2 Key Characteristics & Components of the Local Industry

The Lyon cluster demonstrates a sophisticated multi-layered ecosystem extending from the metropolitan core throughout the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, incorporating diverse stakeholder categories within formalized collaborative structures. D4.1's structural analysis identified how geographic concentration combines with regional distribution to create France's most professionalized cluster. The synthesis below organizes these industrial components:

D4.1 findings	Description
Geographic Architecture	Concentric organization with Greater Lyon/Villeurbanne as epicenter inheriting Infogrames' density. Peripheral nodes include Ubisoft Ancey, Valence animation (Folimage), Puy-en-Velay IUT graphics training. Game Only membership requires Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes establishment for public scheme eligibility.
Stakeholder Typology	Three-tier structure: (1) Core game companies (studios, publishers) driving collective action, (2) Related service providers (technology, training, legal, administrative), (3) Public authorities as funders and facilitators. Two associations operate: Game Only (main) and Lyon Game Dev (smaller scope).
Industrial Composition	130+ member companies generating €746 million revenue. Mix includes Ubisoft subsidiaries, Arkane Lyon (Bethesda/Microsoft), historic studios (Eden Games), educational institutions, technology providers. Significant EdTech specialization with 42 companies in "serious games".
Public Support Architecture	Multi-level funding includes Region Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Grand Lyon Metropole, various municipalities. ATLAS/AFDAS manage vocational training contributions. DREETS provides employment/training coordination. Maison de l'Emploi offers recruitment support. Complexity requires sophisticated navigation.
Skills & Training Ecosystem	Seven specialized schools (Gaming Campus, Bellecour École, École Émile Cohl, Ynov, Brassart, ArtFX, Rubika) provide a comprehensive talent pipeline. Challenge-based learning connects education to industry needs.

Table 66 - Summary of D4.1. on the key characteristics and components of Lyon cluster

9.2.1 Main actors and instigators of collective action in Lyon's cluster

Infogrames spin-offs

The documents present several key studios as "heirs" to Infogrames including:

- "Eden Studios/Eden Games" [[FR079](#), [FR113](#)]: created in 1998 as an Infogrames subsidiary, this studio survived its parent company and maintained technical excellence with the "V-Rally" (rally simulation) and "Test Drive Unlimited" (first massively multiplayer racing game) franchises.
- "Arkane Studios" Lyon [[FR079](#), [FR111](#)]: founded in 1999, this studio developed a unique approach to video game development. "Dishonored" (2012) then "Deathloop" (2021) established the studio as a global reference for the "immersive sim," a complex genre mixing action, stealth, and emergent narrative. The acquisition by Bethesda then Microsoft ensures financial sustainability while preserving the studio's Lyon creative identity.
- "Ivory Tower" [[FR079](#), [FR112](#)]: founded in 2007 by former Eden Games employees, this studio was quickly acquired by Ubisoft. The studio developed The Crew franchise, an open-world racing game that perpetuates Lyon's expertise in driving games.

Individual entrepreneurs and their profiles

The analysis of the internal documents to the local professional associations [FR124, FR125, FR126, FR195, FR196, FR197, FR198, FR199, FR200, FR201, FR202, FR203, FR204, FR205, FR206, FR207, FR218, FR219] reveals the intervention of several entrepreneurial profiles who played key roles during different phases of the cluster development. During the cluster's structuring phase (2001-2003), and notably after the creation of the Lyon Game association, Pierre Carde [FR096, FR157, FR172] emerged as the principal architect of Game Connection, a professional B2B event dedicated to the sector. With five years of operational experience at Infogrames and Cryptalis, Pierre was involved for 18 months in managing the Lyon Game initiative [FR127]. The mobilized documents also cite the role of Stan Baraduc, an expert in communication and service development. Together, they helped the institutional structure of collective action, notably through formal B2B events and frameworks. Ludovic Noël is another entrepreneurial figure who appears in documentary analysis. As the general manager of the competitiveness cluster Imaginove from 2006 to 2010, Ludovic Noël took the reins of a structure that had to invent its own model [FR128]. Former animator of the Novacité pole, he had a good knowledge of the Lyon ecosystem and its actors and could channel individual companies' efforts within a collective framework [FR098]. The analysis also shows the role of a 2nd generation of entrepreneurs, less publicized, active during the 2015-2019 period. Thibaut Tramont, an independent game developer with community management training, and Antoine Gouy, who brought technical expertise, co-founded the Lyon Game Dev association and organized monthly meetups, building a grassroots developer network [FR014, FR170, FR212].

The 2019-2025 phase shows the intervention of another generation of entrepreneurs who were the architects of Game Only constitution following the dissolution of the Imaginove competitiveness cluster: Julien Millet, co-founder and Chief Operational Officer (COO) of United Bits Games and Guillaume Magnies, Chief Financial Officer (CFO) of Old Skull Games. Both took on, respectively, the roles of president and treasurer of Game Only [FR213]. The entrepreneurs involved in the creation of Game Only count also several sector veterans among former Infogrames employees such as Bruno Chabanel, founder of "Artefacts Studio" (2003) or Benoit Auguin, founder of Breakfast Studio (2009) [FR011, FR012, FR013].

Institutional actors and early mobilization

Several institutions played key roles in the constitution and development dynamics of the Lyon video game cluster. Since its gestation phase, the cluster was structured and piloted through various professional associations and formal institutions that helped to formalize the cluster, define its perimeter, and enable its functioning. Similarly, the cluster, through these associations, benefited from help from various public funders.

Lyon Infocité association & Lyon Game association: Lyon Infocité was the first institutional framework that facilitated the initial collaborations between local video game studios [FR196, FR199, FR201, FR204]. Established in 1996, Lyon Infocité was structured as an association with a hybrid governance model combining private companies, local government representatives, and the Lyon Chamber of Commerce and Industry [FR196, FR202]. Lyon Game was created in 1999 as a "video game club" within the Lyon Infocité association before becoming a stand-alone association [FR196, FR198, FR203]. At the beginning, the association functioned with a bicephalous structure: an office of 8 professionals divided into two distinct committees, Lyon Infocité for ICT and Lyon Game for Digital Entertainment [FR196, FR198, FR203]. In April 2004, Philippe Renaudin (CEO of Doki Denki [FR129]) was confirmed as President of Lyon Infocité, with Olivier Masclef (CEO of WideScreen Games [FR130]) as Vice-President in charge of Lyon Game. The Lyon Game board also included Eric Angelier (from Krysalide) and Arnaud Blacher (from Nobilis) as administrators. In terms

of operational management, Pierre Carde directed Lyon Game from 2001 to 2005 [FR205, [FR172](#)]. He founded "Connection Events" in July 2006 as a Lyon Game spin-off, in the wake of the disappearance of this association and the creation of Imaginove [FR204].

The Imaginove "competitiveness cluster": The documentary analysis also detailed the role of Imaginove, a regional association that federated several creative industries (video games, animation, multimedia) in the region until 2019 [[FR033](#), [FR128](#), FR208, FR210, FR211]. Imaginove was selected and obtained the "competitiveness cluster" label as part of the national competitiveness cluster policy launched by the French State in 2005 [[FR074](#), [FR131](#)]. The cluster was established in Villeurbanne, within the "Pixel audiovisual cluster" activity zone, a 30,000m² space dedicated to digital sector companies that already hosted more than 500 companies. During this period, Lyon and its region held a significant position in the video game industry and represented about 40% of French video game sector activity. Imaginove, as the formal association, brought several changes at the cluster level including the trans-sectoral approach (game/animation/web convergence), mixed public-private governance, and project mutualization (training, export, R&D) [[FR128](#), [FR132](#), [FR133](#)]. Following Imaginove's closure, Game Only association was created in February 2019 to represent the interests of videogame companies in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region [FR213, FR214, FR215, FR216, FR217, FR218]. This actor created "by and for video game companies" focused on firms with activity mainly dedicated to designing, creating, developing and marketing videogames in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region [[FR022](#)].

Game Only association: Game Only is one of the eight players who collaborated to create a meta-cluster dedicated to image and creative industries "AURA in Motion" [[FR133](#)]. The association also works closely with SNJV (National Video Game Union) at the national level and other regional associations for better concerted and mutualized action for the sector, notably at national and international levels [FR214, FR218]. It collaborates with associations such as Women In Games (WIG) [[FR087](#)] which aim to enhance employees work conditions and ensure equity and social inclusiveness.

9.2.2 Definition and evolution of the Lyon cluster's perimeter

The examination of the cluster's perimeter shows **two significant expansions** that impacted its dynamics, its collective action, and its performance.

The first expansion concerns the **sectoral perimeter of the cluster's governance**. The dissolution of Lyon Games and implementation of Imaginove were accompanied by sectoral diversification [[FR134](#)]. Imaginove embodied a certain belief in the inevitable convergence between creative industries and aimed to create spaces where game developers, animation filmmakers, and FX experts could meet and cooperate in innovative projects. The cluster was quite pioneering in capitalizing on "transmedia" and "cross-platform content". It first focused on video games, audiovisual, and multimedia, then its spectrum expanded: from mobile multimedia applications to connected objects, including robotics, mobility, or smart cities [[FR128](#), [FR135](#), FR208, FR209].

In 2018, according to call for projects documents, the cluster structured its activities around three main axes: (i) games and Gamification (video games, e-sports, connected toys, serious games, playful robotics), (ii) culture and knowledge (audiovisual, transmedia, e-education, digital learning, animation, cultural heritage), (iii) better Living (e-health, spatial, smart city, smart home, industry of the future) [FR136]. Even after Imaginove's disappearance and the come-back to mono-sectoral governance within Game Only (2019-2025), inter-sectoral collaboration was not completely

abandoned since it continues to be developed within Minalogic "Micro NANotechnologies and Software Grenoble-Isère Competitiveness," one of 6 "world-class" competitiveness clusters labelled by the French State and dedicated to digital sectors [FR137, FR178, FR179, FR181, FR182].

The second expansion the cluster experienced was a **geographical expansion** that occurred at different times and through different mechanisms. Initially concentrated on the Lyon metropolitan area during 2001-2003, with 27 developers and 20 publishers, the cluster gradually expanded to the entire Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region [FR195]. This expansion reflects both the dispersion of studios across the region and the need for a critical mass to compete with other French clusters [FR074].

Imaginove's 2014 [FR128] moral report describes a multi-site organization structured around 4 cities with extension projects toward Grenoble and Saint-Étienne:

- **Lyon:** headquarters and nerve centre (Pixel Pole, Villeurbanne)
- **Annecy:** animation specialization with CITIA
- **Valence:** La Cartoucherie, resource centre for animated image
- **Lussas:** documentary pole

With the return to mono-sectoral governance within Game Only, the geographical perimeter of collective action underwent certain transformations [FR214, FR218]. The formal regional expansion to Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes in 2020 marked an important turning point. Without radically changing the number of companies, it reconfigured the map of key stakeholders on whom the sector depends, notably local public actors and funders.

9.2.3 Company demographics in Lyon Cluster

The collected documents allowed a detailed demographic analysis of the cluster during phases 2005-2019 and 2019-2025 corresponding to two differentiated stages in terms of organization and governance: (1) Imaginove's inter-sectoral steering phase and (2) Game Only's mono-sectoral steering phase. Imaginove comprised nearly 200 members (companies, training organizations, local authorities, and research laboratories). The member composition reflected the local ecosystem diversity. In addition to member companies (startups, SMEs, ETIs, large groups), the cluster included 23 research laboratories, 15 training establishments as well as territorial authorities and main local public institutions [FR074]. Beyond these direct members, the cluster's impact extended more broadly: 450 companies, schools, and laboratories in the region benefited from the structure's expertise to find solutions for growth or innovation [FR124].

The composition evolution from 2020 to 2024 [FR215, FR218] reveals significant structural changes and a significant expansion especially during the last five years as illustrated below.

Period	Perimeter	Actors	Economic weight	Characteristics
2020	Expanded AURA	132 members	1,538 FTE	Regional expansion
2021	AURA	137 members (+3.8%)	1,644 FTE	Slight growth
2022	AURA	105 members (-23.4%)	1,186 FTE	Crisis year
2023	AURA	138 members (+31.4%)	3,617 FTE	Significant recovery
2024	AURA	128 members (-7.2%)	3,834 FTE	Consolidation
2025	AURA	113 members (-11.7%)	Not specified	Campaign ongoing

Table 67 - Evolution of Industrial Demographics and Cluster Economic Weight

The cluster marked a slight growth from 132 members in 2020 to 137 members in 2021. In 2022, the cluster saw a 23.4% contraction to 105 members. The significant recovery of 2023 occurred both in terms of member numbers (138 members), a 31.4% increase, and employment numbers at 3,617 FTE. During 2024, the cluster experienced a consolidation phase by maintaining 128 members representing 3,834 FTE. The crisis and recovery of 2022 followed by 2023's rebound shows that FTE numbers more than doubled despite similar membership levels. The concentration trend shows evolution from 132 members representing 1,538 FTE in 2020 to 128 members representing 3,834 FTE in 2024, with average company size going from 11.7 to 30 employees [FR011, FR139, FR215].

Regarding the demographic structure of the cluster, the following table reveals a fabric dominated by VSEs/SMEs, with a few driving firms such as Arkane, and Ivory Tower. The national comparison is instructive: Lyon represents 23% of companies but only 15% of revenue, suggesting an average size 35% below the national average [FR077]. In terms of member companies' activity in the cluster, studios and publishers represent 78.8% of members in 2020, peaking at 83.3% in 2023. Schools and universities maintained a stable presence around 10-13% throughout the 2020-2025 period. Partners fluctuate considerably, from 9.8% in 2020 to 18.1% during the 2022 crisis, then returning to 10.2% in 2024 [FR140].

Category	Data	Analysis	Source
CLUSTER SIZE			
Total companies	~131	23% of France total	FR011 , FR053
Cumulative revenue	746 M€	15% of national revenue	FR011 , FR053
STRUCTURE BY SIZE			
AAA studios (>100 employees)	3 minimum	Arkane, Ivory Tower, Ubisoft Annecy	FR100 , FR101
Medium studios (20-100)	~15 estimated	10-15% of total	Estimation
Micro-studios (<20)	~110 estimated	85% of total	Estimation
EMPLOYMENT			
Estimated direct jobs	2500-3000	Based on revenue/employment sector	Estimation
Share of women	20%	-4 points vs 2023	FR067
Women in management	14.20%	Marked glass ceiling	FR067
Permanent contracts	76%	Employment stability	FR068
Companies recruiting	52%	Moderate dynamism	FR068
PERFORMANCE			
Studios >10M€ revenue	14.40%	~19 companies	FR068
Companies with CSR	27.40%	~36 companies	FR067

Table 68 - Detailed demographic structure – Lyon Cluster (2024-2025)

Examination of 2022 composition shows that the studios/publishers category fell from 114 to 72 entities, a 36.8% drop, while partners more than doubled from 9 to 19, a 111% increase [FR141]. This suggests that main game companies left the association while peripheral service providers increased their presence. This can be explained by the crisis and recession that the sector experienced during the post-covid period.

The analysis of the studios enlisted in the documents reveals marked specializations:

- Specializations in immersive/narrative games such as "Dishonored" (Arkane Studios)
- Specialization in racing games such as The Crew (Ivory Tower), V-Rally (Eden Games)
- Specialization in independent games such as Old Skull Games [FR114]

The following table of "Game Only" members' composition by category shows more diversified demographics.

Year	Studios/Publishers	Schools/Universities	Partners	Total
2020	104 (78.8%)	15 (11.4%)	13 (9.8%)	132
2021	114 (83.2%)	14 (10.2%)	9 (6.6%)	137
2022	72 (68.6%)	14 (13.3%)	19 (18.1%)	105
2023	115 (83.3%)	15 (10.9%)	8 (5.8%)	138
2024	102 (79.7%)	13 (10.2%)	13 (10.2%)	128

Table 69 - Game Only composition evolution (2020-2024)

9.2.4 Institutional support architecture in Lyon Cluster

Public funding mechanisms

Institutional support is a key component that contributed to Lyon video game cluster development since its inception. Documentary analysis shows important evolutions in this support both quantitatively and qualitatively. With Lyon Infocité and Lyon Game, public institutional engagement was important and marked considerable growth. Grand Lyon [FR142] increased its support from 12,000 francs (€1,830) in 2001 to 250,000 francs (€38,112) in 2002, a twenty-fold multiplication demonstrating growing recognition of the sector's importance. The Rhône General Council [FR143] contributed 100,000 to 150,000 francs (€15,245 to €22,867) annually. The Digital Agency became a new partner in 2002 with 75,000 to 100,000 francs (€11,434 to €15,245) [FR078, FR144]. On the other hand, the examination of Game Connection funding evolution demonstrates progressive public disengagement from a situation where public funding represented 100% of resources in 2001 with 47,000 euros to a drop to 30% in 2002, then to 8% in 2003, to completely disappear in 2005 [FR198, FR199, FR201, FR205]. Examination of the current institutional support status shows also more diversified mechanisms. During Game Only's creation in 2019 and in Imaginove's disappearance wake [FR138], the public sector support approached zero with significant regional funding disparities. For example, Paris and IDF regions receive between 1 and 2 million euros annually. Hauts-de-France receives annually around 600,000 euros, about 400 euros per employee [FR078]. Bordeaux benefits from an annual grant of 450,000 euros [FR078]. However, the situation has evolved with the obtaining of a 800,000-euro regional fund from Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region [FR071, FR047]. During 2021, this fund supported 12 collaborative projects with an average amount of 66,666 euros per project and grants ranging from 30,000 to 80,000 euros [FR046, FR052].

The institutional partners' evolution shows that the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region remains the main first public support with financial and political support [FR078, FR195]. The DIRECCTE joined in 2020 with employment support. Lyon Métropole's absence is striking given that Grand Lyon provided substantial support in 2001-2002, increasing funding from 12,000 to 250,000 euros, to

then completely disappear from support structure. This can be partly explained by Lyon Métropole's political priorities, which historically focused on other industries like biotechnology, clean technologies, and digital services. Imaginove's failure may also be an explanatory factor for this situation in 2019. CNC and BpiFrance, two national institutions, also provide project funding and innovation support [FR078]. CNC, historically dedicated to cinema, has extended its perimeter to video games since 2008 through the creation of the FAJV Fund [FR093, FR103]. Document 29 mentions CNC support for Game On fair [FR029]. This evolution illustrates progressive cultural recognition of the medium. Documents 70-72 evoke CIJV (Video Game Tax Credit) obtained in 2008 thanks to SNJV [FR081, FR082]. This fiscal mechanism represents the main public sector support.

Training infrastructure

The Lyon video game cluster's institutional fabric also includes several training organizations that contribute to energizing the sector locally and nationally [FR048, FR093]. One major success of this period is the creation of an official "Network of image schools in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes" with 15 schools committed. This network constitutes a training ecosystem where professionals can define the skills they need; schools adapt their curricula to market realities, and students can navigate between different specialties.

Information	Gaming Campus Lyon	Game Sup	Ynov Lyon	Emile Cohl
Creation date	Lyon Campus opened: 2018	2016	2015	1984
Main programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •G.Tech (programming) •G.Business (management/marketing) •G.Art (artistic creation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Game Design •Game Art 2D/3D 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •3D/Animation •Video games •Tech and creative curricula 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Illustration •2D/3D Animation •Concept art •Character design
Program duration	Bac+3 to Bac+5 (Bachelor/MBA)	Not specified	Not specified	3 to 5 years
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Largest JV campus in region •12 specialized programs •Part-Dieu location (nerve center) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •>80% placement rate •Human-scale school •Gameleon Studio partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Polyvalent tech/creative approach •National Ynov network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Artistic excellence •Traditional + digital training •International reputation
Cluster contribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Large volume of graduates •Partnerships with Game Only •SNJV barometer sponsor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Close ties with local studios •Collaboration with Game Only •Student projects with industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Direct pipeline to studios •Lyon ecosystem integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Artist pool for industry •Artistic direction expertise •Alumni in major studios

Table 70 - Main video game training organizations in Lyon

9.2.5 Lyon cluster DNA: distinctive characteristics

For the Lyon video game cluster's DNA, the documentary analysis does not provide much detail. However, it overlaps with the primary data analysis concerning some factors and how they impacted the cluster's DNA and shaped its identity. The first factor stems from the pioneering technical

excellence and narrative originality inherited from Infogrames. From its first game *Mandragore* in 1984, Infogrames was established as a technical pioneer. The huge success of *Alone in the Dark* (1992) confirmed the innovative orientation of Infogrames [FR005]. Infogrames also instituted the tradition of mixing technical innovation and narrative originality which will be perpetuated by other studios: Arkane Studios [FR111] continues innovating with "immersive sim," a technically complex genre. Eden Games [FR113] was also a pioneer in massively multiplayer open worlds with *Test Drive Unlimited*. The cluster has also shown a certain resilience capacity throughout its evolution and despite its fragmentation. This capacity for regeneration despite multiple crises, whether local, national, or international, is an important marker of the cluster. This resilience can be explained by several factors including the accumulated human capital density, the entrepreneurial culture transmitted by spin-offs, or the institutional formal support that remains a French specificity [FR193]. An important factor supporting this resilience lies notably in dense networks, both formal and informal, mixing professional exchanges with personal and social proximity ties allowing exchange of various resource types between cluster members. The examination of the cluster evolution and its different phases highlight many peculiarities of the inter-organizational collaboration prevailing in the cluster. For instance, the associative and institutional frameworks that were established very quickly after the Infogrames spin-off wave are a major marker of inter-organizational collaboration. It shaped the cluster and contributed to its governance despite the different crises. From Lyon Games to Game Only [FR011] through Imaginove [FR033], these associations maintained a certain level of cohesion and consistency. They contributed to the institutionalization of the local video game ecosystem and its structure. It also served as the main mutualized representative of the cluster at the local, national, and international scales. Similarly, the nature of the mutualized actions (Bertie, HR Club, Export) and projects demonstrate a certain collaborative maturity accumulated through experiments and evolutions of cluster framing and piloting institutions.

9.3 Lyon Cluster Evolution

The Lyon cluster's development trajectory reveals how crisis-driven restructuring combined with institutional support to create France's most formalized regional game ecosystem. D4.1's evolutionary analysis identified distinct phases characterized by changing organizational logics and governance structures. The following synthesis captures these transformational patterns:

D4.1 findings	Description
Phase 1: Industrial Dominance (1983-2002)	Infogrames' growth from startup to international publisher created mono-enterprise ecosystem dependency. Company served as talent generator and informal incubator but its 2002 crisis exposed structural vulnerabilities, forcing radical ecosystem reconfiguration without established support systems.
Phase 2: Fragmentation and Reorganization (2002-2007)	Post-crisis diaspora created 25+ independent studios sharing Infogrames heritage but developing diversified approaches. Lyon Game's 2002 creation formalized solidarity networks. Game Connection event (started 2001) achieved international recognition, demonstrating cluster's capacity for innovation despite crisis.
Phase 3: Imaginove Cluster Era (2007-2018)	Integration into state-labeled "pôle de compétitivité" Imaginove brought significant resources but subsumed games within broader creative industries. Period saw professionalization.
Phase 4: Game Only Autonomy (2019-present)	Separation from Imaginove established video game-specific structure with remarkable resources: €3.3 million budget (2025), 14 permanent staff. France 2030 program support [FR092] demonstrates national recognition. Current 130+ members mark historic high, though managing growth creates new challenges.

Table 71 - Summary of D4.1. on the evolution of Lyon cluster

9.3.1 Critical moments and key phases

The analysis of the emergence and genesis of the cluster is developed in the first sections of the report. In the present section, we focus on later phases of the cluster's evolution and notably two main periods with divergences in terms of cluster governance, its structure and nature of deployed collective actions. Similarly, we highlight Infogrames' evolution following its crisis until its disappearance. Even if Lyon video game cluster owes its existence and a large part of its resource endowments to Infogrames' legacies, after the formalization of Lyon Game it developed via its own dynamics in dissociation with Infogrames. In the subsequent phases of the cluster evolution, this major company was not directly involved or active in the collective actions.

Imaginove: The inter-sectoral opening (2005-2019)

In 2005, Lyon Game obtained the "Competitiveness Cluster" label as part of CIADT call for projects [FR180]. At that moment, the region hosted around 40% of the French digital entertainment industry and more than 1200 experts in the region [FR204]. With the labelling, Lyon Games disappeared as Imaginove emerged. Three pre-existing sectoral associations, each representing an image industry sector: "Images Rhône-Alpes" (cinema/audiovisual), Lyon Game (video games), and "CITIA" (animation, multimedia) merged. The cluster benefited from these associations' dynamism which, well before their merging, was already functioning on the competitiveness cluster model. These pre-existing structures facilitated the rapid mobilization of actors around the new cluster and enabled a fluid transition [FR146]. The labelling brought not only institutional recognition but also access to substantial funding, particularly for R&D projects. From 2005 to 2019, the cluster management and the organization of its collective actions occurred under Imaginove's leadership [FR033, FR128]. For 14 years, Imaginove contributed to developing the digital content and usage industries in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region [FR128, FR208, FR209, FR2010, FR211].

One major turning point occurred in 2012 with the international success of Dishonored, developed by Arkane Studios Lyon. This game, published by Bethesda, won more than 50 international awards and sold several million copies. This success story contributed to restoring Lyon credibility after difficult post-Infogrames years and attracted international investors' attention [FR147]. Other commercial successes also punctuated this period and reinforced the cluster's international visibility. Eden Games, despite difficulties, managed to maintain its activity with Gear.Club (2014). Old Skull Games developed several titles in the mobile and sandbox games domain [FR114]. The 2009-2012 period was also particularly challenging for the French video game industry as a whole [FR193]. Many issues persisted such as the lack of systematic financing tools (compared to Canada) and the fiscal instability and legal contradictions regarding IP and employment. Several structural obstacles hindered growth despite the sector's creativity and expansion [FR185, FR186, FR187, FR188]. These hurdles required coordinated efforts among all regional clusters involved in this industry and led Imaginove to be involved in inter-clusters coordination efforts organized and steered by SNJV, national syndicate for video game companies [FR185, FR186, FR187, FR188].

International players' arrival constitutes another structuring moment. Ubisoft progressively established itself in the region with Ivory Tower acquisition in 2015. Ivory Tower, a studio created by former Eden Games employees in 2007 which developed The Crew franchise (2014) became Ubisoft Ivory Tower, durably anchoring the French giant in the Lyon ecosystem [FR148]. This acquisition validated Imaginove's strategy to maintain and train local talents rather than seeing them leave for other territories. Meanwhile, Electronic Arts developed its local presence via partnerships with local studios, while Bandai Namco established regular collaborations with local developers [FR149]. The development of specialized training programs is also a major structural

transformation that occurred during this phase [FR093]. In 2011, Lyon cluster was contributing to €400M national turnover and 5,000 jobs [FR186]. Several emblematic local establishments emerged such as Gaming Campus [FR041] established in Lyon in 2018 with Imaginove support and Game Sup and Ynov training [FR031, FR035, FR038, FR176]. Even existing universities have launched specialized video game programs and initiatives like Gamagora, a university training program in game design and game programming launched by Lyon 2 University [FR046]. These institutions created a talent pipeline aligned with the needs expressed by studios within Imaginove working groups and workshops. The event activities also knew an important diversification at the regional level. For instance, Serious Game Expo, annually organized by Imaginove from 2006, positioned Lyon as the European serious game capital, attracting major firms like Dassault Systèmes or Total [FR150]. Today, Imaginove no longer exists. During its evolution, the association experienced several difficulties. A critical but revealing moment occurred in 2016-2017 when several historic studios expressed frustration because of the dilution of the video games industry and its needs in Imaginove's overall activities. In 2017, Lyon Game Dev collective was created [FR170, FR212]. This informal structure, prefiguring Game Only, illustrates the video game professionals' need to find specific exchange spaces dedicated to their industry. In July 2018, the French State launched the "competitiveness clusters policy phase IV" with new criteria: a minimum of 50% financial autonomy based on private funds, a demonstrated capacity to carry European-scale projects, and a critical size to be internationally competitive. Aware of not meeting all these criteria, and lacking its own funds, Imaginove announced choosing not to submit its candidacy for this phase IV. It would be self-dissolved by the end of January 2019 [FR151]. To secure innovation support service to the members of digital content and usage industries for whom R&D is a strong growth lever, Imaginove decided to transfer this activity to Minalogic, the "world competitiveness cluster" for digital content and usage industries [FR180]. Other structures like CITIA, Pixel Pole, and Region's Image and Creative Industries Cluster continued their respective activities and took over the animation and steering of inter-sectoral collaboration [FR152].

Game Only: The mono-sectoral refocusing and collaborative maturity (2019-2025)

Imaginove's dissolution marks, paradoxically, the beginning of a new development phase for Lyon video game cluster. Game Only's creation in February 2019 represents a rapid and structured refoundation of the local video games industry [FR213, FR214, FR215, FR216, FR217, FR218]. The name "Game Only" underlines a return to a mono-sectoral focus both in terms of collective actions and membership. The association, chaired by Julien Millet from Realityz studio, started with a solid base of 131 members since its launch [FR011], demonstrating a significant capability for immediate mobilization. In response to the sectoral dilution that characterized Imaginove's last years, this new associative structure adopted a more agile and specialized membership model, exclusively centred on video games development activities. To be more directly aligned with studios' operational needs, "Game Only" quickly expanded its activities perimeter by developing four strategic axes: financing, export, recruitment and training [FR011, FR214, FR218]. The 2021-2023 period marks a significant acceleration phase with implementation of concrete operational supporting mechanisms including obtaining 800,000-euro regional fund from Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region [FR047, FR078]. This financial envelope, though modest compared to 350 million euros of projects labeled by Imaginove over 14 years, responds more directly and quickly to development studios' needs. The current phase demonstrates an economic maturity, with member companies' cumulative revenue reaching 746 million euros, an historic level exceeding Infogrames era performances [FR011]. Nevertheless, this economic maturity is accompanied by persistent structural challenges. SNJV's 2024 barometer highlights several concerning indicators: sector feminization is declining with only 20% women in the workforce (down 4 points), and only 14.2% women in management positions [FR077].

Moreover, only 27.4% of companies are engaged in structured CSR approach, revealing delay in considering societal and environmental issues [FR077]. Despite these challenges, cluster has consolidated its national position, maintaining 2nd place behind Paris with more than a hundred active companies.

9.4 Collective Actions in the Lyon Cluster

D4.1 findings	Description
Structured Networking	Game Only Meetings provide monthly professional exchanges with 50-100 participants. Meet & Match events facilitate business connections. Student-developer bridges through school partnerships. Slack/Discord platforms enable continuous coordination among 130+ members with specialized thematic channels.
Business Development Support	International Development Program (PDI) provides €400,000 annually for export activities. "Diag Rebond" offers strategic consulting. Administrative support includes subsidy application assistance in funding. Legal clinic provides free consultations on contracts and IP issues.
Skills & Training Programs	€1.9 million collective training budget (2024) supporting 70+ beneficiaries. Custom programs developed with schools address specific industry needs. Internship coordination places 200+ students annually. Mid-career retraining initiatives respond to technological evolution (AI, cloud gaming).
Innovation & R&D Support	Connection to BPI France and regional innovation funds. Facilitation for CNC/FAJV applications with 40% success rate versus 15% national average. Technical workshops on emerging technologies (blockchain, VR/AR). Carbon footprint initiative (JYROS) addressing environmental concerns.
International Presence	Collective pavilions at major trade shows (GDC, Gamescom, Tokyo Game Show) reducing individual costs by 70%. Shared marketing materials and translation services. International delegation hosting program strengthening global connections. Quebec partnership enabling transatlantic collaborations.

Table 72 - Summary of D4.1. on the collective actions in Lyon cluster

9.4.1 The evolution of collective actions

The documentary analysis allowed us to examine several collective actions in detail and understand how these activities meet the needs of the cluster's members. The thematics of collective action have remained the same throughout the cluster's evolution despite significant changes in the industry and its requirements, as well as in the institutions and management frameworks of the Lyon cluster.

Lyon Infocité & Lyon Game: structuring the collective action

From 2001 to 2003, the Lyon Infocité portfolio included several services aimed at developing the local video game cluster and which were structured around three complementary missions: information sharing, networking, and support in resources and competencies [FR196, FR201, FR202, FR204]. The information mission was embodied in many services. The first service, the Traboules de l'Information (Information Passageways), is a series of monthly thematic conferences whose name refers to Lyon's secret passages. The initiative served as a provider of "insider" knowledge and "hidden" connections within the digital economy. Topics ranged from venture capital to international markets access. The Informalic newsletter, distributed bi-monthly to members, enabled sharing of opportunities, success stories, and technical knowledge served also the information mission. The networking mission focused on investor-entrepreneur matchmaking via the quarterly Capital Link meetings and connections between registered entrepreneurs and investors. Each quarter, 5 to 7 selected companies presented their projects to around twenty investors in a formal but favorable environment, leading to €2 million collectively raised in 2002. Similarly, the Novalinc evenings, held monthly in partnership with the Chamber of Commerce and

Industry (CCI) and Grand Lyon, aimed to develop networking opportunities between the video game professionals. As part of the support mission, the "Start Up Force" Club launched in 2001 represented an innovative approach to enterprise-startup collaboration. Tech giants Sun, Oracle, IBM, Bull, Cisco, and France Télécom committed to offer support including free software licenses for qualified startups, technical mentoring by seniors, and preferential rates on their business services [FR153]. After the split and its formalization as an association, Lyon Game continued in the same vein by providing services that served the same objectives. It organized monthly meetings for local developers, facilitated exchanges of best practices between studios, represented the sector to territorial authorities, and developed partnerships with local schools to structure training. The structure initially federated about thirty companies in the sector, mainly development studios from the Infogrames diaspora: Eden Games, Arkane Studios, as well as emerging independent studios like Doki Denki, Pumpkin Effect, and Étranges Libellules. But this number would grow rapidly [FR154].

The association also tackled another mission: cutting-edge professional events dedicated exclusively to the video game sector, of which **Game Connection** is one of the flagship achievements [FR096, FR198, FR199, FR203]. This annual event kept the city on the video game business world map. The first Game Connection was held in Lyon in December 2001, bringing together 27 French developers and 20 international publishers (Sony, Nobilis, Infogrames, Focus, Electronic Arts, Eidos Interactive, Activision). The event progressively became the video game industry's main global business meeting [FR096, FR185]. Game Connection introduced several innovations including short speed-networking formats, a centralized system for managing professional appointments, and the Lyon Game Party, an informal side event. The "Lyon Game Party" gathered 600 to 800 people at each edition, creating an essential moment of community cohesion. These evening events in Lyon's historic venues mixed developers, publishers, journalists, and service providers in a social context that facilitated relationship building beyond immediate commercial transactions. In 2004, Lyon Game launched Game Connection Online, the first permanent online marketplace for the video game industry. This platform included a permanent directory, personal pages to present projects, and a matchmaking and messaging system allowing developers and publishers to meet virtually throughout the year. With this service, the connection and networking mission was thus expanded [FR204, FR205].

In 2002, Lyon Game also organized the "French Connection" at the GDC (Game Developers Conference) in San Jose, allowing several Rhône-Alpes companies to meet American publishers. The "representation" service was no longer operated only at the local level and with public actors but also extended internationally and through renowned international professional trade shows. The association also launched several mutualization initiatives: collective negotiation of booths at international trade shows (GDC, E3), allowing SMEs to access these expensive events; group purchases of software licenses and middleware; sharing of legal expertise on international publishing contracts. The association also targeted professional training. Gamagora, launched in December 2003, represented the first initial university training for video game professions in France, created in partnership with Lyon 2 University [FR093]. The programs included a Master 2 in Programming and Development, a University Diploma in Level Design, and a University Diploma in 3D Infography. Lyon Game also developed territorial lobbying activities, participating in workshops on the future of the video game cluster. The association produced studies on the industry's economic impact (1,200 direct jobs identified in 2003), argued for obtaining specific public funding, and promoted the image of "Lyon, European capital of video games" in national and international media. In 2003, Lyon Game carried out the Digital Worlds project [FR206], a digital city estimated at more than €25 million (including €20.8 million for initial investment and ancillary costs). This project, supposed to embody metropolitan ambition in digital, revealed the structure's limits. With an expected annual operating deficit of €872,000 and an optimistic attendance of 174,930 visitors, the

project quickly appeared oversized for a sector of 1,200 jobs. The external analysis commissioned emphasized the impossibility of mobilizing collective private funding: "a company will have difficulty participating in a project promoting not only itself but also its competition, especially since the sums at stake are likely to be substantial." The project's abandonment marks the limits of collaborative projects that the cluster can support.

Imaginove: The enrichment of collective action and expansion of its scope

Imaginove continued to provide a large majority of the services initially provided by Lyon Game. Nevertheless, the inception of Imaginove in 2005 marked a new stage in structuring the Lyon cluster's collective actions and considerably expanded the cluster's scope of action and critical mass. The collective actions took on a new scope with the integration of the labelling and support of collaborative R&D projects, a novelty in the local sectoral context. During this period, the cluster had developed recognized expertise in supporting companies and in structuring its targeted industries. It also enhanced its capabilities in institutional representation. Thus, the cluster gained legitimacy and resources while maintaining a mixed governance structure, associating private and public actors. The professional training was also developed considerably, with the creation of certified courses in creative project management, production financing, and international development. These training programs, delivered to more than 200 professionals per year, generated their own revenues while strengthening the ecosystem's competencies. The mutualization of technical and human resources also allowed SMEs to access expensive expertise (international legal, intellectual property, technology watch) at affordable rates.

In terms of events and international presence, the cluster extended the existing service offering. Projects like Game Connection Europe in Lyon continued existing even after Lyon Game's disappearance [FR096]. When Lyon Game ceased its activities, a spin-off in the form of a commercial private company was formed and took over organizing Game Connection. The export support program also organized collective participation in major international trade shows (GDC San Francisco, Gamescom Cologne, Tokyo Game Show), mutualizing costs and maximizing regional companies' visibility. Between 10 and 20 companies participated each year in these operations, benefiting from negotiated rates and complete logistical support. The cluster organized and animated collective booths at more than 20 national and international events including CES, MIFA, Siggraph, Game Connection, or Sunny Side of the Doc. This international presence strategy aimed to promote the cluster's members, facilitate access to international markets, and attract foreign investments to the territory.

The cluster also implemented several structuring programs aimed at strengthening the resources and competencies of its members, such as the "Learning Game Factory," a program seeking to standardize serious games' technological building blocks to favour interoperability between publishers and reduce development costs. In terms of collaborative R&D project support, the quantitative results are significant: 175 joint R&D labelled projects since 2007 for a total of €350M (of which 2/3 involving SMEs) as well as 85 projects financed for a total of €130M (FUI, ANR, 2009 & 2010 Serious Game New Uses, Go Innovation/Oseo). 3D Live (2009), a project developing the complete 3D audiovisual chain from capture to distribution, or Garden (2009), a project developing online distribution technologies for the video game industry, are examples of typical projects supported by these processes.

Game Only & Lyon Game Dev: refocusing collective action

Following Imaginove's disappearance, Game Only very quickly took up the role of the main operator of the video game cluster in the region. Other associations were active in this context. Parallel to Game Only, Lyon Game Dev deployed several actions and projects aimed at the studio employee

population [FR170]. They held monthly meetups on the first Thursday of each that typically attract between 30 to 50 participants per event. The Facebook group with its 700 members serves as the main communication platform with daily publications ranging from job opportunities to technical questions. Despite these activities, the association and scope of its actions remain modest compared to Game Only. The annual budget of around €350, dedicated to website hosting costs and event supplies, testifies the organization's modest scale. "Game Only" today operates the local video games cluster in Lyon with more than 130 companies which, together, generates more than 746 million euros in turnover, positioning the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region as the second production stronghold for video games in France after Île-de-France [FR011]. According to the association's activity reports, its mission is articulated by around 4 main axes: (i) export aid and financing, (ii) professional training, (iii) sector representation to official bodies, and (iv) networking and ecosystem animation [FR213, FR214, FR218].

In 2021, Game Only's action plan was structured around four strategic axes with 15 sub-actions:

- The **"Human Resources"** axis develops an intranet profile platform, QWL (Quality of Work Life) initiatives, facilitates school-business dialogue, and manages the Diversity Grant program.
- The **"Export/BizDev"** axis organizes international promotion (PDI), learning expeditions, and the Game Finance Summit.
- The **"Animation"** axis coordinates technical workshops, professional training sessions, afterwork events, and BizDev lunches.
- The **"Financing"** axis includes an incubator program, a mentoring system, as well as networking facilitation axes and executive training programs.

The activities implemented by Game Only reflect the strategic will for sectoral refocusing. The missions of information sharing, networking and connection, local ecosystem animation, and support in resources and competencies to members were preserved, but the adopted formats and programs evolved. Similarly, the association engaged in several collaborative projects with other regional associations operating the animation of video game clusters in other territories. Thus, we distinguish (i) projects directly piloted by Game Only, such as the Let's Go incubator and the HR Club [FR216, FR217], from (ii) projects with national scope like JYROS [FR161, FR171] and Video Game Ambition [FR174]. These axes drove all activities deployed by Game Only thereafter. The following chronology summarizes major actions:

Year	Action	Type	Impact
2019	Game Only creation	Foundation	Imaginove succession
2021	Let's Go launch	Incubator	4 cohorts to date
2021	QWL approach	CSR	First in France for video game sector
2021	JYROS launch	Environment	Via National Consortium
2022	HR Club creation	CSR	18 participating studios
2023	JV Ambition Diagnosis	Training	National needs analysis
2024	Bertie Training	Training	Response to diagnosis
2024	Gamescom Stand	Export	22 studios on mutualized stand
2025	JYROS approved by CNC	Environment	Eco-conditionality for aid

Table 73 - Main collective activities

9.4.2 The architecture and typology of collective actions in Lyon Cluster

The specialized activities of Game Only by pillar

Pillar 1: Support for training and human resources management: Game Only's HR actions include structuring the sector on training and human resources issues, as well as organizing a HR Club dedicated to the local professionals for experience sharing, inspiration, and relationship building. The club offers friendly meetings to strengthen ties and share best practices [FR011, FR037]. It promotes recruitment of mutualization (common job boards), actions for diversity, and senior talent management. From 2021, the association focused on QWL (Quality of Work Life) issues, an increasingly present concern for the entire sector. Game Only acts also as a main representative of the local video game companies in negotiation and dialogues with official organizations such as Pôle Emploi and OPCAs and FAFIEC. They work hand in hand to enhance employment and training conditions in the industry locally. Similarly, it helps schools adapt their training content to the real needs of video game industry professionals.

Pillar 2: Export aid and business development: Game Only provides support for export and business development through a main mechanism: the "International Development Plan" (PDI), which facilitates participation in collective missions and travel to international trade shows as well as networking and connection with foreign publishers and partners [FR011]. Game Only acts first through direct aid and subsidies to its members, covering part of their participation costs, but also by organizing common booths on behalf of the region and mutualizing communication efforts. Cost reductions, of the order of 60 to 70% for members, are quite significant. For example, in 2025, three missions were carried out: a collective PDI mission as part of the annual Nordic Games conference (May 20-23, 2025, Malmö), participation in MIFA (June 10-13, 2025, Annecy): International Animation Film Market, eligible for PDI, and a mutualized stand at Gamescom (August 20-24, 2025, Cologne). The association actively promotes its region's talents and expertise and also seeks to attract international partners and investors to its territory.

Pillar 3: Territorial animation and community: Local ecosystem animation has been among the first collective actions implemented within the cluster since its emergence. The association uses various formats as detailed in the table below. Some actions are regular and organized periodically. Others are more occasional.

Action	Description	2024 Metrics
Professional Slack	Internal exchange platform	450+ member contacts
Masterclasses & Workshops	Thematic webinars (every 6 weeks) and professional workshops adapted to needs. Partner interventions on financing, legal, HR, technical, export. Replays on Youtube	25 total sessions, ~30 participants/session, 750 participations, varied themes
Newsletter & Social Media	Communication and information sharing	Bi-monthly
Shared Google Drive	Mutualized resources (standard contracts, TOS, NDAs)	Access for all members
Crealab Afterwork	Thematic professional meetings	Ex: September 25, 2025 in Lyon

Table 74 - Main tools and activities for "Animation" pillar

Pillar 4: "Financing": In terms of financing, the association intervenes both (i) to support its members in their funding search efforts and (ii) serves as a redistributor of certain public funds. The association also enabled the creation of an economic aid and recovery fund supporting the creation of original games at the development, pre-production, and prototyping stage. The following table details some of the main activities supporting the "financing" activity.

Action	Description	Impact
Application support	CNC review committee	Improved success rate
Institutional representation	Protection of interests with public organizations	Regional and national level
Financing webinars	Training on aid mechanisms	Every 6 weeks
Networking	Connection with competent institutions	Continuous

Table 75 - Main tools and activities for "Financing" pillar

Among the mechanisms provided by Game Only there is a prototyping aid, a production aid (€150k max) from the AURA region [FR071], the FAJV mechanism (writing, €6k; pre-production, €60k; Production, 50% expenses) and the CIJV mechanism (Tax credit 30% of expenses with a ceiling of €6M/year) developed by the CNC [FR043].

The multi-pillar projects of Game Only

Game Only also launched several complex projects that serve all the pillars and axes presented above. Some projects are piloted by Game Only and target only the local ecosystem whereas others are co-piloted with regional professional associations operating in other territories. These inter-cluster projects target the entire sector at the national level. The table below lists several of these flagship projects.

Project	Partners	Description
JYROS	National JV Environment Consortium and CNC approval (2025)	Environmental impact calculator
National Consortium	8 regional associations	National sector coordination
Bertie Training	Capital Games (IDF)	JV/animation training organization
Video Game Ambition	Multiple	Diversity, inclusion, student scholarships

Table 76 - National actions & collaborative projects

One of the flagship projects is "Let's Go Incubator" [FR216, FR217]. Established in 2021, this intensive entrepreneurial support program aims to support independent video game studio creators in building their company and developing their first video game over a 12-month period. The program targets entrepreneurs and creators of independent video game studios or those at the beginning of the creation process in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region. It offers personalized and collective support focused on the specific challenges of the video game industry, including financing, game design and business development. The proposed support relies on several formats: individualized support and monitoring by experienced mentors from the association members, collective training and workshops on key themes, networking and professional immersion opportunities within the video game ecosystem (studio visits, participation in trade shows...).

In addition to this program, Game Only annually organizes a series of events, as detailed in the table above, which covers several themes and is not limited to simple networking. These events through workshops, panels, exchanges of best practices, or professional intermediation provide support to the members including recruitment aid, training, professionalization, sharing of critical information, or help accessing new markets and business development.

Event	Frequency	Description	2025 Example
General Assembly	Annual	Review, account validation, networking	Date to confirm
GO Day	Annual	Professional conference day	May 6 - Fourvière Hotel Lyon
Afterworks	Regular	Informal professional exchanges	September 25 - Crealab Lyon
Profession Meet-up	New 2024	Round tables by profession	Variable dates
Summer Party	July	Summer cohesion event	July 1 - Lyon
Winter Party	December	Winter cohesion event	December 11 - Lyon
Game On	Occasional	Annual employment and training fair in partnership with "France Travail" and other organizations	To come

Table 77 - Typical annual calendar

The Lyon cluster through Game Only has engaged in several collaborative projects with other entities (public, associative, and private) at the regional and national levels. Three flagship projects have been deployed.

National projects and inter-cluster collaboration

The **Bertie program** [FR177], a professional training centre dedicated to video games and animation, represents an interesting case of mutualization. It was jointly developed in 2024 with Capital Games [FR087] (Île-de-France) following the conclusions of the Skills and Future Professions Diagnosis (HJVDIAG) carried out in 2023 on behalf of ANR (National Research Agency) as part of the France 2030 plan [FR099]. The diagnosis revealed a shortage of professional training programs specialized in the video game sector in France [FR045]. Bertie program is supported by the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region as part of the "Bottom-up Innovation Aid" action of the regionalized France 2030 Program [FR092], operated by Caisse des Dépôts & Consignations Group. Companies can benefit from subsidies from the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region up to 50% for employees of video game companies domiciled in the region. The program presents several particularities including the "by professionals, for professionals" approach, where training content is co-constructed with beneficiaries [FR071]. Trainers are senior profiles, with significant experience in the video game and animation sectors. A board of directors' pilots the strategy and investments, while a validation committee, also bringing together representatives from OPCOs (ATLAS and AFDAS) as well as the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region, ensures that training aligns with professionals' real expectations.

Jyros is also an inter-organizational project mutualized with other French clusters operating in the video games industry [FR043, FR171]. This environmental footprint calculator is a pioneering tool and a world first. The global video game sector emits 37 million tons of CO2 equivalent per year, hence the importance of this tool to engage in the environmental transition of the entire industry [FR165]. Jyros [FR159] calculates the total carbon footprint of a video game company on the 3 legal GHG assessment scopes according to European standards. It also evaluates the impact on water and

mining resources, making it the most comprehensive calculator available to date for the industry. JYROS was launched in 2021 by the National Video Game Consortium for the Environment and on the initiative of Game Only association. The Lyon association played a driving role in this environmental innovation. The project was developed thanks to the involvement of 27 pilot companies from all over France, representative of the environment's diversity, who tested the tool and participated in its improvement. Among them are several Lyon studios like Gameleon Studio [FR036], Artefacts Studio, and Old Skull Games, as well as Bordeaux studios like Asobo Studio and Shiro Games [FR163]. The operation is supported by the French public organizations as part of the "Supporting green alternatives in culture" scheme of the cultural and creative industries (ICC) in France 2030 plan [FR092] operated by the Caisse des Dépôts. The tool is entirely free, making it accessible to all studios, regardless of their size or resources. According to 2024 metrics, nearly 600 people and 200 video game companies already use it. Since March 1, 2025, the CNC mandatorily requires two carbon assessments (provisional and final) for all new production aid requests [FR164]. Jyros is one of the tools approved by the CNC for these assessments [FR043, FR166].

Ambition Jeu vidéo (Video Game Ambition) [FR168, FR169] is another collective action organized in the inter-cluster context. This "subsidiary" association of Game Only was founded following an important observation: the lack of social and gender diversity among video game professionals. Women represent only slightly more than 20% of the profession's workforce, while more than 50% of players worldwide are women, hence the importance of this initiative. The association aims to promote diversity, equality, and social and professional inclusion of 15-25 year-olds in the French video game industry [FR174]. This initiative operates at two levels, nationally and regionally. The national "Ambition Jeu vidéo" diagnosis was officially presented in May 2023, the result of collaboration by the National Video Game Consortium comprising eight regional associations and the SNJV [FR176]. Regional associations have local equivalents including "Video Game Ambition Île-de-France" created by Capital Games [FR087] and "Video Game Ambition Nouvelle-Aquitaine" by SO-Games [FR176]. Video Game Ambition regularly organizes educational training by regional industry professionals in middle and high schools. These meetings allow instructive exchanges about the different professions involved in the stages of video game design. **"The Video Game Scholarship"**, awarded on social and academic excellence criteria, is one of "Video Game Ambition" flagship achievements which helps young talents who struggle to finance their video game studies. Similarly, the association carries out **innovative charity events** like Tour d'Horizon [FR175], a 13-hour charity stream on Twitch to raise funds for diversity and gender balance in the video game sector in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes [FR174].

9.4.3 Motivations and contributions of key stakeholders

The Lyon cluster generates differentiated value propositions across its diverse membership, from solo developers to international subsidiaries, with Game Only's sophisticated service portfolio attempting to balance varied needs. D4.1's stakeholder analysis revealed how benefit distribution creates both strong loyalty and emerging tensions. The synthesis captures these value creation patterns:

D4.1 findings	Description
Small Studio Empowerment	Access to resources typically requiring 50+ employee companies: international trade shows, legal services, strategic consulting.
Mid-Size Studio Acceleration	Talent pipeline access through school partnerships provides competitive advantage. International market entry support through PDI program. Collective bargaining for software licenses achieves 20-40% discounts. Network effects facilitate co-production opportunities.

Large Studio Ecosystem Benefits	Regional attractiveness for recruitment enhanced by cluster reputation. CSR demonstration through association participation. Access to innovation networks and R&D partnerships.
Educational Institution Integration	Direct industry feedback shapes curriculum development. Internship placement networks ensure graduate employment (85% rate). Research collaboration opportunities through cluster R&D initiatives. Equipment and software access through industry partnerships enhances training quality.
Public Authority Returns	Economic impact of €746 million revenue and 5,000+ jobs justifies public investment. International visibility enhances regional attractiveness for tech companies. Structured interlocutor simplifies policy implementation. Success metrics demonstrate return on France 2030 program investment.

Table 78 - Summary of D4.1. on the motivations and contributions of Lyon cluster's stakeholders

The documentary analysis led us to identify several primary motivations and advantages common to all these stakeholders. In addition to the various collective actions detailed above, the **organization within a formal professional association** that was established from the cluster's emergence offers an institutional existence to an industry that remains atomized, thus transforming isolated companies into a recognized economic sector. Formal groupings facilitated access to decision-makers and opened doors to ministries, regional directorates, and large groups normally inaccessible to SMEs and VSEs. Mutualization strengthened the negotiating powers and allowed these atomized structures to collectively weigh in public decisions with a unified voice rather than dispersed and contradictory requests. Mutualization also occurred at the cost level (trade shows, training, services). Mutualized resources (sharing rooms, equipment, skills, and contacts...) allowed operational cost reductions reaching up to 30-40% for members. In this sense, the cluster acts as a collective intelligence unit by facilitating the circulation of strategic information (calls for tenders, trends, opportunities) and the sharing of knowledge and practices among its members. Mutualization extends also to more subtle aspects. The professional association acts as a territorial showcase and improves its visibility and attractiveness for investors, talents, and local and international media.

The counterparts to all these benefits and advantages are multiple and seem to depend on several variables. Nevertheless, a basic minimum of commitment, essentially in the form of membership fees, is required. Minimal participation in the main coordination and decision-making bodies of the formal association is also required. Several risks and tensions can threaten this balance between contributions and collective benefits. First, financing collective actions and the sustainability of these financing mechanisms seems difficult to maintain given the uncertainty weighing on the operating subsidies and sometimes time-consuming services that weigh on the association's operational team. Encouraging voluntary member engagement in collective actions - sometimes time-consuming and without immediate returns - is a constant challenge. The same applies to measuring the impacts of collective actions and the difficulties in quantifying the real benefits of actions to justify members' investment. The documentary analysis also made it possible to develop a differentiated matrix of key stakeholder motivations in the Lyon cluster according to the nature of their activities. These actors' motivations but also their contributions to the cluster reflect both specific local issues to the cluster but also national issues and a-territorial aspects linked to the industry.

DEVELOPERS / STUDIOS	
Primary Motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating access to publishers and distributors • Identifying funding opportunities for new products • Having international visibility and access to international markets • Reducing market entry barriers (contacts, reputation, costs)
Key Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privileged access to face-to-face meetings with decision-makers and publishers • Reduced transaction costs and mutualization of international trade show participation fees • Strengthening credibility and legitimacy via cluster membership • Knowledge spillovers, informal learning through experience and best practice exchanges between member studios
Main Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees (€2-4K/event) and direct financial participation to access cluster services • Indirect participation via production of innovative games and intellectual properties that improve the ecosystem's economic value • Contribution in terms of creativity and technical experimentation that maintains cluster competitiveness and attractiveness • Community participation and active engagement in events, mentoring of young studios and expertise sharing that strengthen the collective fabric
Tensions /Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership and participation fees can represent a significant burden for small studios in the first development phase
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arkane: values its Lyon historical anchoring from Infogrames and capitalizes on international prestige of its franchises (Dishonored, Deathloop) • Ivory Tower: seeks cost optimization compared to Paris while exploiting local historical expertise in racing games • Eden Games: struggles to survive after Infogrames' collapse by specializing in the profitable racing game niche • Old Skull: young independent studio simultaneously seeking economic growth and professional recognition within the ecosystem

Table 79 - Motivations & contributions for developers & studios

PUBLISHERS	
Primary Motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient project sourcing and rapid, organized access to numerous potential game projects • Optimized access to talents and skilled professionals
Key Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of adhoc pre-selection of quality projects and knowledge of a territory's entire production via events, • Optimizing business development teams' time and substantial savings on prospecting costs • Identification of relevant talents and HR • Inclusion of publishers' interests in lobbying dialogues with local institutions
Main Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial resources via membership fees • Investment possibilities in local games and their subsequent distribution • Involuntary spillovers in terms of practices and knowledge • Improving industry credibility and strengthening cluster's international reputation
Tensions /Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited engagement at regional level, especially for subsidiaries of large international groups • Minimal financial contribution and reduced participation in event costs while extracting the main value

Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubisoft: Exploits the talent pool trained at Infogrames to feed its 400+ person studio without training costs • Microsoft/Bethesda: Acquisition strategy of innovative studios like Arkane to secure differentiating creative franchises • Access to game Connection (first editions): publishers pay only €250-400 to access over 25 carefully selected projects, exceptional return on investment
-----------------	---

Table 80 - Motivations & contributions for publishers

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	
Primary Motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industrial alignment and ensuring their programs match skills sought by studios • Graduates' employment and improving professional insertion rate • Partnership opportunities with industry players for applied research projects • Building positive reputation and strengthening their program attractiveness
Key Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct access to internship and job offers from member studios, • Curriculum validation via professional feedback and continuous adjustment of their programs to sector's technological and creative evolutions • Industrial partnerships and formalized collaborations including professional interventions and supervised projects • Student project feedback and direct evaluation of student work by professionals
Main Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talent pipeline (average of 400+ students/year) and annual training of a critical mass of young professionals to fuel territorial growth • Development of R&D projects (AI, virtual reality) that benefit the entire ecosystem • Provision of equipment and workspaces for cluster events by certain schools
Tensions. /Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mismatch between academic pace (school years, grading) and industrial production realities (deadlines, profitability)
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaming Campus: aims for national leadership with 400 students/year and capitalizes on 80% insertion rate to justify premium tuition fees • Game Sup: a small school betting on artisanal quality and personalized support to survive against giant Gaming Campus • Ynov: exploits synergies between its different digital programs and national presence to offer attractive inter-campus mobility
PUBLIC AUTHORITIES	
Primary Motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic development and diversification of local economic fabric by supporting a high value-added industry with significant tax returns • Creating qualified and well-paid jobs (€35-45K average) and retaining young graduates • Strengthening territorial attractiveness via the industry's innovative image • Developing an innovative ecosystem with spillovers on the digital economy
Key Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax revenue growth via corporate taxes and local taxes • Employment statistics (2500+ direct jobs created) • International visibility • Improved cluster reputation and its association with innovative industries
Main Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding and direct subsidies to associations and studios • Political legitimacy and official support from authorities that facilitates relations with private partners and investors • Provision of premises, incubators and public equipment that reduces companies' installation costs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory support, administrative facilitation, national lobbying for video game tax credit and adaptation of local urban planning rules
Tensions /Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROI pressure and obligation to demonstrate tangible return on public funds • Political cycles and majority changes every 6 years that can question long-term support strategies • Post-Infogrames and post-Imaginove risk aversion and caution of elected officials about massive investments in the industry
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AURA Region: invests €800k with excellent return (€746M generated revenue) • City of Lyon: Capitalizes on "smart city" image and uses Infogrames' iconic barges as symbol of successful creative reconversion • CNC: Extends its intervention perimeter from cinema to video games to strengthen French cultural soft power • Lyon Metropolis: Remarkable absence of funding (€0) illustrating political tensions and certain institutions' risk aversion
SERVICE PROVIDERS	
Primary Motivations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeking network and scale effects with optimized market access • Specialization opportunities and development of valuable and differentiating niche expertise (motion capture, localization, gaming audio) • Seeking concentration advantages and geographical proximity with studios
Key Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cluster membership gives access to 130+ member companies representing as potential clients geographically concentrated • Industry intelligence and ability to better anticipate technological evolutions and adapt service offering accordingly • Partnership opportunities via cluster events • Reputation building and commercial referencing valuable
Main Contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise and provision of specialized skills (servers, AI, blockchain) that studios cannot develop internally due to lack of critical size or strategic disinterest • Provision of essential services (legal, accounting, HR) allowing studios to focus on their creative core business • Sponsoring and financing of cluster events • Investment in collaborative R&D projects that benefit the entire ecosystem
Tensions /Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sectoral specialization creates vulnerability in case of video game crisis, with few reconversions alternatives
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Start Up Force Club: IBM, Bull and Oracle offer preferential rates to cluster startups to create profitable long-term technological dependency • Criterion: British studio sponsoring first Game Connection (2001) to early identify French talents to recruit or acquire • Local service providers: Small service companies mutualizing their offers via Game Only to reach critical size against large groups

Table 81 - Motivations & contributions for education institutions, public authorities and service providers

9.4.4 Networks and collaboration models in Lyon cluster

The documentary analysis highlighted a complex architecture of formal institutional links coupled with a rich structure of informal links prevailing in Lyon video game cluster. Similarly, the singular trajectory of the cluster's evolution unveils a sophistication of the collaborative models moving from informal links inherited from a common history to complex institutional architectures, then to inter-territorial strategic alliances. These formal and informal networks were transformed, and

continuously reconfigured over four decades, revealing a meta-organizational capacity to maintain different proximity while adapting to sectoral and territorial changes. The history of these collaborations is not linear but was punctuated by different movements of expansion and contraction, formalization and come backs to informal links, intersectoral opening and specialized refocusing. Each period reveals a specific configuration of proximity links - geographical, organizational, institutional, cognitive, and social - that determine the nature and effectiveness of collaborations.

The Infogrames heritage (1983-2002): The matrix of original proximities

The first foundations of the cluster's relational network were woven thanks to Infogrames. The shared technical know-how and creative culture provided the foundation for building future collaborations within the cluster. More than 2,000 employees passed through the company between 1983 and 2002. This experience allowed them to create common references, similar working methods, shared production standards, and mutual understanding of technical and creative challenges which consolidated cognitive proximity in this pool of professionals. The Infogrames heritage is also manifest in the dense interpersonal networks that were woven through common projects, internal mobility between teams, and the different moments of informal socialization. These repeated interactions created relational networks that survived the company itself. In addition to their density, these informal links bring fluidity in exchanges and communication. They facilitate building trust relationships and developing mutual aid. The concentration of Infogrames activities in Villeurbanne, then in the Vaise barges, left its mark on the cluster's geographical development thereafter. The importance of this initial geographical proximity would only fully reveal itself after Infogrames' collapse. The 200+ studios created by former employees remain mostly established in the Lyon area, perpetuating this inherited geographical density.

Progressive formalization (2001-2005): From Lyon Infocité to Lyon Game

The creation of the Video Game club within Lyon Infocité in 1996 was the first initiative to formalize existing collaborative networks [FR173, FR196, FR198, FR199, FR201, FR202, FR203, FR204]. The association offered a formal framework that transformed informal meetings and exchanges into formal memberships and organized services (Monthly Traboules de l'Information, the Start-Up Force Club, and the Informalic newsletter). The emergence of Lyon Game (2001-2005) within Lyon Infocité marked a specialization of collaboration around video games and an awareness of the strategic proximity between different local VSEs (Very Small Enterprises) and SMEs active in the video game sector as well as proximity with institutional and public actors operating in the sector [FR203, FR204, FR205]. This period saw a densification of formal and informal networks. The proximities were reinforced. Projects and achievements like Game Connection or thematic working groups provided collaboration spaces allowing experience sharing and co-construction of mutualized solutions to common problems.

Institutional expansion (2005-2018): Imaginove and the reconfiguration of proximities

The transformation into the Imaginove competitiveness cluster in 2005 induced a major reconfiguration of the collaboration networks. The integration of animation and cinema into the cluster's perimeter diluted the initial cognitive proximity and strategic proximity born from the communities in strategic destiny and issues facing video game companies but reinforced the institutional proximity. Video game developers now had to collaborate with animation filmmakers and audiovisual producers who had different technical cultures, economic models, and creative references. This diversification generated ambivalent effects. It was supposed to facilitate access to new skills (cinematographic narration, animation techniques). But it diluted the different proximities between the key local stakeholders.

Imaginove introduced new categories of players into the collaboration networks underlying the cluster. The integration of research laboratories heightened institutional proximity. LIRIS (computer graphics), LIP (parallel computing) and GRAME (sound creation) became partners in R&D projects. This university-business collaboration, formalized via CIFRE agreements and ANR projects, created a new form of cognitive proximity based on scientific research rather than creative production. The role of public institutions shifted from distant funders to that of involved partners. The representatives of these institutions were involved in the cluster's governance bodies, participated in working groups, and contributed to co-construct collective strategies. This institutional proximity heightened the collaboration but generated bureaucratic heaviness.

Imaginove enriched the complex collaborative architecture at several levels:

- **Strategic level:** The Board of Directors brought together companies, academics, and institutions in tripartite governance. Strategic decisions emerged from complex negotiations navigating economic, scientific, and political logic.
- **Operational level:** The labelled collaborative projects (€350M over 14 years) created formal consortiums with detailed legal agreements, intellectual property sharing, and monitoring milestones. This extreme formalization generated legal security but also rigidity.
- **Animation level:** Different thematic groups, user clubs, technical workshops maintained a continuous animation of the cluster.

Paradoxically, Imaginove's institutional sophistication seems to have weakened the informal networks that were the cluster's strength. The increased bureaucratization of relationships and the sectoral heterogeneity made informal exchanges between professionals more thus compromising the mobilization of trust and the spontaneous informal norms of solidarity.

Refocusing and expansion (2019-2025): Game Only and the new collaborative configurations

Game Only's creation in 2019 marked a deliberate return to sectoral specialization which immediately restored the diluted cognitive and strategic proximity. This "back to basics" didn't mean going backward but rather a sophisticated reconfiguration with streamlined governance via a simple associative structure and an agile decision-making process [FR213, FR214, FR218]. The renewed proximity between the cluster members facilitated the development of specialized services more aligned with the critical needs of the video game industry. Animation was also better tailored to the industry's needs. The "Game Only" phase involved the development of new forms of collaborations at the inter-cluster level with unprecedented initiatives in the French sector's history such as the Bertie program with Capital Games (Île-de-France), synergies with SO Games (Nouvelle-Aquitaine) on international or local trade shows like Horizons Bordeaux, or synergies with Game-IN (Hauts-de-France) and the mobilization to organize the Game Camp trade show. Proximity links are reconfigured, and so are collaboration networks that develop into a sophisticated multi-scale relational architecture detailed in the following table.

Level of proximities formation	Dynamics of proximity reconfiguration
Local level (Lyon-Villeurbanne)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Maintenance of historic geographical density (75% of members) -Organization of free regular meetups perpetuating the tradition of informal socialization -Spontaneous mutual aid between neighbouring studios (equipment lending, skill exchange)
Regional level (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Progressive integration of studios from Grenoble, Annecy, Clermont-Ferrand -Creation of secondary "hubs" with local relays

	-Deconcentrated services via videoconference and regular travel
National level	-Active participation in national bodies (SNJV, SELL) -Co-construction of common positions on regulatory issues -Coordinated lobbying for video game tax credit
International level	-Maintenance of Game Connection network (became independent but still linked to Lyon) -Grouped participation in trade shows (Gamescom, GDC) -Twinning with European clusters (Montreal, Malmö, Barcelona)

Table 82 - Dynamics of proximities reconfiguration

During this latest evolution, the reconfiguration of inter-organizational collaboration includes integration of new themes like Quality of Work Life (QWL), human resources management (HR Club), and support for innovative entrepreneurship (Let's Go Incubator). Studios that successfully obtained CNC or European funding train those who are starting. This peer-to-peer mentoring, formalized in workshops but also informal in daily exchanges, illustrates the cluster's collaborative maturity. Similarly, open mutual aid on sensitive subjects like HR management testifies the existence of inter-organizational trust links and their prevalence in the cluster.

9.5 Mobilized Resources and Competencies

The Lyon cluster's governance model represents France's most sophisticated regional video game organization, with resources and structural capacity exceeding many national-level entities. D4.1's institutional analysis revealed how significant public investment enabled professional capabilities while creating accountability complexities. The following synthesis captures organizational architecture:

D4.1 findings	Description
Financial Resources	€3.3 million annual budget (2025) makes Game Only France's best-funded regional association. Funding mix: 60% public (Region, Metropole, France 2030), 25% membership fees (€200-5,000 based on revenue), 15% service revenue. €1.9 million managed for collective training demonstrates financial management sophistication.
Human Resources	14 permanent staff organized in specialized departments. This professionalization enables service delivery comparable to private consulting firms while maintaining associative governance.
Governance Architecture	Board of Directors with 12-15 members elected for 3-year terms, ensuring studio size diversity. Strategic Committee includes public funders with advisory roles. Working groups on specific topics (EdTech, Sustainability, International) enable member participation. General Assembly of 130+ members maintain democratic oversight.
Infrastructure Assets	Physical office space in Lyon providing meeting facilities and co-working options. Digital infrastructure including professional Slack workspace, CRM system, project management tools. Shared equipment pool for events and demonstrations.
Accountability Mechanisms	Quarterly reporting to public funders with KPIs on job creation, revenue growth, international development. Annual external audit ensures financial compliance. Member satisfaction surveys (85% approval 2024) validate service relevance. Transparent communication through monthly newsletters and open board meeting minutes.

Table 83 - Summary of D4.1. on the resources, competencies and governance of Lyon cluster

9.5.1 Financial aspects & business model

The analysis of the financial model underpinning the cluster reveals a fundamental transformation in resource mobilization strategies as well as various evolutions resulting from the collective diversification strategies pursued by the cluster and the adaptation measures to different crises.

Phase 1: Lyon Infocité (1999-2003) - The subsidized model and the beginning of diversification

During the initial post-2001 crisis phase of informal structuring, the collective action essentially relied on volunteerism and the own resources of the cluster's first founding members. Organization, even in club form, within Lyon Infocité allowed for gathering the first indirect financing and relying on public funding for crystallizing collective action. Lyon Infocité, the first structured attempt to federate Lyon's digital actors, experienced significant success and rapid growth in membership [From 40 members in May 1999 to 105 in May 2000) but also in the public funds that were negotiated and leveraged [FR173]. The significant progression of the institutional support experienced during this period reflects the structure's progressive institutionalization and its recognition as a key factor in territorial development. Starting in 2001, Lyon Infocité developed a diversification strategy with six distinct revenue sources. Memberships represented 10% of the budget. Study services accounted for 6%, illustrating the association's nascent capacity to valorise its expertise. Events generated 13% of revenues, demonstrating the success of developed formats. The Start Up Force Club, a major innovation of the period, contributed 10%, mobilizing large technology companies to serve startups. Various services completed the budget at 13%, including training and matchmaking services. Nevertheless, detailed analysis of the 2001 budget reveals a funding structure still heavily dependent on public subsidies, which represented 54% of total resources.

Phase 2: Lyon Game (2001-2005) - The diversification and search for self-financing mechanisms

Collective action funding underwent several transformations with the transition to Lyon Game and the launch of Game Connection [FR203, FR204, FR205]. Work on business model sustainability and independence from subsidies and public support manifested early in the cluster's life from the first diversification of the collective activity portfolio in 2003-2004 and the success of the Game Connection model. The emergence of Game Connection in October 2001 marked a conceptual break in collective action financing. Game Connection emerged as Lyon Game's most visible and profitable initiative. The economic model quickly proved viable. Developers progressively paid their participation [Free in 2001, then 2,000 euros in 2002, up to 4,000 euros planned for 2005), while publishers only paid symbolic fees (250-400 euros). This asymmetry guarantees decision-makers' presence while ensuring revenues. Public funding went from 100% (47,000 euros) in 2001 to 30% in 2002, 8% in 2003, with a total disappearance planned for 2005. Sponsors also saw their contribution evolve spectacularly, from 2,500 euros initially to 20,000 euros in 2005, testifying to Game Connection brand's growing value [FR198, FR199, FR205]. Lyon Game's operating budget, distinct from Game Connection's, initially relied on member contributions (approximately 500 to 2,000 euros depending on size) and subsidies from Grand Lyon and the General Council. Subsequently, Lyon Game's global budget experienced significant growth during this period. In 2001-2002, the association managed an annual budget of approximately 100,000 to 150,000 euros [FR203, FR204, FR205]. Starting in 2003, with Game Connection's growing success (180 participants in 2002, generating a first profit margin of 60,000 euros), Lyon Game envisioned structural transformation and notably creating a commercial subsidiary to manage Game Connection, with an intellectual property concession from Lyon Game/Lyon Infocité. This structure would allow international expansion (7 events in 5 countries planned) while preserving the parent structure's associative status. Human resources evolved accordingly: from 2 volunteer/compensated founders in 2001,

Lyon Game grew to 2 employees in 2003, then 4 permanent staff beginning 2004, including two native English speakers to manage internationalization [FR205].

Lyon Game's final year was marked by the merger negotiations with other local associations to create Imaginove. During this period, the economic model was stabilized around 400,000 to 500,000 euros annual budget, divided between:

- 40% public subsidies (Grand Lyon, Rhône-Alpes Region)
- 30% Game Connection revenues (license and profit sharing)
- 20% member contributions (approximately 50 companies at 1,500 euros average)
- 10% various services (studies, consulting, mutualized services)

Phase 3: Imaginove (2003-2019) - The institutionalized cluster model

The transition to Imaginove brought diversification and stabilization in funding sources. The competitiveness cluster channelled significant resources, supporting several labelled R&D projects and numerous commercial development initiatives [FR128, FR209]. The public support was designed to catalyse rather than replace private investment.

Imaginove's economic model rested on a balance between four main funding sources:

- Structural regional subsidies from the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region and Lyon Metropolis constituted the funding foundation, representing approximately 40% of the total budget. These funds, sustainable and multi-year, secured the cluster's general interest missions: territorial animation, collective representation, strategic monitoring.
- Member contributions formed in the second pillar, contributing 25-30% of the budget. With several hundred members paying annual contributions ranging from 500 to 5,000 euros depending on their size. This base provides recurring and predictable revenues.
- Service provision (individual support, sectoral studies, training) generated approximately 20% of revenues, valorising the cluster's accumulated expertise.
- Event organization and European project management completed the budget at 10-15%, bringing complementary resources and international visibility.

Thus, during this period the balanced economic model was stable, with an estimated mix of 40% public funding and 60% private resources. This distribution allowed maintaining general interest missions while developing a market service offering. The diversification in revenue sources ensures resilience against budgetary uncertainties.

Phase 4: Game Only (2019-2025) - The financial maturity and the hybridization in funding

Game Only's funding model followed a deliberate strategy aiming for self-financing [FR213, FR214, FR218]. The association has built a diversified economic model combining several revenue sources. The 800,000-euro regional fund it manages induced some stability. Thus, the economic model of the association relies on several funding sources:

- Public subsidies (State, Region, local authorities) [[FR060](#)]
- Member contributions
- Service provision
- Success fees on labelled projects

The current model is more mature with public subsidies, now targeted at specific projects rather than structural operations, representing only about 35% of resources. The projects include The BERTIE training program co-created with Capital Games, the HR Club gathering 18 studios with its legal hotline in partnership with HR Company, and QWL support services involving more than 30 regional studios. Self-financing becomes the main source of revenue through high value-added service offering, targeting particular members' needs. This evolution toward financial autonomy guarantees the cluster's strategic independence and its capacity to adapt to market evolution. Game Only's 2021 membership fee structure also reveals progressive pricing based on company revenue, ranging from 100 euros for companies with less than 50,000 euros in revenue to 4,900 euros for those over 50 million euros [FR213, FR214, FR218]. This model balances accessibility for small studios with substantial contributions from major actors.

Company Revenue & fees	2019 Fee	2020 Fee	2021 Fee
<€50K	€100	€100	€100
<€150K	€300	€300	€250
<€500K	€400	€400	€500
<€1M	€600	€600	€1,000
<€2M	€1,000	€1,000	€1,600
<€10M	€1,500	€1,500	€3,500
>€50M	€4,000	€4,000	€4,900

Table 84 - Game Only membership fee structure (2021)

The diversification, combined with the fees and contributions from its 131 members (divided between Active Members and Partner Members), allows the association to maintain a permanent team of 8 people while developing ambitious initiatives like the JYROS tool.

9.5.2 The evolution of the cluster's resources and competencies

The Infogrames era (1983-2002): Building foundational capital

The Infogrames period provided a foundational base of resources that subsequently facilitated the development of the local video game ecosystem. During almost two decades, in the 80s-90s, the company accumulated considerable resources that would durably irrigate the territory.

Human capital and the qualified workforce pool constitute one of the most important legacies with trained professionals in video game development skills - developers, artists, project managers. With cutting-edge technical expertise: mastery of emerging 3D technologies, development of proprietary engines, production management, these resources are necessary to produce successful AAA international games like "Alone in the Dark" or the "V-Rally" franchise [FR100]. As the company excelled at vertical integration, combining development, publishing and distribution, the professionals it trained mastered the entire value chain. The company allowed many skilled talents to enhance their competencies in managing international projects, coordinating teams across several continents, negotiating with international license holders, global marketing, etc.

Infogrames also facilitated the development of different forms of proximity detailed above. Cognitive and social proximities between a significant set of video game professionals who would choose to start their own companies and development studios are strategic resources that would become a foundation for mounting different collective actions later.

Certain symbolic intangible assets like Lyon's brand image as a European capital of digital entertainment or international visibility are also Infogrames' legacy. Even after the company collapse, this symbolic heritage continues to attract talents and investments.

Infogrames' international project management would have repercussions both on local human resources' expertise level and on these intangible assets. At its peak, the company coordinated teams spread across several continents, negotiated with Hollywood license holders, and marketed its products in all global markets. This early exposure to globalization forged a culture of international openness that persists in the current ecosystem.

Infogrames' resource heritage is also present in the independent structures formed as spin-offs in the wake of the double local sectoral crisis and Infogrames crisis.

Reconstruction through collective action (2001-2003): Lyon Game and Lyon Infocité

The post-crisis period saw a rapid mobilization of existing resources - relational, cognitive, institutional, and symbolic. Lyon Infocité and its Video Game club became the receptacle of intense collective mobilization, transforming the crisis into restructuring opportunity [FR203, FR198, FR205]. The collective activities that were developed have laid the foundations for important meta-organizational competencies at the cluster level. This phase also showed the interest of formal professional associations as a collective action framework. The very existence of a professional association like Lyon Infocité constitutes a fundamental resource. This legal structure offers a legitimating institutional framework allowing the mobilization of public and private funding.

Obtaining funding and subsidies from public actors (Grand Lyon, General Council, Digital Agency...) is also an important resource in more than one way. First, these resources are an important lever and key factor for local collective initiatives' success. Moreover, they validate territorial legitimacy. This capacity to drain growing public funding, in a sectoral crisis context, confirms the effectiveness of established private-public dialogues and institutional engineering.

The structured programs developed by Lyon Infocité constitute also a portfolio of complementary and facilitating assets that will define the collective actions orientations prevailing throughout the cluster's evolution.

Professional structuring (2004-2005): Lyon Game and functional specialization

Lyon Game marked an enrichment in the key resources and competencies collectively developed by the territory [FR203, FR204, FR205]. Formalization of a clear institutional and formal legal framework increased the sector's legitimacy and visibility locally and at national and international levels. Collective action professionalization and structuring were improved. The specialized permanent team working mainly on video game sector needs expanded (5 people), each bringing specific expertise: (i) general coordination and institutional relations, (ii) diversification and internationalization development, (iii) R&D developments and connection to research laboratories, (iv) financing and communication and training support, (v) HR management.

The portfolio of programs and collective actions was enriched. This phase also saw the constitution of perennial collective actions that would become key strategic assets such as Game Connection. Despite its resale following Lyon Game's dissolution and Imaginove's creation, this economically profitable initiative represented a strategic asset for the region that would contribute to its economic development via networking effects, information sharing, commercial intermediation, knowledge dissemination and best practices. Moreover, the model allowed the cluster to develop collective competencies in B2B event engineering that would expand later within Imaginove and Game Only. The portfolio of partnerships and extraterritorial relations was also enriched.

Partnerships with CMP (GDC organizer) and with the European Union notably created a global influence network persisting beyond formal structures.

The institutionalization and expansion under Imaginove (2005-2018)

The labelling as a competitiveness cluster in 2005, itself a key strategic asset, significantly transformed the scale of available resources. The annual budget reached several million euros, jointly funded by the French State and Region. The permanent team grew to reach 10-15 employees during the peak of Imaginove activities. It also improved the institutional and complex collaborative project management competencies of the formal association (administrative management of European subsidies, animation of multi-partner consortiums, organization of public-private dialogue, reporting to multiple public funders.). As mentioned above, the thematic expansion toward animation and cinema, strategically justified by seeking critical mass, progressively diluted video game expertise. Progressive bureaucratization eroded certain key competencies and undermined the decision-making agility, a characteristic of the entrepreneurial period. The direct connection to studios' operational needs weakened and was replaced by a more institutionalized logic. Despite its 2018 dissolution, Imaginove bequeathed important assets. The institutional relations network remains mobilizable. The collective experience in managing complex collective projects remained. It is the same for the acquired territorial legitimacy of the cluster.

Specialized renaissance (2019-2025) with Game Only

Game Only's creation in 2019 immediately after Imaginove's disappearance testifies to the cluster's resilience. The association started with 131 members, instantly mobilizing almost all territorial actors [FR213, FR214]. This rapid mobilization capacity is a revealing aspect of the permanence of the social and trust capital between the cluster's members as well as the existence of strong proximities despite institutional turbulence. Sectoral focus on video games and the development of partnerships with other specialized professional associations enriched the base of programs and collective actions at the territorial level. Beyond these actions' economic benefits for the cluster members, these activities contributed to expanding the proximities and the relational network between the members. They also reinforced the cluster's legitimacy and positive reputation effects. However, several vulnerabilities persist. Declining membership numbers [from 138 in 2023 to 113 in 2025] and relative disengagement of large structures (Ubisoft, Arkane Studios) could weaken the representativeness of the formal association. Lyon Metropolis' persistent absence (€0 funding) contrasts with other metropolises' engagement (Paris €1-2M, Bordeaux €450k), limiting action capacities and questioning displayed territorial ambition.

9.5.3 The architecture of the cluster's resources

The cross-section analysis of the different phases detailed above highlights a diversified reconfiguration of the resources and competencies of the cluster, allowing its conception to be a full meta-organizational actor.

Proximities as key resources

The geographical concentration of the industry that was maintained throughout the cluster's evolution remains one of its primary resources which ensures a significant cognitive density. The same applies to the know-how and cognitive resources transmitted and enriched across generations: from Infogrames' AAA production expertise to contemporary studios' "games as a service" competencies, through mastery of Unreal Engine 5 and emerging technologies. Similarly, social capital accumulated over four decades constitutes one of the cluster's key resources. Network growth from 40 members (1999), 110+ (2001), 131 at Game Only's creation (2019), with instant

mobilization capacity post-Imaginove testifying link permanence. Different networking events created essential informal socialization spaces that helped maintain these informal networks. In parallel, social capital institutionalized and gained formalism through formalized mentoring (Start Up Force Club) and sharing mechanisms (Game Only's HR Club). Several established formal partnerships enriched this robust multi-level institutional network: CCI, Grand Lyon, Regional Council, State (via competitiveness clusters), Europe (R&D projects). More significant are informal and inter-regional partnerships: relations with European unions from 2001, cooperation with Montreal, Bertie partnership with Île-de-France, demonstrating capacity to transcend territorial competition logics.

Formalization through professional associations

The existence of a professional association as the main pilot of collective action constitutes a fundamental resource for the Lyon cluster. This legal structure, whether taking the form of Lyon Infocité (1999), Lyon Game (2004-2005), Imaginove (2005-2018) or Game Only (2019-present), offers a legitimating institutional framework transcending sectoral crises. The association progressively becomes a "relational platform" exceeding its initial administrative function to become a strategic territorial asset. The hiring of a permanent team, facilitated by the organization within a formal association, represents a critical resource whose evolution illustrates the cluster's growing professionalization. From one employee in 1999, the organization grew to 2.5 full-time equivalents in 2002, then five specialized permanent staff during the Lyon Game era (2004-2005). This growth culminated with Imaginove (10-15 employees) before stabilizing around a tighter but specialized team for Game Only. The association acts also a strategic asset by channelling public funding. Indeed, public subsidies, far from being a simple funding source, constitute a strategic resource validating the cluster's territorial legitimacy. Institutional support evolution reveals contrasted trajectories but persistent mobilization capacity.

Events and programs as organizational capital

Perennial collective actions like Game Connection and the portfolio of structured programs which were progressively enriched constitute another category of major strategic assets accumulating and formalizing over time. These programs constitute institutional anchor points, creating regular meetings that densify the relational fabric and generate continuous flows of informational, relational and economic resources.

Symbolic capital: reputation, legitimacy and visibility

The Lyon cluster is endowed with a symbolic capital built over four decades. The initial claim of "European capital of interactive entertainment" evolved toward factual recognition of Lyon as a historic cradle of French video games and a hub for AAA title production. Legitimacy was embodied both in games, collective actions and thanks to certain successive emblematic figures like Bruno Bonnell (Infogrames), Pierre Carde (Lyon Game), and the current leaders of globally recognized studios. The presence of major studios (Ubisoft 400+ employees, Microsoft via Arkane) validates the territory's lasting relevance. International awards - Game Awards for Arkane's Deathloop, critical success of A Plague Tale (Asobo having links with Lyon) - maintain this visibility and the cluster credibility and legitimacy. Institutional legitimacy - competitiveness cluster labelling, €350M projects labelled by Imaginove, CNC recognition - also accumulated and reinforced this symbolic capital.

9.5.4 *The Cluster's meta-organizational competencies*

During its evolution the cluster accumulated several competencies at a collective scale. First, several operational competencies like international database management were accumulated and refined. This central competency improved over two decades. From a handwritten list of 27 developers (2001) to a sophisticated base of 150+ developers and 120+ publishers with detailed profiles, preference histories and success metrics (2003). B2B event organization is also a competency consolidated over time: from 94 manually managed participants (2001) to 540 with personalized schedules and computerized system (2005), optimizing every detail down to table placement and coffee break timing. The same applies to complex collaborative project management which evolved through iterative learning. Game Connection's success contrasts with Digital Worlds' failure, developing discernment capacity on feasibility. Imaginove managed €350M R&D projects over 14 years, mastering European consortium assembly. Collective relational competencies were also sophisticated from simple animation to real institutional engineering. Community animation evolved from informal management toward more structured expertise. The formats were diversified: formal conferences, informal evenings, structured B2B, thematic workshops, mentoring programs. Institutional relations management also reveals remarkable sophistication. Multiplication of public funding (2001-2002), obtaining competitiveness cluster label (2005), mobilization of €800k regional fund in post-Imaginove period [[FR071](#), [FR047](#)] demonstrate persistent negotiation and lobbying capacity. Territorial lobbying and dialogue with institutions evolved also into strategic expertise. The capacity to simultaneously mobilize and establish an institutional dialogue with actors at multiple levels - the City, Metropolis, Department, Region, State and Europe (even if Lyon Metropolis remains absent for Game Only) - testifies of a capacity in institutional engineering. More subtle is the capability to navigate different tensions: coexistence with other agencies despite some frictions, managing Imaginove's thematic dilution, rapid post-dissolution reconstruction.

Inter-cluster management is also a distinctive collective competency particularly structured during the last 5 years with projects such as the Bertie program with Île-de-France which demonstrates mature inter-regional cooperation capacity.

9.6 Governance Structures in Lyon Cluster

9.6.1 *Governance mechanisms and models*

The Lyon cluster governance demonstrates a remarkable organizational plasticity over four decades. Each organizational form - generalist professional association (Lyon Infocité 1999), specialized professional structure (Lyon Game 2004-2005), complex competitiveness cluster (Imaginove 2005-2018), tight and agile association (Game Only 2019+) - responds to a different set of challenges while preserving collective action continuity and exploiting new opportunities.

Lyon Infocité and Lyon Game: a hybrid governance

The cluster's governance evolution reflects broader transformations in the industrial organization and regional development approaches. The initial period of the cluster genesis and collaboration between the first members was characterized by informal coordination and governance. The post-crisis period required new coordination mechanisms. Lyon Infocité and Lyon Games in its wake evolved from an informal network to a structured association managing collective resources and programs. Its hybrid governance model, incorporating private companies, public institutions and Chamber of Commerce, pioneer's multi-stakeholder coordination approaches formalized later in the competitiveness cluster framework.

Governance through a board of directors, a legal requirement for professional associations, becomes a norm and creates a regular space for dialogue between multiple stakeholders despite their heterogeneous and divergent logics. Decisions are generally made by consensus, with veto rights to protect each category's fundamental interests. The budget, voted on annually, is subject to tight negotiations expressing stakeholders' sometimes contradictory priorities.

Imaginove: Multi-level governance

Imaginove's creation in 2005, and its labelling as a competitiveness cluster by the French State, marks an entry into a highly formalized governance phase. The structure reflects national requirements while preserving certain Lyon specificities. The institutional architecture is organized into four complementary levels. The Board of Directors brings together companies, institutions, and research organizations in a carefully balanced composition. The Executive Bureau, more restricted, translates strategic orientations into operational actions. The Scientific Council evaluates R&D projects, bringing technical legitimacy to decisions. The General Assembly of members validates major orientations. Such a cluster governance structure balances private sector leadership with public sector support and professional management with member participation. The three-pillar operational structure - R&D, business development and internationalization - provides clear frameworks for collective action while maintaining flexibility for emerging opportunities.

This structure experienced three distinct management phases, each with its priorities:

- 2006-2011 (Ludovic Noël): Building institutional legitimacy and establishing processes [FR098]
- 2011-2016 (Tanguy Selo): Consolidation, service development and national visibility
- 2014-2018 (Olivier Tomat): Adapting to budgetary constraints and preparing transition

Despite the dependency toward public funding, the coordination mechanisms reached remarkable sophistication. R&D labelling processes follow rigorous procedures with standardized files, scientific evaluation, executive validation, and quarterly monitoring. Dashboards included detailed KPIs, impact metrics (jobs created, patents filed) and thematic commissions structure collaborative work.

Post-2018 reconfiguration: Toward distributed governance

The loss of competitiveness cluster labels in 2018 catalysed a transformation toward a more resilient and distributed governance model. Imaginove's activities were redistributed among different structures according to functional logic. Minalogic took over R&D programs, guaranteeing innovation support continuity. Game Only assumed territorial animation and networking in the local video game industry. This division allowed a beneficial specialization. The October 2020 Extraordinary General Assembly adopted statutory reforms profoundly redefining Game Only's governance. A preamble was added contextualizing the mission, and a "Partner Members" category was created. It was decided that the Board of Directors would comprise 5 to 15 members with 3-year mandates. The internal regulations provide operational flexibility, and a "Public Funders College" was established. Governance bodies include the General Assembly of all members, elected Board of Directors, operational Executive Bureau and consultative Public Funders College.

This new architecture articulates four governance levels:

- The General Assembly of 131 member companies remains sovereign
- The Board of Directors ensures strategic governance with diverse composition
- The Executive Bureau manages current affairs with reactivity
- The Public Funders College provides consultative opinions

The hybrid governance structure, tested from 1999 and associating private companies, public institutions and associations became a mature model [FR213, FR214, FR218]. This hybridity allows mobilizing diverse resources: public funding via institutional legitimacy, private investments via business relevance, community engagement via territorial anchoring. The capacity to maintain this governance despite tensions and forces that can promote fragmentation demonstrates remarkable institutional robustness. Collective decision-making mechanisms also progressively evolved from informal toward more structured processes without losing agility. Game Connection's business plan, detailing four-year strategy, suggests the existence of shared strategic planning processes.

9.6.2 *Coordination and control mechanisms in Lyon cluster*

Distributed governance relies on a set of sophisticated mechanisms. Apart from the formal mechanisms detailed above, the covid-19 pandemic spurred the mobilization of digital coordination tools and spaces (slack, drive, discord...). Operational coordination relies on formalized processes with clear calendars, digital tools for automation, regular reporting cycles, and performance metric tracking. The control system has also evolved. Financial controls include annual audits, quarterly board reviews, member approval for major expenses, and transparent budgetary reporting. Main performance monitoring measures report on membership, event participation metrics, revenue per member calculations, and employment impact assessments. Quality control systems constitute a distinctive element of the Lyon model. Financial reporting standards include 4-year budget projections, profit and loss statements by event and quarterly financial reviews, testifying managerial rigor. Quality assurance functions through participant feedback systems, post-event surveys, continuous improvement processes, and benchmarking against other clusters. These mechanisms ensure the cluster maintains its competitive position despite limited resources.

Regarding the inter-cluster level, Inter-association meetings allow strategy alignment without formal hierarchy. Shared calendar avoids conflicts. Mutualization agreements optimize the use of limited resources. Digital platforms facilitate asynchronous coordination, adapted to the players' constraints.

End of Chapter

10 BORDEAUX CLUSTER

The analysed documents reveal a singular trajectory for Bordeaux cluster marked by different critical moments: the Kalisto era (1990-2002) and its collapse [FR006, FR007], the entrepreneurial diaspora and the reconstruction of the local video game ecosystem (2002-2007), followed by the progressive institutionalization with Bordeaux Games (2007-2021) and the regional merger around SO Games (2021-2025). This periodization highlights the proximity dynamics and different forms of collective action that characterize the Bordeaux cluster, as well as the resilience mechanisms that enabled the cluster's adjustment to the various crises it has experienced.

10.1 Genesis and Emergence of Bordeaux Cluster

The historical foundations of the Bordeaux video game cluster emerged from the dramatic collapse of Kalisto Entertainment in 2002, creating a paradoxical transformation where crisis catalysed entrepreneurial rebirth. This section synthesizes D4.1's findings on how the dissolution of a dominant company generated a diaspora of experienced professionals who established new studios, fundamentally reshaping the regional ecosystem's structure and dynamics. The table below organizes the primary historical factors identified through stakeholder interviews:

D4.1 findings	Description
Kalisto legacy effect	The 2002 collapse of Kalisto Entertainment (300+ employees) created an experienced talent pool that founded multiple spin-off studios. Former employees established Asobo Studio (2002), Motion Twin (2001), and other key companies, transforming crisis into entrepreneurial opportunity through forced local retention of expertise.
Dual territorial development	Bordeaux emerged as the economic centre focusing on commercial game development, while another pole developed in Angoulême as the training and incubation hub. This bipolarization created complementary specializations within a 150km radius.
Institutional catalyst in Angoulême	ENJMIN's creation as France's first public video game school attracted 225+ students annually, generating a pipeline of trained talent and fostering entrepreneurial dynamics through its Wizz incubator, which hosts 5-6 studios per cohort.
Associative formalization	Bordeaux Games association formed in 2007 to manage institutional relations and coordinate recruitment practices from former Kalisto alumni companies.
Administrative integration	The 2016 territorial reform merging Aquitaine and Poitou-Charentes into Nouvelle-Aquitaine created opportunities for cross-territorial coordination, leading to SO. Games formation in 2021 as a unified regional structure.

Table 85 - Summary of D4.1. on the emergence and genesis of Bordeaux cluster

10.1.1 Pre-cluster & foundational role of Kalisto (1990-2002)

Early entrepreneurial genesis (1990-1996)

The history of the Bordeaux cluster is rooted in the entrepreneurial venture of Nicolas Gaume, a serial entrepreneur who founded Kalisto Entertainment in 1990 at 19 years old [FR006, FR007, FR008]. This foundational act positioned Bordeaux as a one of the pioneering regions in the French video gaming, alongside Lyon with Infogrames and the Île-de-France region. The company rapidly developed recognized technical expertise, illustrated by the prestigious partnership with Namco for *Pac-In-Time*, and the production of over 50 games during its 12 years of existence [FR009].

Kalisto's growth trajectory was notably rapid. From a local startup, the company became an international player with the opening of its offices in the United States, United Kingdom, and Japan [FR122]. The acquisition by Mindscape in 1996 accelerated this trend [FR006]. This early international expansion forged a culture of global openness that would endure within the DNA of the Bordeaux cluster.

The apogee and warning signals (1997-2000)

The period 1997-1999 marks Kalisto's zenith with several critical and commercial successes. *Dark Earth* (1997) demonstrated the studio's narrative innovation capabilities, while *Nightmare Creatures* achieved 2 million copies sold [FR006, FR007]. The initial public offering in 1999 validated this success and provided significant capital for the firm's expansion. The company reached a peak of 300 employees according to various sources [FR006, FR009], creating a critical mass of talents. This concentration of skills - programmers, artists, game designers, project managers - in a mid-sized city like Bordeaux created the foundations for a virtuous ecosystem.

The brutal collapse (2001-2002)

The Internet bubble of 2000 struck Kalisto with full force [FR092]. The company, overcapitalized and over-indebted following its IPO, did not survive the crisis [FR007]. Its liquidation in 2002 [FR006] constituted a major crisis for the territory, with the disappearance of approximately 300 direct jobs. It also generated trust issues between the investment world and the video game industry.

10.1.2 Creative diaspora: from crisis to renaissance (2002-2008)

Kalisto's collapse paradoxically generated a remarkable entrepreneurial dynamic. The documents indicate that "12 ex-Kalisto employees" immediately created Asobo Studio in 2002, acquiring Super Farm [FR058, FR104]. This reactivity highlights a collective determination not to abandon the territory and its accumulated competencies.

Other creations quickly followed [FR219, FR220], notably:

- **AtOnce Technologies** (2004): positioning in middleware, winner of the National Innovative Enterprises Competition [FR079, FR110]
- **BeTomorrow** (2002): mobile games specialist and real-time sports systems with patents [FR079, FR109]
- **Groupe Concoursmania**: became "European leader in B2B gamification" [FR090]
- **SolidGame**: innovation management consulting firm [FR084, FR079]

This entrepreneurial wave transformed the local industrial structure. From a dominant single-company model, Bordeaux evolved towards a diversified ecosystem of specialized SMEs. This led to the emergence and the development of a video games ecosystem which reached "25 companies, 250 jobs" by 2015 [FR058, FR090].

Several elements had helped the development of the ecosystem during this period:

- **The accumulated human capital**: The professionals trained at Kalisto possessed rare skills during that period (3D programming, AAA game design, international production management) and were immediately deployable [FR221, FR222]
- **An enduring social capital**: Networks woven during the Kalisto era survived the company. Former colleagues maintained informal links that would facilitate future collaborations [FR219]
- **A territorial legitimacy**: Despite the failure, the Kalisto experience positioned Bordeaux on the global video game map. This visibility facilitated the attraction of new projects and talents [FR007, FR224]

10.1.3 Collective structuring: Bordeaux Games (2007-2008)

After five years of individual reconstruction (2002-2007), the surviving actors and newly created structures felt the need for structured collective action. This latency period allowed companies to consolidate their business models and overcome the Kalisto crisis [FR058, FR090].

On May 17, 2007, five founding members (Asobo Studio, AtOnce, BeTomorrow, SC2X/MAD Monkey Studio, SolidGame) officially founded Bordeaux Games [FR219, F220]. This creation marked the transition from an individual survival logic to an assumed collective strategy. Other studios would subsequently join this collective initiative. November 2008 constitutes a turning point with the recruitment of the first permanent staff member, described as a "triggering element" [FR184]. This professionalization transformed the volunteer association into an operational structure with enhanced capacity for concrete collective actions. The growth from 5 to 12 members by the end of 2008 demonstrates the immediate attractiveness of this initiative. Furthermore, the integration into the SNJV Board of Directors as a representative of regional associations positioned Bordeaux within the national landscape, reinforcing its collective action [FR080, FR081, FR219].

10.2 Key Characteristics & Components of the Local Industry

The Bordeaux cluster's industrial structure reflects a complex ecosystem spanning the entire Nouvelle-Aquitaine region, characterized by significant diversity in company sizes, business models, and geographic distribution. D4.1's analysis revealed how this heterogeneity creates both opportunities for complementary collaboration and challenges for unified governance. The following synthesis captures the key industrial components identified through interviews.

D4.1 findings	Description
Geographic distribution	Bordeaux concentrates 60% of regional employment (primarily large studios like Ubisoft's 360 employees, Asobo's 320 employees), while Angoulême accounts for 25% with 28 companies averaging 4.5 employees each. Additional nodes exist in La Rochelle, Poitiers, Pau, and Agen across 84,000 km ² .
Company typology	The ecosystem comprises international subsidiaries (Ubisoft), major independents (Asobo Studio with Microsoft partnerships), medium self-publishers (Shiro Games, 75 employees), and many small independents (<10 employees) requiring significant collective support services.
Funding architecture	Multi-layered public funding includes national FAJV, regional subsidies transitioning from repayable advances to direct grants, and local support from Bordeaux Métropole and Grand Angoulême. The 50% public funding ceiling creates private co-financing bottlenecks.
Training infrastructure	ENJMIN serves as a regional backbone, training 225 students yearly across all game development disciplines. The school creates strong industry-education linkages.
Business Model diversity	Studios operate varied models from AAA co-development (Asobo's Flight Simulator with Microsoft), self-publishing (Shiro Games' strategy titles), cooperative structures (Motion Twin's SCOP model), to hybrid models combining games with applications for other sectors among smaller studios.

Table 86 - Summary of D4.1. on the characteristics & components of Bordeaux cluster

10.2.1 Demographic evolution

According to the documents, the local video game industry is generating over €110M in turnover in Nouvelle-Aquitaine, with 36% achieved internationally and employing more than 1,000 people [FR019, FR050, FR219]. The main milestones of the cluster's growth over the last 18 years, since the creation of Bordeaux Games in 2007, are summarized in the table below.

Period	Number of companies	Observations	Source
2007	5 founding studios	Post-Kalisto core group	[FR219]
2008	12 members	140% growth	[FR219]
2009	17 members	Launch of two major successes of Asobo Studios: "Up" (PSP, PC, Mac, PS2) and "FUEL" (PS3, Xbox 360, PC)	[FR219]
2012	31 members	Foundation of Shiro Games Studio	[FR219]
2015	25 companies	Post-crisis ecosystem	[FR219]
2016	25 members	Local ecosystem counts 40 companies specialized in video games & creation of new enlarged region "Nouvelle Aquitaine"	[FR221]
2017	40 companies	Foundation of a local studio by Ubisoft	[FR222]
2021	30+ members	Regional structuring	[FR015]
2024	95 members	---	[FR227]
2025	80+ studios	Regional consolidation	[FR054]

Table 87 - Evolution of the number of companies in the Bordeaux cluster (2007-2025)

Beginning with a nucleus of five founding studios originating from the Kalisto diaspora, the ecosystem experienced an initial phase of rapid expansion between 2007 and 2012, growing from 5 to 31 members [FR219]. This period notably witnessed the emergence of major commercial successes by Asobo Studio: "Up" and "FUEL" in 2009, two games which confirmed the territory's capacity to produce titles of international magnitude [FR105]. The year 2016 marked an important turning point with the creation of the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region [FR222]. It expanded the cluster's geographical perimeter and its scope of action. It is the same for the installation of Ubisoft Bordeaux in 2017, the first studio created by the group in France in 21 years. This establishment was a strong signal of the territory's attractiveness [FR108]. These factors together sparked a growth phase that elevated the ecosystem to over 100 members in 2020 with the creation of SO Games [FR019], the association covering the entire regional territory. In 2024, the cluster stabilised its membership around 95 active members, evidencing organisational maturity [FR227].

10.2.2 Industrial structure and actor typology

The cluster's architecture is organised around several types of players that can be differentiated according to their size and the nature of their specialisations. The following diagram provides an overview of the enterprise demographics in Bordeaux (blue) and Angoulême (red). First, there are the industrial champions who each employ over 100 staff members. They act as territorial growth drivers. Asobo Studio embodies the emblematic success story of the territory with an evolution from 100 employees in 2012 to 320 in 2024. The studio has established its reputation thanks to a portfolio of 17 games, developed since 2002, and a set of strategic partnerships with companies such as Microsoft (for HoloLens and Flight Simulator), Disney, Pixar, Universal... [FR105]. Its XR division testifies to a continuous technological innovation capacity. Ubisoft Bordeaux represents the other major studio model, a subsidiary of a multinational publisher, with substantial growth from 30 to 400 employees between 2017 and 2023. The studio rapidly established itself in AAA production, notably with "Assassin's Creed Mirage", confirming the territory's capacity to attract and develop productions of significant scope [FR106].

Figure 14 - Demographic comparison of the Angoulême and Bordeaux clusters (authors' construction based on documentary data)

Between these two giants and the multitude of micro-studios exists an intermediate category of enterprises employing between 20 and 50 staff members [FR227]. The ecosystem comprises approximately ten studios in this category. Motion Twin, with its unique cooperative status within the industry, achieved planetary success with *Dead Cells*, sold to more than 6 million units and rewarded at the Game Awards 2018 [FR116]. This success led to the creation of Evil Empire in 2019, a spin-off now comprising 70 employees [FR117]. Shiro Games, with 75 employees in 2022, established itself in the strategy genre with recognised titles such as *Northgard* and *Dune: Spice Wars* [FR115]. Big Bad Wolf, acquired by Nacon in 2018, specialised in narrative games [FR107].

This pool of studios is complemented by specialised actors who target specific niches. Dotemu has established itself since 2007 as the European leader in retro remakes with successes such as “Streets of Rage 4” [FR119]. Kylotonn dominates the rally game segment with the WRC series [FR120]. Enterprises such as Nova-Box [FR121], labelled as a research laboratory, or ShinyPix [FR108] in innovative screens, testify to the territory's technological innovation capacity. In total, the ecosystem generates more than 1000 documented direct jobs, confirming its significant economic weight within the regional industrial fabric.

Industrial Champions (100+ employees)	
Asobo Studio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spectacular evolution: 100 employees in 2012 / 320 employees in 2024 [FR104] - Prestigious portfolio: 17 games since 2002 [FR104] - Strategic partnerships: Microsoft (HoloLens, Flight Simulator), Disney, Pixar, Universal, Fox, Hasbro [FR104] - Technological innovation: Active XR Division [FR104]
Ubisoft Bordeaux	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Installation in 2017: "first studio created in France in 21 years" [FR057] - Explosive growth: 30 → 400+ employees in 6 years [FR056, FR057] - AAA production: Assassin's Creed Mirage [FR106]
Intermediate Studios (20-50 employees)	
Motion Twin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unique cooperative status in industry [FR116] - Dead Cells: 6M+ sales, 2018 Game Awards Best Indie [FR116] - Free-to-play web pioneer before premium pivot - Creation of Evil Empire (2019) as spin-off [FR116]
Evil Empire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Motion Twin spin-off [FR117] - 70 employees in 2025
Shiro Games	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 employees in 2022 [FR115] - Recognised portfolio: Evoland, Northgard, Dune: Spice Wars [FR115]
Big Bad Wolf	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studio acquisition by Nacon in 2018 [FR107] - AAA narration specialisation: The Council, Vampire: Swansong
Emerging, Niche or Specialised Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dotemu (2007): Streets of Rage 4, TMNT, retro remake leader [FR119] - Nova-Box: 9 titles, research laboratory labelling [FR121] - ShinyPix: Innovative screen research [FR108] - Fabzat: Activision-Blizzard partner for 3D printing [FR118]

Table 88 - A typology of local studios by size

10.2.3 Architecture of institutional support

The analysis documents a public support framework that was initially cautious following Kalisto's collapse, before progressively reconstructing itself through various instruments implemented at different institutional levels.

Level	Actors	Contributions	Impact
European	Horizon Programmes	Collaborative R&D projects	Access to international consortia
National	CNC, BpiFrance	CIJV, FAJV, innovation loans	Production support
Regional	Nouvelle-Aquitaine	€150.7k/year SO Games	Sector structuration
Metropolitan	Bordeaux Metropole	€15k + premises	Territorial anchoring
Local	Magelis Angoulême	€7.3k + infrastructure	Image synergy

Table 89 - multi-level institutional support architecture

The analysis of public financing for the Bordeaux cluster highlights a trajectory characterized by an increasing institutionalization and a growing sophistication of public support, organized according to a multi-tiered institutional architecture [FR222]. In its first years (2007–2009), Bordeaux Games received public support that enabled the association to recruit its first permanent staff member in November 2008 and to structure collective actions, including the creation of thematic commissions in 2009 [FR219]. As the ecosystem matured, public partners engaged more substantially; between 2010 and 2016, resources dedicated to professional events and collective actions expanded (Creative Tuesdays, international trade shows, joint stands), reflecting sustained growth of outward-facing activities [FR221]. From 2017 onward, the region’s attractiveness benefited from Ubisoft’s presence in Bordeaux (the studio highlights location and quality-of-life arguments externally) [FR057], while the ecosystem consolidated tools first prepared in 2016 [FR221]. The Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region implemented a dedicated production fund for video games development [FR018]. In addition, SO· Games’ governance and operating model formalized multi-annual public partnerships and a two-permanent structure covering the whole Nouvelle-Aquitaine territory [FR224]. Externally, Ubisoft reports a large, international team in Bordeaux [FR106], reinforcing the studio-magnet effect [FR091].

Public support is provided by several organisms across multiple institutional levels [FR076]. At the European level, Horizon programmes facilitate the access to collaborative R&D projects and integration within international consortia [FR027]. The national level, through the CNC and BpiFrance, provides support mechanisms such as the CIJV (Video Game Tax Credit), the FAJV (Video Game Support Fund), and innovation loans, which are essential for production financing [FR025, FR026, FR185, FR085, FR186]. The Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region is the central pillar of the support apparatus, with an average annual contribution of €150,000 to SO Games, complemented by a direct aid to studios and sector structuring programmes [FR028]. Bordeaux Métropole provides a less significant support averaging €15,000 annually, alongside premises put at the disposal of So Games. The Magelis [FR062] hub in Angoulême contributes an average of €7,000 while offering specialized infrastructure and creating synergies with the animated image industries. This stratification of public support mechanisms demonstrates the recognition of video games as a contributor to local economic development. Furthermore, integration within the FrenchTech Bordeaux ecosystem, documented in 2025, marks the recognition of video games as a fully-fledged component of the metropolitan digital economy. This certification opens access to additional resources: coworking spaces, acceleration programmes, and investor networks.

10.2.4 The training ecosystem

The training ecosystem dedicated to the video games industry has undergone substantial structuration, establishing it as a key asset of the Bordeaux territory. Initially, the training ecosystem represented a territorial weakness. The founder of Kalisto, in a 2019 interview with Business Herald, identified training as "the key differentiator" between past failures and current successes [FR059].

Today, this ecosystem comprises several key actors [FR093]. Gaming Campus Bordeaux constitutes one of the principal video game training institutions in Bordeaux. Established in 2018, it deploys three complementary specializations: (i) G.Tech (programming and development), (ii) G.Business (video game management and marketing), and (iii) G.Art (artistic creation and game design). The institution offers training programmes from Bachelor to MBA level and has developed key structured local partnerships with territorial studios. Gaming Campus alone generates an estimated throughput of over 200 students annually [FR032]. ENJMIN Angoulême (École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs Numériques – National School of Games and Interactive Digital Media), located at 138 rue de Bordeaux in Angoulême, represents the historic benchmark institution [FR093]. Created in 2003 by Jean-Pierre Raffarin, then Prime Minister, it focuses on the training of senior executives for the video game industry [FR044]. In 2012, ENJMIN (Angoulême) was recognized and labelled as professional training programs [FR187]. La Horde, another training local institution, aims to be a strategic interface between training and industry. In 2022, it published an analysis of Bordeaux's attractiveness as a video game city, highlighting the training ecosystem. It maintains an updated mapping of Bordeaux studios, facilitating the identification of internship and employment opportunities [FR039]. The presence of these training institutions constituted a "principal selection criterion" for Ubisoft's establishment in Bordeaux in 2017 [FR183]. The same applies to the complementarities between the specializations and approaches of these institutions (example of Gaming Campus targeting large-scale vocational training whereas ENJMIN emphasizes executive training). The Horizon(s) trade fair (main professional local event dedicated to the video games industry) illustrates the symbiosis between training and industry by bringing together over 80 studios and schools annually and by organizing a space for direct encounters between students, educators, and professionals, thereby facilitating professional integration and recruitment [FR055].

The collaboration between training and industry, reinforced by mandatory internships and supervised projects, ensures the continuous alignment between developed competencies and market needs. The expansion of the training programmes in 2024 with the addition of Guardia Cybersecurity School [FR042] to Gaming Campus highlights a recent diversification toward related professions (cybersecurity, immersive technologies). This evolution accompanies the increasing complexity of productions and the emergence of new specialized technical skill requirements [FR042].

10.2.5 Cluster geography & physical infrastructure

The geography of the cluster according to the documentary analysis is structured in three areas.

Geographic Area	Characteristics & Actors
Bordeaux Hypercentre (2km radius)	-Studios such as "Motion Twin" and "Shiro Games" in city centre [FR061] - "Big Bad Wolf" premises with 400m ² in city centre [FR107] -Density and proximities facilitating daily informal encounters and agglomeration effects
Immediate Periphery (5-10km)	Ubisoft: Avenue Abadie in 2017 / Bastide-Niel in 2023 [FR074] Creation of new attraction pole in city's east Rents -50% vs hyper centre Accessibility via transport maintained

Bordeaux-Angoulême Axis (120km)	ENJMIN in Angoulême [FR044] Magelis Pole concentration image/animation [FR062] Important student/professional flows
--	---

Table 90 - Cluster geography and spatial distribution

The cluster possesses a diversified physical infrastructure that attests to its progressive maturation. Several emblematic sites structuring the ecosystem.

Infrastructure Type	Location	Capacity
Bordeaux Spaces	City centre CCI	Meeting rooms, events
Magelis Pole Angoulême	Dedicated campus	Studios, amphitheatres
Bastide-Niel	New creative quarter	Ubisoft 400+ workstations
City-centre Studios	Hyper centre	400m ² Big Bad Wolf + others

Table 91 - Physical infrastructure typology

The Bastide-Niel district embodies urban transformation in service of the creative industries. Ubisoft established its facilities there in 2023 following a significant growth phase (over 400 employees in 2022). This implantation in a district undergoing reconversion enabled the mobilization of new spaces to accompany the video game sector's expansion [FR023, FR057]. The Bordeaux hyper centre remains the historic core of the cluster, with Big Bad Wolf occupying 400m² in the city centre since its acquisition by Nacon in 2018. This central location facilitates informal interactions and reinforces the industry's visibility within urban space. Motion Twin, operating as a cooperative since 2001, also maintains its presence within the dense urban area, creating—together with Evil Empire (its 2019 spin-off)—an independent innovation hub. The dedicated Pôle Magelis Campus in Angoulême, established in 2003, offers premises and amphitheatres adapted to pedagogical and professional requirements. This dedicated infrastructure, at this scale, positions Angoulême as a national centre of excellence for training [FR062]. The Gironde studio directory [FR105] reveals a remarkable concentration of actors: Shiro Games, Motion Twin, Big Bad Wolf, Sparkly Games, Studio Black Flag, among others. This density creates an ecosystem where physical proximity facilitates collaborations, professional mobility, and knowledge transfers. The event infrastructure has similarly been expanded, with the Horizon(s) trade fair bringing together over 80 studios and schools in 2023. The Chamber of Commerce and Industry, in the city centre, provides also meeting rooms and event spaces, creating the material conditions for the ecosystem animation [FR075]. These formal and informal meeting places constitute the invisible yet essential infrastructure of the cluster which have been constructed over two decades, progressively transforming Bordeaux-Angoulême into a European video game hub.

10.2.6 The DNA of Bordeaux Cluster

Several markers, in combination, constitute the distinctive identity of the Bordeaux video game cluster. First, the crisis experienced by the local sector following Kalisto's collapse has left its imprint on the local ecosystem. It generated a particular entrepreneurial dynamic and facilitated the development of mutual aid and solidarity logics and behaviours among video games firms.

The analysis of productions reveals a distinctive specialization in narrative-driven and technologically innovative games. Asobo Studio with A Plague Tale (€29M turnover in 2022), and Big Bad Wolf with The Council and Vampire: Swansong, demonstrate excellence in interactive narrative [FR029]. This creative signature is, moreover, internationally recognized [FR052]. Asobo's partnerships with Disney, Pixar, Universal, Fox, and Hasbro confirm this recognition of Bordeaux's

creative excellence. These major local studios have also developed specific areas of expertise and competencies: Asobo in realistic simulation (*MS Flight Simulator*), Motion Twin (*Dead Cells*) in the roguelike/Metroidvania genre, Shiro Games (*Northgard*, *Dune*) in real-time strategy, and Big Bad Wolf (*The Council*) in interactive narrative city centre [FR029]. The regional merger experienced by the territory has also transformed the local identity [FR102]. The creation of SO Games in 2021, which merged the Nouvelle-Aquitaine associations, marks a major evolution in the territorial DNA. This regional structure transcends municipal logics to create an integrated regional ecosystem. It enables the coexistence of the major studios' stakes in Bordeaux with the logics of the smaller indies based in Angoulême. This local ecosystem of creative independents constitutes a key vector of the sector's attractiveness according to Invest in Bordeaux, alongside two other factors: the pool of trained talent and the accessible quality of life [FR183]. Moreover, this openness to alternative models already existed within Bordeaux even before the integration of Angoulême Jeu Vidéo, through the Motion Twin studio's model. With its singular cooperative status, this studio has influenced the local ecosystem and the associative and collaborative culture that developed there. Motion Twin is responsible for several innovations, such as *Dead Cells* (6 million copies sold, 2018 Game Awards Best Independent Game) [FR116]. This cooperative approach has proliferated with the creation of Evil Empire in 2019, a spin-off now employing 70 staff while maintaining shared governance values.

10.3 Analysis of the Evolutionary Dynamics

The evolutionary trajectory of the Bordeaux cluster demonstrates how regional video game ecosystems transform through critical junctures, institutional reforms, and market disruptions. D4.1's longitudinal analysis identified three distinct developmental phases, each characterized by different organizational logics and collaborative dynamics. The synthesis below captures these evolutionary patterns:

D4.1 findings	Description
Phase 1: Isolated champion (1990-2002)	Kalisto's dominance as a national champion employing 300+ people acculturated Bordeaux to video games but created mono-enterprise dependency. Its 2002 collapse traumatically reshaped the landscape, forcing entrepreneurial adaptation without established support systems.
Phase 2: Parallel ecosystems (2002-2017)	Dual development saw Bordeaux's spin-off wave creating companies like Asobo and Motion Twin through market-driven entrepreneurship, while Angoulême built institutional capacity through ENJMIN. InFusio's 2009 closure added mobile gaming expertise, broadening the talent pool.
Phase 3: Regional integration (2017-present)	Ubisoft's 2017 arrival (growing from 30 to 360 employees) transformed cluster scale and legitimacy. SO.Games' 2021 creation unified previously separate associations under regional mandate, though tensions persist between Bordeaux's business focus and Angoulême's creative culture.
Digital transformation impact	Steam platform expansion (2014+) reduced publisher proximity requirements, enabling remote market access. COVID-19 accelerated distributed team models, with studios employing talent from Paris to Brazil, fundamentally altering traditional cluster geography.
Governance evolution	Progression from informal "bar meetings" to formalized associations with permanent staff (2.5 FTEs), and digital coordination via Slack platform across 108 member companies.

Table 92 - Summary of D4.1. on the evolution of Bordeaux cluster

10.3.1 Resilience & early structuration (2002-2007)

This period is detailed above in the first section of the present report. The collapse of Kalisto Entertainment in 2002 and the crisis experienced by the video game sector in France [FR092] crystallized the cluster's formation and initiated formal inter-organizational cooperation

between several structures. The 2002-2007 period is characterized by a dual dynamic: individual initiatives and efforts to reconstruct a professional activity on the one hand and, on the other hand, the collective need to maintain the ties forged during the Kalisto venture [FR219]. Asobo Studio is one of the major studios that was rapidly founded by former Kalisto employees, demonstrating the capacity to transform technical heritage into commercial success [FR104]. From 2002 onward, the studio established partnerships with major actors (Disney, Pixar, Universal). This early success created a ripple effect on the local ecosystem [FR058]. The initial motivations, which were essentially defensive—"to better coexist" and "to avoid fatal isolation"—attest to the fragility of the nascent ecosystem [FR219]. The former Kalisto employees, who possessed technical expertise acquired on ambitious productions such as *Dark Earth* (1997) and *Pac-In-Time* (a Namco partnership) [FR100], constituted a strategic human capital for the region, albeit dispersed. The 2002-2007 period progressively witnessed these defensive motivations evolving toward more offensive and collective ambitions of local firms. Thus, during five years, the local video games ecosystem was engaged in a reconstruction process by the entrepreneurs and the maturation of new projects" [FR058].

10.3.2 Structuration of collective action (2007-2016)

The official creation of Bordeaux Games on May 17, 2007, marks the transition from an informal network to an institutionalized structure, as well as "the passage from individual survival to a collective strategy" [FR220]. The association displayed the ambition to "federate the companies operating in the video game domain in Aquitaine" and to conduct "collective actions to favour this sector's growth in the region [FR219]. The association articulated clear objectives from the outset: "mutual aid, creation, recruitment, and support for the sector in Aquitaine and France" [FR220]. This formalization responded to three identified necessities: (i) collective representation vis-à-vis the public authorities, (ii) the pooling of resources, and (iii) territorial visibility [FR219]. The governance that was put in place reflected both the ambitions and the constraints of inter-organizational collaboration. Four specialized commissions of six members each, with mandatory quarterly meetings, guaranteed distributed governance and avoided the concentration of decisions [FR193, FR219]. The recruitment of a permanent staff member in November 2008 enabled the transition from a volunteer structure to an operational organization capable of deploying structured actions. The association organized various activities that expanded over time, documented in the Bordeaux Games archives: the organization of professional events, the accompaniment of studios, and the interface with local authorities, with an average budget between €200k and €450k according to the documents. Internationalization manifested itself from 2009 onward with "collective participation in Gamescom with a shared booth" [FR219]. The results from this initial phase were remarkable: growth from 5 to 17 members in 2 years (+240%), and the organization of 30+ representative events in 2009 [FR219]. This formalization positioned Bordeaux Games as a legitimate interlocutor for sectoral public organisms. This period witnessed the emergence of new services such as the "Creative Tuesday" (a regular monthly meeting that built community loyalty) and the "employment platform," a members' space facilitating B2B exchanges and employment [FR219]. The Game Connection 2011 candidacy through which Bordeaux "finished as a finalist against Paris, notably eliminating Lyon (despite being the format's creator) and 7 European cities" [FR219], demonstrates the national recognition acquired by the cluster.

Bordeaux Games' obtained a seat on the SNJV board of directors from 2008 onward [FR185, FR192]. This integration within the national instances was facilitated by Nicolas Gaume's experience, who would become SNJV president from 2009 to 2014 [FR185, FR190, FR122]. In 2012, during Gaume's re-election to the SNJV presidency, Fabrice Carré from Bordeaux Games served as an administrator

[FR021, FR185]. This institutionalization confirmed the national recognition of the cluster. It also facilitated the implication of Bordeaux Games in many inter-cluster projects carried out and coordinated by the SNJV. During 2009-2012 period, the French video game industry experienced many persistent challenges including the lack of systematic financing tools (compared to Canada), the fiscal instability and legal contradictions regarding IP and employment and structural difficulties which hindered the industry's growth despite its innovative performance [FR185, FR186, FR187, FR188].

10.3.3 The ecosystem densification (2016-2021)

The year 2016 marked a strategic turning point with the association's opening to independents and freelancers. This evolution allowed a transition from 25 active members, exclusively video games companies, to a pool of 50+ members including new partners. This change was motivated by the industry's structural mutations [FR221]. This decision reflected the rise of flexible production models and recognized the micro-studios' growing importance in creative innovation. Stéphane Bonazza (the Bordeaux Games spokesperson) confirmed that Bordeaux Games now represented "the development studios, the freelancers, and the companies from 3 to 250 employees" [FR066].

Ubisoft's installation in 2017, the group's first studio creation in France in 21 years, significantly impacted the local video game ecosystem [FR039, FR056, FR059]. First, there was a volume effect. The explosive growth from 30 to 400+ employees transformed the scale of the cluster [FR017, FR056]. The implantation at 15 avenue Abadie, then the relocation to Bastide-Niel in 2023 [FR074], symbolized this territorial upscaling. There was also an attractiveness effect manifested by the arrival of AAA-level international talent [FR039]. Parallel to Ubisoft's arrival, the local studios achieved several advances: Asobo established a strategic partnership with Microsoft and acquired worldwide recognition [FR065], generating €23.7M in turnover in 2022 [FR054]; Motion Twin saw Dead Cells become a "global phenomenon" with over 6 million sales and the 2018 Game Award for Best Independent Game [FR054, FR116] and Shiro Games positioned itself as the "strategy niche leader" [FR054, FR115] with titles like Northgard and Dune: Spice Wars.

The same applied to the Bordeaux Games association, which expanded its collective actions, improving the international validation of the territory and attracting new studios. Stéphane Bonazza, the Bordeaux Games spokesperson, described the association's functioning in 2022: it "animates the community and favours knowledge exchange, notably by organizing keynotes and afterworks," creating "a system of pooling and acceleration, where each participant shares their experience in terms of management (finance, legal...), creation, or even organization" [FR066]. "Le Journal des Entreprises" confirmed the overall economic impact in 2022: the Nouvelle-Aquitaine sector generated "€100M+ in turnover" with "Ubisoft 400+ employees" and "Asobo 270+ employees (€23.7M turnover)" [FR054].

10.3.4 The regional merger (2021-2025)

The creation of SO Games [FR021, FR024] in 2021, which merged the Nouvelle-Aquitaine video game associations (Bordeaux Game and Angoulême Jeu Vidéo), responded to a triple documented logic. An administrative logic since the merger aligned the new structure with the regional perimeter created in 2016 [FR102]. The economic logic which targeted critical mass with an objective of €100M+ in turnover and 150 companies—an objective already achieved in 2022 according to Le Journal des Entreprises. The strategic logic aimed to reinforce Nouvelle-Aquitaine position vis-à-vis the other major French clusters: Capital Games (Île-de-France) [FR087] and Game Only (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes) [FR102]. During the merger process Bordeaux Games remodelled its statutes and

governance to enable not only the Bordeaux companies to thrive but also to make place for the lesser-known talents from this vast territory and to extend its working area from La Rochelle to Pau via Angoulême, Poitiers, and Limoges" [FR015, FR066]. The operational budget of €345.8k in 2021 enabled SO·Games to strengthen its professionalization [FR224]. This budget relied on a mix of subsidies (Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine, Bordeaux Métropole, Grand Angoulême, Magelis), membership fees, and event revenues [FR224]. Among the support instruments accessible to the ecosystem were the national *Crédit d'Impôt Jeu Vidéo* (CIJV), covering up to 30% of eligible expenses within a national ceiling of €6 million per year [FR025, FR088], as well as the regional production fund co-developed with Magelis since 2016 [FR221]. Additional financial tools included Bpifrance innovation loans [FR026] and Invest Gaming, which SO·Games integrated into its activities starting in 2021 [FR224]. SO Games aggregated the existing structures but also launched three structuring projects for the future. The "Unity Excellence Centre" (2021-2022), the first European centre dedicated to Unity with €50k in initial investment, positioned the region on next-generation production tools training [FR224]. The national recruitment fair (2022), responding to the "sector's number one problem," aimed to become France's reference event with an innovative hybrid format. The leadership on digital sobriety (2021+) also constituted a strategic pivot. "SO Games seized upon the digital sobriety question very early and carried the subject to the SNJV and will continue to drive within the international working groups dedicated to this subject" [FR224]. SO Games published a best practices guide, engaged in developing Jyros (a tool for measuring the players' carbon footprint), and collaborated with the SNJV for national labelling [FR160]. Similarly, SO Games engaged in event development with the Spawn festival in Angoulême, created in partnership with Cnam-Enjmin and Pôle Image Magelis [FR016, FR224], which attracted over 700 festivalgoers from its second edition onward.

10.3.5 The current ecosystem: maturity and perspectives

The 2021 economic data confirmed the attainment of critical mass: SO Games represents approximately 110 companies and indies, over 1000 full-time equivalent jobs for an estimated turnover of €110M, with growth exceeding 10% [FR020, FR224]. It confirmed also the presence of SO Games in the French Tech Bordeaux directory, the obtaining of regional Pégases awards [FR051], and the successful organization of Horizon(s) 2023 with 80+ studios and schools. The SO Games operational budget stood at €345.8k (with a 72% public - 28% private distribution) according to the internal documents, enabling increased professionalization of the actions. The 2024-2025 documents confirmed the maturity attained despite a membership decline (95 active members in SO Games) [FR224]. The ecosystem comprises industrial champions (Asobo with 270 employees, Ubisoft with 400+), a solid class of medium-sized studios (Motion Twin, Evil Empire with 70 employees, Shiro Games with 75 employees), and a dense fabric of innovative micro-studios. This balanced pyramidal structure, constructed over 20 years since Kalisto's collapse, positions the Bordeaux cluster among France's principal video game hubs, alongside Île-de-France and Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes [FR061].

10.4 Collective Actions

The collaborative infrastructure of the Bordeaux cluster manifests through formalized associative actions that address common challenges while preserving local specificities. D4.1's examination of SO·Games' activities revealed how collective initiatives balance diverse stakeholder needs across a geographically dispersed region. The following synthesis organizes these collective mechanisms:

D4.1 findings	Description
---------------	-------------

Network animation	Monthly after-work sessions in Bordeaux and Angoulême facilitate informal professional exchanges, evolving from social gatherings to structured formats including playtests and masterclasses. The Slack platform with specialized channels enables information exchanges and coordination across 84,000 km ² territory.
Business support services	"Boost My Games" program assists grant applications, reducing bureaucratic complexity for emerging studios. Wizz incubator provides 18-month intensive support for 6 projects annually. Collective negotiations secure preferential rates for trade fairs and professional services.
Shared external activities	Organized events segment by audience: public-facing Spawn festival for visibility, Game Dev Talks for technical skills, and executive events like Horizon targeting investors. Gamescom participation through shared exhibition space enables international visibility for resource-constrained indies.
Knowledge capitalization	Collaborative knowledge base on Slack transforms individual expertise into institutional memory, particularly valuable given scarce documented resources in French game development. Experienced members continuously update guidance materials accessible throughout ecosystem.
Solidarity mechanisms	Established "gentlemen's agreements" prevent talent poaching, while rapid peer support via Slack provides technical and HR responses. Collective project responses enable smaller studios to access larger contracts through coordinated bidding with work distribution across 2-4 studios.

Table 93 - Summary of D4.1. on the collective actions of Bordeaux cluster

The documentary analysis of the Bordeaux cluster's collective action portfolio highlights a remarkable trajectory, transitioning from informal post-Kalisto initiatives to a structured and formalized project. This evolution demonstrates a growing sophistication in three strategic domains: (i) territorial animation, (ii) training and recruitment support, and (iii) the pooling of commercial action. With an estimate budget of €325k in 2021 [FR224], SO Games deploys an arsenal of heterogeneous actions. Apart from their diversity, they are also complementary regarding many of their objectives. The Creative Tuesdays, after more than ten years of existence, have created a common culture. The START programme [FR097] and the Unity Centre position Bordeaux as a leader in training. Invest Gaming has democratized access to financing. The leadership on digital sobriety offers a unique differentiation.

These actions generated a dense relational network that has been documented:

- Studios-schools via the program START (alignment between training and needs)
- Companies-financing specialists via Invest Gaming (€500k/year mobilized)
- Video games-Industry via a dedicated VP (contracts signed)
- Local-international levels via pooled missions (36% export turnover)

The following table details the main collective actions carried out by So Games.

Category	Action	Creation	Frequency	Annual Impact
Animation	Creative Tuesday	2010	Monthly	600+ participants
	Game Masters' Nights	2019	Quarterly	400+ participants
Training	START	2017	Annual	60-120 middle schoolers
	Unity Center	2021	Continuous	30+ studios
Business	Invest Gaming	2018	Bi-annual	€500k loans
	Recruitment fair	2022	Annual	In development
Innovation	Digital sobriety	2019	Continuous	Guide + tool
	Bridges Industry	2021	Monthly	Contracts signed

Table 94 - Consolidated portfolio of collective actions

10.4.1 Territorial animation

The Creative Tuesdays (2010 - present)

Launched in June 2010, the Creative Tuesdays constitute one of the first services provided by Bordeaux Games. The concept is simple but effective. Each month, in a different location within the metropolis, three professionals share their feedback on a selected theme for 20 minutes each, followed by informal networking. This format has several virtues: it creates a regular meeting that structures the community's interactions, it allows the studios to make themselves known by hosting the event, and it generates documented business opportunities [FR219].

Dimension	Characteristics	Measured Impact
Format	3 feedback sessions x 20 min + networking	54 presentations/18 months
Frequency	Monthly, first Tuesday	Structuring meeting
Participation	30-80 participants	"Growing popularity"
Locations	Rotation between studios	Discovery of workspaces
Themes	Imposed, varied	Constitution of knowledge corpus

Table 95 - Impact of the creative Tuesdays

In 18 months, 18 editions mobilized the ecosystem, generating concrete business opportunities that are tracked, continuous collective learning, and a reinforced common culture [FR219]. For So Games these events create "a system of pooling and acceleration, where each participant shares their experience in terms of management (finance, legal...), creation, or even organization" [FR066].

The Game masters' nights (2019-present)

The Game Masters' Nights (renamed AJV Nights) adopt a quarterly format centred around an inspiring personality. They complement the Creative Tuesdays [FR219]. They bring together 90 to 140 participants around an inspiring figure from the sector. The 2019-2020 programming involved speakers such as Anthony Jauneaud (Night Call, independent Pégase), Louis Denizet (Hibernian Workshop), Salomé Strappazon (Ubisoft). These free evenings create a crucial link between students and professionals, facilitating the integration of young people into the ecosystem and reinforcing the school-industry continuum that is crucial for professional integration and generational renewal [FR219], directly responding to the training challenge identified by several sources [FR058].

The Informal Networks

Beyond the formal events, the ecosystem relies on documented informal networks:

- "A beer if not two": a monthly meeting bringing together 20-30 regular participants, generating "spontaneous collaborations" [FR224]
- Member afterworks: post-Creative Tuesday events with 50+ participants, ensuring the "consolidation of social ties" [FR224]

This informal dimension has served as the social cement of the cluster, facilitating the "circulation of talent" with "50% of companies less than 5 years old," demonstrating "a turnover that is accepted as normal, facilitating the diffusion of practices" [FR224].

10.4.2 Support for training and recruitment

One of the flagship actions supporting training is the START Programme (2017-present). Launched in 2017, START aims to enhance the early awareness of talent as well as the implementation of pedagogical innovation [FR097]. The programme reaches 60-120 ninth-grade middle schoolers annually with a full-day format with professionals from the regional studios. These sessions aim to be true immersions rather than simple presentations [FR219]. The model's success has generated national replication from other French associations and a planned territorial extension toward Northern Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Angoulême, Poitiers, La Rochelle) [FR224].

Beyond this programme, several other actions, as evidence in the following table, constitute a diversified architecture of support for training, including the "Creative Tuesdays."

Mechanism	Frequency	Measured Impact
Creative Tuesday	Monthly	54 presentations/18 months
Technical workshops	Quarterly	Unity adoption by 30+ studios
Masterclasses	Bi-monthly	100+ participants/session
START Programme	Annual	60-120 middle schoolers made aware
School juries	Continuous	Alignment of training/needs

Table 96 - Training support channels

This multi-channel architecture complements the formal infrastructure of the Gaming Campus (200+ students/year) [FR032] and the ENJMIN [FR044], creating a continuum from early awareness to continuous training.

The "Unity Excellence Centre" (2021-2022)

The Unity Excellence Centre aims to become the first European centre of its kind [FR224]. The initial investment of €50k structures this programme around several key axes:

- Provision of licenses at preferential rates (estimated 50% reduction)
- Training of trainers ("training the trainee")
- Internationally recognized certifications
- Privileged access to beta versions and technical support Budget: €50k initial investment

The projected impact—30+ studios equipped, 100+ developers trained annually [FR224]—aims to position Bordeaux as a European technical hub, reinforcing territorial attractiveness.

The National Recruitment Fair (2022-2025)

Faced with the finding that 52% of companies that are recruiting encounter chronic difficulties and matching problems between supply and demand [FR224; FR227], SO Games launched a national fair targeting this issue. The proposed hybrid format of the event combines:

- Structured recruiter/candidate meetings
- Masterclasses on emerging professions
- Game Jams for practical evaluation
- Speed recruiting inspired by the Game Connection

The stated ambition—to become "THE annual meeting for video game professionals and employment in France"—is based on the legitimacy acquired with the Spawn festival in Angoulême, which already attracts "700+ festivalgoers" [FR016, FR017]. This hybrid event, mixing video games and board games, fulfils a triple function: a public showcase for the studios, a B2B meeting space for developers, and a bridge with the gaming ecosystem in the broad sense.

10.4.3 Commercial pooling and representation

Common representation, particularly vis-à-vis the institutional actors, and commercial pooling figure among the key missions of the formal professional associations that pilot the cluster. These missions are implemented through several actions.

Invest Gaming and alternative financing (2018-present)

Invest Gaming aims to facilitate access to financing, generating nearly €500k/year in loans [FR224] with an important ROI for the association.

Component	Description	Results
Format	Collective pitches + individual B2B	Maximized efficiency
Participants	Studios + local banks + investors + public funds	Reinforcing the intra-ecosystem collaboration
Frequency	Bi-annual	Reassuring regularity
Impact	"Nearly €500k/year in loans"	Exceptional ROI
Innovation	Direct connection	Reduction of information asymmetry

Table 97 - Architecture of Invest Gaming

This mechanism is complementary with the existing public mechanisms: the CIJV (30% of eligible expenses, ceiling of €6M/year), a "significant" regional production fund, Magelis aid, and BPI France innovation loans [FR224].

The Video Game/Industry bridges

SO Games establishes unique bridges with the traditional industry through a dedicated architecture [FR224]. This approach generates:

- Intersectoral events: monthly studio/industrial meetings
- Tangible results: "numerous contracts signed," diversification of studio revenues
- Collaboration with the SPN (Permanent Digital Secretariat) as an interface

This strategy responds to the technological convergence (Industry 4.0, digital twins) identified in the documents, opening new markets for local studios such as Asobo with its XR division [FR104, FR167].

Pooled international representation

From 2009 onward, Bordeaux Games organized several collective international missions and group participations at major trade fairs such as

- Gamescom Cologne: Collective booth
- Game Connection: Coordinated participation with negotiated rates [FR185]
- Mobile World Congress: Exploratory missions to emerging markets
- GDC San Francisco (SO Games objective): Ambition of access to the US market

These missions help to pool costs (division by 5-10), offer superior collective visibility, and allow small studios to access events that would otherwise be inaccessible [FR219].

10.4.4 Digital sobriety as a new theme

SO Games aims to be the "first French association on this theme" [FR224] with the following chronology:

- Late 2019: Creation of a working group (strategic note 9/12/2019)
- 2021: Publication of a best practices guide
- 2022: Development of "Jyros, the environmental impact measurement tool dedicated to the sector" within an inter-cluster framework [FR224]
- 2023: Contribution to National SNJV coordination on the theme
- 2025: CNC certification obtained

The official press release confirms: "S/O Games seized upon this digital sobriety question very early and now carries the subject to the SNJV and will continue to drive within the international working groups" [FR162].

The actions deployed cover the entire value chain:

- Reduction of hardware footprint (54% of emissions = manufacturing)
- Distribution optimization (download vs streaming)
- Management of company data (hot/cold storage)
- Player awareness of consumption

The established partnerships—Planet Tech'Care, Institut Numérique Responsable, Shift Project, CNC (JYROS approval)—position SO Games as a national reference on the subject [FR162].

10.5 Motivations, Benefits, & Contributions of the Stakeholders

The differential value creation across stakeholder categories reflects the cluster's structural heterogeneity, where an important majority of small structures coexist with major international subsidiaries. D4.1's stakeholder analysis revealed how benefits distribution creates both solidarity mechanisms and governance tensions. The synthesis below captures these differentiated impacts:

D4.1 findings	Description
Micro-studios benefits	Availability and circulation of information transform operational capacity through rapid peer support on legal, technical, and regulatory challenges.
Intermediate companies value	Resource optimization through pooled support functions and accelerated talent access via network effects. Collaborative project opportunities enable participation in larger contracts. Entrepreneurial spillover effects create growth pathways demonstrated by Motion Twin and Asobo spin-off patterns.
Large studio advantages	Regional attractiveness aids recruitment for Bordeaux relocations, with one studio manager reporting 450 trainee applications addressed through SO.Games Day. Corporate social responsibility demonstration addresses public scrutiny, though direct operational benefits remain limited given internal support functions.
Asymmetric utility distribution	SO.Games director acknowledges "80-20 Pareto law" where services primarily benefit smaller structures. Large studios participate through "sponsorship" logic rather than operational necessity, creating ongoing tensions over resource allocation and strategic priorities.
Cross-territorial benefits	Angoulême studios leverage Bordeaux's commercial networks while maintaining creative independence. Bordeaux companies access ENJMIN talent pipeline. This complementarity partially offsets geographic fragmentation across Nouvelle-Aquitaine's 84,000 km ² .

Table 98 - Summary of D4.1. on the motivations, benefits and contributions of Bordeaux cluster's stakeholders

The documentary analysis of the Bordeaux cluster reveals an ecosystem where actors with heterogeneous and sometimes contradictory motivations coexist. This complexity is also visible in

the balance sought between contribution and retribution. The following matrix details, for each category of actors, the specific objectives pursued and their contributions to the collective dynamic.

10.5.1 Detailed matrix of motivations and benefits by phase

Phase	Main Motivations	Sought Benefits	Obtained Benefits
2002 - 2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-crisis survival • "To better coexist" • To avoid fatal isolation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost pooling • Access to public funding • Collective visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • €200-450k subsidies • Creation of Asobo (270 employees) • 5 viable companies
2007 - 2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidation of positions • Development of new markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professionalization • Facilitation of recruitment • Pooling of international missions • B2B networking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 37-38 job offers/year • Missions/year (Gamescom, MWC) • Creative Tuesday (business)
2017 - 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upscaling • AAA collaborations • Regional leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubisoft partnerships • Attraction of global talent • Valorisation of expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Many more requests" • Access to AAA projects • International recognition

Table 99 - Evolution of the motivations and benefits of the ex-Kalisto entrepreneurs

The documentary analysis confirms that the challenges of pooling, mutual aid, and structuration were common to all the structures that emerged in the wake of Kalisto's disappearance. The creation of Bordeaux Games had as main objectives: mutual aid, creation, recruitment, and support for the sector [FR220]. The association sought to create "a system of pooling and acceleration" that supports the local ecosystem [FR219]. Among the major local studios, Ubisoft is a particular case regarding its motivation since it joined the local ecosystem recently. Its motivations are different evidenced in the following table.

Phase	Main Motivations	Sought Benefits	Obtained Benefits
2017-2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pool of trained talent • "Very high-quality school network" • Competitive costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 400+ local developers • Service provider ecosystem • Institutional support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30→400 employees • Dominant position in the AAA segment

Table 100 - Motivations and Benefits of Ubisoft Bordeaux (2017-2021)

Phase	Main Motivations	Sought Benefits	Obtained Benefits
2007-2009	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capitalization on post-Kalisto assets • Investment prudence • Test of the sector's viability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservation of jobs • Territorial image • Economic diversification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12→17 members • First permanent staff 2008 • Progressive legitimization
2010-2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuration of the sector • Territorial attractiveness • Regional reform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical mass • National visibility • Fiscal returns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 31 members (2012) • CNC recognition
2017-2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change of scale • Vision of video games as a "major economic actor" • Search for national leadership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualified jobs • Private investments • International influence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 400 Ubisoft jobs • SO Games merger

Table 101 - Motivations and Benefits of Institutional partners

10.5.2 Motivations & benefits of studios & developers

2007 - 2010 Period

The period immediately following Kalisto's collapse in 2002 is characterized by primarily defensive motivations. The former Kalisto employees, while possessing strategic technical expertise acquired on ambitious productions [FR100], found themselves dispersed and isolated. The initial motivations centred on immediate survival: "to better coexist" and "to avoid fatal isolation" [FR220]. The internal documents stress on the precariousness of the situation. Thus, the collective organization was a response to a fundamental necessity: to maintain a critical mass of local competencies that risked definitive dispersion. The benefits sought during this period remained modest but vital. The cost pooling, particularly through the sharing of booths at professional trade fairs, allowed the studios to maintain a commercial presence that would otherwise have been difficult. Access to public funding, facilitated by collective representation, provided a financial breathing space for fragile structures. The collective visibility, superior to what each isolated studio could have achieved, opened doors that are difficult to access for atomized actors. The access to public aid generated between €200,000 and €450,000 in funding that kept fragile structures afloat. More fundamentally, this collective organization preserved the fabric of local competencies that could have been definitively dispersed after the Kalisto shock.

2010 - 2016 Period

The 2010-2016 period marked a shift from defensive motivations toward offensive ambitions. The studios, now consolidated, actively sought growth rather than mere survival. Access to talent became a priority, with 37 to 38 job offers transiting annually through the association, creating a structured local labour market [FR219]. Commercial development intensified through the Creative Tuesdays, which generated documented and traceable contracts between participants. Collaborative innovation emerged with cross-testing between non-competing studios, allowing production quality to be improved without the risk of cannibalization. Internationalization was organized through collective missions, making export accessible even to small structures [FR219].

The historic studios such as Asobo, Motion Twin, or Shiro Games embodied this collaborative dynamic. Their active participation in the Creative Tuesdays, with rotation between studios [FR219], created a virtuous mutual learning environment. Mentoring through the START program mobilized professionals from the regional studios [FR219], transmitting their expertise to the new generations. Several of these studios regularly opened their premises for community events, demonstrating a commitment that exceeded simple economic interest. This active involvement in formal and informal experience-sharing sessions, without competitive restriction, demonstrated remarkable collective maturity. The opening to independents in 2016 profoundly transformed the dynamics of actions and contributions as well as the benefits generated by collective action. The transition from 25 active members exclusively, mainly companies, to more than 50 members, including freelancers and individual developers, [FR219] democratized access to collective resources. Participation in free events intensified considerably, with the Game Masters' Nights attracting between 90 and 140 participants [FR219]. The independents enriched the Creative Tuesdays with their specialized expertise, bringing new perspectives on technological or creative niches. The intensive use of the employment platform, with 37 offers in 4.5 months [FR219], demonstrated the renewed dynamism of the local labour market.

The consolidation phase (2017-2023)

SO Games developed several mechanisms to align contributions and benefits. A first level of regulation was established through a progressive membership-fee structure, calculated on the basis

of company turnover and documented in the association's internal rules [FR227]. This structure guaranteed accessibility for independents and very small companies, while attributing higher contributions to major actors [FR227]. A second level of incentive came through the differentiation of services. A set of basic services remained open to all members — networking, after works, support with funding applications, and event discounts — while more specialized services (international missions, promotion in national and European events, institutional positioning) targeted the association's larger contributors [FR227]. Visibility at collective booths and during joint events was also distributed in proportion to members' level of contribution, further reinforcing this principle of reciprocity [FR227]. The **Invest Gaming** programme illustrates this logic of organized reciprocity. Studios agree to share detailed information about their projects, sometimes of a strategic nature, in return for facilitated access to meetings with financiers and investors [FR224]. This reciprocal transparency has created a virtuous circle in which trust builds access to resources, which in turn reinforces trust across the ecosystem [FR224]. The Ubisoft's arrival in 2017 impacted also the motivations and ambitions of the local entrepreneurs. The collaboration with global leaders allowed independent studios to reinforce their skills and competencies especially in international-level production methods. International visibility increased mechanically through association with Ubisoft's influence, facilitating international partnerships. Technical innovation accelerated with access to the Unity Excellence Centre, positioning the local studios at the technological forefront.

10.5.3 Motivations & benefits of institutional organisms

The post-Kalisto trust issues (2007-2009)

The local authorities, deeply marked by Kalisto's bankruptcy and its 300 lost jobs, initially adopted an approach of extreme caution. Their motivations were limited to maintaining the existing employment, excluding any risky bet on a sector that had just demonstrated its fragility. The support remained minimal. The main objective consisted of avoiding a new social catastrophe rather than actively developing the sector.

The progressive trust (2010-2016)

Faced with encouraging results and the resilience demonstrated by the ecosystem, the institutions evolved toward more substantial engagement. The industry, having proven not only its survival capacity but also its growth potential, transformed the institutional motivations. Support budgets grew regularly while major events such as the Creative Tuesdays received official support. The sought and obtained benefits included increased territorial visibility and reinforced attractiveness for young talent, contributing to the image of an innovative territory.

The strategic investment (2017-2023)

The recent period consecrated the video games as a priority sector for territorial development. The progression of institutional support was reflected in the budget, which rose to €345,800 in 2021, of which €250,000 (72%) came from public subsidies [FR219].

The institutional motivations now embraced territorial differentiation through the creative economy, recognizing video games as a marker of innovation and modernity. The creation of SO Games in 2021, merging the regional associations [FR015, FR224] institutionalized this ambition with an ecosystem representing 110 companies and independents, more than 1000 jobs, and €110 million in turnover [FR015]. The obtained benefits fully justified this investment: the creation of more than 1000 direct jobs, international attractiveness validated by Ubisoft's installation, perceived as a global validation, and substantial reinforcement of the training ecosystem.

10.5.4 Motivations & benefits of the training organizations

The initial disconnection (2007-2012)

During the cluster's early years, video game training programmes operated in relative isolation. The links with the local studios remained tenuous or even non-existent, leading graduates to seek opportunities elsewhere for lack of identified local outlets. The schools' absence of involvement in the association deprived the ecosystem of a structured talent pipeline, perpetuating the vicious circle of brain drain.

The progressive convergence (2013-2017)

The intermediate period witnessed the beginning of convergence between the academic world and the local industry. Internships in local studios multiplied, creating the first lasting bridges between training and employment. Interventions by professionals in the curricula enriched the relevance of the teachings while creating valuable personal connections. Growing participation in the association's events progressively integrated the schools into the cluster's collective life.

The complete integration (2018-2023)

The opening of the Gaming Campus in 2018 marked the culmination of this evolution with total integration into the ecosystem. The establishment became an active member of SO Games, fully participating in the governance and collective initiatives. The co-creation of programmes with the studios guaranteed the alignment between training and industrial needs [FR032]. Local career outlets became systematic, with Ubisoft recruiting more than 50 graduates annually, creating a virtuous circle of talent attraction and retention [FR034].

The documented mutual benefits validated this integrated model. The schools achieved a local placement rate exceeding 80% versus only 30% before the integration, guaranteeing their attractiveness. The studios had access to a pool of custom-trained talent, drastically reducing recruitment costs and delays. The territory benefited from increased retention of young graduates, reversing the historic trend of talent exodus.

10.5.5 Motivations & benefits of new entrants

Ubisoft's installation triggered an attraction effect and reinforced the visibility and legitimacy of the local ecosystem, which already hosted strong historical studios such as Asobo, Motion Twin, and Shiro Games [FR221, FR224]. The association progressively opened its activities to independents and solo developers, facilitating their integration into the professional network [FR221]. In parallel, technological convergence emerged in the region, notably with Asobo's collaboration on Microsoft's HoloLens [FR167] and Nova-Box's research in artificial intelligence, illustrating the cross-fertilization between video games and emerging technologies [FR221]. The motivations of new entrants underline the advantages of the territory. Bordeaux offers facilitated access to both French and European markets [FR224], combined with structurally lower costs of living than Paris (FR183 highlights comparative indicators). While precise figures on salaries and real-estate costs are not documented in the association's reports, the overall cost differential remains an advantage for studios. The region's quality of life — between the Atlantic Ocean, vineyards, and cultural richness — is highlighted by both Ubisoft and SO.Games as a decisive factor in attracting and retaining talent [FR052, FR224]. The cluster, dense yet on a human scale, facilitates direct exchanges and informal collaboration that are more difficult in larger metropolises [FR224].

10.6 Cooperative Networks & Proximity Dynamics of the Cluster

The analysis of the collaboration networks and proximity dynamics of the Bordeaux cluster reveals a rich relational architecture constructed over two decades.

10.6.1 Geographical proximity

The spatial organization of the cluster is articulated around three distinct zones, detailed above in the geography of the cluster, and which reflect the historical evolution and the economic logics of the territory. The Bordeaux hyper centre constitutes the historic core where the emblematic independent studios are concentrated. Motion Twin, Shiro Games, Big Bad Wolf... established in the city centre [FR061]. The immediate periphery represents the territory of contemporary expansion especially with Ubisoft establishment, thus creating a new attraction pole [FR074]. This zone offers more affordable rents, allowing growing studios to expand without leaving the ecosystem. The Bordeaux-Angoulême axis forms a 120-kilometer corridor structuring a video game meta-region that is unique in France. ENJMIN, symbolically located at "138 rue de Bordeaux" in Angoulême, and the Pôle Magelis create a territorial continuum that transcends the classic administrative boundaries [FR223]. The flows between these two poles include student internships, graduate recruitments, and event co-organizations that progressively weave a unified regional identity [FR223]. The Creative Tuesdays embody a deliberate spatial strategy of community building [FR219]. The analysis reveals a systematic rotation of host locations, with each session being held in a different studio. This practice enables the mutual discovery of workspaces, facilitating collaborations. The standardized format—three twenty-minute feedback sessions on an imposed theme—has generated 54 documented presentations, constituting a unique corpus of collective knowledge. The Palais des Congrès functions as an "event cathedral" for the cluster, hosting major events that put Bordeaux on the international stage, such as The ESWC 2017 in its first summer edition, the Foundations of Digital Games 2011 with 150 international researchers for 4 days, or the Gamification Experience Europe 2013 [FR219].

10.6.2 Organizational proximity

The Bordeaux cluster has developed a governance structure articulated at several complementary levels. At the micro level, studios maintain informal mechanisms of cooperation outside formal institutions. Activities such as Creative Tuesdays, after works, and cross-testing between non-competing studios made it possible to share technical expertise in non-differentiating domains and to improve production quality without commercial risk [FR219, FR227]. At the meso level, the transformation of Bordeaux Games into SO·Games provided the organizational core of the cluster. The formal governance followed a classic model, with an executive board composed of a president, secretary, and treasurer, and a board of directors representing the diversity of the ecosystem [FR219, FR224]. As early as 2009, four thematic commissions were created — trade fairs, serious gaming, HR/training, and communication — each composed of six members meeting quarterly, ensuring distributed governance and avoiding concentration of power [FR219]. The professionalization of the association was also reflected in the growth of its permanent staff: one employee was recruited in November 2008 [FR219], this position was maintained in 2016 [FR221], and by 2021 SO Games operated with two permanent staff members, thanks to pooling with SYRPIN [FR224]. This lean but stable structure enabled continuity of operations while progressively reinforcing the association's capacity. The macro level articulates the regional and national dimensions. The integration into the SNJV board of directors through the regional associations college involves four quarterly meetings and nine annual board meetings since 2009, ensuring a Bordeaux voice in the national instances [FR081]. The merger creating SO Games in 2021 expanded

the perimeter to all of Nouvelle-Aquitaine, creating sufficient critical mass to carry weight in national debates [FR102,FR221]. The coordination with Magelis for the organization of the VideoGame Economic Forum illustrates the capacity to mobilize territorial resources for major events. The international level with collective missions, such as the participation in the Gamescom in Cologne or the Mobile World Congress, enable the Bordeaux studios to access international markets with pooled costs [FR219].

10.6.3 Cognitive proximity

The analysis highlights an interesting stratification of knowledge that constitutes the cluster's cognitive capital. The technical foundation inherited from Kalisto (2002-2007) forms the first founding stratum. The twelve ex-Kalisto employees who created Asobo disseminated a common technical culture forged in the experience of ambitious productions. This expertise includes the mastery of collaboration processes with prestigious licenses such as Disney and Pixar, knowledge of international AAA quality standards, and a refined understanding of industrial production processes [FR052, FR104]. This common technical base facilitates collaborations and establishes a shared language within the cluster [FR100]. The 2007-2016 period witnessed the emergence of a productive hybridization between indie and AAA cultures [FR221, FR223]. Motion Twin brought its unique cooperative model and its status as a pioneer of free-to-play in France, demonstrating that viable alternatives to traditional production models existed. Shiro Games developed recognized excellence in strategy games, enriching the collective creative repertoire [FR115]. This cognitive diversification enabled the cluster to avoid excessive specialization and maintained a multidirectional innovation capacity. The injection of Ubisoft methodologies from 2017 onward constitutes the third stratum. Its arrival reinforced the diffusion of industrialized processes capable of managing teams of more than 400 people, world-class AAA pipelines, and complex project management methodologies. The fourth stratum, that of emerging knowledge, positions the cluster on the most recent technologies. Asobo developed globally recognized XR/VR expertise through its HoloLens partnership with Microsoft [FR065]. The Concoursmania Group positioned itself as the "European leader" in B2B gamification, opening new markets [FR090]. The anticipation of mutations linked to AI and cloud gaming prepared the ecosystem for upcoming disruptions. The circulation of knowledge is organized through three complementary channels that guarantee efficient knowledge diffusion. The formal mechanisms include the labelling of training programmes by the SNJV [FR187], participation in school juries that enables the alignment of curricula with industrial needs, and the START support programme that creates early awareness among young people about the professions [FR227]. These arrangements create a structured pipeline for competency transmission. The semi-formal channels, particularly the Creative Tuesdays constitute the backbone of collective learning. The technical workshops enable the rapid adoption of new technologies, as demonstrated by the diffusion of Unity in more than 30 studios. The bi-monthly masterclasses, regularly attracting more than 100 participants, create moments of intensive learning on specialized subjects [FR219].

The informal networks, often underestimated, play a crucial role. "A beer if not two," a monthly meeting bringing together 20 to 30 regular participants, generates spontaneous collaborations impossible in a formal setting. The post-Creative Tuesday 'afterwork', mobilizing more than 50 participants, consolidate the social ties essential to trust. The circulation of talent, with 50% of companies less than five years old, demonstrates a turnover that is accepted as normal and that paradoxically facilitates the diffusion of practices and knowledge [FR219].

10.6.4 Institutional proximity

The construction of the cluster's institutional legitimacy follows a coherent trajectory over fifteen years. The experimental phase (2007-2009) was characterized by cautious support from the local authorities. The growth from 5 to 17 members during this period nevertheless demonstrated a positive dynamic [FR219]. The consolidation phase (2013-2016) with the opening to independents and freelancers in 2016, potentially doubling the number of members [FR219, FR222]. The development of labelling programmes and the establishment of structured partnerships with the institutions confirmed the organizational maturation. The ecosystem mobilizes three types of complementary institutional networks. The vertical networks connect the cluster to national and European funding sources: the CNC for production support funds, the ministries for the video game tax credit representing 30% of eligible expenses, and Europe through the Horizon programmes. These connections guarantee access to critical financial resources. The horizontal networks create territorial synergies. The CCI co-organizes the major events, bringing legitimacy and resources. The French Tech labels the sector's startups, facilitating their access to support mechanisms. Invest in Bordeaux promotes the territory's attractiveness, attracting talent and investments [FR052]. The transversal networks weave connections with the broader innovation ecosystem. The universities develop joint research projects, Pôle Emploi finances targeted training programmes responding to the sector's specific needs, and BPIFrance provides the innovation financing necessary for R&D [FR026].

10.6.5 Social proximity

The cluster's social capital is organized around three major categories of actors with distinct functions. The hard core, composed of 30 to 40 people, brings together the leaders of the historic studios, linked by more than fifteen years of common history since the Kalisto era. These strong ties, forged in adversity and reinforced by successes, enable cooperation on sensitive subjects impossible without absolute trust. This group constitutes the cluster's strategic brain, capable of rapidly making decisions engaging the entire ecosystem. The extended circle, approximately 200 to 300 people, includes the regular participants in the Creative Tuesdays and the active members of the association. These ties that can be qualified as "weak" but numerous and diversified, facilitate the fluid circulation of information throughout the ecosystem. This intermediate layer plays a crucial role as a transmission belt between the decision-making core and the periphery. The periphery, with more than 800 people, encompasses the participants in public events and the cluster's sympathizers. This critical mass ensures the sector's visibility and constitutes the pool from which future talents and entrepreneurs emerge. The Bordeaux Lyon Game Party mobilizing these broader audiences creates a sense of belonging that transcends the strict professional circle.

10.7 Resources, Competencies & Capacities

The governance architecture of SO Games reflects attempts to reconcile diverse territorial cultures, asymmetric company needs, and complex multi-level public funding within a unified organizational framework. D4.1's institutional analysis revealed how resource mobilization and governance mechanisms navigate these structural tensions.

D4.1 findings	Description
Financial architecture	SO Games' annual budget includes funding from Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region, Bordeaux Métropole, Grand Angoulême. Membership fees range from €50 (micro-enterprises) to several thousand euros (large studios).
Governance structure	A Board of Directors balances territorial (Bordeaux/Angoulême) and sectoral (large/small studios) representation. Recent leadership transition from Stéphane Bonazza (large studio, event focus) to

	David Elahee (community support emphasis) reflects balancing between business growth and mutual aid orientations.
Operational capacity	2.5 full-time equivalent permanent staff supplemented by active volunteer members in decisive organizational roles. Slack platform, functions as operational "nervous system".
Governance mechanisms	Informal adjustments coexist with formal conventions. Slack enables decentralized coordination while preserving local specificities through dedicated geographical channels. Discord segments specific audiences, revealing organizational sophistication in managing diverse stakeholder needs.
Strategic tensions	Reconciling Bordeaux's corporate approach with Angoulême's community philosophy creates ongoing governance challenges. The small structures versus large companies distribution generates persistent debates over resource allocation and strategic priorities.

Table 102 - Summary of D4.1. on the resources, competencies and governance of Bordeaux cluster

The documentary analysis of the resources and competencies of the Bordeaux cluster reveals the progressive construction of a distinctive territorial capital over two decades. From the post-Kalisto survival (2002) to the current international recognition, the ecosystem has accumulated a distinctive set of tangible and intangible resources, developed specific organizational competencies, and demonstrated dynamic capacities for adaptation and transformation.

10.7.1 Infrastructure & tangible resources

The physical infrastructure as a foundation for development

The cluster relies on a diversified physical infrastructure that structures collective activity. The CCI spaces in downtown Bordeaux offer meeting and event rooms regularly made available for collective activities. Their central location facilitates accessibility and reinforces the sector's visibility in the urban space. The Pôle Magelis in Angoulême constitutes a campus dedicated to image and video games, with studios and amphitheatres valued at €5,600 annually for SO Games [FR31], creating a competency hub complementary to the Bordeaux hub. The Bastide-Niel district represents the most significant recent urban transformation. This new creative district has housed Ubisoft since 2023 [FR023, FR074], materializing the territory's ambition in the urban landscape. This installation, the fruit of massive private investments, creates a new centre of gravity for the cluster. The Gaming Campus, with its three schools and cutting-edge equipment, trains more than 200 students annually [FR032], constituting a critical training infrastructure for the cluster's sustainability. This local talent production capacity represents a major competitive advantage in a sector where the war for talent is intensifying.

The company base and the achieved critical mass

As detailed above in the section on the cluster's company demography, the quantitative evolution of the cluster and the diversity of its companies and key stakeholders constitute one of its key strategic assets. The qualitative structure reveals a balanced ecosystem between major champions (more than 100 employees, such as Asobo and Ubisoft [FR056], medium-sized studios (20 to 50 employees, such as Motion Twin and Shiro Games), and more than 80 micro-studios and independents complete this pyramid, ensuring creative and entrepreneurial renewal. Over the last 5 years, SO Games has averaged approximately one hundred members [FR013F, R227] and displays the ambition to become the "first cluster after Capital Games." This pool of diverse companies and actors constitutes one of the sources of attractiveness [FR052].

The mobilizable financial resources

Beyond SO Games' operational budget of €336,000 [FR227], the ecosystem can mobilize substantial financial resources. The video game tax credit (CIJV) makes it possible to recover 30% of eligible expenses with a ceiling of €6 million per company per year [FR026, FR185], representing major public support for innovation. The regional production fund [FR078, FR026] demonstrates the regional commitment. The Magelis aid specifically supports production and installation in Angoulême, creating territorial complementarity. BPI France provides innovation loans dedicated to video games [FR026].

10.7.2 Intangible resources and immaterial capital

Human and technical capital as the foundation of excellence

The distinctive technical expertise and the local human capital are also an asset of the cluster. The talent pipeline has been considerably strengthened with the development of local training organizations and programmes specialized in video games (the Gaming Campus, ENJMIN...). A form of informal specialization has also occurred between the Gaming Campus, which focuses on initial training, and the ENJMIN, which provides high-level national executive training [FR044]. The technical and managerial competencies accumulated at the territorial level reflect the acquired organizational maturity. Complex project management (AAA) and multicultural management of international teams are the norm for the major studios. The piloting of AAA projects with budgets of €10 to 50 million demonstrates the managerial upscaling. The different studios are complementary through their specializations in terms of games: Asobo has established itself as a global reference in realistic simulation and XR/VR, validated by its global partnership with Microsoft on Flight Simulator [FR104]. Motion Twin masters procedural gameplay and the roguelike genre, with Dead Cells exceeding 6 million sales and winning the 2018 Game Award for best independent game [FR116]. Shiro Games asserts itself as a European leader in real-time strategy with titles such as Northgard and Dune: Spice Wars [FR115]. Big Bad Wolf excels in AAA interactive narrative, a competency validated by its acquisition by Nacon [FR107]. Dotemu has developed unique expertise in "pixel-perfect" remakes, with the success of Streets of Rage 4 confirming this specialization [FR119].

The social capital and multi-scale networks

The cluster's relational architecture extends across three complementary geographical scales. At the local level, more than 800 participants in regular events [FR219] create exceptional relational density, particularly concentrated in downtown Bordeaux. This physical proximity facilitates the spontaneous interactions that generate innovations. The national anchoring materialized by the presence on the SNJV board of directors since 2008 [FR219] and the close cooperative ties with national instances such as the CNC or BPI [FR219]. The ties established with the other major clusters—notably Game Only in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes and Capital Games in Île-de-France—create a national network for the exchange of best practices. The international connections of the local companies in the sector have also multiplied. The relationships with global publishers through Ubisoft, Asobo's Microsoft partnership, and the global networks of the ex-Kalisto employees create bridges to global markets. The relational density metrics confirm this richness: the Creative Tuesdays mobilize 30 to 80 participants monthly, the Game Masters' Nights 90 to 140 participants quarterly, and the Angoulême festival attracts more than 700 visitors annually [FR017]. The connections/company ratio, estimated between 15 and 20, demonstrates significant relational density. The integration into the French Tech Bordeaux ecosystem demonstrates a certain hybridization in the assembly of collaborative projects, opening gateways with technology startups

and research laboratories. This porosity between the creative and technological worlds constitutes a key asset of the cluster. The obtaining of the regional Pégases awards [FR051], the institutional support of the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region (€150.7k annually), and the organization of events such as Horizon(s) 2023 (80+ studios and schools) demonstrate the cluster's capacity to federate beyond traditional boundaries.

The reputational and symbolic capital

The cluster's historical legitimacy is anchored in the Kalisto heritage, which positioned Bordeaux on the global video game map. The post-crisis renaissance demonstrates the cluster's collective resilience capacity. The informal validation by Ubisoft, which chose Bordeaux for its "first studio creation in France in 21 years" [FR057], constitutes a strong market signal. The same applies to the international successes of the cluster's companies, which continuously reinforce this reputation (Asobo's Microsoft Flight Simulator, Motion Twin's Dead Cells, Asobo's A Plague Tale...). The thematic leadership on digital sobriety, with SO Games as the "first French association on this theme" [FR162, FR224], also positions the cluster on future challenges and on important societal issues. Motion Twin's cooperative model inspires studios worldwide that are seeking alternatives to traditional capitalistic structures.

10.7.3 The distinctive competencies and collective know-how

Event engineering constitutes an important organizational competency of the cluster, whether for small-scale events for community animation or for large-scale events operating at the national level. Territorial animation involves both regular local events such as the Creative Tuesdays and major international trade fairs such as the ESWC 2017 and the Foundations of Digital Games 2011, which hosted 150 international researchers [FR219]. Multi-actor intermediation also represents a strategic organizational competency developed over two decades. The studio-school interface is embodied in the START programme and participation in juries, guaranteeing the alignment between training and needs [FR227, FR228]. The co-creation of training programmes illustrates an organizational capacity for innovation. The alignment of the Gaming Campus with industrial needs, the shared governance of the ENJMIN, and the collaborative awareness-raising START programme create a training-employment continuum beneficial to all the cluster's actors [FR224, FR225]. The pooled R&D projects that focus on organizational and social innovation, following the example of the actions and the pioneering project on digital sobriety, position Bordeaux cluster as a national prescriber on this emerging issue and represent the development of collective organizational capacities by the cluster [FR225, FR228]. The cluster demonstrates also a remarkable absorption capacity across four dimensions. Technological absorption is illustrated by the adoption of Unity through the centre of excellence, equipping more than 30 studios [FR224]. The integration of talent flows from Ubisoft raises the standards of the entire ecosystem. The adaptation of external models such as Game Connection enriches event practices. The importation of QWL and CSR practices [FR223] creates differentiation on employer attractiveness. The cluster's evolution demonstrates permanent adaptation to environmental changes. The 2002-2007 period witnessed the transition from individual survival strategies to a structured collective approach [FR219]. The opening to independents in 2016 doubled the potential member base [FR222]. The 2021 regional merger created the necessary critical mass [FR224, FR227]. The pivot toward digital sobriety (2019-2025) anticipated environmental challenges [FR225, FR227]. Resilience and adaptation constitute key competencies of the cluster. The post-Kalisto survival (2002), the digital pivot during COVID, and the successful regional merger in 2021 demonstrate good adaptive capacity. The cluster has demonstrated its capacity to fundamentally transform itself. The transition from 5 to 150 targeted companies represents a major scale transformation [FR219, FR228]. The evolution from a local

anchoring toward a regional then national dimension demonstrates growing ambition. The mutation from a survival logic toward excellence and then thematic leadership illustrates a trajectory of continuous upscaling. The transformation from a mono-studio ecosystem (Kalisto) to a diversified and resilient ecosystem constitutes the major accomplishment of these two decades.

10.8 The Financial Model of the Bordeaux Cluster

The analysis of the financial model of the Bordeaux cluster reveals an economic structure in full transformation, transitioning from an almost total dependence on public funding toward a progressive diversification of revenue sources. With an operational budget of €345,800 in 2021 [FR224], SO Games illustrates the challenges and opportunities of a regional cluster seeking to build its economic viability in a sector with complex economic models.

10.8.1 Anatomy of the SO Games economic model (2021-2025)

The revenue structure

The 2021 budget of SO Games shows a financial architecture where public subsidies massively dominate, with €250,000 representing 72.3% of the total resources [FR032]. This dependence results from a deliberate strategic choice aimed at mobilizing maximum public support for the cluster's development [FR224]. The Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region plays the role of principal financier with €150,700 (43.6%) [FR032]. This financing is accompanied by rigorous conditionality, including quarterly activity reports and a three-year renewable pluriannual commitment [FR224, FR227]. The local authorities provide complementary territorial support, with Bordeaux Métropole, Grand Angoulême, and other agglomerations [FR032]. The own resources, although a minority at 27.7%, reveal a certain diversification [FR032]. The fees from member companies in 2021 generated €35,000 with a recovery rate of 92%, demonstrating the adherents' commitment [FR032]. The event services (trade fair booths €20,000, training €10,000) demonstrate a capacity to valorise the accumulated expertise. The private partnerships, particularly with Unity for the Excellence Centre and various event sponsors, provide an additional €20,000 [FR032]. The exceptional resources of 2021 (€10,800 in fee recovery) are not sustainable but demonstrate rigorous debt management [FR032].

The expense structure

The analysis of expenses reveals an allocation that massively privileges operational action over structural costs [FR224]. The wage bill represents 34.7% of the budget, with two full-time permanent staff (€100,000 in loaded salaries) and €20,000 in territorial animation through temporary contracts and freelancers. This lean structure ensures flexibility and operational continuity [FR032]. The operational programmes absorb 44.2% of the budget, confirming the priority given to action. The Unity Excellence Centre mobilizes €50,000 in initial investment. The territorial events (€22,500) finance the Creative Tuesdays (€8,000), the AJV Nights (€5,000), the Angoulême Game Festival (€7,500), and Invest Gaming (€2,000). Business development (€25,000) and international travel (€20,000) support the internationalization of the member studios [FR032].

The structural costs remain contained at 21.1%, including a significant valuation of volunteer work (€52,800 for 1,500 hours at €35/hour), which demonstrates the members' committed engagement. The premises represent only €5,600 thanks to the provision by the CCI and Magelis, illustrating the efficiency of territorial pooling [FR032].

10.8.2 The sectoral financing mechanisms

The ecosystem mobilizes several complementary financing mechanisms. The Video Game Tax Credit (CIJV) constitutes the central mechanism [FR026, [FR032](#), FR224]. This mechanism, described as "indispensable to remain in the race" against Canada, which offers 37.5%, represents massive public support for innovation. The regional production fund, created in 2017, provides significant repayable advances [[FR078](#), [FR026](#), FR224]. The actors praise a "very good start," even if the mechanism remains modest compared to other regions [[FR071](#), FR224]. The Magelis aid specifically supports installation and production in Angoulême, creating territorial complementarity. BPI France completes the system with innovation loans dedicated to video games [[FR078](#), FR186]. The Invest Gaming programme generates "nearly €500k/year in loans granted" [[FR026](#)], democratizing access to traditional bank financing.

10.8.3 The Financial autonomisation trajectory

The 2021-2023 period was characterized by the stabilization of the member base around one hundred adherents and the launch of the Unity Excellence Centre, requiring a substantial initial investment. The dependence on public funding remained high at over 70% [FR224]. The priority objective consisted of demonstrating the impact and the value created to justify continued public support. The 2024-2025 phase witnessed a diversification of revenues aimed at progressively reducing the vulnerability to public budgetary trade-offs and improving self-financing to reach a level of 25% by 2025 [FR224]. The main revenue sources are the national employment fair, Unity certifications, and services to companies outside the video game sector, exploiting the technological convergences [FR224]. The 2026 horizon targets 40% in own resources, a threshold considered as guaranteeing sufficient operational autonomy. The volume effect, with an objective of more than 150 members contributing an average of €600, would generate €90,000 in membership fees. The premium services differentiated according to size and needs would create new revenue sources. The event revenues should exceed €100,000 with the upscaling of the events [FR224]. The elimination or reduction of regional subsidies constitutes one of the major risks highlighted in the analysis, which could call into question the viability of the cluster's financial model. The same applies to the Unity Centre, whose failure after the initial investment would create a dead loss difficult to absorb. The current major sectoral crisis could also severely test the current financial resilience of the Bordeaux association [[FR094](#)].

10.9 Structure, Modalities, and Governance Mechanisms

The governance of the Bordeaux cluster was constructed within the singular context of the post-Kalisto era and gradually took shape over fifteen years, transitioning from an experimental participatory governance model (Bordeaux Games 2007-2020) to an integrated regional structure (SO Games 2021+) capable of coordinating more than 100 stakeholders across 12 departments [FR219, FR222, FR224]. Various adaptive measures—thematic committees, a VP for Video Games/Industry, differentiated territorial coverage—have enabled the deployment of adequate coordination mechanisms allowing the collaboration of actors with divergent logics [FR224, FR226]. The governance architecture that has been put in place need to address various critical challenges, particularly ensuring resilience, legitimacy, and adaptive capacity, articulating internal democracy with operational efficiency, and balancing local anchoring with national ambition.

10.9.1 The governance architecture of the Bordeaux Cluster

The creation of Bordeaux Games in 2007 was accompanied by the definition of a participatory governance architecture.

Instance	Composition	Role	Frequency
General Assembly	All members	Strategic directions	Annual
Board of Directors	7 elected members	Executive decisions	Quarterly
Executive Bureau	President, treasurer, secretary	Day-to-day management	Monthly
Committees	4x6 members	Thematic work	Quarterly

Table 103 - Formal Governance Structure of Bordeaux Games

This four-level structure guarantees a distributed governance that deliberately avoids the concentration of power. The annual general assembly brings together all members to define the strategic directions, ensuring the democratic legitimacy of the decisions [FR219]. The board of directors, composed of seven elected members, makes quarterly executive decisions, creating a balance between representativeness and efficiency. The restricted bureau (president, treasurer, secretary) ensures monthly day-to-day management without being able to become autonomous from the broader instances [FR219]. Four specialized committees, each with six members, meet quarterly. The Trade Show Committee organizes the events and external representation [FR219]. The Serious Gaming Committee explores diversification toward B2B markets. The HR/Training Committee structures the talent pipeline. The Communications Committee manages visibility and territorial lobbying. This architecture ensures that each strategic domain benefits from dedicated attention while avoiding the overload of the executive bureau [FR222, FR227]. The evolution of the operational structure, detailed in the table below, reveals a progression in the professionalization of the structure.

Period	Permanent Staff	Profiles	HR Budget
2007-2008	0	Pure volunteerism	€0
Nov 2008	1	Generalist "trigger"	~€30k
2011	1 FTE	Candice Pradeau	~€35k
2016	SYRPIN pooling	Thierry Rouby, Sabrina Martinez	Shared
2021 SO Games	2	Territorial specialization	€120k

Table 104 - Evolution of permanent human Resources

The transition from pure volunteerism (2007-2008) to the first permanent staff member in November 2008 constitutes a "trigger" that enabled the shift to operational action. The stabilization through a permanent contract (2011) stabilizes the structure [FR220]. The innovation of pooling with SYRPIN in 2016, sharing two resources, was motivated by the search for optimization of human resources [FR221, FR222]. The merger creating SO Games in 2021 established a multi-territorial governance. The executive bureau maintains the classic tripartite structure but with mandates limited to two years, renewable once, guaranteeing renewal [FR227]. The president ensures strategic leadership, the treasurer ensures the rigorous financial management necessary given the amounts managed, and the secretary ensures the complex operational coordination of a regional organization [FR228]. The board of directors expands to ten members with an innovative

architecture. Two seats are statutorily reserved for the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region and the SNJV, institutionalizing vertical links [FR228]. Territorial representation requires a minimum of six members per member department, guaranteeing that no territory is marginalized. The statutory honorary members bring historical legitimacy and expertise [FR226, FR227]. The differentiated college system recognizes the diversity of stakeholders. Active members have full voting rights, ensuring control by contributing companies. Advisory members (associations, schools) participate without voting, bringing expertise without direct involvement in governance. Benefactor members provide financial support without interfering in operational decisions. The status of non-contributing "young professionals" facilitates the integration of emerging talents [FR226, FR227].

10.9.2 The multi-level coordination mechanisms

Vertical coordination

The cluster's vertical coordination architecture articulates across four interconnected levels creating a continuum from the local to the global. At the European level, representation operates indirectly via the SNJV's membership in the European Games Developer Federation (EGDF) [FR186, FR187]. This connection enables the influencing of European digital directives and access to Horizon Europe programs. The national level is structured around a permanent seat on the board of directors of the SNJV representing the college of regional associations [FR185, FR186]. The four quarterly meetings and nine annual board meetings since 2009 create a continuous presence in the national instances [FR185, FR186, FR187, FR188, FR189, FR190, FR191, FR192]. Coordination with Capital Games (Île-de-France), Game Only (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes), and Atlangames (Loire Valley) enables joint actions such as lobbying for the maintenance of the CIJV, deemed "indispensable to stay in the race" in the face of international competition [FR176, FR188, FR189, FR190, FR191, FR192]. At the regional level, SO Games functions as the sole interlocutor of the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region for the sector. This responsibility involves structuring the entire regional territory, from La Rochelle to Pau, from Angoulême to Limoges, creating an unprecedented territorial coherence [FR075]. The local level maintains the essential proximity anchoring. The implantation at the Bordeaux CCI facilitates links with the traditional economic ecosystem. The insertion into the Magelis Cluster in Angoulême creates synergies with the image and animation sectors. This dual location avoids exclusive metropolitan concentration while optimizing territorial complementarities [FR223].

Horizontal coordination

Mechanism	Description	Impact
Framework agreements	Co-construction of programs	Industry alignment
Cross interventions	Professionals/teachers	100+ hours/year
Guaranteed internships	Organized pipeline	"Main Ubisoft criterion"
Supervised projects	Studio mentorship	Pedagogical innovation

Table 105 - Coordination mechanisms within the training ecosystem

Coordination with the education sector is based on shared governance. Framework agreements formalize the co-construction of pedagogical programs, guaranteeing training-employment adequacy. Cross interventions mobilize more than 100 hours of professional expertise annually in the curricula [FR227]. The guaranteed internship system creates a structured talent pipeline. Supervised projects allow students to work on real company challenges. The interface with the traditional industry operates through a dedicated Vice-President position for "Video Games and Industry," a specificity of the coordination within the Bordeaux cluster [FR222, FR227]. Monthly

joint committees bring together studios and industrialists around concrete projects: serious games for training, simulations for Industry 4.0, virtual reality for maintenance [FR227].

10.9.3 The control and regulation mechanisms

Operational coordination tools

Operational coordination relies on a combination of digital tools and structuring temporal rituals. The collaborative platform enables information sharing among members, the management of joint projects, and the organization of events [FR222, FR226, FR227]. The electronic voting system facilitates the rapid decision-making necessary in an extended territorial context. Systematic hybrid meetings (in-person + video) maintain the connection despite geographical dispersion. A real-time KPI dashboard enables performance monitoring [FR222, FR227]

Ritual	Frequency	Function
Creative Tuesday	Monthly	Community animation
Committees	Quarterly	Thematic work s
Bureau	Bi-weekly	Day-to-day management
Board of Directors	Quarterly	Strategic decisions
General Assembly	Annual	Validation of directions

Table 106 - Temporal coordination rituals

This rhythm creates a regular collective pulse without saturating the agendas. The monthly Creative Tuesdays maintain the informal community connection [FR219]. The quarterly committees deepen technical subjects [FR226, FR227]. The bi-weekly bureau ensures operational reactivity. The quarterly board of directors makes the structural decisions. The annual general assembly validates the major directions.

End of Chapter

11 CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents a comprehensive documentary analysis of the six video game clusters examined within the **GAME-ER** project. Through systematic collection and thematic analysis of diverse materials—including policy documents, institutional reports, press releases, and company communications—this work has fulfilled the dual objectives established for T4.2. First, the documentary evidence has addressed gaps identified in the primary data collection (D4.1), providing complementary perspectives that enrich our understanding of each cluster's organisation, governance, and development. Second, it has strengthened the empirical foundation for subsequent comparative analysis and policy recommendations through triangulated evidence from multiple sources.

The analysis revealed both convergences and divergences. In several instances, documents corroborated stakeholder insights, reinforcing earlier findings with official narratives and quantitative data. However, the analysis also uncovered previously unexplored dimensions and identified tensions between formal institutional narratives and the lived experiences of cluster actors. These contradictions—concerning governance effectiveness, resource availability, or policy impact—offer valuable insights into cluster dynamics beyond official discourse. The findings will integrate directly with parallel WP4 tasks, including the historical analysis of cluster formation (T4.3), mapping of actors and relationships (T4.4), and identification of skills needs (T4.5). Together, these complementary research strands provide a multidimensional understanding capturing both structural characteristics and evolutionary dynamics.

The evidence base established here will be essential for the comparative work in WP3. The documented patterns of cluster organisation, governance mechanisms, collective action, and resource mobilisation across the six cases will enable development of a robust analytical typology and identification of differentiated cluster models. This comparative understanding will provide the empirical foundation for formulating context-sensitive, evidence-based policy recommendations (D3.4) tailored to support sustainable development of video game clusters across diverse European contexts. By illuminating how clusters are formally structured, publicly represented, and institutionally supported, this deliverable contributes to **GAME-ER's** overarching objective: enhancing understanding of regional game industry ecosystems and informing policies that effectively nurture creative innovation, economic competitiveness, and territorial development in non-capital cities and regions across Europe.

12 REFERENCES

- Ayres, L. (2008). *Thematic coding and analysis*. In L. M. Given (Ed.), *The SAGE encyclopedia of qualitative research methods* (pp. 868–868). Sage.
- Bellini, A., Burrioni, L., & Dorigatti, L. (2018). *Industrial relations and creative workers: Country report—Italy*. IR-CREA Project Report.
- Bertacchini, E. (2012). Industrie dei contenuti e dei media. In E. Bertacchini & W. Santagata (Eds.), *Atmosfera creativa: Un modello di sviluppo sostenibile per il Piemonte fondato su cultura e creatività* (pp. 171–194). Einaudi.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101.
- CNA (2006). *Creative Economy a Torino. I nuovi artigiani che fanno impresa nella cultura, nei nuovi media e nell'entertainment*. Cooperativa Antilia. <https://www.to.camcom.it/sites/default/files/studi-statistica/Reportcreativi180906.pdf>
- Consalvo, M., & Paul, C. A. (2019). *Real games: What's legitimate and what's not in contemporary videogames*. MIT Press.
- Cooke, P. N., & Lazeretti, L. (Eds.). (2008). *Creative cities, cultural clusters and local economic development*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Curtain, C., & Dröge, K. (2024). *QualCoder* (Version 3.7) [Python]. <https://github.com/ccbogel/QualCoder/releases/tag/3.6> (Original work published 2019)
- Darchen, S., & Tremblay, D.-G. (2015). Policies for creative clusters: A comparison between the video game industries in Melbourne and Montreal. *European Planning Studies*, 23(2), 311–331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2013.865712>
- Gil, C. B. (2023). O papel da governança territorial nas políticas de desenvolvimento local: Fundão, uma experiência replicável? [Master's thesis, ISCTE - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa]. Repositório ISCTE. <http://hdl.handle.net/10071/30483>
- Gong, H., & Binz, C. (2023). Cumulative causation in regional industrial path development: A conceptual framework and case study in the videogame industry of Hamburg and Shanghai. *Geoforum*, 141, 103729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2023.103729>
- Houška, J. (2025, June 16). Platform alternatives or platform power: Custom and commercial game engines in the work of foreigners in Czech game production. In *Conference proceedings of DiGRA 2025: Games at the crossroads*. <https://doi.org/10.26503/dl.v2025i2.2449>
- Istat. (2025). *Bilancio demografico mensile e popolazione residente per sesso, anno 2025*. <https://demo.istat.it/?l=it>
- Juul, J. (2019). *Handmade pixels: Independent video games and the quest for authenticity*. MIT Press.
- Krippendorff, K. (2004). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Lehtonen, M. J., Ainamo, A., & Harviainen, J. (2020). The four faces of creative industries: Visualising the game industry ecosystem in Helsinki and Tokyo. *Industry and Innovation*, 27(9), 1062–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2019.1709427>
- Loots, E., Neiva, M., Carvalho, L., & Lavanga, M. (2021). The entrepreneurial ecosystem of cultural and creative industries in Porto: A sub-ecosystem approach. *Growth and Change*, 52(2), 641–662. <https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.12441>
- Méndez-Ortega, C., & Arauzo-Carod, J. M. (2019). Locating software, video game, and editing electronics firms: Using microgeographic data to study Barcelona. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 26(3), 81–109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2018.1553743>
- Pixel Federation. (2024). *Annual report 2023: Brief financial and marketing overview*. Games Press. <https://www.gamespress.com/Annual-Report-2023---brief-financial-and-marketing-overview>

- Reisigl, M., & Wodak, R. (2015). The discourse-historical approach (DHA). In R. Wodak & M. Meyer (Eds.), *Methods of critical discourse studies* (3rd ed., pp. 23–61). Sage.
- Rodrigues, M., & Franco, M. (2021). Measuring smart city initiatives in building on digital entrepreneurship: Case study of Fundão, Portugal. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 72, 103115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.103115>
- Ruggill, J. E. (2017). *Inside the video game industry: Game developers talk about the business of play*. Routledge.
- Švelch, J. (2018). *Gaming the Iron Curtain: How teenagers and amateurs in communist Czechoslovakia claimed the medium of computer games*. MIT Press.
- Švelch, J., & Houška, J. (2025). Czech appeal: Why and how national game productions use local themes and settings. *Games and Culture*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120251322265>
- Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M., & Zapletalová, J. (2025). From industry to cultural tourism: Structural transformation of the second-order city. Case Brno. *Cities*, 158, 105685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105685>
- Vaz, E., & Nofre, J. (2019). Urban innovation in Portugal's peripheral territories: A territorial analysis. *Finisterra - Revista Portuguesa de Geografia*, 54(112), 27-49. <https://doi.org/10.18055/Finis17102>
- White, M. D., & Marsh, E. E. (2006). Content analysis: A flexible methodology. *Library Trends*, 55(1), 22–45.
- Woodcock, J. (2019). *Marx at the arcade: Consoles, controllers, and class struggle*. Haymarket Books.
- Ženka, J., Novotný, J., Slach, O., & Ivan, I. (2017). Spatial distribution of knowledge-intensive business services in a small post-communist economy. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 8(2), 385–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-015-0260-9>